

Title: NCS INDOOR: A Python Django-Based Online Booking System for Indoor Cricket Facilities

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Date: 27th April 2022

Note: *This project was independently developed and submitted as part of an undergraduate degree requirement. It explores the development and deployment of an indoor cricket booking system using Python and Django.*

Abstract

This report gives an insight view of the Web and Mobile application based on NCS Indoor Cricket. This project is basically to develop one of the best applications to promote cricket in Nepal community by upgrading the cricket to another level. This report covers all the research, background, plans and work done till now in order to complete project. The report is split into various chapters i.e. Introduction, Background, Developments, Progress, Future Work, References and Appendix.

In the first chapter i.e. Introduction includes aims, objectives, problem statement and features. In the second chapter i.e. Background contains the background of cricket and research done for this project. The development part includes the work completed till date for the project. In the Progress chapter, it shows the status of each task is shown and check if the task is completed or not completed within time, and if not completed within time, then again planning to recover time.

In Future work chapter shows the remaining work of the project and planning done to complete within given time. The reference section all the references for the project i.e., books, documents, websites, etc. are included. And in the Appendix section all the additional documents are provided for the proof that all the progress is successfully done.

Acknowledgement

In order to research and learn about the project, this required a lot of assistance and guidance. I am extremely thankful to them for being part of our supervisor Mukesh Regmi and Bijay Luitel who have guided me a lot.

I respect and extend my gratitude to Islington College (London Metropolitan University), for providing me an opportunity to work on the project and providing me with all the resources, support, and guidance. Especially, I am extremely thankful to the supervisor and external supervisor. I am thankful to and fortunate enough to be able to work for the Project and learned and gain vast knowledge.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction to the topic

There is various aspect of sports in Nepal that receives very limited attention but cricket is one the fastest growing sports worldwide and as well nation wise. With the various opportunities as tournament, cricket is something that would be a great investment for not only the one who is planning to pursue a career as a sportsman but also for the people who are looking for fun, good workout and being social as well. But in spite of so many pros the proper practicing ground for the cricket is still a problem that is faced by most of the people in the country. So to overcome this problem, these days indoor cricket is being very popular among people of Nepal where it not only fixes the problem of space but also accelerates the learning curves and skill. It is also initiative, safe, easy to learn and more of all very efficient in the busy world that we live in.

1.2. Current Scenario

With the advancement of indoor cricket in Nepal, not only people are getting a platform to explore in sports but also many people are getting employment with this business. Various tournaments have been held till the day where both genders are prioritized. According to one article from The Himalayan times, the women supper indoor cricket tournament was held at ultimate indoor cricket by rising cricket for women where five teams were included in the tournament. The winners of the tournament were held with a huge amount of cash prize ([The Himalayan Times, 2018](#)). With this statement also we can see the encouragement of the indoor cricket in the nation. And as per Mr Ravi Timilsina, a pioneer of Nepal's indoor cricket scene 'Indoor cricket has brought together cricket lovers of all ages and professional backgrounds where it has been a sort of social event and a great unifier' which clearly states the progress of the indoor cricket in Nepal ([Lockett, 2021](#)). As indoor cricket is ever rising in Nepal so with the help of this project the business can get a technical pros, informative data and a systematic management.

1.3. Problem Domain

As discussed above, there are so many positive factors of indoor cricket in Nepal but by saying that we cannot deny the fact of problem scenario that we have been facing here in this business. There are still so many things that have to be fixed in order to run the business in a more convenient way. With the various problems like space, cancellation of booking in the last moment, national cricket news affairs, online booking system and so on there are various so many other problems that are discussed below:

- There is no booking system for the indoor cricket technically or application wise so people have to reach out to the place or still make a call in order to book for the game.
- Today people are getting more into virtual games rather than physical games which is a matter of problem about their health in day to day life.
- In context of Nepal there are no any authentic news application to promote nation wise cricket news in order to uplift the national cricket industry.
- Some people don't go to the place after the booking is done which may cause a loss for the indoor cricket team.
- Nowadays, there are no proper space for people to play cricket with also the proper guidance. Especially in urban areas.
- People still follow the traditional way of money transaction which may lead a loss during the cancellation at the last moment for the company.

1.4. Scope

This application is being developed for NCS indoor cricket for booking the indoor ground. The NCS agenda focuses on children and youth who are very actively involved in cricket. Due to the less playground in the valley NCS is building more indoor ground for the people who are interested in cricket. They also provide facilities like trainer for the beginner. The trainer helps people to improve their game and technique so they can improve their performance. They organize local level events for the people to participate. And they provide news, article, and blog about cricket in local, national, and international level. So, people can be updated about cricket. The market in this field is increasing rapidly and more people are interested in indoor cricket. So, people can be updated about cricket. Nowadays people are focused in their health so they are interested in various sports.

1.5. The project as a solution

The difficulties with the indoor cricket that we discussed above cannot be deduced unless people have a correct mind set and proper utilization of the technology in that respected field. However, this project can assist and encourage people to be more engaged in cricket in a systematic and convenient manner. Below there are few solution for the above problem which is solved with the help of this project:

- This project encourages people to perform an online booking system for the players to play on the specific day.
- This project encourages people to perform an online transaction rather than the physical money transaction which can solve the problem of last moment cancellation.
- This project encourages people to read the blogs and news of the self-play or professionals playing cricket nationally.
- This project encourages people to gather around in one specific place in order to play cricket with proper guidance in case of space problem with their community.

1.6. Aim and Objectives

1.6.1. Aim

The main aim of the project is to create a portal for technical communication between the NCS indoor cricket and their customer which will ultimately be beneficial for both the customers and the company in the efficient manner.

1.6.2. Objectives

The objectives are: -

- To enhance the technical communication portal like online booking, online transaction and so on between the company and customers.
- To provide blogs and news regarding the cricket so that people will have more knowledge about the cricket affairs nationally.
- To learn about the implementation, testing and usability of the newly developed system.
- To learn about the Django framework for the website development.
- To learn about the database implementation.
- To develop the skill in research and prepare documentation in a very efficient way.
- To learn about the time management and the development of web application like the real world based project.

1.7. Report Structure

1.7.1. Background

The background has all the background of the client and requirement of the client. And research similar application and comparing with application.

1.7.2. Development

The development has considered methodology and choose methodology with reason. It also includes the work that have been completed till date like Work breakdown structure, use case, high use case, normalization, ERD diagram and wireframe.

1.7.3. Analysis of progress

The analysis of the progress is the status of the task carried out till date. If the work is not completed according to the Gantt chart, then providing reason for delay is provided along with the plan to complete the delayed work.

1.7.4. Future Work

It includes the work to be done in the near future with proper planning.

2. Background

2.1. Client's Description and Requirements

2.1.1. Client's Name

Nepal Cricket School Pvt. Ltd (NCS)

2.1.2. Description

Nepal Sports School Pvt. Ltd is an initiative of the group of enthusiasts and persons from different backgrounds to help promote, encourage, and develop the cricket activities of the country. Although the initial idea of NSM (Nepal Sports School Pvt. Ltd.) was invented a decade ago due to lack of resources, it was not successfully completed before but finally the idea was implemented somehow with the support of many people and manage to establish on 28th November 2015 which is located at Rato Pool, Kathmandu. Now, it has successful in running academy from more than 6 years. It is also known as Pre-Primary and Primary Education of Cricket. (directorykathmandu, 2021)

Figure 1: Nepal Cricket School Indoor Field

The Nepal cricket school also allows people to play cricket by booking the ground except the training timetable. Many people do not know that they can book the ground if they want to play cricket. So, to promote cricket and Nepal cricket school they are trying to update in digital marketing and their own application. Although Nepal cricket school has successful developing players like Rit Gautam and Jitender Singh Thakuri who have played for Nepal Under 16 team, Nepal Under 19 team and Nepal National Team, they are looking for more children who will play for their country.

Figure 2: Sharad Vesawkar taking with coach

Figure 3: Paras Khadka Training NCS Students

The Nepal Cricket School has provided all the facilities and utilities which are required to proper cricket or proper training. Also

provided an opportunity to tour South Africa, New Zealand, Mumbai and different cricketing cities of the nation for one day, 2 days, T20 matches with training camps, medical assessments, fitness and diet classes at the unbeatable prices. Nepal Cricket School organize inter school competition and provides scholarship opportunities for those with good grades at school and with good cricket background. And also invites the legend of cricket to train their student at academy to motivate youngster seeing at their role models. Nepal Cricket School manage to bring all the nepal national player and also south Africa legend Jonty Rhodes.

Figure 4: Africa Legend Jonty Rhodes Training NCS Students

2.2. Similar projects

2.2.1. Project 1: Pretty Sports Drift

Figure 5: Pretty Sports Drift Application

Figure 6: Pretty Sports Drift Booking Feature

Pretty Sports Drift is an advanced facility with a multiple array of choices in the sport of your choice where on the website you can easily book your reservation with a click of a button. In this website you also can send reviews of the website and your time on the ground, but this website does not consist of an appointment to the coach.

2.2.2. Project 2: Achievers Cricket Academy

Figure 7: Achievers Cricket Academy Application

Achievers Cricket Academy is an elaborate sports school where in the website you can book your time to play along with online coach if you want to book the different feature that this website consists is the detailed enquiry form in which you have to provide almost all of your information a coach need and also we can provide our review of the website and the thoughts of the academy also can be sent in the review.

2.2.3. Project 3: V Play Sports

Figure 8: V Play Sports Application

Figure 9: V Play Sports Booking Feature

V Play Sports has a rather simple website where you can book your reservations to cricket and to a variety of other sports of your choice in this website you can send a review of the website as well as the playground.

2.2.4. Smart Cricket Experience Zone

Figure 10: Smart Cricket Experience Zone Application

Figure 11: Smart Cricket Experience Zone Review Feature

Smart Cricket Experience Zone has a complex website with lots of features where you can book online reservations like normal but apart from that you can book one to one lessons to groups classes we are even provided the feature of free workshop and free tutorials of cricket swings and throws. One of the best thing about this website is that you can organize tournaments and we can know about the latest news in cricket from a click of a button.

2.3. Comparison of Table

Features	Project 1	Project 2	Project 3	Project 4	This project
Online booking	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
News	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Trainer	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓
E-payment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monthly Subscription	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Feedback	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Local Events	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓

2.4. The conclusion from similar projects

There are few applications related to this project which have great features and services, but the only problem is all the application are developed in foreign country. There are no applications related to indoor cricket or cricket in Nepal. So, in order to promote cricket, this application will be helpful. And also, while researching about similar application, I found out that there are many features which are not implemented till now such as local events new, monthly subscription and enrolling in cricket academy. So, comparing with the other application also I think this application can beat other application which have deployed till now.

3. Development

3.1. Considered methodologies

3.1.1. Spiral methodology

The spiral methodology is the methodology which is used develop software until the software is up to date or client are completely satisfied with the application. It allows incremental releases of the product or incremental refinement through each iteration around the spiral. The spiral methodology goes to become expensive if it is not utilized properly. (techtarget, 2019)

Figure 12: Spiral Methodology (tutorialspoint, 2021)

The use of spiral methodology is to make changes whenever require according to the requirement or the client. Client can see the progress every time and also view and review the system before deploying the project finish. So, it is most important to calculate cost and risk analysis of the project. To calculate risk and reduce it, development is being divided into smaller parts and the risky parts should be developed before the development which helps in better risk management. (tutorialspoint, 2021)

3.1.2. Evolutionary methodology

Evolutionary prototyping is a software development method where construction of a prototype is done at first. Prototypes are created after receiving initial feedback from the client, each with additional features or enhancements, before the final product emerges. The prototype can be changed multiple times as the requirement of the client might change overtime. In a simple word, it is basically comparing planned results and outcome results and analyze disparities. (Wieners, 2021)

Figure 1: The role of evaluation in the project cycle

Figure 13: Evolutionary Methodology (Wieners, 2021)

Evolutionary Methodology gives the opportunity to see and understand what exactly outcome will be delivery and also, they will have good idea about where their money is utilized. A good evaluation is key to work on other project if you can show the transparency and trust which will helps us to frame our work as a competent. (Wieners, 2021)

3.2. Selected methodology

3.2.1. DSDM Methodology

DSDM is an agile software development methodology which works in an iterative, incremental approach that is mostly based on the Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology. The aim of a DSDM project is to meet client needs and deliver on time with the more benefits. It also focusses on project where benefits are clear, the solution is feasible, and solid foundations are in place before starting the project. It also allows to remain flexible and meet client's requirements according to it. (Bugajenko, 2021)

Figure 14: DSDM Methodology (knowledgetrain, 2019)

According to the DSDM methodology philosophy, it is necessary to make principle to make project easy and better. The DSDM methodology have eight principle which are focusing on the business need, delivering on time, collaborate, never compromise quality, build incrementally from firm foundations, develop iteratively, communicate continuously and clearly, and demonstrate control which will help to complete the project in systematic way. (Bugajenko, 2021)

Figure 15: DSDM Principles (knowledgetrain, 2019)

If time and budget are less and features are also less important than the important features are added to the product. The least important features are developed. The prioritization of the features is done using the MoSCoW prioritization. MoSCoW prioritization is basically dividing the features of the project into Must haves, Should haves, Could haves and Won't haves. And the development process is broken down into fixed duration iterations and features which helps to calculate phase is called as Timeboxes.

3.2.2. Advantages of DSDM

The advantages of DSDM Methodology can be viewed in many ways. They are: -

- Projects are delivered on time
- It is more flexibility than other methodology
- Progress can be easily tracked
- Business cases are at the core of the DSDM model, ensuring delivered projects have real business value.

3.2.3. Disadvantages of DSDM

The disadvantages of DSDM Methodology can be viewed in many ways. They are: -

- Large management overhead
- Costly implementation makes this unsuitable for project
- DSDM can be restrictive and inhibit developer creativity.
- Projects are likely to be completed exactly as specified, even if more elegant solutions are available.

3.2.4. Reason for choosing DSDM methodology for this project

DSDM deals with projects rather than just the development and delivery of a product. The project context requires a focus on the wider business need and all aspects of the solution that evolves to meet that need. DSDM has a long track record of successful project delivery in all types of environments, and has proved to be fully scalable, working effectively in small simple businesses, large or any complex organizations.

The reason for choosing the DSDM methodology is simply to deliver the application according to the main features of the application within certain period. It is one of the most important reasons to choose DSDM because we can deploy application even if the application is not completely ready to delivery, it only requires main must have prioritized features to be completed to be delivered. After completing the must have features, we can slowly add more features according to the time box which will not affect the application while upgrading.

Another reason is that clients or customer can view the product while ongoing development is going on. And also, if the features and given time of customer/ client cannot be completed within time then we can simply divide features according to the least important features on future work so that we can deploy application without having any impact on the application.

3.3. PHASES OF METHODOLOGY (Brief explanation of activities of each phase)

3.3.1. Pre-project

The first phase of the DSDM project is pre-project, during which everyone involved in the project should be aware of the project goals. The pre-project ensures that only the right projects are initiated and that the project is properly set up.

3.3.2. Feasibility study

The project's financial and technical analysis are confirmed during this phase. The project is also evaluated to see if it is suited for Rapid Application Development (RAD). If the RAD is proven to be feasible, only project development will begin otherwise, the project will not be executed.

3.3.3. Foundations

During this phase, the project's business points are established, and the project's research is conducted. Every project should be evaluated from a commercial standpoint, including whether the project will be profitable and what resources will be necessary during its development. Once the business aspect of the project is identified the architectural framework of the project is prepared.

3.3.4. Exploration

The primary goal of this phase of the project is to create a prototype and obtain user feedback. The necessary required requirements and changes are gathered from the user feedback, and the necessary adjustments are implemented in the prototype through user feedback. This method is repeated until an agreed-upon section of the functional model is found.

3.3.5. Engineering

Throughout this phase, the prototypes must be successfully and appropriately engineered to meet the needs of the client. During this phase, the software should be

ready for deployment once the client is satisfied with the product; otherwise, necessary adjustments should be implemented based on the client's suggestions.

3.3.6. Review

In this phase, the product is evaluated to see if it fits the iteration's requirements and standards. Every function and software are assembled and review thoroughly. The product is tested through its paces to ensure that it is ready for deployment.

3.3.7 Deployment

Once the product is assembled, and the project is extensively reviewed in this step. The product will be available for deployment once the assembly and review are completed.

3.3.8. Post project

Following the product's final deployment, the developed product is monitored to assess its effectiveness, and any problems with the product are addressed. The identified problem is examined, and relevant solutions are presented. Finally, the firm can attain optimal value delivery.

3.4. Design

3.4.1. Use Case

A use case is a framework analysis approach for identifying, explaining, and coordinating framework requirements. The use case is made up of a number of possible communications sequences between frameworks and clients in a certain environment and for a specific goal.

Figure 16 Use case of Add Feedback

The user adds the feedback, and the admin will view the feedback

Figure 17 Use case of Add Article

The admin will add the article and user can view the article.

Figure 18 Use case of Add Blog

The admin will add the blog and user can view the blog.

Figure 19 Use case of Add Events

Admin will add the event and user can view the event.

Figure 20 Use case of Add FAQ

Admin will add the FAQ and user can view the FAQ.

Figure 21 Use case of Add News
Admin will add the news and user can view the news.

Figure 22 Use case of Add Training

Admin will add the training and user can view the training.

Figure 23 Use case of Register

To register the account user, have to verify details and verify password. If details and password is incorrect the error message will pop out.

Figure 24 Use case of Add Subscription

Admin will add subscription details and user can view subscription details.

Figure 25 Use case of Add Profile

User can add profile and view profile.

Figure 26 Use case of Login

To login the system user has to enter username and password. The system will verify username and password. If username and password is incorrect, the error message will pop out. User can also change the password.

Figure 27 Use case of Booking

To book user have to login into the system after login user have to select date and time. User can also choose the payment method. After booking admin will confirm the booking details.

Figure 28 Use case of Delete Article

Admin can delete the article after deleting the article the article will be displayed from database.

Figure 29 Use case of Delete FAQ

Admin can delete FAQ after deleting the FAQ from database FAQ will be displayed.

Figure 30 Use case of Delete Events
Admin can delete FAQ after deleting the FAQ from database FAQ will be displayed

Figure 31 Use case of Delete Profile

User can admin both can delete profile. Admin can also view profile details.

Figure 32 Use case of Delete Blogs

Admin can delete Blog after deleting the Blog from database Blog will be displayed.

Figure 33 Use case of Delete Feedback

User can admin both can delete feedback. Admin can also view feedback details.

Figure 34 Use case of Delete News

Admin can delete News details after deleting the news from database news will be displayed.

Figure 35 Use case of Delete Training

Admin can delete training details after deleting the training from database training details will be displayed.

Figure 36 Use case of Delete Subscription

Admin can delete subscription details after deleting the subscription from database subscription details will be displayed.

Figure 37 Use case of Edit Events

Admin can update the event details after updating the event the updated event details will be displayed.

Figure 38 Use case of Edit Subscription

Admin can update the subscription details after updating the subscription the updated subscription details will be displayed.

Figure 39 Use case of Edit Profile

Admin can update the profile details after updating the profile the updated profile details will be displayed.

Figure 40 Use case of Edit Article

Admin can update the article details after updating the article the updated article details will be displayed.

Figure 41 Use case of Edit News

Admin can update the news details after updating the news the updated news details will be displayed.

Figure 42 Use case of Edit Feedback

Admin can update the feedback details after updating the feedback the updated feedback details will be displayed.

Figure 43 Use case of Edit FAQ

Admin can update the FAQ details after updating the FAQ the updated FAQ details will be displayed.

Figure 44 Use case of Edit Training

Admin can update the training details after updating the training the updated training details will be displayed.

Figure 45 Use case of Edit Blog

Admin can update the blog details after updating the blog the updated blog details will be displayed.

Figure 46 Use case of View FAQ

When admin adds FAQ data user then can view the FAQ data.

Figure 47 Use case of View Training

When admin adds training data then user can view the training data.

Figure 48 Use case of View Blogs

When admin adds blog data then user can view the blog data.

Figure 49 Use case of View Events

When admin adds event data then user can view the event data.

Figure 50 Use case of View Payment

When admin adds payment data then user can view the payment data.

Figure 51 Use case of View Subscription

When admin adds subscription data then user can view the subscription data.

Figure 52 Use case of View Article

When admin adds article data then user can view the article data.

Figure 53 Use case of View Profile

When admin adds profile data then user can view the profile data.

Figure 54 Use case of View Feedback

When admin adds feedback data then user can view the feedback data.

3.4.2. High level use case

Use Case	Register a user
Actors	New Users
Description	New users should register to log in into the app. New users should fill their personal details and confirm their registration.

Use Case	Login
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	Users and Admin should log in to app.

Use Case	Blog
Actors	Users, Staff
Description	User can view the blog and admin can view and post the blog after they log in to the system.

Use Case	Booking
Actors	Users, Staff
Description	User can view the booking details and book the ground. Staff can view the booking details.

Use Case	Payment
Actors	Users
Description	User can pay through e-payment after they log into their account.

Use Case	Event
Actors	Users, Admin

Description	Users can view event and register of an event. Admin can add event details.
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Use Case	News
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	User can view the news and admin can add news.

Use Case	Article
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	Users can view article. Admin can add article details.

Use Case	FAQ
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	Users can view FAQ and admin can add FAQ details.

Use Case	Feedback
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	Users can fill feedback form and admin can view feedback details.

Use Case	Subscription
Actors	Users, Admin
Description	Users can view subscription details and admin can add subscription details.

3.4.3. Expanded Use Case

User	System
User can register by filling up the form	Verify the details and create account
User enter user id and password	Verify the details and redirect to homepage
User can view and edit profile	Store data and update profile
User books the ground in available time	Verify the details and confirm booking
User can view the events and register the events	Store data and confirm registration
User can view the news	Store the data of news that have been updated
User can view the article	Store the data of article that have been published
User can view the FAQ	Store the data of FAQ that have been published
User can fill up the feedback form	Store the data of feedback that have been submitted
User can view the blog	Store the data of blog that have been published
User can view the subscription and choose the package	Store the subscription data and allocate the package according to time
User can pay through the different method	Store the information and confirm the payment
Admin	System
Admin can login into the system	Verify the data and redirect to the admin portal
Admin can register by filling up form	Verify the details and create account
Admin can update and delete the event. Admin can verify the register events	Verify, upload, delete and store the event data.
Admin can edit, update, and delete the article data	Verify, upload, delete and store the article data
Admin can confirm the booking	Verify the booking details
Admin can edit, update, and delete the news data	Verify, upload, delete and store data of news.
Admin can edit, update, and delete the blog data	Verify, upload, delete and store data of blog.
Admin can edit, update, and delete the FAQ data	Verify, upload, delete and store data of FAQ.
Admin can review the feedback form	Verify and store feedback data

Admin can update and delete subscription package and can view the customer details respectively.	Verify, update, delete and store the subscription data.
Admin can view the customer details regarding the payment	Verify the payment data.

3.4.4. Activity Diagram

Figure 55 Activity Diagram of Add Article

Figure 56 Activity Diagram of Add Profile

Figure 57 Activity Diagram of Add Subscription

Figure 58 Activity Diagram of Add News

Figure 59 Activity Diagram of Add FAQ

Figure 60 Activity Diagram of Add Events

Figure 61 Activity Diagram of Add Blogs

Figure 62 Activity Diagram of Add Feedback

Figure 63 Activity Diagram of Delete Blog

Figure 64 Activity Diagram of Delete Feedback

Figure 65 Activity Diagram of Delete News

Figure 66 Activity Diagram of Delete Subscription

Figure 67 Activity Diagram of Delete Event

Figure 68 Activity Diagram of Delete Article

Figure 69 Activity Diagram of Delete FAQ

Figure 70 Activity Diagram of Register

Figure 71 Activity Diagram of Login

Figure 72 Activity Diagram of Update Profile

Figure 73 Activity Diagram of Update Subscription

Figure 74 Activity Diagram of Update News

Figure 75 Activity Diagram of Update Feedback

Figure 76 Activity Diagram of Update FAQ

Figure 77 Activity Diagram of Update Event

Figure 78 Activity Diagram of Update Blog

Figure 79 Activity Diagram of Update Article

3.4.5. Sequence Diagram

Figure 80 Sequence Diagram of Add Events

Figure 81 Sequence Diagram of Add Profile

Figure 82 Sequence Diagram of Add Subscription

Figure 83 Sequence Diagram of Add FAQ

Figure 84 Sequence Diagram of Add Feedback

Figure 85 Sequence Diagram of Add Article

Figure 86 Sequence Diagram of Add News

Figure 87 Sequence Diagram of Add Blog

Delete

Figure 88 Sequence Diagram of Delete Subscription

Figure 89 Sequence Diagram of Delete Profile

Figure 90 Sequence Diagram of Delete FAQ

Figure 91 Sequence Diagram of Delete Article

Figure 92 Sequence Diagram of Delete News

Figure 93 Sequence Diagram of Delete Feedback

Figure 94 Sequence Diagram of Delete Blog

Figure 95 Sequence Diagram of Delete Events

Update

Figure 96 Sequence Diagram of Update Feedback

Figure 97 Sequence Diagram of Update FAQ

Figure 98 Sequence Diagram of Update Article

Figure 99 Sequence Diagram of Update News

Figure 100 Sequence Diagram of Update Subscription

Figure 101 Sequence Diagram of Update Blog

Figure 102 Sequence Diagram of Update Event

Figure 103 Sequence Diagram of Update Profile

View

Figure 104 Sequence Diagram of View Profile

Figure 105 Sequence Diagram of View Feedback

Figure 106 Sequence Diagram of View FAQ

Figure 107 Sequence Diagram of View Article

Figure 108 Sequence Diagram of View News

Figure 109 Sequence Diagram of View Subscription

Figure 110 Sequence Diagram of Payment

Figure 111 Sequence Diagram of View Blog

Figure 112 Sequence Diagram of View Event

3.4.6. Communication Diagram

Figure 113 Communication Diagram of Add Subscription

Figure 114 Communication Diagram of Add News

Figure 115 Communication Diagram of Add Article

Figure 116 Communication Diagram of Add FAQ

Figure 117 Communication Diagram of Add User Profile

Figure 118 Communication Diagram of Add Feedback

Figure 119 Communication Diagram of Add Blog

Figure 120 Communication Diagram of Add Event

Delete

Figure 121 Communication Diagram of Delete Subscription

Figure 122 Communication Diagram of Delete Blog

Figure 123 Communication Diagram of Delete Event

Figure 124 Communication Diagram of Delete Profile

Figure 125 Communication Diagram of Delete Feedback

Figure 126 Communication Diagram of Delete FAQ

Figure 127 Communication Diagram of Delete Article

Figure 128 Communication Diagram of Delete News

Figure 129 Communication Diagram of Update Subscription

Figure 130 Communication Diagram of Update Article

Figure 131 Communication Diagram of Update News

Figure 132 Communication Diagram of Update FAQ

Figure 133 Communication Diagram of Update Profile

Figure 134 Communication Diagram of Update Event

feedbacks

Figure 135 Communication Diagram of Update Feedback

Figure 136 Communication Diagram of Update Profile

Figure 137 Communication Diagram of Registration

Figure 138 Communication Diagram of View FAQ

Figure 139 Communication Diagram of View Article

Figure 140 Communication Diagram of View Blog

Figure 141 Communication Diagram of View Feedback

Figure 142 Communication Diagram of View Event

Figure 143 Communication Diagram of View News

Figure 144 Communication Diagram of View Profile

Figure 145 Communication Diagram of View Subscription

Figure 146 Communication Diagram of Payment

Figure 147 Communication Diagram of Login

3.5. MOSCOW PRIORITISATION

MoSCoW prioritization is a technique which arrange tasks according to the most important features in project. It shows the features prioritizing on the development process. It will be easy to start project for developer because they will have the priorate set for them to complete project.

Must Have	Should Have	Could Have	Won't have this time
M01. Login and Registration	S01. User Profile	C01. Student Enrollment	W01. Mobile Application
M02. Online Booking	S02. Events	C02. Online Payment	W02. Training Videos
M03. Article	S03. Trainers Details	C03. Notification	W03. Sports E-commerce
M04. Logout	S04. Feedback		

3.6. Moscow Story Point

3.6.1. Must have

Priority	ID	User Story	Story Point
Must Have	M01	As a user login and registration to the system is one of the important element for user and for security.	5
	M02	As a Sports app, booking feature is very important for user to book the ground.	8
	M04	As a Indoor cricket application, user must be able to read article about cricket.	3
	MO5	As a user, privacy and security is top priority for that logging out from the system is important after using the application	3

Table 1: Table of Must Have

3.6.2. Should Have

Priority	ID	User Story	Story Point
Should Have	S01	User can view and edit information cause some of the information are temporary and need to be change.	8
	S02	As a user, they could view the events and register for upcoming game.	8
	S03	As a user, they need to view trainers details to select coach and view details.	5
	S04	As a user, feedback form is necessary to send feedback to the admin.	13

Table 2: Table of Should Have

3.6.3. Could Have

Priority	ID	User Story	Story Point
Could Have	C01	As a user, they can enroll training through the application.	8
	C02	As a user, they can pay from the application by online payment methods.	9
	C0	As a user, they could get notification if new article, blogs, news is updated and also booking available time can be notified.	5

Table 3: Table of Could Have

3.6.4. Won't Have This Time

Priority	ID	User Story	Story Point
Wont Have This Time	W01	As a user, they have to access this application through web site only if mobile application is also provided it would be a lot easier for them. However, we won't be able to provide mobile application this time	8
	W02	As a user, they could train remotely if training video are available. However, we won't be able to provide training video this time.	13
	W03	As a user, if cricket accessories were available from this site, they could buy directly from this application which could save their time and make it a lot easier. However, we won't be able to provide sports E-Commerce this time.	

Table 4 : Table of Wont Have This Have

3.7. Timebox Planning

In order to complete the development project. A timebox of 5 weeks or 24 working days is created. In the past, our solution's average velocity per timebox was 16 story points. As a result, our team will begin with 16 story points per timebox for this project and arrange the timebox accordingly.

3.7.1. Time Box: 1

ID	User Story	MoSCoW	Story Points	Remarks
M01	As a admin, I want more user to register into my system. So, more user can login and use the application.	Must	5	
M02	As a admin, I want to provide information about the booking and provide information about available time and date so users can navigate easily and book the ground.	Must	8	
M04	As a admin, I want user to give freedom to logout form the application also for security and privacy reason.	Must	3	

Table 5: Table of Time Box 1

Objective of Time Box 1

This time box 1 contain the important feature of the booking application like registration/login, booking and logout. Without this three features the application can't be deployed other features can be add on later. According to the priority this time box is created to achieve the goal of the system.

3.7.2. Time Box: 2

ID	User Story	MoSCoW	Story Points	Remarks
M03	As user, they can read article from different publisher and can get UpToDate information about cricket world.	Must	5	
S01	As user, the privacy is most important so to keep the user information secure they need private account. So, they can edit information and change password.	Should	5	

Table 6: Table of Time Box 2

Objective of Time Box 2

In the first phase the application can be deployed but in second phase the basic requirement is completed. This two features are the basic requirements for the user to engage in the application.

3.7.3 Time Box:3

ID	User Story	MoSCoW	Story Points	Remarks
S03	As a admin, the user are given freedom to chose the trainer so they could choose the trainer according to the rating and customer feedback.	Should	5	
C02	After the booking user can pay through the application by online payment. User can choose different payment methods.	Could	8	

Table 7: Table of Time Box 3

Objective of Time Box 3

User can view the trainer and chose the coach that they desire and enroll in the training.

As a user, they will always seek the easiness. So, after the booking or enroll in the training they could pay by online or event has option for cash in hand as per their requirement

3.7.4. Time Box: 4

ID	User Story	MoSCoW	Story Points	Remarks
S02	User can view information of events and can register for an upcoming events.	Should	13	
S03	As a user, they have their thoughts about the products, they could write what they like, don't like and what could be change in the product in the feedback form	Should	5	

Table 8: Table of Time Box 4

Objective of Time Box 4

As, a user for more activity events are organized so more users can participate in the events. As the user can give feedback to the admin about their thought about the product

3.8. Project Plan

S.No.	Activity	Deliverable	Start Date	End Date	Duration (Working Days)
1.	Pre-Project Phase	TOR and Budget Allocation Report	17/09/2021	20/09/2021	3 days
1.1	Identify roles of Features		17/09/2021	18/10/2021	1 day
1.2	Prepare Term of Reference (TOR)	TOR	19/10/2021	21/10/2021	2 days
2.	Project Phase life Cycle	Feasibility Study Report, Prioritized list of Requirement and SRS.	20/09/2021	13/10/2021	23 days
2.1	Feasibility Study	Feasibility Study Report	14/10/2021	24/10/2021	10 days
2.1.1	Technical Feasibility	Technical Requirements and Feasibility Report	14/10/2021	17/10/2021	3 days
2.1.2	Time Feasibility	Time Allocation Report	18/10/2021	21/10/2021	3 days
2.1.3	Research and Conformation of Methodology	Methodology Comparison Report	21/10/2021	24/10/2021	4 days
2.2	Foundation	Prioritized List of Requirements and SRS Document	25/10/2021	07/11/2021	12 days

2.2.1	Identify and Define Scope of Project		25/10/2021	27/10/2021	2 day
2.2.2	Meeting with Client		28/10/2021	29/10/2021	1 days
2.2.3	Determining Functional, Non-Functional Requirements and Useable features		30/10/2021	31/10/2021	2 day
2.2.4	Defining User stories		01/11/2021	04/11/2021	4 day
2.2.5	MoSCoW Prioritization		05/11/2021	08/11/2021	3 day
3.	Time Box 1		09/11/2021	05/12/2021	26 days
3.1	Exploration	Graphic Designs and Activity Flow Diagrams	09/11/2021	19/11/2021	11 days
3.1.1	Selection of tool for UI design		09/11/2021	09/11/2021	1 day
3.1.2	Identify/Design UI	Wireframes	10/11/2021	11/11/2021	2 days
3.1.3	Chosen UI/UX Concept	Graphic Design	12/11/2021	12/11/2021	1 days
3.1.4	Identify Attributes of product		13/11/2021	13/11/2021	1 day
3.1.5	Final Layout Concept	Activity Flow Diagram, Sequence Diagram	14/11/2021	16/11/2021	3 days
3.1.6	User Authentication Concept	Use Case	17/11/2021	18/11/2021	2 days
3.1.7	Communication Concept	Communication Diagram	19/11/2021	19/11/2021	1 days

3.2	Design and Build Integration	Web Application Development, Solution Assurance Plan, Deployment Plan	20/11/2021	05/12/2021	15 days
3.2.1	Design		20/11/2021	20/11/2021	1 day
3.2.2	CSS/JavaScript Integration		21/11/2021	23/11/2021	3 days
3.2.3	Web Application Design	Framework	23/11/2021	23/11/2021	1 day
3.2.4	Database Design and Development		24/11/2021	24/11/2021	2 days
3.2.5	Web App Development		24/11/2021	04/12/2021	10 days
3.2.6	Solution Testing	Solution Assurance Plan	05/12/2021	05/12/2021	1 day
3.2.6.1	Technical Testing		06/12/2021	07/12/2021	2 day
3.2.7	Planning Deployment Phase	Deployment Plan	08/12/2021	08/12/2021	1 day
4.	Time Box 2		09/12/2021	05/01/2022	26 days
4.1	The tasks of this time box are similar as the time box1.				
5.	Time Box 3		06/01/2022	01/02/2022	26 days
5.1	The tasks of this time box are similar as the time box1.				
6.	Time Box 4		02/02/2022	28/02/2022	26 days
6.1	The tasks of this time box are similar as the time box1.				

7.	Time Box 5		01/03/2022	26/03/2022	26 days
7.1	The tasks of this time box are similar as the time box1.				
8.	Implementation		27/03/2022	08/04/2022	12 days
8.1	User Approvals Guidelines		27/03/2022	01/04/2022	5 days
8.2	Train Staff Users		02/04/2022	05/04/2022	3 days
8.3	Implementation/Setup	User Manual	06/04/2022	09/04/2022	3 days
8.5	Final Delivery of Product		10/04/2022	10/04/2022	1 day
9.	Post – Project		11/04/2022		On Going
9.1	Maintenance		On going	On going	

Assumptions for developing project plan

- Total no of 6 days is calculated in a week excluding Sunday in a project plan.
- The past average velocity is considered as 16 Story Points.
- The time box is created according to the planning.
- The timebox is reviewed at last and adjusted if needed.
- In terms of the time box, which has 16 user story points, it can be further divided into sub stories when completing the assignment.

3.9. Implementation

3.9.1. Database Design

Database design refers to a set of procedures that make it easier to plan, create, implement, and maintain enterprise data management systems. A well-designed database is simple to manage, increases data consistency, and saves money on disk storage space. The database designer determines how data items relate to one another and what information must be saved. The primary goals of database design in DBMS are to create logical and physical models of the database system under consideration. The logical model focuses on the data requirements and data to be stored without regard to physical constraints. It is unconcerned with how the data will be saved or where it will be physically stored. (Guru99, 2022)

Er

An ER (Entity Relationship) is a form of flowchart that help people to understand how "entities" such as people, object or concept interact with one another in a system. Entity Relationship Diagram is mostly used to design and debug the system. It is also used in software engineering, information system and education field. Er diagram is a visual representation of the system it consists of a set of symbol like rectangles, diamonds, ovals, and lines to connect to each other. (Lucidchart, 2022)

Data structure diagrams (DSDs) are similar to ER diagrams in that they focus on interactions between pieces within entities rather than relationships between entities. Data flow diagrams (DFDs), which map out the movement of information for processes or systems, are frequently used in conjunction with ER diagrams. (Lucidchart, 2022)

The business rules and relationship of all the entities are:

- There is only one admin of the application.
- A user can book ground multiple times.
- A user can register upcoming events.
- A user can choose only one coach in training.
- A user can have multiple addresses and must have one address as their default address.
- A user can comment multiple times.
- A user can write multiple feedback to the admin.
- A user can pay through online payment system.
- A user can pay through online payment or cash in hand after booking
- Admin can add, edit, and update news.
- Admin can add, edit, and update article.
- Admin can add, edit, and update blog.
- Admin can add, edit, and update Events.
- Admin can open registration form of an event.
- Admin can view booking details.
- User can view news, article, events, and blogs.
- User can view and edit their profile details.
- User can cancel the booking.

Normalization

UNF

Customer (**Customer_id***, Customer_name, Customer_username, Customer_password, Customer_email, Customer_DOB, Customer_gender, Customer_phone_number, {Booking_id, Booking_details, Booking_date, Booking_Time, Booking_confirmation, {Trainer_name, Trainer_role, Trainer_age, Trainer_gender, Trainer_experience, {Payment_id, Payment_Type, Payment_Amount, Payment_Details, {Admin_name, Admin_username, Admin_password, Admin_email, Admin_DOB, Admin_gender, Admin_phone_number }}}}))

1NF

Customer (**Customer_id***, Customer_name, Customer_username, Customer_password, Customer_email, Customer_DOB, Customer_gender, Customer_phone_number)

Booking (**Booking_id***, Booking_details, Booking_date, Booking_Time, Booking_confirmation, Trainer_name, Trainer_role, Trainer_age, Trainer_gender, Trainer_experience, Payment_id", Customer_id")

Payment (**Payment_id***, Payment_Type, Payment_Amount, Payment_Details)

Admin (**Admin_id***, Admin_name, Admin_username, Admin_password, Admin_email, Admin_DOB, Admin_gender, Admin_phone_number)

Events (Events_id*, Event_title, Event_details, Event_Snippet, Event_date, Event_time, event_location, Article_id, Article_title, Article_description, Article_snippet, Article_writer, Admin_id”)

2NF

Customer (Customer_id*, Customer_name, Customer_username, Customer_password, Customer_email, Customer_DOB, Customer_gender, Customer_phone_number)

Booking (Booking_id*, Booking_details, Booking_date, Booking_Time, Booking_confirmation)

Payment (Payment_id*, Payment_Type, Payment_Amount, Payment_Details)

Training (Training_id*, Trainer_name, Trainer_role, Trainer_age, Trainer_gender, Trainer_experience, Payment_id”)

Admin (Admin_id*, Admin_name, Admin_username, Admin_password, Admin_email, Admin_DOB, Admin_gender, Admin_phone_number)

Events (Events_id*, Event_title, Event_details, Event_Snippet, Event_date, Event_time, event_location, Admin_id”)

Article (Article_id*, Article_title, Article_description, Article_snippet, Article_writer, Admin_id”)

3NF

Customer (**Customer_id***, Customer_name, Customer_username, Customer_password, Customer_email, Customer_DOB, Customer_gender, Customer_phone_number)

Booking (**Booking_id***, Booking_details, Booking_date, Booking_Time, Booking_confirmation)

Payment (**Payment_id***, Payment_Type, Payment_Amount, Payment_Details)

Training (**Training_id***, Trainer_name, Trainer_role, Trainer_age, Trainer_gender, Trainer_experience, Payment_id")

Admin (**Admin_id***, Admin_name, Admin_username, Admin_password, Admin_email, Admin_DOB, Admin_gender, Admin_phone_number)

Events (**Events_id***, Event_title, Event_details, Event_Snippet, Event_date, Event_time, event_location, Admin_id")

Article (**Article_id***, Article_title, Article_description, Article_snippet, Article_writer, Admin_id")

3.11.2. Important Code.

Folder Structure of development

The screenshot shows an IDE window for a Django project named 'NCS_booking'. The left sidebar displays the project's folder structure, including:

- assets
- contact
- customer
- events
- faq
- manager
- NCS
 - _mfa_.py
 - api.py
 - settings.py
 - urls.py
 - wsgi.py
- news
- registration
- static
- templates
- view
- _mfa_.py
- db.sqlite3
- manage.py
- requirements.txt
- External Libraries
- Scratches and Consoles

The main editor area shows the contents of the `settings.py` file, which includes:

```
WSGI_APPLICATION = 'NCS.wsgi.application'

DATABASES = {
    'default': {
        # ENGINE: 'django.db.backends.sqlite3',
        # NAME: os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'db.sqlite3'),
        'ENGINE': 'django.db.backends.mysql',
        'NAME': 'classdb',
        'USER': 'root',
        'PASSWORD': '',
        'HOST': 'localhost',
        'PORT': '3306',
    }
}

# Password validation
# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/3.5/ref/settings/#auth-password-validators

AUTH_PASSWORD_VALIDATORS = [
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.UserAttributeSimilarityValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.MinimumLengthValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.CommonPasswordValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.NumericPasswordValidator',
    },
]
```

Figure 148 Folder Structure of development

Setting.py

```
from pathlib import Path
import os
# from . info import *

BASE_DIR = os.path.dirname(os.path.dirname(os.path.abspath(__file__)))

SECRET_KEY = '+jpf6)!6czis^i@gx(ddd=&g470c5v^px0+#e^8e45u@snizji'

DEBUG = True

ALLOWED_HOSTS = []

INSTALLED_APPS = [
    'registration',
    'manager',
    'customer',
    'news',
    'events',
    'crispy_forms',
    'django.contrib.admin',
    'django.contrib.auth',
    'django.contrib.contenttypes',
    'django.contrib.sessions',
    'django.contrib.messages',
    'django.contrib.staticfiles',
]

MIDDLEWARE = [
    'django.middleware.security.SecurityMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.sessions.middleware.SessionMiddleware',
    'django.middleware.common.CommonMiddleware',
    'django.middleware.csrf.CsrfViewMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.auth.middleware.AuthenticationMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.messages.middleware.MessageMiddleware',
    'django.middleware.clickjacking.XFrameOptionsMiddleware',
]

ROOT_URLCONF = 'NCS.urls'

TEMPLATES = [
    {
        'BACKEND': 'django.template.backends.django.DjangoTemplates',
        'DIRS': [os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'templates')],
        'APP_DIRS': True,
        'OPTIONS': {
            'context_processors': [
                'django.template.context_processors.debug',
                'django.template.context_processors.request',
                'django.contrib.auth.context_processors.auth',
                'django.contrib.messages.context_processors.messages',
            ],
        },
    },
]
```

```

]

WSGI_APPLICATION = 'NCS.wsgi.application'

DATABASES = {
    'default': {
        # 'ENGINE': 'django.db.backends.sqlite3',
        # 'NAME': os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'db.sqlite3'),
        'ENGINE': 'django.db.backends.mysql',
        'NAME': 'classdb',
        'USER': 'root',
        'PASSWORD': '',
        'HOST': 'localhost',
        'PORT': '3306',
    }
}

# Password validation
# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/3.0/ref/settings/#auth-password-validators

AUTH_PASSWORD_VALIDATORS = [
    {
        'NAME':
'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.UserAttributeSimilarityValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME':
'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.MinimumLengthValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME':
'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.CommonPasswordValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME':
'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.NumericPasswordValidator',
    },
]

# Internationalization
# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/3.0/topics/i18n/

LANGUAGE_CODE = 'en-us'

TIME_ZONE = 'Asia/Kathmandu'

USE_I18N = True

USE_L10N = True

USE_TZ = True

```

```
STATIC_URL = '/static/'
STATICFILES_DIRS = [os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'static')]
STATIC_ROOT = os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'assets')

LOGIN_REDIRECT_URL = '/'
LOGOUT_REDIRECT_URL = '/'

DEFAULT_AUTO_FIELD = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'
```

Manage.py

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
"""Django's command-line utility for administrative tasks."""
import os
import sys

def main():
    os.environ.setdefault('DJANGO_SETTINGS_MODULE', 'NCS.settings')
    try:
        from django.core.management import execute_from_command_line
    except ImportError as exc:
        raise ImportError(
            "Couldn't import Django. Are you sure it's installed and "
            "available on your PYTHONPATH environment variable? Did you "
            "forget to activate a virtual environment?"
        ) from exc
    execute_from_command_line(sys.argv)

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()
```

Urls.py

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
"""Django's command-line utility for administrative tasks."""
import os
import sys

def main():
    os.environ.setdefault('DJANGO_SETTINGS_MODULE', 'NCS.settings')
    try:
        from django.core.management import execute_from_command_line
    except ImportError as exc:
        raise ImportError(
            "Couldn't import Django. Are you sure it's installed and "
            "available on your PYTHONPATH environment variable? Did you "
            "forget to activate a virtual environment?"
        ) from exc
    execute_from_command_line(sys.argv)

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()
```

Wsgi.py

```
import os

from django.core.wsgi import get_wsgi_application

os.environ.setdefault('DJANGO_SETTINGS_MODULE', 'NCS.settings')

application = get_wsgi_application()
```

int.py

```
import pymysql

pymysql.install_as_MySQLdb()
```

Asgi.py

```
import os

from django.core.asgi import get_asgi_application

os.environ.setdefault('DJANGO_SETTINGS_MODULE', 'NCS.settings')

application = get_asgi_application()
```

A detailed explanation of development and implementation is provided in the Appendix.

3.11.3. System Architecture

Figure 149 System Architecture Diagram

The logical layout or design of a web server is the foundation upon which a web server is planned, developed, and deployed. It specifies the architectural architecture and components of a web server, which are necessary for delivering the web server's required activities and services. (Techopedia , 2022)

After gathering the requirement form the client, system architecture of NCS Indoor Cricket is design through the requirement. Firstly, the data will be stored in MySQL Database, while user is using the application the data in the database is stored in MySQL. After the data is stored in MySQL then data is sent to the front end where the user interact through the application. In the front-end part python and JavaScript has been used.

3.7. High level use case description

Name: Register into System

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers have to register their personal details into the system.

Name: Login into System

Actor: Patient (Primary), Admin (Secondary)

Description: Customers and admin both have to login into the system in order get access to web application. Also both can access only after the verification.

Name: View Events

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers and admin both have to login into the system in order get access to web application. Also both can access only after the verification.

Name: Enrol Training

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers will be able to enrol for training either in a monthly basis with the proper guidelines of the trainers or a one can get some visual training as clips and documentation will be provided.

Name: Make Booking

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers will be able to make booking for a match on the specific date and time through this website.

Name: Read Article and Commercial Product

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers will be able to read the article or blogs in order to view the news about Nepal cricket industries and even commercial product such as cricket kits, accessories and so on

Name: Make Payment

Actor: Patient (Primary)

Description: Customers will be able to make online transaction prior or on the match day as per the company's policy.

Name: View Profile

Actor: Patient (Primary), Admin (Secondary)

Description: Customers will be able to read the article or blogs in order to view the news about Nepal cricket industries and even commercial product such as cricket kits, accessories and so on.

Name: View Booking Details

Actor: Patient (Primary), Admin (Secondary)

Description: Customers and admin both will be able to view the booking details which a customer have made.

Name: View Payment Details

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Admin will be able to view the payment details after the transaction done by the customers.

Name: Update Events

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Whenever the company will require to post anything about the events admin will have access to do so.

Name: view list of trainers

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Admin will be able to view the list of trainers and other staff of the company.

Name: View list of customers

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Admin will have access to track the list of the customers and their details.

Name: Update training details

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Admin will have access to view the training details such as customer's enrolment details, training categories and so on.

Name: Send Notification

Actor: Admin (Secondary)

Description: Admin will have access to send notifications for quick updates like reminder, invitation and so on to their customers.

Name: Send Verification Code and verify it

Actor: Patient (Primary), System (Secondary)

Description: When the customer will login to the system then system will have access to check the verification and send verification code.

Name: Automated Reminder

Actor: System (Secondary)

Description: System will be able to send auto reminders to the customers regarding training and payment.

Name: Keep record of the payment

Actor: System (Secondary)

Description: System will be able to keep all the details of the transactions made by customers.

4. Testing and Analysis

4.1. Test Plan

4.1.1. Test Plan

After developing the product, the most important thing is to test the product to check whether the product is stable, easy to use, bug free and performance. To achieve this goal every part of the product must be tested for the quality and whether the product meets its desired quality. A test plan assists us in determining the amount of effort required to validate the quality of the application being tested. (Guru99, 2022)

Three testing are described below:

4.1.2. Unit Testing

Unit testing is a process of software development where every small part of the application is tested individually. Unit testing is very important step in the development process because it helps to find small, big bugs in the application in the early stages, which could be difficult to find and solve in later stage. (Techtarget, 2022)

4.1.3. System Testing

System testing is a process where the (QA) quality assurance team evaluates, how the application is interacting with the integrated system or application. The system testing ensures whether the application perform as intended design. Every small part of the system is tested to ensure that it performs as intended design. (Techtarget, 2022)

4.1.4. Customer Evaluation Testing

The final testing is evaluation testing where the end- user or the client test the system before deploying to the production. After the unit testing and system testing the customer evaluation testing is done it is done in last. Certain end-user or client test the product according to the real-world scenario.

4.2. Unit Test

Test Cases	Objectives
1	Test for user login validation testing
2	Test for user login validation unauthorized user.
3	Test for user register using empty data Validation:
4	Test for user Register using correct validation
5	Test for event registration
6	Test for user profile
7	Test for feedback form
8	Test for user using invalid data profile
9	Test for user payment redirect
10	Test for Payment Successful

UNIT TESTING

4.2.1. Unit Test Case 1

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for user login validation testing
Expected Result	Should redirect to home page
Actual Result	Redirect to Home page
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 150 System Login page

Figure 151 System Home page

4.2.2. Unit Test Case 2

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for user login validation unauthorized user.
Expected Result	Should show error message
Actual Result	Please enter correct username and password
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 152 Login page using unauthorized user

Figure 153 Login error page

4.2.3. Unit Test Case 3

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for user register using empty data Validation.
Expected Result	Error message
Actual Result	Please fill out the field
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 154 Registration using empty validation

4.2.4. Unit Test Case 4

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for user Register using correct validation
Expected Result	Redirect to login
Actual Result	Redirect to login page
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 155 Testing Registration

Figure 156 Testing Login

Figure 157 Testing Home page

4.2.5. Unit Test Case 5

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for event view
Expected Result	Should show the events
Actual Result	Successful
Conclusion	The Test was successful

LOCAL EVENTS

National Indoor Cricket Tournament

We proudly present national indoor cricket and we welcome you to fight for the trophy and cash prize

April 22, 2022, 8:28 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Sankhamul Dashain Tihar Events

We will be organizing a grand cricket tournament at NCS Indoor cricket and we proudly welcome to fill up the forms and fight for the trophy and cash prize.

April 26, 2022, 6:47 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Figure 158 Testing Event page

4.2.6. Unit Test Case 6

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for Home page
Expected Result	After login should redirect to home page
Actual Result	Home page will display different category, nav bar
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 159 Home page

4.2.7. Unit Test Case 7

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for Add Booking
Expected Result	User can book ground
Actual Result	User will select available slot and time and fill out the field and place order
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 160 Testing add booking

Figure 161 Testing Available slot

Figure 162 Testing Booking Place Order

Server: 127.0.0.1 » Database: classdb » Table: manager_field

Browse Structure SQL Search Insert Export Import Priv

+ Options

			id	Book_number	chosen_date_slot_id	price	is_booked	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	1	1	1	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	2	2	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	3	3	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	4	4	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	5	5	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	6	6	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	7	7	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	8	8	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	9	9	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	10	10	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	11	11	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	12	12	1	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	13	1	2	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	14	2	2	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	15	3	2	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	16	1	3	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	17	2	3	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	18	3	3	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	19	4	3	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	20	1	4	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	21	2	4	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	22	3	4	5000	1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	23	1	6	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	24	2	6	5000	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	Edit	Copy	Delete	25	3	6	5000	0

Check all With selected: Edit Copy Delete Export

Figure 163 Booking database

4.2.8. Unit Test Case 8

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for feedback form
Expected Result	User could fill feedback form
Actual Result	User can send feedback form
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Contact Us

Name

Email

Message

Send Message

Figure 164 Testing Contact Us

CONTACT US

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Commodo consectetur debitis delectus eius ex excepturi fugit itaque magnam, modi neque, pariatur possimus praesentium recusandae similique unde veritatis voluptas voluptate voluptatum.

You can send us your queries and we will get back to you as soon as possible.

Samir Shrestha

samir@gmail.com

I would like to get involved in the events that you have been planning to conduct. I have viewed in events from the website

SEND MESSAGE

LOCATION

Figure 165 Testing Feedback form

4.2.9. Unit Test Case 9

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	Test for user payment method
Expected Result	Open payment method page
Actual Result	User will can choose the payment method
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 166 Testing Payment Method

4.2.10. Unit Test Case 10

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for FAQ
Expected Result	Should show FAQ page
Actual Result	User can view different FAQ question
Conclusion	The Test was successful

FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS

What are the benefits of NCS?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Cupiditate expedita ipsam modi pariatur quisquam. Accusamus aliquam, delectus dolor doloribus dolorum exercitationem explicabo fugiat, incidunt minima perferendis repudiandae sapiente voluptatibus voluptatum?

How easy is it to use NCS website?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Amet at consectetur dolor eligendi eos fugit incidunt iure laborum, libero modi, molestias nam nulla quaerat repudiandae similique suscipit unde vel vero.

What is the main motive of NCS?

lorem

Can NCS improve for my cricket skills?

Yes, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Ab asperiores consequuntur cum, earum eligendi excepturi expedita in inventore necessitatibus nulla pariatur praesentium rem rerum sapiente sunt suscipit tenetur vero voluptatibus.

Figure 167 FAQ

4.3. SYSTEM TESTING

4.3.1. System Test Case 1

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for Adding Events
Expected Result	Should add events
Actual Result	Admin will enter events data and events will successfully add
Conclusion	The Test was successful

LOCAL EVENT FORM

[← Back to list](#)

Event Title (Enter the event title please)*

Event Description (Enter the event description please)*

A former Pakistan batter has claimed that him becoming the captain did not sit well with Wasim Akram and Waqar Younis, two of Pakistan's greatest fast bowlers of all time and one of the most menacing pace-bowling pairs of the 1990s.

Event snippet*

Event Date (Enter the event publisher please)*

Event Location (Enter the event publisher please)*

Figure 168 Testing Adding Event

4.3.2. System Test Case 2

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for adding news
Expected Result	Should add news
Actual Result	Admin will add news data and will store in database
Conclusion	The Test was successful

[← Back to list](#)

News Title (Enter the title please)*

SJDC vs AL Dream11 Prediction, Fantasy Cricket Tips, Dream11 Team, Playing XI, Pitch Report, Injury Update- Dhaka ODD

News Description (Enter the news description please)*

The 68th match of the Dhaka ODD will see Sheikh Jamal [Dhanmondi Club](#) facing off against [Abahani Limited](#) on 26th April at the [Shere Bangla National Stadium](#).

For all the [Dream11](#) Tips and Fantasy Cricket Live Updates, follow us on [Cricketaddictor](#) Telegram Channel.

This game is scheduled to start at 8:30 AM [IST](#) and live score and commentary can be seen on [FanCode](#) and [CricketAddictor](#) website.

News Snippets (Enter the news snippets please)*

News Publisher (Enter the news publisher please)*

 Submit

Figure 169 Testing Adding News

NEWS LIST

[+ Add New](#)

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher	
SJDC vs AL Dream 11 Prediction, Fantasy Cricket Tips, Dream11 Team, Playing XI, Pitch Report, Injury Update- Dhaka	geghdfguaejrggSheikh Jamal Dhanmondi Club is currently placed at the top of the points table of this season of the Dhaka ODD whereas Abahani Limited is currently placed at the second spot on the points table. Sheikh Jamal Dhanmondi Club played ten matches of this season of the Dhaka ODD where they won nine matches while Abahani Limited also played ten matches in this season where they managed to win seven games.	fef	efew	

Figure 170 Testing News

Our Recent Stories

News

NCS Indoor Cricket Tournament

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry.

[See More](#)

NCS Indoor Cricket Tournament

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry.

[See More](#)

NCS Indoor Cricket Tournament

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry.

[See More](#)

Figure 171 Adding news Successful

4.3.3. System Test Case 3

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for deleting News
Expected Result	Should delete preexistence news
Actual Result	Admin will delete news from database
Conclusion	The Test was successful

NEWS LIST

[+ Add New](#)

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher	
SJDC vs AL Dream11 Prediction, Fantasy Cricket Tips, Dream11 Team, Playing XI, Pitch Report, Injury Update- Dhaka	geghdfguaejrgrgSheikh Jamal Dhanmondi Club is currently placed at the top of the points table of this season of the Dhaka ODD whereas Abahani Limited is currently placed at the second spot on the points table. Sheikh Jamal Dhanmondi Club played ten matches of this season of the Dhaka ODD where they won nine matches while Abahani Limited also played ten matches in this season where they managed to win seven games.	fef	efew	

Figure 172 Testing deleting news

NCS HOME ABOUT LOCAL EVENTS NEWS CONTACT FAQ [admin](#)

NEWS LIST

[+ Add New](#)

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher
-------	-------------	----------	-----------

Copyright © NCS Indoor Cricket Design: Darpan

Figure 173 News deleted successful

4.3.4. System Test Case 4

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for deleting events
Expected Result	Should delete events
Actual Result	Admin will delete events from database.
Conclusion	The Test was successful

[+ Add New](#)

LOCAL EVENTS

National Indoor Cricket Tournament

We proudly present national indoor cricket and we welcome you to fight for the trophy and cash prize

April 22, 2022, 8:28 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Sankhamul Dashain Tihar Events

We will be organizing a grand cricket tournament at NCS Indoor cricket and we proudly welcome to fill up the forms and fight for the trophy and cash prize.

April 26, 2022, 6:47 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Figure 174 Local Events

NATIONAL INDOOR CRICKET TOURNAMENT

Delete news Edit news

Fight To Win
April 22, 2022, 8:28 p.m.
We proudly present national indoor cricket and we welcome you to fight for the trophy and cash prize

Figure 175 Testing Deleting Events

+ Add New

LOCAL EVENTS

Sankhamul Dashain Tihar Events

We will be organizing a grand cricket tournament at NCS Indoor cricket and we proudly welcome to fill up the forms and fight for the trophy and cash prize.

April 26, 2022, 6:47 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Figure 176 Events Deleted successful

4.3.5. System Test Case 5

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test update Events
Expected Result	Should update preexistence events
Actual Result	Update preexistence events
Conclusion	The Test was successful

The screenshot shows the NCS National Indoor Cricket Tournament website. The header includes the NCS logo and navigation links: HOME, ABOUT, LOCAL EVENTS, NEWS, CONTACT, FAQ, and an admin button. The main heading is "NATIONAL INDOOR CRICKET TOURNAMENT". Below the heading are two buttons: "Delete news" and "Edit news". The news content includes the title "Fight To Win", the date "April 22, 2022, 8:28 p.m.", and the text "We proudly present national indoor cricket and we welcome you to fight for the trophy and cash prize". The footer contains "Copyright © NCS Indoor Cricket" and "Design: Darpan".

Figure 177 Testing Updated events

NCS HOME ABOUT LOCAL EVENTS NEWS CONTACT FAQ [admin](#)

Event Title (Enter the event title please)*

National Indoor Cricket Tournament

Event Description (Enter the event description please)*

A former Pakistan batter has claimed that him becoming the captain did not sit well with [Wasim Akram](#) and [Waqar Younis](#), two of Pakistan's greatest fast bowlers of all time and one of the most menacing pace-bowling pairs of the [1990s](#).

Event snippet*

Fight To Win

Event Date (Enter the event publisher please)*

2022-04-22 20:28:49

Event Location (Enter the event publisher please)*

NCS Academy

[Submit](#)

Figure 178 Editing event

NCS HOME ABOUT LOCAL EVENTS NEWS CONTACT FAQ [admin](#)

[+ Add New](#)

LOCAL EVENTS

National Indoor Cricket Tournament

A former Pakistan batter has claimed that him becoming the captain did not sit well with Wasim Akram and Waqar Younis, two of Pakistan's greatest fast bowlers of all time and one of the most menacing pace-bowling pairs of the 1990s.

April 22, 2022, 8:28 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Sankhamul Dashain Tihar Events

We will be organizing a grand cricket tournament at NCS Indoor cricket and we proudly welcome to fill up the forms and fight for the trophy and cash prize.

April 26, 2022, 6:47 p.m.

[See More ...](#)

Figure 179 Updating events successful

4.3.6. System Test Case 6

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for admin login page
Expected Result	Admin will enter username and password it will redirect to admin home page.
Actual Result	Redirect to home page
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Figure 180 Testing Admin Login Page

Figure 181 Admin Home Page

4.3.7. System Test Case 7

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for view booking
Expected Result	Admin can view booking details
Actual Result	Booking details will save to database admin can view the details.
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Browse		Structure		SQL		Search		Insert		Export		Import		Privileges	
+ Options															
← T →		▼		id	room_number	chosen_date_slot_id	price	is_booked							
<input type="checkbox"/>				1	1	1	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				2	2	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				3	3	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				4	4	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				5	5	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				6	6	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				7	7	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				8	8	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				9	9	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				10	10	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				11	11	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				12	12	1	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				13	1	2	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				14	2	2	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				15	3	2	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				16	1	3	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				17	2	3	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				18	3	3	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				19	4	3	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				20	1	4	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				21	2	4	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				22	3	4	5000	1							
<input type="checkbox"/>				23	1	6	5000	0							
<input type="checkbox"/>				24	2	6	5000	0							

Figure 182 Booking details

4.3.8. System Test Case 8

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for view login database
Expected Result	Should display login details
Actual Result	Admin can view login database where login details will store
Conclusion	The Test was successful

Showing rows 0 - 6 (7 total, Query took 0.0006 seconds.)

SELECT * FROM `django_session`

Profiling [Edit inline] [Edit] [Explain SQL] [Create PHP code]

Show all | Number of rows: 25 | Filter rows: Search this table

+ Options

session_key	session_data	expire_date
sl9rqeudvct5l7tf6z0ffpfov8eqvl6	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hCZAQsX7nsGMjBUqgaS0q6MdzckXej2v...	2022-04-27 11:58:34.136046
o15svsrpcu925vb2r4wrm70h9qch3bxo	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2pBCoTAu3fcMZlahUjWQIHZlvLtt0oVu...	2022-05-01 04:30:30.745405
ovpjs6lwl9cbpcxsongrattl3coohvef	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hCZAQsX7nsGMjBUqgaS0q6MdzckXej2v...	2022-05-01 17:31:12.767979
jnpmqd058970fle6kkat0ejk6r6wkqg9	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hCZAQsX7nsGMjBUqgaS0q6MdzckXej2v...	2022-05-06 01:41:52.396998
mdjivcpw5okq243m9z88jzp934pdpww1	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hCZAQsX7nsGMjBUqgaS0q6MdzckXej2v...	2022-05-06 09:13:15.572452
v1aqex36quuxoiixt7fm9co1qhknpeoi	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hCZAQsX7nsGMjBUqgaS0q6MdzckXej2v...	2022-05-06 14:43:46.826559
s6tfcz5s7657h2vz8mjxyc3ozalbgz5	.eJxVjEEOwiAQR_C2hAKDgwu3fcMZIBBqoYmpV0Z765NutDtf...	2022-05-10 17:19:23.825223

Show all | Number of rows: 25 | Filter rows: Search this table

Query results operations

Print Copy to clipboard Export Display chart Create view

Bookmark this SQL query

Label:

Let every user access this bookmark

Bookmark this

4.10.9. System Test Case 9

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for add article
Expected Result	Should add article
Actual Result	Admin will add article and user can view article
Conclusion	The Test was successful

ARTICLE FORM

[← Back to list](#)

Article Title (Enter the title please)*

Inspire From IPL and Their Influence

Article Description (Enter the articles description please)*

Royal Challengers Bangalore will take on the Rajasthan Royals in their next encounter at the MCA Stadium in Pune. The Faf du Plessis side had a completely off game against SRH in their previous game after being all out for just 68 and there wasn't a lot that they could have done with the total. Anuj Rawat has been inconsistent at the top of the order and they might be tempted to bring in Mahipal Lamror who isn't a bad option while pushing Virat Kohli up the order.

Articles Snippets (Enter the articles snippets please)*

International Inspiration

Articles Publisher (Enter the articles publisher please)*

Editor, Ram Kumar Basnet

 Submit

Figure 183 Testing Add Article

ARTICLES LIST

+ Add New

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher	
Working Hard Play Hard	Contrary to popular belief, Lorem Ipsum is not simply random text. It has roots in a piece of classical Latin literature from 45 BC, making it over 2000 years old. Richard McClintock, a Latin professor at Hampden-Sydney College in Virginia, looked up one of the more obscure Latin words, consectetur, from a Lorem Ipsum passage, and going through the cites of the word in classical literature, discovered the undoubtable source. Lorem Ipsum comes from sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 of "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" (The Extremes of Good and Evil) by Cicero, written in 45 BC. This book is a treatise on the theory of ethics, very popular during the Renaissance. The first line of Lorem Ipsum, "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.", comes from a line in section 1.10.32. The standard chunk of Lorem Ipsum used since the 1500s is reproduced below for those interested. Sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 from "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" by Cicero are also reproduced in their exact original form, accompanied by English versions from the 1914 translation by H. Rackham.	Lorem Ipsum	Editor, Krishna Shakya	
Inspire From IPL and Their Influence	Royal Challengers Bangalore will take on the Rajasthan Royals in their next encounter at the MCA Stadium in Pune. The Faf du Plessis side had a completely off game against SRH in their previous game after being all out for just 68 and there wasn't a lot that they could have done with the total. Anuj Rawat has been inconsistent at the top of the order and they might be tempted to bring in Mahipal Lamror who isn't a bad option while pushing Virat Kohli up the order.	International Inspiration	Editor, Ram Kumar Basnet	

Copyright © NCS Indoor Cricket

Design: Darpan

Figure 184 Adding Article Successful

4.2.10. System Test Case 10

Test Cases	Objectives
Objective	To Test for deleting article
Expected Result	Admin will delete article
Actual Result	Article is deleted
Conclusion	The Test was successful

ARTICLES LIST

+ Add New

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher	
Working Hard Play Hard	Contrary to popular belief, Lorem Ipsum is not simply random text. It has roots in a piece of classical Latin literature from 45 BC, making it over 2000 years old. Richard McClintock, a Latin professor at Hampden-Sydney College in Virginia, looked up one of the more obscure Latin words, consectetur, from a Lorem Ipsum passage, and going through the cites of the word in classical literature, discovered the undoubtable source. Lorem Ipsum comes from sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 of "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" (The Extremes of Good and Evil) by Cicero, written in 45 BC. This book is a treatise on the theory of ethics, very popular during the Renaissance. The first line of Lorem Ipsum, "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.", comes from a line in section 1.10.32. The standard chunk of Lorem Ipsum used since the 1500s is reproduced below for those interested. Sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 from "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" by Cicero are also reproduced in their exact original form, accompanied by English versions from the 1914 translation by H. Rackham.	Lorem Ipsum	Editor, Krishna Shakya	
Inspire From IPL and Their Influence	Royal Challengers Bangalore will take on the Rajasthan Royals in their next encounter at the MCA Stadium in Pune. The Faf du Plessis side had a completely off game against SRH in their previous game after being all out for just 68 and there wasn't a lot that they could have done with the total. Anuj Rawat has been inconsistent at the top of the order and they might be tempted to bring in Mahipal Lamror who isn't a bad option while pushing Virat Kohli up the order.	International Inspiration	Editor, Ram Kumar Basnet	

Copyright © NCS Indoor Cricket

Design: Darpan

Figure 185 Testing Deleting Article

ARTICLE LIST

[+ Add New](#)

Title	Description	Snippets	Publisher	
Working Hard Play Hard	Contrary to popular belief, Lorem Ipsum is not simply random text. It has roots in a piece of classical Latin literature from 45 BC, making it over 2000 years old. Richard McClintock, a Latin professor at Hampden-Sydney College in Virginia, looked up one of the more obscure Latin words, consectetur, from a Lorem Ipsum passage, and going through the cites of the word in classical literature, discovered the undoubtable source. Lorem Ipsum comes from sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 of "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" (The Extremes of Good and Evil) by Cicero, written in 45 BC. This book is a treatise on the theory of ethics, very popular during the Renaissance. The first line of Lorem Ipsum, "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet..", comes from a line in section 1.10.32. The standard chunk of Lorem Ipsum used since the 1500s is reproduced below for those interested. Sections 1.10.32 and 1.10.33 from "de Finibus Bonorum et Malorum" by Cicero are also reproduced in their exact original form, accompanied by English versions from the 1914 translation by H. Rackham.	Lorem Ipsum	Editor, Krishna Shakya	

Figure 186 Delete Article Successful

4.4. Critical Analysis

In the testing phase, various testing was done like unit testing and system testing. In the unit testing test of users, login validation was done where users will fill the log in detail and press the login button after that it will redirect to the home page where users can book ground, read the article, news, blogs, and many more. There were some bugs while testing but it was solved with the help of teachers and online resources.

I have done more testing, but only 10-unit testing is included in the report. My objectives were to test login validation with unauthorized user, registration, booking, payment after payment integrations, news, articles and event and so on. The test was to find possible bugs before deploying the product. Before the end user uses the product. Every function, page was tested during the testing and the result were successful.

Similarly, system testing was also done, without system testing the product couldn't be deployed. In the system testing admin side were focused where admin functionality was tested like adding events, news, article, login page, view booking, payment, delete events, article and so on. Every testing was successful.

The system should be updated on a regular basis so that there are no problems on the admin side the system testing is done.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Legal, Social and Ethical Issues

5.1.1. Ethical issue

Ethics refers to a system of moral principles that regulates how the developers or the administration must operate. Ethical issues arise in situations that conflict the moral principles. Moral principles are the concept of individual or societal right and wrong. Moreover, ethical issues can arise in any workspace and certainly in web development as well. Some of the ethical issues that may arise in web development are as follows:

- **Privacy and Trust:**

The production of log files by web application accumulates information from the system for instance their name, address, contact number, and several other personal details and information. As an ethical Web practitioner, it is their responsibility to educate the product users about how their information would be used by the company and if it will be distributed to other organizations.

- **Public Safety and Welfare:**

The ethical difficulty we may encounter is protecting public safety and welfare by communicating and displaying realities and the genuine nature of our offerings, rather than marketing deceptive items and services. In addition, we shall make sure that all necessary information is showcased and communicated to our consumers. We shall guarantee that we adopt proper security to our process to make sure that confidential information is not disclosed, as well as apply appropriate measures to limit the repercussions of any intrusions on our system.

- **Property Right Infringement:**

Respect for the author's success, respect for beneficial ownership, and acknowledgment of the societal claim to the products of creative work and the right to unrestricted access to information are all concerns that may emerge in copyright ethics. As it is incredibly easy to copy content and get encouraged by notions due to high usage and availability of and on the Internet. Nevertheless, we ought to be cautious that encouragement does not cross the threshold of plagiarism. We must guarantee that only original concepts are used while building our website and offering services, and in other cases, we must provide accountability where it is needed according to legal standards.

5.1.2 Legal Issue

- Trademark Infringement

Trademarks are the contents that represents a company's product or services, it could be a brand name, an image, a quote and many more. If certain trademarks cause misunderstanding about whose products or services users are purchasing, we may face trademark infringement fines. Exclusive rights to a trademark are granted to the person who first uses it commercially in countries where trademark common law is applied, such as the United States. Infringement of trademarks can be readily avoided by registering a trademark and using a trademark search tool.

- Defamation

Defamation is the act of causing harm to someone's reputation by spreading incorrect information. A remark must be communicated to a third party in order to be defamatory, and the particular person who posted the remark must know or should have known that the information was untrue. However, not all offensive utterances are defamatory. For instance, a fair comment, an honest remark published based on their personal view, is not defamatory.

- Website Design

If the website's design is too similar to other sites that have already been launched a legal issue may emerge. The company's logo, banner, color schemes, and so on are some examples of such designs.

5.1.3. Social Issues

While developing the application we have to know what issue can be caused by the application in the society. The technology is moving at very fast pace so we must address what problem might it create in the society. Because it affects many people in the society.

a) Security and Privacy

While developing the app we have to make sure that customer security and privacy is kept top priority especially in this type of the application cause many security challenges occur in the booking site. If the application security is not tight some people, try to take advantage and steal the user's information which is very risky.

As we can hear cybercrime has been increasing rapidly. So, while developing the application the necessary precautions should be followed to keep the data secure and private.

b) Customer Loyalty

If the business do not have any loyal customer the business cannot achieve sustained business growth. So every business needs a loyal customer, more loyal customer the business growth also increase rapidly. If the user do not trust the business they don't want to get service from that business. As an example, Apple the most successful company have a lot of loyal customers they have maintain their loyalty from the very beginning of the company.

Business can lose the customer loyalty very easily once they lose their loyalty. After that it is very hard to earn the customer loyalty. One business cannot gain customer loyalty easily it takes time to gain a customer loyalty. For that the business should provide better service, facility and security and privacy of users.

5.2. Advantages

This application is a web-based application that helps people to book the indoor cricket ground online. In today's date there are very less public ground where children, adult can go play and exercise. Many people are interested to play but their very less ground which the can play so to solve this problem the NCS indoor cricket allows those interested people to play indoor with facilities like bathrooms, chaining rooms, cricket equipment's and many more that are needed while playing games. Some of the advantages of the NCS indoor cricket application are:

1. People can book the ground and pay through online which can save their time.
2. People can train through our coach and can improve their performance.
3. Many events are organized so many people can participate and play the game.
4. People can get information about cricket through news section of the application where national and international news are updated.
5. People can also read the article and blogs published by different writer which are very interested and updated timely.
6. Users have their own profile where they can change the information and password for their privacy and security reason.

5.3. Limitations

As everything's as their own limit likewise our application also has its own limitations. Some of the limitations of the NCS project are:

1. User cannot delete their profile if they are no longer interested in the applications.
2. User are required to register and login to use the booking features.
3. The application can be only accessed through browser, mobile application is not available.
4. Online training video are not available many people can train at home.
5. NCS indoor cricket is available only at some city its is not available through Nepal
6. Sports E- commerce features is not available which can help people save time and money.

5.4. Future Work

I could not put all the feature in this application this time but on future I have plan to put some more features. One of the feature I will add on is the training video which people could train remotely and ask question to the coach. The NCS indoor cricket is not available every place so people who couldn't enroll in training can train through the video and coach feedback. The other features I will most add is sports e-commerce where people can buy cricket accessory like shoe, bat, ball, and others accessory easily on the NCS indoor cricket site. People don't have to visit different site for accessory they can train, book ground, and buy from same site which saves time and money.

Today every person has a mobile phone so in my future I am planning to release a NCS mobile app. So, people can easily access the NCS indoor application. People can download the app form app store or play store and can book the ground or enroll easily. This time there no notification feature, but this features can also help people for notify their upcoming booking, events, news and other notification which they can forget or newly updated news or events.

6. Analysis of progress

6.1. Progress Table

S.N.	Task	Sub-Task	Start-Date	End-Date	Status
1.	Pre-project	Brainstorming, Background Research, Risk Analysis	Sept 23, 2021	Sept 31, 2021	Completed
2.	Feasibility study	Research, Analysis	Nov 01, 2021	Nov 16, 2021	Completed
3.	Foundations	Requirement Analysis	Nov 16, 2021	Nov 20, 2021	Completed
4.	Exploration	Wireframe, ERD diagram	Nov 21, 2021	Dec 01, 2021	Completed
5.	Engineering	Database, Database Migration	Dec 01, 2021	Dec 10, 2021	Completed
6.	Document	Interim Report	Nov 10, 2021	Dec 15, 2021	Completed

6.2. Progress Review

6.2.1. Pre-project, Feasibility study and Foundations

The first stage of the project was requirement gathering, and analysis which has been successfully completed. During the requirement gathering period I have finalized my project topic and have done some research about and went through some similar apps like Pretty Sports Drift, Achievers Cricket Academy, V Play Sports and Smart Cricket Experience Zone.

6.2.2. Exploration

Then project was quick design in which I have created UI/UX, Use-case diagram, High case diagram, Initial ER-Diagram, Normalization, and final ER-Diagram. In this phase all the design and basic system knowledge has been known so that there will be no problem in the system in the future.

6.2.3. Engineering

Till the interim report, I was only available to design database and certain part of coding because I was doing this project according to the Gantt Chart made in DSDM methodology, it was only the starting part of development.

6.2.4. Documentation

The report for the interim report has been completed according to the requirement of this project.

6.3. Progress Table

S.N.	Task	Sub-Task	Start-Date	End-Date	Status
1.	Engineering	NCS Indoor App	Dec 10, 2021	March 19, 2022	On Going
3.	Testing	Black box and white box testing	Mar 19, 2022	Apr 9, 2022	In future
4.	Post Project	Project final checking by implementing with few users	Apr 9, 2022	Apr 16, 2022	In future
5.	Document	Making final documentation for this project.	March 19, 2022	May 16, 2022	In future

6.4. Phases to complete

6.4.1. Engineering

The development of application will be started after the interim report submission.

6.4.2. Testing

The testing stage of the project is where we test the system in every way possible and finalize the product.

6.4.3. Post Project

The system will be checked if does or does not work according to the client requirement. This phase is also the test phase of phase application because we need to train user to use the application.

6.4.4. Documentation

Making final report for this project and other require reports like user manual, SRS and other import report.

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9. Appendix

9.1. Appendix A: WBS Review

Figure 187 WBS

The project is initiated with the research work about the topic, gathering information of the hardware and software used, research about the similar topics to get the proper understanding about the topic, and to complete proposal for the project. This make take up to 21 days. The Use case diagram also helps to how and what features can be used by people. The Initiation consists of the steps which provides detail knowledge about the topic to start working on the project.

Then the data collection for the project is carried out to make the DBMS of a proposed project. The planning may take up to 5-10 days. DBMS helps to build systematic data management system and normalizing the database so that it will take less storage. Then I will be designing system design which is the sketch of application requirement and the expected outcome of the application. It is necessary to design application before developing application because it will be easy to design application and make change changes according to client before the project development starts. To design all the system design, it may take up to 10 - 15 days and also depends upon feedback provided by client.

Then the development part will be started. Completing all the requirement and research required in this project, we will be developing the application accordingly. This process might take up to 2-3 months, but the delivery of the application will provide according to the feature according to the timebox. The development is divided into two sections i.e., Backend and Fronted Development. All responses of app are depending upon backend development. Frontend Development is the design of website. It is necessary to make website user-friendly and attractive so that non-technical people can feel comfortable and easy while using this application.

After the development is completed, it is mandatory to do testing of application because there might be certain bugs which we cannot see and certain bug to make secured. It is like check all the application function and finding loophole and fixing it. It might take up to 12- 16 days.

After completing all the development part and testing part. Then the I will be doing the documentation part. This will be final process of completing project. It will carry all the documentation of the development, research, methodology, testing and required materials of this project. The documentation is important part because in documentation all the details, features, roles, and responsibilities, etc. are written. This documentation is used give more information our app for IT field or non-IT field. This may take up to more than one month. After that, I will be looking forward to rechecking multiple times and submitting the project in RTE classroom.

9.2. Appendix B: Project Risks, Threads and Contingency Plan

9.2.1. Risk and Threats

SN	Risk Description	Probability	Impact	Contingency Plans
1	Hardware and technologies that are incompatible	Medium	High	Prior to using an app, make sure it is compatible with it.
2	Disruption of Light and Internet	Low	High	Creating a backup of the data, have a fast internet connection and battery backup.
3	Crash of Hardware or Software	Low	High	The data is being backed up in the cloud.
4	Technically difficulties might occur.	Medium	High	Have a proper study over internet and consult with respective supervisors.
5	All the information may not be available on the internet	Medium	Medium	Seeking assistance from the teachers who are good at information
6	Misleading information can occur in a variety of ways while finding the resources.	Low	High	Taking the resources from authentic sites and following it up with the supervisors.

There are so many other features which might be included in the web application if all the expected outcomes and deliverables are developed in the time. Some of these features are listed below.

Probable Additional Features:

- Online shopping platform for the people where they could buy all the necessary cricket kits and accessories.
- A section where players can book the enrolled tutors or coach for the proper guidance or practice.

9.3. Appendix C: Resource Requirement

9.3.1. Hardware

Computer or Laptop	A laptop/computer is required to create and develop the database and website of NCS indoor cricket. Also, all the report of the project is done and maintained in laptop/computer.
Camera	Camera is required to capture all the pictures for the website of players playing cricket. It is necessary for the website's various section.
Internet	For the research and learning purpose a good internet, proper ethernet cable, and a high-end router is required.
Other Hardware Required	Other hardware such as storage devices, external wires, and a good environment during the development is required.

9.3.2. Software

Balsamiq Wireframes	Wireframe is required to structure the website during the initial stage before the development in code.
Figma	Using Figma all the mockup designs are designed of the website.
Sublime	Sublime is an IDE where codes of Django is written and maintained.
Django	Django framework is used for the development of the website.
Web Browser	Web Browser is used to see the outcome of the website that is being developed.
MySQL	MySQL is a free and open- source relational database management system. It is used for larger projects.
Terminals	Terminals is used to connect the server for the website.
Draw.io	Draw.io is used to draw various diagrams such as class diagram, sequence diagram, use case diagram and so on.

Microsoft word	Using Microsoft word all the reports and required documentation are made ready and maintained.
----------------	--

9.4. Appendix D: Milestone

Milestone 1: Topic Selection

The topic selection is first thing which needs to be done so that topic will be approved by the supervisor.

Milestone 2: Researching about the background

The topic which has been approved should be research background and use of the application to solve the problem.

Milestone 3: Collecting and gathering all the data and information

After completing research then we need to collect all the data about the topic.

Milestone 4: Research about methodology

The project should be done within methodology so that it will complete within given time period. There are many methodologies which be found but we need to do within only one methodology. So, I need to find one methodology which will be suitable for the project.

Milestone 5: Selecting the methodology

Various methodologies are suitable for different types of projects so selecting the suitable methodology is the one of the changeling tasks because after selecting methodology we need to do rest of the task ordering to the methodology.

Milestone 6: Finalizing the framework, programming language and database.

The programming language, framework and database can also be found in large quantity. So, we need to find suitable and good knowledge framework, programming language and database in early stage so that we don't need to change in the middle of the project.

Milestone 7: Making Wireframe and mockup

The wireframe and design of the application is important because we need to full fill the desire outcome of client. If we can confirm design before development, then it will be easy to develop application according to the client.

Milestone 8: Designing the normalized database

The normalized database is also important thing before developing the application because we do not have to change in the middle of the project, we can simply update certain row or table.

Milestone 9: Interim Report

This milestone is the half part of the completing the application. It is important for this project because all the expected outcome and research part will be completed in this period.

Milestone 10: Completing the Software Requirement Software (SRS)

All the requirement of the software should be listed on Software Requirement Software (SRS) so that technical and non-technical field people can understand who the project is going on and update in the future according to it.

Milestone 11: Completing frontend development

The development part will be started from developing frontend development. The development of frontend development does not take a lot of time and we can view the project before completing.

Milestone 12: Completing any one feature of development

The most important part will be completed in this phase because it will cover main feature of the application.

Milestone 13: Completing minimum required of application

Then we will focus on completing minimum requirement of the application so that it can be delivered on time.

Milestone 14: Adding content in the application

After completion of the application then we will be adding demo content in the application.

Milestone 15: Completing the document required to complete final year project.

The main important thing is document because everything about application is explained in the documentation which will be very helpful to about the application purpose, use and how it is be worked.

Milestone 16: Testing everything on the application

The milestones help to complete development part. This achieve is big step of success of this project. Then another most important part will start.

Milestone 18: Submitting the project

The milestones help to know us the project has been successful completed. This achievement helps to free stress and pressure.

Milestone 19: Preparing for viva

The preparation for viva is the most important thing to complete this project.

9.5. Appendix E: Survey

9.5.1. Pre – Survey

Is there any Indoor cricket center near you?

60 responses

Figure 188: Survey 1

How much do you love cricket?

60 responses

Figure 189: Survey 2

Is there any ground in your area to play cricket?

60 responses

Figure 190: Survey 3

Do you think more application should be developed regarding cricket sector?

60 responses

Figure 191: Survey 4

Do you play cricket?

60 responses

Figure 192: Survey 5

Do you think this application will help in developing cricket sector in Nepal?

60 responses

Figure 193: Survey 6

How do you prefer regarding money transaction?

60 responses

Figure 194: Survey 7

How do you get your cricket related news?

60 responses

Figure 195: Survey 8

Do you wish to enroll training with good coach?

60 responses

Figure 196: Survey 9

Do you wish to get update about local cricket event?

60 responses

Figure 197: Survey 10

How many times do you go to play indoor cricket or cricket?

60 responses

Figure 198: Survey 11

How do you preferred to book indoor cricket reservation?

60 responses

Figure 199: Survey 12

Have you ever done indoor cricket booking?

60 responses

Figure 200: Survey 13

9.5.2. Sample of Filled Pre-Survey Form

64 responses

Accepting responses

Summary Question **Individual**

< 1 of 64 >

Responses cannot be edited

NCS Indoor Cricket

NCS Indoor Cricket is the application to book indoor cricket in nepal cricket school which also provide training for the people, news, local tournament and articles about nepal cricket. This application is being develop in order to promote nepali cricket and develop nepali cricket.

***Required**

Your Name? *

Yogesh Bikram Shah

Figure 201: Filled Pre-Survey 1

Your Age? *

21

Email? *

yogeshbikramshah@gmail.com

How much do you love cricket? *

Not at all

Too Much

Option 3

Do you play cricket? *

Yes

No

Figure 202: Filled Pre-Survey 2

Is there any ground in your area to play cricket? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Is there any Indoor cricket center near you? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Have you ever done indoor cricket booking? *

- Yes
- No

Figure 203: Filled Pre-Survey 3

How do you preferred to book indoor cricket reservation? *

Online

On site

How many times do you go to play indoor cricket or cricket? *

Never

Once a week

Twice a week

More than two days a week

Everyday a week

Figure 204: Filled Pre-Survey 4

Do you wish to get update about local cricket event? *

Yes

No

Do you wish to enroll training with good coach? *

Yes

No

Maybe

Figure 205: Filled Pre-Survey 5

How do you get your cricket related news? *

- Television
- Facebook
- Application
- Newspaper

How do you prefer regarding money transaction? *

- E-sewa
- Khalti
- Mobile Banking
- Cash In Hand

Figure 206: Filled Pre-Survey 6

How do you get your cricket related news? *

- Television
- Facebook
- Application
- Newspaper

How do you prefer regarding money transaction? *

- E-sewa
- Khalti
- Mobile Banking
- Cash In Hand

Figure 207: Filled Pre-Survey 7

Do you think this application will help in developing cricket sector in Nepal? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Do you think more application should be developed regarding cricket sector? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Is there any feedback for this project?

I really hope this project will uplift the cricket industry however it would be great if an ecommerce feature would be added where I could find cricket accessories and kits

Figure 208: Filled Pre-Survey 8

9.5.3. Post – Survey

NCS Indoor Cricket

NCS Indoor Cricket is the application to book indoor cricket in nepal cricket school which also provide training for the people, news, local tournament and articles about nepal cricket. This application is being develop in order to promote nepali cricket and develop nepali cricket.

1. How much would you rate the applicant according to your experience? *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Figure 209: Post Survey 1

⋮

2. Did the application meet your expectations? *

yes

no

3. Was the application user friendly? *

yes

no

4. Did you find it easy to use booking feature than other booking application? *

yes

No

Other...

Figure 210: Post Survey 2

5. Would you agree that local event feature in the application is useful? *

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

6. Would you agree that News feature in the application is useful? *

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

Figure 211: Post Survey 3

7. Would you agree that Blog feature in the application is useful?

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

8. Did you find feature that you needed in the cricket booking application? *

yes

No

Figure 212: Post Survey 4

9. Which feature would you recommend this application to your friend and family? *

- Booking
- Events
- News
- Blog
- Online Payment
- All of the above

10. Please rate online payment features in the application. *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Figure 213: Post Survey 5

11. Was there any problem while booking the indoor cricket? *

Yes

No

12. Was there any problem while login into the application? *

Yes

No

13. Was there any problem while registering in the application? *

Yes

No

Figure 214: Post Survey 6

14. How much useful did you find this application? *

Short-answer text

15. What could we improve in this application?

Short-answer text

Figure 215: Post Survey 7

9.5.4. Sample of Filled Post-Survey Form

NCS Indoor Cricket

NCS Indoor Cricket is the application to book indoor cricket in nepal cricket school which also provide training for the people, news, local tournament and articles about nepal cricket. This application is being develop in order to promote nepali cricket and develop nepali cricket.

 Draft saved

* Required

1. How much would you rate the applicant according to your experience? *

1

2

3

4

5

2. Did the application meet your expectations? *

yes

no

Figure 216: Filled Post Survey 1

3. Was the application user friendly? *

yes

no

4. Did you find it easy to use booking feature than other booking application? *

yes

No

Other: _____

5. Would you agree that local event feature in the application is useful? *

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

Figure 217: Filled Post Survey 2

6. Would you agree that News feature in the application is useful? *

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

7. Would you agree that Blog feature in the application is useful?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Clear selection

Figure 218:: Filled Post Survey 3

8. Did you find feature that you needed in the cricket booking application? *

yes

No

9. Which feature would you recommend this application to your friend and family? *

Booking

Events

News

Blog

Online Payment

All of the above

Figure 219:: Filled Post Survey 4

10. Please rate online payment features in the application. *

1

2

3

4

5

11. Was there any problem while booking the indoor cricket? *

Yes

No

12. Was there any problem while login into the application? *

Yes

No

Figure 220: Filled Post Survey 5

13. Was there any problem while registering in the application? *

Yes

No

14. How much useful did you find this application? *

Very Useful

15. What could we improve in this application?

News section should be updated day by day

Submit

Clear form

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

Figure 221: Filled Post Survey 6

9.6. Appendix H: Designs

ER Diagram

Figure 222: ERD of NCS Indoor Cricket

9.6.1. Class Diagram

Class Diagram is the static view of the application, which is not only used for visualizing, describing, and documenting different aspects of a system but also for constructing executable code of the software application.

(tutorialspoint, 2021)

Figure 223: Class Diagram of NCS Indoor Cricket

9.6.2. Flow Chart

Figure 224 Flow Chart

9.6.3. Wireframe

Web Wireframe

Figure 225: Web Wireframe of Home Page

Figure 226: Web Wireframe of Booking Indoor Cricket

Figure 227: Web Wireframe of Article

Figure 228: Web Wireframe of Events

Figure 229: Web Wireframe of News

Figure 230: Web Wireframe of Feedback Form

Figure 231: Web Wireframe of FAQ

Figure 232: Web Wireframe of Register

Figure 233: Web Wireframe of Log In

9.6.5. Mobile Wireframe

Figure 234: Mobile Wireframe of Home Page

Figure 235: Mobile Wireframe of Login

Figure 236: Mobile Wireframe of Article

Figure 237: Mobile Wireframe of Feedback

Figure 238: Mobile Wireframe of News

Figure 239: Mobile Wireframe of Register

Figure 240: Mobile Wireframe of Event

Figure 241: Mobile Wireframe of Booking

9.7. Appendix J: Screenshots of the system

Figure 242 System Registration Page

Figure 243 System Login Page

Figure 244 System Home Page

Figure 245 System Home Page-2

Figure 246 System Home page News Section

Figure 247 System Home Page Footer Section

ABOUT

Nepal Cricket school is an indoor facility where the players receive professional cricket training sessions from the finest coaches of the country 6 days a week, twice a day , one in the morning from 6 am- 8am & the other in the afternoon from 4 pm - 6 pm. Faster, higher, stronger. The Olympic motto could perhaps be applied to web design and this is what we look for at Awwwards: sites that go beyond the conventional, where no man has gone before. They work better and are more usable, they are smooth to navigate to find the information you seek. They are strong, consistent, well-built from back-end forward. We give you this entry on sensational websites related to sport. Because in web design as in everything else, if the human being has limits ... we haven't reached them yet.

OUR TEAM

**Ram Kumar
Basnet**
CEO

Shyam Rai
Trainer

**Mithun
Chamling**
Trainer

Hari Karki
Trainer

Figure 248 System About Section

CONTACT US

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Commodo consectetur debitis delectus eius ex excepturi fugit itaque magnam, modi neque, pariatur possimus praesentium recusandae similique unde veritatis voluptas voluptate voluptatum.

You can send us your queries and we will get back to you as soon as possible.

LOCATION

Figure 249 System Feedback Section

FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS

What are the benefits of NCS?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Cupiditate expedita ipsam modi pariatur quisquam. Accusamus aliquam, delectus dolor doloribus dolorum exercitationem explicabo fugiat, incidunt minima perferendis repudiandae sapiente voluptatibus voluptatum?

How easy is it to use NCS website?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Amet at consectetur dolor eligendi eos fugit incidunt iure laborum, libero modi, molestias nam nulla quaerat repudiandae similique suscipit unde vel vero.

What is the main motive of NCS?

lorem

Can NCS improve for my cricket skills?

Yes, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing elit. Ab asperiores consequuntur cum, earum eligendi excepturi expedita in inventore necessitatibus nulla pariatur praesentium rem rerum sapiente sunt suscipit tenetur vero voluptatibus.

Figure 250 System FAQ

Figure 251 System Events Section

Figure 252 System News Section

9.8. Appendix L: Initial SRS

Purpose

Software Requirements Specification (SRS) document is developed to provide a detailed information about functionalities that are required for application that helps people to book indoor ground. This document defines features that are required for the web application. This document shows detailed information about non-functional specification, Features, functionalities, hardware, software, and various other technical dependencies is being explained in this report.

Intended Audiences and Reading Suggestions

This document is developed for the system developers to develop web application which helps people book the indoor ground. The end user for this application will be public who are willing play indoor cricket, attend event and join the events. The user can also select the coach and enroll in training. This document will be a blueprint to develop a system. The users can use this document to obtain knowledge about the features that are required in the web application.

Project Scope

This application is being developed for NCS indoor cricket for booking the indoor ground. The NCS agenda focuses on children and youth who are very actively involved in cricket. Due to the less playground in the valley NCS is building more indoor ground for the people who are interested in cricket. They also provide facilities like trainer for the beginner. The trainer helps people to improve their game and technique so they can improve their performance. They organize local level events for the people to participate. And they provide news, article, and blog about cricket in local, national, and international level. So, people can be updated about cricket. The market in this field is increasing rapidly and more people are interested in indoor cricket. So, people can be updated about cricket. Nowadays people are focused in their health so they are interested in various sports.

Overall Description

2.1 User Needs System features

Some of the features that should be included in the android app are as follows:

Payment

Once user book the ground and booking is confirmed and the user have to make payment.

Booking

Users must book the ground according to available time and date.

Profile

Users can view and edit their personal information and password.

Event

User can check upcoming events and participate the event.

News

User can check the latest news about international, national cricket.

Feedback option

Users will also be facilitated to send their feedback to the developer so that necessary changes can be carried out in the application.

Article

User can read blogs and local level articles.

Training

User can view coach and enroll in training.

User class and characteristics

Following are the class of users who will be using this NCS indoor cricket. Application with their roles:

UC1: Normal User

UC1.1

Simple user interface for operation.

UC1.2

Book ground with the help of application.

UC1.3

Obtain knowledge about NCS indoor cricket.

UC1.4

View a events and register.

UC1.5

Send feedback for further improvement.

Figure 253 Use Case Customer Diagram

Figure 254 Activity Diagram Admin

UC3: Admin

UC3.1

Check for logical errors and provide updates for bugs fixes.

UC3.2

Add additional features.

UC3.3

Implement Database

UC3.4

Register a trainer.

Figure 255 Activity Diagram Customer

Figure 256 Use Case Diagram Admin

Operating Environment

OE1

In the present context, NCS indoor cricket is focused only on the Web platform. Future planning is to run this application even in other platform like android, IOS and develop a desktop application if possible. Web platform also runs in mobile browser. The application is responsive to different device.

OE2

NCS indoor cricket operates in any types of browsers. Everyone requires browser to access the web platform.

Assumptions and Dependencies

AS1: The application is targeted mainly for the youth and children who are interested in cricket.

AS2: There will be connection of the application with the database.

AS3: Developed application can be use only online.

AS4: The documentation and reports of the system are only accessible to special persons like client and developer.

Functional Requirements

Booking

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.01	All the users can book the platform with available time and date.
	System Requirement
	SR.01 User can view the booking information.
	SR.02 To provide vaccination, they need to call in given contact number. To book the platform, they need to provide number and information.
SR.03 Give their address and do payment.	
FR.02	Logins feature is required.

News

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.03	All the users can view the international, national and local level news posted by NCS indoor cricket whenever the respected organization will post news.
	System Requirement
	SR.01 Everyone can read the news.
FR.04	Logins feature is required.

Events

FR.01	All the users will be able to view the events section whenever the respected organization will post any events	
	System Requirement	
	SR.01	On opening the application users will be able to register for the upcoming events.
	SR.02	To register, user need to fill up the fields
	SR.03	Fill up all the required fields and register the user information in the application.
FR.02	Login feature is required	

Article

Req.ID	Requirement Description	
FR.03	All the users can view the article posted by the respected organization.	
	System Requirement	
	SR.01	User can read the article posted by the admin.
FR.04	Logins feature is required.	

Profile

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.01	User will be able to view and edit their personal information and change their password
	System Requirement
	SR.01 Users need to fill information correctly
SR.02 Fields cannot be blank.	
FR.02	Login feature is required.

Feedback option

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.01	All the users can send feedback.
	System Requirement
	SR.01 Users can write their queries or suggestions in this tab
SR.02 Fill up all the required fields and register the user information in the application.	
FR.02	Login feature required.

Payment

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.01	After booking the user can make payment.
	System Requirement
	SR.01 User can choose payment method.
FR.02	Login feature required.

Training

Req.ID	Requirement Description
FR.01	User can view coach and enroll in training.
	System Requirement
	SR.01 User can select coach and fill the form.
FR.02	Login feature required.

External Interfaces Requirements

Hardware

Since, web application is being develop, user should have their own laptop/desktop to use this application. The web application will use the hardware

Software

The application will be using standard software resources required for developing application and maintaining database. The software that are required for this project are PyCharm Professional for coding, Django framework and MySQL database to store various data and information that are required for the application.

System Features

- **Booking**
User can book the ground according to available time and date.
- **News**
User can read recent news about cricket.
- **Article**
User can read, view article, blog posted by admin.
- **Training**
. User can choose coach and enroll in training.
- **Feedback**
Users can write their queries or suggestions and send the feedback.
- **Payment**
Payment can be done after booking with various methods.

- **Profile**
User can view and change their personal details and change their password.
- **Events**
User can view upcoming events and register for the events.

Nonfunctional Requirement

- **User Profile**
User will have their profile.
- **Home Page**
Home page will be used to make customer attractive.

er

9.9. Appendix M: Gantt Chart

Figure 257: Gantt Chart

Gantt chart is the representation of the tasks that are completed or the tasks that are to be completed in a timeline format. It represents when and for how long the processes are carried out. In the above Gantt chart, we can see the work breakdown structure which is divided and calculating the time period to develop this app. There are also various milestones set throughout the time duration which is shown in the milestone section above. The total time for the completion of the project from the beginning is approximately 9 months. The timeline starts from the date when proposal of fyp was submitted and ends with the submission of the project.

After the interim the development phase was started from 15 November to 16 Feb. Many front end part was already done in the interim so only few changes was required in this phase. The backend part was a bit difficult which took a longer period of time. In the backend python was used as a programming language and Django as framework and in database MySQL was used in the application.

In the testing phase different testing was conducted. Test logical error, find bugs, get best possible way to record data in database and Debugging all the bugs were done. While developing the system I have simultaneous tested the application and debugging it. I also research on how to collect data in database in the best possible way, I also consulted with the teacher in this field. After the overall application is ready, I tested the system and found different bugs and I started to be debugging them.

I decided to start the documentation after the application was fully developed but for the convenience, I started the documentation during the testing phase. The documentation nearly took a month to complete. I have completed the application according to the gantt chart and kept updated about my progress to the respected teachers.

9.10. Appendix N: Meeting Log

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 1	Date: November 18, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Methodology b. Work Breakdown Structure c. Gantt Chart Achievements: a. Completed Methodology b. Completed WBS Problems: Problem on Gantt Chart Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Gantt chart and proposal	

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Figure 258: Logbook 1

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 2	Date: November 23, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. WBS b. Milestones c. Gantt Chart d. Proposal	
Achievements: a. Completed WBS b. Completed Milestones c. Completed Gantt Chart d. Completed Proposal	
Problems: Problem on Gantt Chart	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Proposal and review	

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Figure 259: Logbook 2

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 3	Date: November 23, 2021
Start Time: 3:00 PM	End Time: 5:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Proposal b. Interim Report	
Achievements: a. Completed proposal	
Problems: Problem on WBS	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Introduction of Interim Report b. Background of Interim Report	

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Figure 260: Logbook 3

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 4	Date: November 26, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Background b. Wireframes d. Interim report requirements	
Achievements: a. Completed Background	
Problems: Problem on Wireframes	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of background. b. Completion of WBS c. Completion of Wireframes.	

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Figure 261: Logbook 4

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 5	Date: December 03, 2021
Start Time: 3:00 PM	End Time: 5:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Background of Interim Report b. ERD c. Class Diagram d. Development	
Achievements: a. Completed Introduction of Interim Report b. Completed Background	
Problems: Problem on ER-Diagram	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Use Case Diagram b. Initial Wireframe	

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Figure 262: Logbook 5

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 6	Date: December 10 2021
Start Time: 3:00 PM	End Time: 5:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Wireframe b. Use Case Diagram c. Similar Projects d. Requirements for projects	
Achievements: a. Completed Use Case Diagram b. Completed Comparing to other similar projects	
Problems: Problem on background elaboration.	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Interim report and review	

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Figure 263: Logbook 6

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 7	Date: December 13, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Wireframe b. Use Case Diagram c. Similar Projects d. Interim report requirements	
Achievements: a. Completed Use Case Diagram b. Completed Comparing to other similar projects c. Completed Wireframe d. Completed Class Diagram	
Problems: Problem on Normalization	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Interim report and review	

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Figure 264: Logbook 7

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 8	Date: December 14, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Normalization b. Use Case Diagram c. Interim report requirements	
Achievements: a. Completed Normalization c. Completed Wireframe d. Completed Case Diagram	
Problems: No Problems	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Interim report and review	

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Figure 265: Logbook 8

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 9	Date: December 24, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Front End b. Backend	
Achievements: a. Completed design of frontend	
Problems: Problem on Backend	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of User Registering	

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Figure 266: Logbook 9

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 10	Date: December 31, 2021
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Django b. Admin Login c. User Login	
Achievements: a. Completed User Login b. Completed Admin Login	
Problems: Problem on User registering	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of User registering	

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Figure 267: Logbook 10

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 11	Date: February 25, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. User Registering b. Booking	
Achievements: a. Completed User Registering	
Problems: Problem on Booking part	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Booking part	

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Figure 268: Logbook 11

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 12	Date: March 04, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. API b. Payment segment c. News	
Achievements: a. Completed News segment designing b. Completed displaying map location	
Problems: Problem on Payment	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Payment portal	

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Figure 269: Logbook 12

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 13	Date: March 11, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Project Artefact b. Final Report Content Requirement c. Development of app d. Payment Portal	
Achievements: a. Completed Payment b. Completed Full designing of app	
Problems: Problem on Report	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Some given topic of FYP report.	

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Figure 270: Logbook 13

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 14	Date: March 25, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Development of app b. Activity Diagram c. FYP report requirements	
Achievements: a. Completed some Activity Diagram b. Completed Development of app	
Problems: Problem on Report	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of discussed topic of report and review	

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Figure 271: Logbook 14

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 15	Date: April 1, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Testing and analysis b. Legal social and ethical issues c. Survey	
Achievements: a. Completed Survey	
Problems: Problem on Testing	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of Testing and review	

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Figure 272: Logbook 15

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet

FYP Logbook Entry Sheet	
Meeting No: 16	Date: April 15, 2022
Start Time: 2:00 PM	End Time: 3:00 PM
Items Discussed: a. Testing and Analysis b. Critical Analysis	
Achievements: a. Completed Analysis b. Completed Comparing to other similar projects c. Completed Wireframe d. Completed Class Diagram	
Problems: Problem on Testing	
Tasks for Next Meeting: (Write down the task assigned to you by your supervisor) a. Completion of FYP report, Testing and review	

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Figure 273: Logbook 16

9.11. User Manual

- Register
- Login
- Profile
- Booking
- Article
- Events
- Blogs
- News
- Training
- Subscription
- Payment
- Feedback
- FAQ

1. Launch the Application

2. User Register

- a) Launch the application
- b) Fill up all the fields
- c) Press register button
- d) User Registers Successful

3. Login

- a) Fill up username fields
- b) Fills up password fields
- c) Press Login button
- d) User Sign in Successful

4. Dashboard

After logging in, user will be able to view the about us section. User can also view short section of blogs, news, and event section. User will have access to go to profile, booking, events, article, news, blog from top navigation bar. Also, through other activities by opening drawer.

- a) Feedback
- b) FAQ

5. Profile

After logging in, user will be able to view their own profile. User will have access to edit the profile by pressing edit button and also change the password.

- a) Edit Profile
- b) Change Password

6. Booking

After logging in, user will be able to book the ground. Users need to select the available date, time and duration. User will also need to select the payment method like COD (cash on hand), khalti and Esewa. After filling up the required data user need to press book now button. After Confirming the booking user will be navigate to online payment.

- a) Book now
- b) Payment page

7. Article

In the top navigation bar, there is a article section where user can view the articles. After clicking in the article section user be able to view article about cricket.

- a) Article

8. Events

After logging in, user will be able to view the events posted by the organizations. User can be a part of the organized program as per their feasible time. User can also find events in drawer.

- a) Events
- b) Drawer

9. Blogs

After logging in, user will be able to view the blog posted by the organization by different publisher. User can read different article about cricket by different publisher.

- a) Blogs

10. News

In the top navigation bar user can view news section. In the news section user can read different news about international and national cricket.

- a) News

11. Training

After logging in, user can go to training section. In the training section user can select the couch and enrol in the training.

- a) Training

12. Subscription

After coming to home page, there will be a navigation bar where user can see the subscription section. After clicking in subscription section user will be displayed to subscription form where user can see various packages. User will have to select the package button as per their requirement. After selecting the package button user will be navigate to online payment.

- a) Subscription
- b) Buy Package

13. Feedback

User can go to the feedback section where user can fill out the fields. User can either press submit or cancel button.

- a) Cancel
- b) Submit

14. FAQ

User can view frequently answer question in FAQ section.

15. Payment-

Making online payment after booking and selecting different subscription package user will have to make the online payment through esewa an online payment method.

9.13. Appendix O: Development Work

9.13.1. Requirement.txt

```
asgiref==3.5.0
certifi==2021.10.8
charset-normalizer==2.0.12
Django==4.0.4
django-crispy-forms==1.14.0
idna==3.3
PyMySQL==1.0.2
requests==2.27.1
sqlparse==0.4.2
tzdata==2022.1
urllib3==1.26.9
```

9.13.2. Registration

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class RegistrationConfig(AppConfig):
    name = 'registration'
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path , include
from django.views.generic.base import TemplateView
from django.http import request

from . import views

urlpatterns = [
    path('', include('django.contrib.auth.urls')) ,
    path('', TemplateView.as_view(template_name='registration/home.html'),
name='home'),
    path('signup/', views.SignUp.as_view(), name='signup'),
    # path('about/', TemplateView.as_view,
template_name='registration/about.html', name='about'),
]
```

views.py

```
from django.contrib.auth.forms import UserCreationForm
from django.urls import reverse_lazy
from django.views import generic
from django.shortcuts import render

class SignUp(generic.CreateView):
    form_class = UserCreationForm
    success_url = reverse_lazy('login')
    template_name = 'registration/signup.html'

class show_about(generic.CreateView):
    template_name = 'registration/about.html'
```

9.13.3. News

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin
from .models import News_post

# Register your models here.

admin.site.register(News_post)
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class NewsConfig(AppConfig):
    default_auto_field = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'
    name = 'news'
```

Form.py

```
from django import forms
from .models import News_post

class NewsForm(forms.ModelForm):

    class Meta:
        model = News_post
        fields = ('news_title', 'news_description', 'news_snippets',
'news_publisher')
        labels = {
            'news_title': 'News Title (Enter the title please)',
            'news_description': 'News Description (Enter the news description
please)',
            'news_snippets': 'News Snippets (Enter the news snippets
please)',
            'news_publisher': 'News Publisher (Enter the news publisher
please)'
        }
```

Models.py

```
from django.db import models
from audioop import reverse
# from django.contrib.auth.models import User
# from login.models import Admin

# Create your models here.

class News_post(models.Model):
    news_title = models.CharField(max_length=255, null=True)
    news_description = models.TextField()
    news_snippets = models.CharField(max_length=255)
    news_publisher = models.CharField(max_length=500)
    # admin_id = models.ForeignKey(Admin, on_delete=models.CASCADE)

    # def __str__(self):
    #     return self.news_title

    # def get_absolute_url(self):
    #     return reverse('news')
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path
from . import views

urlpatterns = [
    path('', views.news_main, name='news_main'),
    path('<int:id>', views.news_detail, name='news_detail'),
    path('insert', views.news_form, name='news_insert'),
    path('update/<int:id>', views.news_form, name='news_update'),
    path('delete/<int:id>', views.news_delete, name='news_delete'),
    path('list', views.news_list, name='news_list')
]
```

Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render, redirect
from .form import NewsForm
from .models import News_post
```

```

from django.contrib.admin.views.decorators import staff_member_required
# Create your views here.

def news_main(request):
    context = {'news_main': News_post.objects.all()}
    return render(request, "news.html", context)

def news_detail(request, id):
    context = {'news_detail': News_post.objects.filter(pk=id)}
    return render(request, "news_detail.html", context)

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def news_list(request):
    context = {'news_list': News_post.objects.all()}
    return render(request, "news_list.html", context)

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def news_form(request, id=0):
    if request.method == "GET":
        if id == 0:
            form = NewsForm()
        else:
            news = News_post.objects.get(pk=id)
            form = NewsForm(instance=news)
        return render(request, "news_form.html", {'form': form})
    else:
        if id == 0:
            form = NewsForm(request.POST)
        else:
            news = News_post.objects.get(pk=id)
            form = NewsForm(request.POST, instance=news)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
        return redirect('/news/list')

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def news_delete(request, id):
    news = News_post.objects.get(pk=id)
    news.delete()
    return redirect('/news/list')

```

9.13.4. Manager

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin
from .models import DateAndSlot , AvailableRooms , Field
# Register your models here.

allModels = [

    DateAndSlot ,
    AvailableRooms ,
    Field

]

admin.site.register(allModels)
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class ManagerConfig(AppConfig):
    name = 'manager'
```

Forms.py

```
from django.core.exceptions import ValidationError
from django.forms import ModelForm
from django import forms

import datetime
from .models import AvailableRooms , DateAndSlot, Field

#Form for taking inputs of DateSlotModel
class DateInput(forms.DateInput):
    input_type = 'date'

class NumberInput(forms.NumberInput):
    input_type = 'number'

#Forms for adding a particular slots
class DateSlotForm(forms.ModelForm):
    class Meta:
        model = DateAndSlot
        fields = ('booking_date', 'booking_slot', 'booking_price')
        widgets = {
            'booking_date': DateInput(),
            'room_price': NumberInput()
        }

#Form for taking inputs of AvailableRooms
class AddRoomForm(ModelForm):
    class Meta:
        model = AvailableRooms
        fields = ['fields_available']

        # model = Room
        # fields = ['price']
        # widgets = {
        #     'price': NumberInput()
        # }

#Form taking inputs in form of Date
class DateRangeForm(forms.Form):
    start_date = forms.DateField(label = 'From Date', required = True ,
    widget = DateInput() )
    end_date = forms.DateField(label = 'End Date', required = True , widget
= DateInput() )
```

Models.py

```
#Django utils import
from django.db import models
from django.contrib import messages
from django.core.exceptions import ValidationError
from django.core.management.base import BaseCommand, CommandError

#Import datetime libraray
from datetime import datetime, timedelta
import datetime

SLOT_CHOICES = (
    ('Slot 1' , 'Morning : 5 AM') ,
    ('Slot 2' , 'Morning : 7 AM') ,
    ('Slot 3' , 'Morning : 9 AM') ,
    ('Slot 4' , 'Morning : 11 AM') ,
    ('Slot 5' , 'Afternoon : 1 PM') ,
    ('Slot 6' , 'Afternoon : 3 PM') ,
    ('Slot 7' , 'Evening : 5 PM') ,
    ('Slot 8' , 'Evening : 7 PM') ,
    ('Slot 9' , 'Night : 5 PM') ,
)

class DateAndSlot(models.Model):
    booking_date = models.DateField(blank = False )
    booking_slot = models.CharField(max_length=225, choices = SLOT_CHOICES,
    blank = False)
    rooms_added = models.BooleanField(default = False)
    booking_price = models.IntegerField(default = 3500)

    # DateAndSlot model methods for validation
    class Meta :
        unique_together = ('booking_date', 'booking_slot', 'booking_price')

    def save(self, *args, **kwargs ):
        if self.booking_date < datetime.date.today():
            raise ValidationError("date must be in future")
        super(DateAndSlot, self).save(*args, **kwargs)

    def handle(self, *args, **options):
        DateAndSlot.objects.filter(booking_date - timedelta(days=1)).delete()
        self.stdout.write('Deleted objects older than 10 days')

    def __str__(self):
        return ("Date : {0} \n Slot: {1}" .format(self.booking_date ,
self.booking_slot, self.booking_price ))

# Model for declaring rooms for particular time slot
```

```

class AvailableRooms(models.Model):
    booking_date_slot = models.OneToOneField(DateAndSlot ,
on_delete=models.CASCADE , blank=False , unique = True)
    fields_available = models.IntegerField(null = True)

    def __str__(self):
        return ("Booking Date : {0} \n Booking Slot: {1} \n Available Rooms:
{2} " .format(self.booking_date_slot.booking_date ,
self.booking_date_slot.booking_slot , self.booking_date_slot.booking_price,
self.fields_available ))

#Model for generating rooms object for particular slot.
class Field(models.Model):
    chosen_date_slot = models.ForeignKey(DateAndSlot , on_delete =
models.CASCADE )
    room_number      = models.IntegerField()
    is_booked       = models.BooleanField(default = False)
    price            = models.IntegerField(default = 5000)

    def __str__(self):
        return ("Room No : {0} => {1}".format(self.room_number ,
self.chosen_date_slot, self.price))

```

Urls.py

```
from . import views
from django.urls import path

urlpatterns = [
    path('managerdashboard', views.managerDashboard, name =
'managerDashboard' ) ,
    path('addfield', views.addRooms, name = 'addFields') ,
    path('addfield/<int:slot_id>' , views.addRooms_2 , name = 'addFields') ,
    path('addslot', views.addSlot, name = 'addSlot' ) ,
    path('getAllBookedDates', views.getAllBookedDates, name =
'getAllBookedDates' ) ,
    path('getAllBookedDates/<int:slot_id>' , views.getSlotBookingDetail ,
name = 'getSlotBookingDetail' ) ,
    path('getAllBookedDates/userBookingDetails/<int:booking_id>' ,
views.userBookingDetail , name = 'userBookingDetail' ) ,
]
```

Views.py

```
#imports from django utils
from django.shortcuts import render , redirect , get_object_or_404
from django.http import HttpResponse
from django.contrib import messages
from django.urls import reverse
from django.contrib.admin.views.decorators import staff_member_required

#import datetime library
from datetime import date, timedelta

#import models and forms
from .models import AvailableRooms , DateAndSlot , Field
from .forms import AddRoomForm , DateSlotForm , DateRangeForm
from customer.models import RoomBooking

# view for manager dashboard.
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def managerDashboard(request):
    return render(request , 'manager/managerDashboard.html')

#view for adding slot using DateSlotForm.
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def addSlot(request):

    if request.POST:
        form_ds = DateSlotForm(request.POST)
        if form_ds.is_valid():
            form_ds.save()
            messages.success(request, 'Slot Added Successfully!')
            return addRooms(request)
```

```

form_ds = DateSlotForm()
content = { 'form' : form_ds }
return render(request , 'manager/addSlot.html' , content)

# View for displaying all slots.
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def addRooms(request , slot_id = None):
    slot_list_booked = DateAndSlot.objects.filter(rooms_added =
True).order_by('booking_date') # query for slot for which rooms are allotted
    slot_list_unbooked = DateAndSlot.objects.filter(rooms_added =
False).order_by('booking_date') # query for slot for which rooms are not
allotted

    content = {
        'slot_list_booked': slot_list_booked ,
        'slot_list_unbooked' : slot_list_unbooked
    }
    return render(request , 'manager/addField.html' , content)

#View for adding room
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def addRooms_2(request , slot_id = None):
    selected_slot_obj = DateAndSlot.objects.get(pk = slot_id) # get slot for
a particular id .

    if request.POST:
        # generate room objects for a particular slot
        n = AvailableRooms(booking_date_slot = selected_slot_obj )
        get_room_count_form = AddRoomForm(request.POST , instance = n)
        # booking_price =

        if get_room_count_form.is_valid():
            get_room_count_form.save()
            n.save()

            for room_no in range(1 ,n.rooms_available+1):
                r = Field(chosen_date_slot = selected_slot_obj , room_number
= room_no )
                r.save()

            ds = DateAndSlot.objects.get(pk = slot_id)
            ds.rooms_added = True
            ds.save()
            return managerDashboard(request)

    get_room_count_form = AddRoomForm()

    content = {
        'form': get_room_count_form ,

```

```

    }
    return render(request , 'manager/addField2.html' , content)

# get all the slot dates for which user has done bookings
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def getAllBookedDates(request):
    booking_dates = DateAndSlot.objects.filter(rooms_added =
True).order_by('booking_date')
    # room_prices = DateAndSlot.objects.filter(rooms_added =
True).order_by('room_price')
    content = {
        'booking_dates' : booking_dates
        # 'room_prices' : room_prices
    }
    return render(request , 'manager/getAllBookedDates.html' ,content )

# get all the bookings for selected slot
@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def getSlotBookingDetail(request , slot_id):
    bookings_per_date = RoomBooking.objects.filter(booking_date_slot =
slot_id).order_by('booked_room_number')
    # bookings_per_price = RoomBooking.objects.filter(date_price =
slot_id).order_by('date_price')
    content = {
        'bookings_per_date' : bookings_per_date
        # 'bookings_per_price' : bookings_per_price
    }
    return render(request , 'manager/getSlotBookingDetail.html' ,content )

# get details of User Booking .
def userBookingDetail(request , booking_id):
    user_booking_detail = get_object_or_404( RoomBooking , pk = booking_id)
    if request.method == 'POST':
        user_booking_detail.booked_room_number.is_booked = False
        user_booking_detail.booked_room_number.save()
        user_booking_detail.delete()
        messages.success(request, 'Booking Cancelled Successfully!!!')
        return redirect(reverse('getAllBookedDates' ))

    content = {
        'user_booking' : user_booking_detail
    }
    return render(request , 'manager/userBookingDetail.html' , content)

```

9.13.5. FAQ

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin  
  
# Register your models here.
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig  
  
class FaqConfig(AppConfig):  
    default_auto_field = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'  
    name = 'faq'
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path  
from faq import views  
  
urlpatterns = [  
    path('', views.show_faq),  
]  
]
```

Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render  
  
# Create your views here.  
  
def show_faq(request):  
    return render(request, 'faq.html')
```

9.13.6. Events

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin  
  
# Register your models here.
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig  
  
class EventConfig(AppConfig):  
    default_auto_field = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'  
    name = 'events'
```

Forms.py

```
from django import forms  
from .models import Events  
  
class EventsForm(forms.ModelForm):  
  
    class Meta:  
        model = Events  
        fields = ('event_title', 'event_description', 'event_snippet',  
                'event_date_time', 'event_location')  
        labels = {  
            'event_title': 'Event Title (Enter the event title please)',  
            'event_description': 'Event Description (Enter the event  
description please)',  
            'event_snippets': 'Event Snippets (Enter the event snippets  
please)',  
            'event_date_time': 'Event Date (Enter the event publisher  
please)',  
            'event_location': 'Event Location (Enter the event publisher  
please)'  
        }
```

Models.py

```
from audioop import reverse
from django.db import models
from django.contrib.auth.models import User
from django.utils import timezone

# Create your models here.

class Events(models.Model):
    event_title = models.CharField(max_length=500)
    event_description = models.TextField()
    event_snippet = models.CharField(max_length=25)
    event_date_time = models.DateTimeField(default=timezone.now)
    event_location = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    # admin_id = models.ForeignKey(Admin, on_delete=models.CASCADE)

    # def __str__(self):
    #     return self.event_title
    #
    # def get_absolute_url(self):
    #     return reverse('events')
```

Tests.py

```
from django.test import TestCase

# Create your tests here.
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path
from . import views

urlpatterns = [
    path('', views.show_events, name='show_events'),
    path('<int:id>', views.event_detail, name='event_detail'),
    path('insert', views.event_form, name='event_insert'),
    path('update/<int:id>', views.event_form, name='event_update'),
    path('delete/<int:id>', views.event_form, name='event_delete'),
    path('list', views.event_list, name='event_list')
]
```

Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render, redirect
from .forms import EventsForm
from .models import Events
from django.contrib.admin.views.decorators import staff_member_required
# Create your views here.

def show_events(request):
    context = {'show_events': Events.objects.all()}
    return render(request, "event.html", context)

def event_detail(request, id):
    context = {'event_detail': Events.objects.filter(pk=id)}
    return render(request, "event_detail.html", context)

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def event_list(request):
    context = {'event_list': Events.objects.all()}
    return render(request, "event_list.html", context)

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def event_form(request, id=0):
    if request.method == "GET":
        if id == 0:
            form = EventsForm()
        else:
            events = Events.objects.get(pk=id)
            form = EventsForm(instance=events)
        return render(request, "event_form.html", {'form': form})
    else:
        if id == 0:
            form = EventsForm(request.POST)
        else:
            events = Events.objects.get(pk=id)
            form = EventsForm(request.POST, instance=events)
        if form.is_valid():
            form.save()
        return redirect('/events/list')

@staff_member_required(login_url = '/login/')
def event_delete(request, id):
    events = Events.objects.get(pk=id)
    events.delete()
    return redirect('/events/list')
```

9.13.7. Customer

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin
from .models import RoomBooking

# Register your models here.
admin.site.register(RoomBooking)
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class CustomerConfig(AppConfig):
    name = 'customer'
```

Forms.py

```
from django import forms
from manager.models import DateAndSlot
from .models import RoomBooking

class RoomBookingForm(forms.ModelForm):
    class Meta:
        model = RoomBooking
        fields = ('customer_name', 'customer_email', 'customer_contact',
                'booking_purpose', 'payment_method')
```

Models.py

```
from django.db import models
from manager.models import AvailableRooms, DateAndSlot, Field

METHOD = (
    ('Cash', 'Cash'),
    ('Khalti', 'Khalti'),
    ('Esewa', 'Esewa')
)

class RoomBooking(models.Model):
    booking_date_slot = models.ForeignKey(DateAndSlot,
on_delete=models.CASCADE, blank=False)
    booked_room_number = models.OneToOneField(Field, unique = True,
on_delete = models.CASCADE, blank = False, related_name='+')
    bookee_username = models.CharField(max_length = 50, blank = False,
```

```

default = 'Admin')
    # booking_price = modatedels.OneToOneField(Room, on_delete =
models.CASCADE, blank=False)
    # date_price = models.ForeignKey(DateAndSlot, on_delete = models.CASCADE,
related_name='+', default=4500)
    payment_method = models.CharField(max_length=20, choices=METHOD,
default="Cash")
    payment_completed = models.BooleanField(default=False, null=True,
blank=True)

#field to be taken as input
customer_name = models.CharField(max_length = 60 , blank=False)
customer_email = models.EmailField(unique = True, max_length=254)
customer_contact = models.CharField(unique = True , max_length = 12)
booking_purpose = models.CharField(max_length = 254 , blank = True)

def __str__(self):
    return self.customer_name

```

Tests.py

```

from django.test import TestCase

# Create your tests here.

```

Urls.py

```

from django.urls import path
from . import views
from .views import *

urlpatterns = [
    path('', views.customerDashboard , name = "customerDashboard" ) ,
    path('<int:slot_id>/' , views.displayFields , name = 'displayFields') ,
    path('<int:slot_id>/<int:room_id>/' , views.customerRoomBooking , name =
'customerRoomBooking') ,
    path('user-bookings/' , views.getUserBookings , name = 'userRoomBooking')
,
    path('user-bookings/<int:booking_id>/' , views.deatiledUserBooking , name
= 'deatiledUserBooking') ,
    # path('delete/' , views.deleteUserBooking , name = 'deleteUserBooking')
,
    path("esewa-request/" , EsewaRequestView.as_view() , name="esewarequest") ,
    path("esewa-verify/" , EsewaVerifyView.as_view() , name="esewaverify") ,
    path('khalti-request' , KhaltiRequestView.as_view() ,
name='khaltirequest') ,
    path("khalti-verify/" , KhaltiVerifyView.as_view() , name="khaltiverify") ,
]

```

Views.py

```
#Importing django utils
import requests as requests
from django.shortcuts import render , redirect , get_object_or_404
from django.contrib import messages
from django.http import HttpResponse , Http404
from django.urls import reverse
from django.contrib.auth.decorators import login_required

from django.views import View

#Import Model and Forms
from .forms import RoomBookingForm
from manager.models import DateAndSlot , Field , AvailableRooms
from .models import RoomBooking
from django.http import JsonResponse

#import system datetime
import datetime

#Customer Dashboard
def customerDashboard(request):
    if request.user.is_authenticated:
        room_list = Field.objects.filter(is_booked = False) # all unbooked
        room objects

        date_slot_list = []
        for room in room_list:
            if room.chosen_date_slot not in date_slot_list:
                date_slot_list.append(room.chosen_date_slot)

        all_date_slot_list =
        DateAndSlot.objects.all().order_by('booking_date')

        full_slots = list(set(all_date_slot_list) - set(date_slot_list))

        # getting full slots and available slots

        content = {
            'full_slots' : full_slots ,
            'date_slot_list' : date_slot_list ,
        }
        return render(request, "customer/customerDashboard.html",content)
    else:
        return render(request, "sorry_page.html")

# display the rooms available for particular slot
@login_required(login_url='/login/')
def displayFields(request, slot_id):
```

```

    selected_slot_obj = DateAndSlot.objects.get(pk = slot_id)
    room_list_for_slot = Field.objects.filter(chosen_date_slot =
selected_slot_obj , is_booked = False) # Display unbooked rooms for the
selected slot

    content = {
        'room_list_for_slot': room_list_for_slot
    }
    return render(request , "customer/displayFields.html" , content)

# For displaying all the user bookings
@login_required(login_url='/login/')
def getUserBookings(request):

    user_booking_list = RoomBooking.objects.filter(bookee_username =
request.user) # User Bookings
    current_date = datetime.date.today()

    content = {
        'user_booking_list' : user_booking_list ,
        'today'             : current_date ,
    }
    return render(request , 'customer/userBookings.html' , content)

# Room booking view.
@login_required(login_url='/login/')
def customerRoomBooking(request, slot_id , room_id):
    # Handle POST request
    if request.POST :
        rb = RoomBooking()
        rb.booked_room_number = Field.objects.get(pk = room_id)
        rb.bookee_username = request.user.username
        rb.booking_date_slot = DateAndSlot.objects.get(pk = slot_id )

        form = RoomBookingForm(request.POST, instance = rb)
        if form.is_valid():
            pm = form.cleaned_data.get("payment_method")
            booking = form.save()
            # booking.save()
            if pm == "Khalti":
                # return redirect('{URL: https://uat.esewa.com.np }')
                return redirect(reverse('khaltirequest') + "?o_id" +
str(booking.id))
            elif pm == "Esewa":
                return redirect(reverse('esewarequest') + "?o_id" +
str(booking.id))
            room = Field.objects.get(pk = room_id)
            room.is_booked = True
            room.save()

            messages.success(request, 'Booking Done Successfully!!!')
            return redirect(reverse('userRoomBooking'))

```

```

# Handle GET request
form = RoomBookingForm()
room_number = Field.objects.get(pk = room_id).room_number
booking_price = DateAndSlot.objects.get(pk = slot_id).booking_price
content = {
    'room_number': room_number,
    'booking_price': booking_price,
    'form': form
}
return render(request, "customer/customerRoomBooking.html", content)

class KhaltiRequestView(View):
    def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs ):
        booking_id = request.GET.get("o_id")
        order = RoomBooking.objects.get(pk=booking_id)
        # Field.objects.get(pk=room_id)
        context = {
            "order": order
        }
        return render(request, "khaltirequest.html", context)

class KhaltiVerifyView(View):
    def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):
        token = request.GET.get("token")
        amount = request.GET.get("amount")
        o_id = request.GET.get("booking_id")
        print(token, amount, o_id)

        url = "https://khalti.com/api/v2/payment/verify/"
        payload = {
            "token": token,
            "amount": amount
        }
        headers = {
            "Authorization": "Key
test_secret_key_f59e8b7d18b4499ca40f68195a846e9b"
        }

        order_obj = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=o_id)

        response = requests.post(url, payload, headers=headers)
        resp_dict = response.json()
        if resp_dict.get("idx"):
            success = True
            order_obj.payment_completed = True
            order_obj.save()
        else:
            success = False
        data = {
            "success": success
        }
        return JsonResponse(data)

class EsewaRequestView(View):
    def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):

```

```

o_id = request.GET.get("o_id")
order = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=o_id)
context = {
    "order": order
}
return render(request, "esewarequest.html", context)

class EsewaVerifyView(View):
    def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):
        import xml.etree.ElementTree as ET
        oid = request.GET.get("oid")
        amt = request.GET.get("amt")
        refId = request.GET.get("refId")

        url = "https://uat.esewa.com.np/epay/transrec"
        d = {
            'amt': amt,
            'scd': 'epay_payment',
            'rid': refId,
            'pid': oid,
        }
        resp = requests.post(url, d)
        root = ET.fromstring(resp.content)
        status = root[0].text.strip()

        booking_id = oid.split("_")[1]
        order_obj = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=booking_id)
        if status == "Success":
            order_obj.payment_completed = True
            order_obj.save()
            return redirect("/")
        else:
            return redirect("/esewa-request/?o_id="+booking_id)

# Get the details of user bookings .
def deatiledUserBooking(request, booking_id):
    user_booking_detail = get_object_or_404(RoomBooking, pk=booking_id)

    if request.method == 'POST':
        user_booking_detail.booked_room_number.is_booked = False
        user_booking_detail.booked_room_number.save()
        user_booking_detail.delete()
        messages.success(request, 'Booking Cancelled Successfully!!')
        return redirect(reverse('userFieldBooking'))

    content = {
        'booking': user_booking_detail,
    }
    return render(request, 'customer/detailedUserBooking.html', content)

# class EsewaRequestView(request):
#     customerBooking_id = request.session.get('booking_id')
#     booking = get_object_or_404(RoomBooking, id=customerBooking_id)

```

```

#     host = request.get_host()

# class EsewaRequestView(View):
#     def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):
#         o_id = request.GET.get("o_id")
#         customerbooking = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=o_id)
#         context = {
#             "booking": customerbooking
#         }
#         return render(request, "esewarequest.html", context)

# class EsewaVerifyView(View):
#     def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):
#         import xml.etree.ElementTree as ET
#         oid = request.GET.get("oid")
#         amt = request.GET.get("amt")
#         refId = request.GET.get("refId")
#
#         url = "https://uat.esewa.com.np/epay/transrec"
#         d = {
#             'amt': amt,
#             'scd': 'epay_payment',
#             'rid': refId,
#             'pid': oid,
#         }
#         resp = requests.post(url, d)
#         root = ET.fromstring(resp.content)
#         status = root[0].text.strip()
#
#         order_id = oid.split("_")[1]
#         order_obj = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=order_id)
#         if status == "Success":
#             order_obj.payment_completed = True
#             order_obj.save()
#             return redirect("/")
#         else:
#             return redirect("/esewa-request/?o_id="+order_id)

# class EsewaRequestView(View):
#     def get(self, request, *args, **kwargs):
#         o_id = request.GET.get("o_id")
#         book = RoomBooking.objects.get(id=o_id)
#         context = {
#             "book": book
#         }
#         return render(request, "esewarequest.html", context)

```

9.13.8. Contact

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin
# Register your models here.
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class ContactConfig(AppConfig):
    default_auto_field = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'
    name = 'contact'
```

Models.py

```
from django.db import models
# Create your models here.
```

Tests.py

```
from django.test import TestCase
# Create your tests here.
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path
from contact import views

urlpatterns = [
    path('', views.show_contact),
]
```

Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render

# Create your views here.

def show_contact(request):
    return render(request, 'contact.html')
```

9.13.9. About

Admin.py

```
from django.contrib import admin

# Register your models here.
```

Apps.py

```
from django.apps import AppConfig

class AboutConfig(AppConfig):
    default_auto_field = 'django.db.models.BigAutoField'
    name = 'about'
```

Models.py

```
from django.db import models

# Create your models here.
```

Tests.py

```
from django.test import TestCase  
  
# Create your tests here.
```

Urls.py

```
from django.urls import path  
from about import views  
  
urlpatterns = [  
    path('', views.show_about, name='about'),  
]  
]
```

Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render  
  
# Create your views here.  
  
def show_about(request):  
    return render(request, 'about.html')
```

9.13.10. Templates

Customer

CustomerDashboard.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<!-- CUSTOMER DASHBOARD -->
<section class="dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="dashboard_box">
    <div class="left">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <div>
          <h3>Customer Dashboard</h3>
          {% if date_slot_list %}
            <h4> Available Slots for Booking: </h4>
            <div class="table">
              {% for slots in date_slot_list %}
                <div class="column">
                  <a href="{ { slots.id } }/">
                    <div class="cell">
                      { { slots.booking_date } } &nbsp;&nbsp; { {
slots.booking_slot } }
                    </div>
                  </a>
                </div>
              {% endfor %}
            </div>
          {% else %}
            <p>No Slots are available.</p>
          {% endif %}

          {% if full_slots %}
            <h4> Full Slots :</h4>
            <div class='table'>
              {% for slots in full_slots %}
                <div class="row">
                  <a href="{ { slots.id } }/">
                    <div class="cell">
                      { { slots.booking_date } } &nbsp;&nbsp; { {
slots.booking_slot } }
                    </div>
                  </a>
                </div>
              {% endfor %}
            </div>
          {% endif %}
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>
</div>
</div>
```

```

        {% endfor %}
    </div>
    {% else %}
    {% endif %}

    <br>
    <br>
    <br>
    <br>
    <div class="">
    <a href="{% url 'userRoomBooking' %}"> <i class="fa fa-
list"></i> &nbsp;
        Your Bookings
    </a>
    </div>
    </div>
    </div>
    </div>
    </div>
    <div class="right">
    <div class="right-text">
    <h2>NCS</h2>
    <h5>| BOOKING | PLAYING | TRAINING |</h5>
    </div>
    </div>
</div>
</section>

{% endblock %}

```

CustomerRoomBooking.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block title %}    Customer Form    {% endblock %}

{% block content %}

<!-- CUSTOMER Field BOOKING -->

<section class="display_booking"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="booking_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec booking-form">
        <h3>Customer Field Booking Form</h3>
        <h5> For Field Number : {{ room_number }} </h5>
        <h5> Price : {{ room_price }} </h5>
        <br>
        <br>
        <form method="POST" class="post-form">
          {% csrf_token %}
          {{ form.as_p }}
          <input class="button-custom btn form-control custom-btn bg-color mt3
aos-init aos-animate" id="submit-button" name="submit" type="submit"
value="Save">
        </form>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

DisplayFields.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<!-- AVAILABLE Fields -->

<section class="display-dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Available Fields for Selected Time Slot</h3>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <div class="table">
          {% if room_list_for_slot %}
          <ul id="horizontal-list">
            {% for room in room_list_for_slot %}
              <a href = {{ room.id }} >
                <li>
                  {{ room.room_number }}
                </li>
              </a>
            {% endfor %}
          </ul>
          {% else %}
          <p>No Fields are available for selected time slot.</p>
          {% endif %}
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

</div>
{% endblock %}
```

Esewarequest.html

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <title>Document</title>
  <style>
    #myform{
      display: none;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <h3 style="text-align: center;">You will be redirected to the esewa
  website..</h3>
  <form action="https://uat.esewa.com.np/epay/main" method="POST"
  id="myform">
    <input value="{{booking.booking_date_slot.room_price}}" name="tAmt"
  type="hidden">
    <input value="{{booking.booking_date_slot.room_price}}" name="amt"
  type="hidden">
    <input value="0" name="txAmt" type="hidden">
    <input value="0" name="psc" type="hidden">
    <input value="0" name="pdc" type="hidden">
    <input value="epay_payment" name="scd" type="hidden">
    <input value="booking_{{booking.id}}" name="pid" type="hidden">
    <input value="http://127.0.0.1:8000/esewa-verify/" type="hidden"
  name="su">
    <input value="{{request.build_absolute_uri}}" type="hidden"
  name="fu">
    <input value="Submit" type="submit">
  </form>

  <script>
    setTimeout(function(){
      document.getElementById("myform").submit()
    }, 500)
  </script>
</body>
</html>
```

Khaltirequest.html

```
<html>
<head>
  <script src="https://unpkg.com/khalti-checkout-web@latest/dist/khalti-checkout.iff.js"></script>
</head>
<body>
  <h3>Your order amount is Rs. {{booking.room-price}}</h3>

  <button id="payment-button">Pay with Khalti</button>
  <a href="/">Go to Home page</a>

  <script
src="https://cdn.jsdelivr.net/npm/axios/dist/axios.min.js"></script>
  <script>
    var config = {
      // replace the publicKey with yours
      "publicKey": "test_public_key_dc74e0fd57cb46cd93832aee0a390234",
      "productId": "booking_{{booking.booking_id}}",
      "productName": "booking_{{booking.booking_id}}",
      "productUrl": "http://localhost:8000",
      "paymentPreference": [
        "MOBILE_BANKING",
        "KHALTI",
        "EBANKING",
        "CONNECT_IPS",
        "SCT",
      ],
      "eventHandler": {
        onSuccess (payload) {
          // hit merchant api for initiating verification
          axios.get("/khalti-verify/", {
            params: {
              "token": payload.token,
              "amount": payload.amount,
              "booking_id": "{{booking.booking_id}}"
            }
          }).then(function(resp) {
            if (resp.data.success == true) {
              alert("Thanks. Payment Completed Successfully")
              location.href = "/"
            } else {
              alert("Sorry. Error occurred")
              location.href = "{{request.build_absolute_uri}}"
            }
          })
        },
        onError (error) {
          console.log(error);
        },
        onClose () {
          console.log('widget is closing');
        }
      }
    };
  </script>
</body>
</html>
```

```
var checkout = new KhaltiCheckout(config);
var btn = document.getElementById("payment-button");
btn.onclick = function () {
    // minimum transaction amount must be 10, i.e 1000 in paisa.
    checkout.show({amount: {{booking.room_price}}*100});
}
</script>
<!-- Paste this code anywhere in you body tag -->
</body>
</html>
```

UserBooking.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<!-- CUSTOMER Field BOOKING -->

<section class="display-dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Your Bookings</h3>
        <br>
        {% if user_booking_list %}
        <table class="neumorphic">
          {% if user_booking_list %}
          <ol>
            {% for booking in user_booking_list %}

            <li>
              <a href ='{{ booking.id }}'> {{ booking }} -
&nbsp; &nbsp;{{ booking.booking_date_slot.booking_date }} </a>
            </li>
            <br>
            {% endfor %}
          </ol>
          {% endif %}
        </table>
        {% else %}
        <p> No bookings are available. </p>
        {% endif %}
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

2. Manager

AddDates.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display-dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Automatically add the both slots for date Range</h3>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        <form >

          {{ form.as_p }}
          <input class="button-custom" type="submit" value="Add">

        </form>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

AddField.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display_booking"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="booking_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact mdb mdb-list dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Add Fields</h3>
        {% if slot_list_unbooked %}
        <ul>
          {% for slot in slot_list_unbooked %}
            <li> <a href ='addfield/{{ slot.id }}'> <p> {{ slot
}}</p> </a> </li>
          {% endfor %}
        </ul>
        {% else %}
          <h5> Add Slot First </h5>
        {% endif %}

        {% if slot_list_booked %}
        <h3> Fields Alloted For Slot </h3>
        <ul>
          {% for slot in slot_list_booked %}
            <li> {{ slot }} </li> <br>
          {% endfor %}
        </ul>
        {% else %}
        {% endif %}

      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

<div class="wrap">

  <script>
    $(function(){
      $('.datepicker').datepicker({
        endDate: '+0d',
        autoclose: true
      });
    });
  </script>

</div>
```

```
{% endblock %}
```

AddField2.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display-dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact slot dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Add Fields</h3>
        {% if messages %}
          <ul class="messages">
            {% for message in messages %}
              <li {% if message.tags %} class=" {{ message.tags }}
" {% endif %}> {{ message }} </li>
            {% endfor %}
          </ul>
        {% endif %}

        <form method = "POST">
          {% csrf_token %}
          {{ form.as_p }}
          <input class="button-custom btn form-control custom-
btn bg-color mt3 aos-init aos-animate" type="submit" value="Submit">
        </form>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

AddSlot.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display-dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_slot_dashboard_sec">
        <h3>Add Slot</h3>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec">
        {% if messages %}
          <ul class="messages">
            {% for message in messages %}
              <li{% if message.tags %} class="{{ message.tags }}" {% endif %}>
                {% if message.level == DEFAULT_MESSAGE_LEVELS.ERROR
%}Important: {% endif %}
                {{ message }}
              </li>
            {% endfor %}
          </ul>
        {% else %}
        {% endif %}

        <form method = "POST">

          {% csrf_token %}
          {{ form.as_p}}

          <input class="button-custom btn form-control custom-btn
bg-color mt3 aos-init aos-animate" type="submit" value="Submit">

        </form>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

GetAllBookedDates.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display_booking"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="booking_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec booking-form">
        {% if messages %}
        <ul class="messages">
          {% for message in messages %}
            <li class="{{ message.tags }}">{{ message }}</li>
          {% endfor %}
        </ul>
        {% endif %}

        <h3> Booking Dates </h3>
        {% if booking_dates %}
        <ul>
          {% for date in booking_dates %}
            <li><a href ='getAllBookedDates/{{ date.id }}'>{{
date.booking_date }}: {{ date.booking_slot }} - Rs. {{ date.room_price}}
</a></li><br>
          {% endfor %}
        </ul>
        {% else %}
          <p> Invalid </p>
        {% endif %}
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

GetSlotBookingDetail.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display_booking"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="booking_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec booking-form">
        {% if messages %}
      <ul class="messages">
        {% for message in messages %}
          <li class="{% message.tags %}">{{ message }}</li>
        {% endfor %}
      </ul>
      {% endif %}

      <h3 style="color: #13294B; ;"> Bookings for Slot </h3>

      {% if bookings_per_date %}
      <ul>
        {% for booking in bookings_per_date %}
          <li><a href ='userBookingDetails/{{ booking.id }}'> Field No.:  {{
booking.booked_room_number.room_number }} </a></li>
<!--          <li><a href ='userBookingDetails/{{ booking.id }}'> Room No.:  {{
booking.date_price.room_price }} </a></li>-->
        {% endfor %}
      </ul>
      {% else %}
        <p> No Bookings available for selected slot . </p>
      {% endif %}
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

ManagerDashboard.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display-dashboard mdb"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="display_box">
    <div class="display">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact mdb dashboard_sec">
        <h3> Manager Dashboard</h3>
      </div>
      <div class="contact mdb dashboard_sec">
        {% if messages %}
        <ul class="messages">
          {% for message in messages %}
            <li {% if message.tags %} class=" {{ message.tags }}" {% endif %}>
{{ message }} </li>
          {% endfor %}
        </ul>
        {% endif %}

        <div class='space'>
          <h3>
            <a href="{% url 'addSlot' %}">
              <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>
              Add Slot
            </a>
          </h3>
        </div>

        <br>
        <br>

        <div class='space'>
          <h3>
            <a href="{% url 'addFields' %}">
              Add Fields
            </a>
          </h3>
        </div>

        <br>
        <br>

        <div class='space'>
          <h3>
            <a href="{% url 'getAllBookedDates' %}">
              <i class="fa fa-calendar"></i>

```

```

        Bookings
    </a>
</h3>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</section>
{% endblock %}

```

UserBookingDetail.html

```

{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="display_booking"></section>
<section class="container">
    <div class="booking_box">
        <div class="display">
            <div class="top_link">
                <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
            </div>
            <div class="contact_dashboard_sec booking-form">
                <h3>Booking Details: </h3>
                <br>
                {% if user_booking %}
                <div class='table'>

                    <div class="row">
                        <div class="cell">
                            Name :
                        </div>
                        <div class="cell">
                            {{ user_booking.customer_name }}
                        </div>
                    </div>

                    <div class="row">
                        <div class="cell">
                            E-mail :
                        </div>
                        <div class="cell">
                            {{ user_booking.customer_email }}
                        </div>
                    </div>

                    <div class="row">
                        <div class="cell">
                            User-Id :

```

```

        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.bookee_username }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Contact :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.customer_contact }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Booking Purpose :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.booking_purpose }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Field Number :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.booked_room_number.room_number }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Date :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.booking_date_slot.booking_date }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Slot :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.booking_date_slot.booking_slot }}
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Price :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.booking_date_slot.room_price }}
        </div>
    </div>

```

```

        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Payment Method :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.payment_method }}
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="row">
        <div class="cell">
            Payment Completed :
        </div>
        <div class="cell">
            {{ user_booking.payment_completed }}
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="box">
    <a class="button-delete btn form-control custom-btn bg-color mt3
aos-init aos-animate" style="font-size : 20 px;" href="#popup1">Cancel
Booking</a>
</div>

<div id="popup1" class="overlay">
    <div class="popup">
        <a class="close" href="#">&times;</a>
        <h5> Are you Sure?</h5>
        <form method = 'POST' >
            {% csrf_token %}
            <p> <input class = "button-delete btn form-control
custom-btn bg-color mt3 aos-init aos-animate" type = 'submit' value = "yes"/>
<a href='../'></a></p>
            </form>

        </div>
    </div>

    {% else %}
        <p>No booking exist for selected Id.</p>
    {% endif %}
</div>
</div>
</section>

{% endblock %}

```

3. Registration

Home.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block title %}Home{% endblock %}
{% block content %}

<section class="hero d-flex flex-column justify-content-center align-items-center" id="home">

    <div class="bg-overlay"></div>

    <div class="container">
        <div class="row">

            <div class="col-lg-8 col-md-10 mx-auto col-12">
                <div class="hero-text mt-5 text-center">

                    <h6 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="300">One of
The First Indoor Cricket In Nepal </h6>

                    <h1 class="text-white" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-
delay="500">GET YOUR BOOKING FOR NEXT GAME</h1>

                    <a href="{% url 'signup' %}" class="btn custom-btn
sub-bordered mt-3" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="600">Signup</a>

                    <a href="{% url 'login' %}" class="btn custom-btn
bordered mt-3" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="700">Login</a>

                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</section>

<section class="feature" id="feature">
    <div class="container">
        <div class="row">

            <div class="d-flex flex-column justify-content-center ml-lg-
auto mr-lg-5 col-lg-5 col-md-6 col-12">
                <h2 class="mb-3 text-white" data-aos="fade-up">@NCS
INDOOR CRICKET</h2>

                <h6 class="mb-4 text-white" data-aos="fade-up">TRAIN,
PLAY & GROW</h6>

                <p data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200" class="text-
white">NCS brings you first indoor cricket where you can book games, train
with professionals and grow as a career</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</section>

```

```

        <a href="#" class="btn custom-btn bg-color mt-3" data-
aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="300" data-toggle="modal" data-
target="#membershipForm">See Articles</a>
    </div>

    <div class="mr-lg-auto mt-3 col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12">
        <div class="about-working-hours">
            <div>

                <h2 class="mb-4 text-white" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="500">We are open at</h2>

                <strong class="mt-3 d-block" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="700">Sunday-Saturday</strong>

                <p data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="800"
class="text-white">07:00 AM - 09:00 PM</p>

                <strong class="mt-3 d-block" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="700">Tuesday</strong>

                <p data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="800"
class="text-white">6:00 AM - 01:00 PM</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</section>

<!-- Book now -->
<section class="booknow" id="booknow">
    <div class="container">
        <div class="row">
            <span style="color: white; font-size: 50px;">Let's Get Your
Booking Done</span>
            <div>
                <!-- <a href="#" class="btn custom-btn bordered mt-12
col-lg-2" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="700" style="margin-left:
1000px;">Book</a> -->
                <button type="button" class="btn custom-btn bordered mt-
12 col-lg-12" style="margin-left: 150px; margin-top: 20px;">
                    <a href="{% url 'customerDashboard' %}" style="color:
#cc6047;">Book Now</a></button>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</section>

<!-- ABOUT -->
<section class="about section" id="about">
    <div class="container">
        <div class="row">
            <div class="mt-lg-5 mb-lg-0 mb-4 col-lg-5 col-md-10 mx-auto

```

```

col-12">
        <h2 class="mb-4" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-
delay="300">About Us</h2>
        <p data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="400">Nepal Cricket
school is an indoor facility where the players receive professional cricket
training sessions from the finest coaches of the country 6 days a week, twice
a day , one in the morning from 6 am- 8am & the other in the afternoon
        from 4 pm - 6 pm.</p>
        </div>
        <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" data-
aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="700">
        <div class="team-thumb">
                
                <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
                        <h3>Ram Bahadur Thapa</h3>
                        <span>CEO</span>
                        <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                                <li>
                                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                                </li>
                                <li>
                                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                                </li>
                        </ul>
                </div>
        </div>
        </div>
        <div class="mr-lg-auto mt-5 mt-lg-0 mt-md-0 col-lg-3 col-md-6
col-12" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="800">
        <div class="team-thumb">
                
                <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
                        <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
                        <span>Trainer</span>
                        <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                                <li>
                                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                                </li>
                                <li>
                                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                                </li>
                        </ul>
                </div>
        </div>
        </div>
        </div>
        </div>
</section>

<!-- CLASS -->
<section class="class section" id="class">
        <div class="container">
                <div class="row">

                        <div class="col-lg-12 col-12 text-center mb-5">

```

```

        <h6 data-aos="fade-up">Get Yourself a Trainer</h6>
        <h2 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">Our
Professionals</h2>
        </div>

        <div class="col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="400">
        <div class="class-thumb">
            

            <div class="class-info">
                <h3 class="mb-1">Batting</h3>

                <span><strong>Trained by</strong> - Paras
Khadka</span>

                <span class="class-price">Rs 8500</span>

                <p class="mt-3">Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet,
consectetur adipiscing</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="mt-5 mt-lg-0 mt-md-0 col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12"
data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="500">
        <div class="class-thumb">
            

            <div class="class-info">
                <h3 class="mb-1">Bowling</h3>

                <span><strong>Trained by</strong> - Sandeep
Khadka</span>

                <span class="class-price">Rs 5000</span>

                <p class="mt-3">Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet,
consectetur adipiscing</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

    <div class="mt-5 mt-lg-0 col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12" data-
aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="600">
        <div class="class-thumb">
            

            <div class="class-info">
                <h3 class="mb-1">Feilding</h3>

                <span><strong>Trained by</strong> - Sompal
Kami</span>

```

```

                <span class="class-price">Rs 3000</span>
                <p class="mt-3">Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet,
consectetur adipiscing</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</section>

<!-- Stories -->
<section class="schedule section" id="schedule">
    <div class="container">
        <div class="row">
            <div class="col-lg-12 col-12 text-center">
                <h6 data-aos="fade-up">Our Recent Stories</h6>
<h2 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">News</h2>
            </div>
            <div class="col-lg-12 col-12 text-center mb-5">

                <div class="col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="400">
                    <div class="class-thumb">
                        

                        <div class="class-info">
Tournament</h3>

                <p class="mt-12">Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text
of the printing and typesetting industry.Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of
the printing and typesetting industry.</p>
                <a class="btn btn-link"
href="https://www.facebook.com/NepalCricketSchool" role="button">See More</a>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

    <div class="col-lg-4 col-md-6 col-12" data-aos="fade-up"
data-aos-delay="500">
        <div class="class-thumb">
            

            <div class="class-info">
Tournament</h3>

                <p class="mt-12">Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text
of the printing and typesetting industry.Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of
the printing and typesetting industry.</p>
                <a class="btn btn-link"

```



```

        <h2 class="mb-4 " data-aos="fade-up " data-aos-delay="600
">Location</h2>

        <div class="google-map " data-aos="fade-up " data-aos-
delay="900 ">
            <iframe
src="https://www.google.com/maps/embed?pb=!1m14!1m8!1m3!1d14128.379722314565!
2d85.3373998!3d27.7143551!3m2!1i1024!2i768!4f13.1!3m3!1m2!1s0x0%3A0xe9fc1c0f9
ce6a8d0!2sNepal%20Cricket%20School%20(%20NCS%20)!5e0!3m2!1sen!2snp!4v16453363
70680!5m2!1sen!2snp"
            width="2000 " height="300 " frameborder="0 "
style="border:0; " allowfullscreen=" "></iframe>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</section>

<!-- Modal -->
<div class="modal fade " id="membershipForm " tabindex="-1 " role="dialog
" aria-labelledby="membershipFormLabel " aria-hidden="true ">
    <div class="modal-dialog " role="document ">

        <div class="modal-content ">
            <div class="modal-header ">

                <h2 class="modal-title " id="membershipFormLabel
">Membership Form</h2>

                <button type="button " class="close " data-dismiss="modal
" aria-label="Close ">
                    <span aria-hidden="true ">&times;</span>
                </button>
            </div>

            <div class="modal-body ">
                <form class="membership-form webform " role="form ">
                    <input type="text " class="form-control " name="cf-
name " placeholder="John Doe ">

                    <input type="email " class="form-control " name="cf-
email " placeholder="Johndoe@gmail.com ">

                    <input type="tel " class="form-control " name="cf-
phone " placeholder="123-456-7890 " pattern="[0-9]{3}-[0-9]{3}-[0-9]{4} "
required>

                    <textarea class="form-control " rows="3 " name="cf-
message " placeholder="Additional Message "></textarea>

                    <button type="submit " class="form-control "
id="submit-button " name="submit ">Submit Button</button>

                    <div class="custom-control custom-checkbox ">
                        <input type="checkbox " class="custom-control-
input " id="signup-agree ">

```

```
                <label class="custom-control-label text-small
text-muted " for="signup-agree ">I agree to the <a href="#" ">Terms
&amp;Conditions</a>
                </label>
            </div>
        </form>
    </div>

    <div class="modal-footer "></div>

</div>
</div>
</div>

{% endblock %}
```


Signup.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block title %}Sign Up{% endblock %}

{% block content %}

<style>
.helpertext{
  display : none ;
}

</style>

<section class="signup"></section>
  <section class="container">
    <div class="signup_box">
      <div class="left">
        <div class="top_link">
          <a href="index.html" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp; Return home</a>
        </div>
        <div class="contact signup_form">
          <form method="post">
            {% csrf_token %}
            <h3>Sign In Now</h3>
            <form method="post">
              {% csrf_token %}
              {{ form.as_p }}
              <input class="button-custom btn form-control custom-
btn bg-color mt3 aos-init aos-animate" type="submit" value="Sign up"
style="color: #CC6047;">
            </form>
          </form>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="right">
        <div class="right-text">
          <h2>NCS</h2>
          <h5>| BOOKING | PLAYING | TRAINING |</h5>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock %}
```

About.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<!-- ABOUT -->
<section class="article section">
  <div class="container">
    <h1 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">About</h1>
    <p data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">Nepal Cricket school is an
indoor facility where the players receive professional cricket training
sessions from the finest coaches of the country 6 days a week, twice a day ,
one in the morning from 6 am- 8am & the other in the afternoon
      from 4 pm - 6 pm.</p>
    <br>
    <div class="row" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="250">
      <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
        <div class="team-thumb">
          
          <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Ram Bahadur Thapa</h3>
            <span>CEO</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
              <li>
                <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
              </li>
              <li>
                <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
              </li>
            </ul>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
        <div class="team-thumb">
          
          <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
              <li>
                <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
              </li>
              <li>
                <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
              </li>
            </ul>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
        <div class="team-thumb">
          
```

```

        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="250">
    <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
        <div class="team-thumb">
            
            <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
                <h3>Ram Bahadur Thapa</h3>
                <span>CEO</span>
                <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                    <li>
                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                    </li>
                    <li>
                        <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                    </li>
                </ul>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
    <div class="team-thumb">
        

```

```

        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
<br>
<div class="row" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="250">
    <div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
        <div class="team-thumb">
            

```

```

        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Ram Bahadur Thapa</h3>
            <span>CEO</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12" >
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>
            <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="ml-lg-auto col-lg-3 col-md-6 col-12">
    <div class="team-thumb">
        
        <div class="team-info d-flex flex-column">
            <h3>Hari Bahadur Shakya</h3>
            <span>Trainer</span>

```

```
        <ul class="social-icon mt-3">
          <li>
            <a href="#" class="fa fa-facebook"></a>
          </li>
          <li>
            <a href="#" class="fa fa-instagram"></a>
          </li>
        </ul>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
  <br>
</div>
</section>

{% endblock content %}
```

Base.html

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
{% load static %}
<html lang="en">
  <head>

    <link rel="stylesheet" href="https://cdnjs.cloudflare.com/ajax/libs/font-
awesome/4.7.0/css/font-awesome.min.css">
    <title>NCS Indoor Cricket</title>
    <meta charset="UTF-8">
    <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=Edge">
    <meta name="description" content="">
    <meta name="keywords" content="">
    <meta name="author" content="">
    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1,
maximum-scale=1">
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="{% static 'css/bootstrap.min.css' %}">
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="{% static 'css/font-awesome.min.css'
%}">
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="{% static 'css/aos.css' %}">
    <!-- MAIN CSS -->
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="{% static 'css/style.css' %}">

  </head>

  <body data-spy="scroll" data-target="#navbarNav" data-offset="50">
    <!-- MENU BAR -->
    <div class="navbar navbar-expand-lg fixed-top">
      <div class="container">
        <a class="navbar-brand" href="{% url 'home' %}">NCS </a>
        <button class="navbar-toggler" type="button" data-
toggle="collapse" data-target="#navbarNav" aria-controls="navbarNav" aria-
expanded="false" aria-label="Toggle navigation">
          <span class="navbar-toggler-icon"></span>
        </button>
        <div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="navbarNav">
          <ul class="navbar-nav ml-lg-auto">
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a href="{% url 'home' %}" class="nav-
link">Home</a>
            </li>
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a href=" ../about/" class="nav-link">About</a>
            </li>
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a href=" ../events/" class="nav-link">Events</a>
            </li>
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a href=" ../news/" class="nav-link">News</a>
            </li>
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a href=" ../contact" class="nav-link">Contact</a>
            </li>
            <li class="nav-item">

```

```

        <a href="../../../faq" class="nav-link">FAQ</a>
    </li>

    <li class="nav-item">
        <a href="{% url 'customerDashboard' %}"
class="nav-link">Customer DashBoard</a>
    </li>
    {% if user.is_authenticated %}
    {% if user.is_staff %}
    <li class="nav-item">
        <a href="{% url 'managerDashboard' %}"
class="nav-link">Manager Dashboard</a>
    </li>
    {% else %}
    {% endif %}
    <li class="nav-item">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" class="nav-link">{{
user.username }}</a>
        <a href="{% url 'logout' %}" class="nav-
link">LOGOUT</a>

    </li>
    {% else %}
    <li class="nav-item users-entry">
        <a href="{% url 'signup' %}" class="nav-
link">SignUp</a>
    </li>
    <li class="nav-item users-entry">
        <a href="{% url 'login' %}" class="nav-
link">Login</a>
    </li>
    {% endif %}
</ul>
</div>
</div>
</div>

{% block content %}
{% endblock content %}

<!-- FOOTER -->
<footer class="site-footer">
    <div class="container ">
        <div class="row">
<div class="ml-auto col-md-12 col-lg-6">
            <p class="copyright-text ">Copyright &copy; NCS Indoor
Cricket</p>
        </div>
        <div class="col-md-12 col-lg-6">
            <p class="float-right">Design: <a
href="https://www.facebook.com/NepalCricketSchool">Darpan</a></p>
        </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</footer>

```

```
<!-- SCRIPTS -->
<script src="{% static 'js/jquery.min.js' %}"></script>
<script src="{% static 'js/bootstrap.min.js' %}"></script>
<script src="{% static 'js/aos.js' %}"></script>
<script src="{% static 'js/smoothscroll.js' %}"></script>
<script src="{% static 'js/custom.js' %}"></script>

</body>
</html>
```

Contact.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}
  <!-- CONTACT -->
  <section class="contact section">
    <div class="container">
      <h1 class="mb-4 pb-2" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-
delay="200">Contact Us</h1>
      <div class="row" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">
        <div class="mt-4 mt-lg-0 mt-md-0 col-lg-5 col-md-6 col-12 ">
          <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipisicing
elit. Commodi consectetur debitis delectus eius ex excepturi fugit itaque
magnam, modi neque, pariatur possimus praesentium recusandae similique unde
veritatis voluptas voluptate voluptatum.</p>
          </div>
          <div class="mx-auto col-lg-5 col-md-6">
            <p>You can send us your queries and we will get back to
you as soon as possible.</p>
            <form action="#" " method="post " class="contact-form
webform "role="form ">
              <input type="text " class="form-control " name="cf-
name " placeholder="Name ">
              <input type="email " class="form-control " name="cf-
email " placeholder="Email ">
              <textarea class="form-control " rows="5 " name="cf-
message " placeholder="Message "></textarea>
              <button type="submit " class="btn form-control
custom-btn bg-color mt3 aos-init aos-animate" id="submit-button"
name="submit" >Send Message</button>
            </form>
          </div>
        </div>
      <div class="location" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">
        <h1>Location</h1>
        <div class="google-map">
          <iframe
src="https://www.google.com/maps/embed?pb=!1m14!1m8!1m3!1d14128.379722314565!
2d85.3373998!3d27.7143551!3m2!1i1024!2i768!4f13.1!3m3!1m2!1s0x0%3A0xe9fc1c0f9
ce6a8d0!2sNepal%20Cricket%20School%20(%20NCS%20)!5e0!3m2!1sen!2snp!4v16453363
70680!5m2!1sen!2snp"
width="2000 " height="300 " frameborder="0 "
style="border:0; " allowfullscreen=" "></iframe>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </section>
{% endblock content %}
```

Event.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- EVENTS -->
{% if user.is_staff %}
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-12 float-right">
        <div class="top-text header-text float-right" style="margin-top:
5rem;
margin-bottom: -10rem;">
          <a href="{% url 'event_insert' %}" class="btn btn-outline-
success">
            <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>&nbsp;&nbsp;Add New
          </a>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
{% else %}
{% endif %}
<section class="events section">
  <div class="container">
    <h1 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">Events</h1>
    <div class="row view-style" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">
      {% for events in show_events %}
        <div class="class-thumb col">
          <h3 class="mb-3">{{events.event_title}}</h3>
          <p class="mt-12">{{events.event_description}}</p>
          <p>{{events.event_date_time}}</p>
          <p>{{events.location}}</p>
          <div class="float-right">
            <a class="btn btn-link" href="{% url 'event_detail'
events.id %}" role="button">See More ... </a>
          </div>
        </div>
      {% endfor %}
    </div>
  <br>
</div>
</section>

{% endblock content %}
```

Event_Detail.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}
    <!-- NEWS FORM -->

    <div class="page-heading">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="row">
                <div class="col-lg-8">
                    {% for events in event_detail %}
                        <div class="top-text header-text">
                            <h1>{{events.event_title}}</h1>
                        </div>
                    {% endfor %}
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
    {% if user.is_staff %}
    <div class="options_detail">
        <div class="container">
            {% for events in event_detail %}
                <a href="{% url 'event_update' events.id %}" class="btn btn-lg
options_button">
                    <i class="fa fa-edit "></i> Edit news
                </a>
                <a href="{% url 'event_delete' events.id %}" class="btn btn-lg">
                    <i class="fa fa-trash "></i> Delete news
                </a>
            {% endfor %}
        </div>
    </div>
    {% else %}
    {% endif %}
    &nbsp;
    <div class="news_details news-form">
        <div class="container">
            {% for events in event_detail %}
                <p><span>{{events.event_snippet}}</span></p>
                <p>{{events.event_date_time}}</p>
                <p>{{events.event_description}}</p>
            {% endfor %}
        </div>
    </div>
{% endblock%
```

Event_Form.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- NEWS FORM -->
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-8">
        <div class="top-text header-text">
          <h1>Event Form</h1>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

<div class="news-form">
  <div class="container">
    <a href="{% url 'event_list' %}" class="btn btn-lg">
      <i class="fa fa-stream"></i>&#8592; Back to list
    </a>
  </div>
  <br>
  <div class="container">
    <form id="add" action="" method="post" autocomplete="off">
      {% csrf_token %}
      {{form.event_title|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.event_description|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.event_snippet|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.event_date_time|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.event_location|as_crispy_field}}
      <div class="row">
        <div class="col-md-12">
          <button type="submit" class="btn btn-secondary btn-lg"><i
class="fa fa-database"></i>&nbsp;Submit</button>
        </div>
      </div>
    </form>
  </div>
</div>

{% endblock content %}
```

Event_list.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- NEWS LIST -->
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-8">
        <div class="top-text header-text">
          <h1>Event List</h1>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div class="float-right">
      <a href="{% url 'event_insert' %}" class="btn btn-outline-
success">
        <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Add New Event
      </a>
    </div>
    <table class="table table-borderless">
      <thead class="border-bottom font-weight-bold">
        <tr>
          <td>Title</td>
          <td>Description</td>
          <td>Snippet</td>
          <td>Date Time</td>
          <td>Location</td>
          <td></td>
        </tr>
      </thead>
      <tbody>
        {% for events in event_list %}
          <tr>
            <td>{{events.event_title}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_description}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_snippet}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_date_time}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_location}}</td>
            <td>
              <a href="{% url 'event_detail' events.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary px-0">
                <i class="fa fa-eye fa-lg"></i>
              </a>
              <a href="{% url 'event_update' events.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary">
                <i class="fa fa-edit fa-lg"></i>
              </a>
              <form action="{% url 'event_delete' events.id %}"
method="post" class="d-inline">
                {% csrf_token %}
            </td>
          </tr>
        {% endfor %}
      </tbody>
    </table>
  </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
```

```
        <button type="submit" class="btn">
            <i class="fa fa-trash fa-lg text-danger float-
right"></i>
        </button>
    </form>
</td>
</tr>
    {% endfor %}
</tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>

{% endblock content %}
```

FAQ.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- NEWS LIST -->
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-8">
        <div class="top-text header-text">
          <h1>Event List</h1>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div class="float-right">
      <a href="{% url 'event_insert' %}" class="btn btn-outline-
success">
        <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>&nbsp;Add New Event
      </a>
    </div>
    <table class="table table-borderless">
      <thead class="border-bottom font-weight-bold">
        <tr>
          <td>Title</td>
          <td>Description</td>
          <td>Snippet</td>
          <td>Date Time</td>
          <td>Location</td>
          <td></td>
        </tr>
      </thead>
      <tbody>
        {% for events in event_list %}
          <tr>
            <td>{{events.event_title}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_description}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_snippet}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_date_time}}</td>
            <td>{{events.event_location}}</td>
            <td>
              <a href="{% url 'event_detail' events.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary px-0">
                <i class="fa fa-eye fa-lg"></i>
              </a>
              <a href="{% url 'event_update' events.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary">
                <i class="fa fa-edit fa-lg"></i>
              </a>
              <form action="{% url 'event_delete' events.id %}"
method="post" class="d-inline">
                {% csrf_token %}
            </td>
          </tr>
        {% endfor %}
      </tbody>
    </table>
  </div>
</div>
```

```
        <button type="submit" class="btn">
            <i class="fa fa-trash fa-lg text-danger float-
right"></i>
        </button>
    </form>
</td>
</tr>
    {% endfor %}
</tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>
{% endblock content %}
```

News.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}
    <!-- NEWS -->
    {% if user.is_staff %}
    <div class="page-heading">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="row">
                <div class="col-lg-12">
                    <div class="top-text header-text float-right" style="margin-top:
5rem;
margin-bottom: -10rem;">
                        <a href="{% url 'news_insert' %}" class="btn btn-outline-
success">
                            <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>&nbsp;&nbsp;Add New
                        </a>
                    </div>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
    {% else %}
    {% endif %}
    <section class="news section">
        <div class="container">
            <h1 data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">News</h1>
            <div class="row view-style" data-aos="fade-up" data-aos-delay="200">
                {% for news in news_main %}
                <div class="class-thumb col">
                    <h3>{{news.news_title}}</h3>
                    <p class="publish">{{news.news_publisher}}</p>
                    <p>{{news.news_description}}</p>
                    <div class="float-right">
                        <a href="{% url 'news_detail' news.id %}" class="btn
btn-link">Read More ... </a>
                    </div>
                </div>
                {% endfor %}
            <br>
        </div>
    </div>
</section>
{% endblock content %}
```

News_details.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}
    <!-- NEWS FORM -->

    <div class="page-heading">
        <div class="container">
            <div class="row">
                <div class="col-lg-8">
                    {% for news in news_detail %}
                        <div class="top-text header-text">
                            <h1>{{news.news_title}}</h1>
                        </div>
                    {% endfor %}
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
    {% if user.is_staff %}
    <div class="options_detail">
        <div class="container">
            {% for news in news_detail %}
                <a href="{% url 'news_update' news.id %}" class="btn btn-lg
options_button">
                    <i class="fa fa-edit "></i> Edit news
                </a>
                <a href="{% url 'news_delete' news.id %}" class="btn btn-lg">
                    <i class="fa fa-trash "></i> Delete news
                </a>
            {% endfor %}
        </div>
    </div>
    &nbsp;{% else %}
    {% endif %}
    <div class="news_details news-form">
        <div class="container">
            {% for news in news_detail %}
                <p>{{news.news_snippets}}</p>
                <p>{{news.news_publisher}}</p>
                <p>{{news.news_description}}</p>
            {% endfor %}
        </div>
    </div>
{% endblock%
```

News_form.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- NEWS FORM -->
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-8">
        <div class="top-text header-text">
          <h1>News Form</h1>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

<div class="news-form">
  <div class="container">
    <a href="{% url 'news_list' %}" class="btn btn-lg">
      <i class="fa fa-stream"></i>&#8592; Back to list
    </a>
  </div>
  <br>
  <div class="container">
    <form id="add" action="" method="post" autocomplete="off">
      {% csrf_token %}
      {{form.news_title|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.news_description|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.news_snippets|as_crispy_field}}
      {{form.news_publisher|as_crispy_field}}
      <div class="row">
        <div class="col-md-12">
          <button type="submit" class="btn btn-secondary btn-lg"><i
class="fa fa-database"></i>&nbsp;Submit</button>
        </div>
      </div>
    </form>
  </div>
</div>

{% endblock content %}
```

News_list.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% load crispy_forms_tags %}
{% block content %}

<!-- NEWS LIST -->
<div class="page-heading">
  <div class="container">
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-8">
        <div class="top-text header-text">
          <h1>News List</h1>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div class="float-right">
      <a href="{% url 'news_insert' %}" class="btn btn-outline-
success">
        <i class="fa fa-plus"></i>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Add New
      </a>
    </div>
    <table class="table table-borderless">
<thead class="border-bottom font-weight-bold">
  <tr>
    <td>Title</td>
    <td>Description</td>
    <td>Snippets</td>
    <td>Publisher</td>
    <td></td>
  </tr>
</thead>
<tbody>
  {% for news in news_list %}
    <tr>
      <td>{{news.news_title}}</td>
      <td>{{news.news_description}}</td>
      <td>{{news.news_snippets}}</td>
      <td>{{news.news_publisher}}</td>
      <td>
        <a href="{% url 'news_detail' news.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary px-0">
          <i class="fa fa-eye fa-lg"></i>
        </a>
        <a href="{% url 'news_update' news.id %}" class="btn
text-secondary">
          <i class="fa fa-edit fa-lg"></i>
        </a>
        <form action="{% url 'news_delete' news.id %}"
method="post" class="d-inline">
          {% csrf_token %}
          <button type="submit" class="btn">
            <i class="fa fa-trash fa-lg text-danger float-
```

```
right"></i>
                </button>
            </form>
        </td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
{% endfor %}
</table>
</div>
</div>

{% endblock content %}
```

Sorry_page.html

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
{% load static %}
{% block content %}

<section class="dashboard"></section>
<section class="container">
  <div class="dashboard_box">
    <div class="left">
      <div class="top_link">
        <a href="{% url 'home' %}" > &#8592;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Return
home</a>
      </div>
      <div class="contact_dashboard_sec" style="flex-direction:
column;">
        <h3>Sorry! Looks like you're not signed in to book the
fields.</h3>
        <p>Please click the button below to sign in.</p>
        <br>
        <br>
        <div class="btn custom-btn bordered mt-3 aos-init aos-
animate">
          <a href="{% url 'signup' %}" style="color:
#cc6047;">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Sign up</a>
        </div>
        </div>
      </div>
    <div class="right">
      <div class="right-text">
        <h2>NCS</h2>
        <h5>Let's Get Your Booking Done</h5>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</section>

{% endblock content %}
```

9.13.11. Static

1. CSS

Aos.css

```
[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-duration="50"],body[data-aos-duration="50"]
[data-aos]{transition-duration:50ms}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="50"],body[data-aos-delay="50"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="50"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="50"]
[data-aos].aos-animate{transition-delay:50ms}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="100"],body[data-aos-duration="100"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.1s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="100"],body[data-aos-
delay="100"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="100"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="100"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.1s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="150"],body[data-aos-duration="150"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.15s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="150"],body[data-aos-
delay="150"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="150"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="150"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.15s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="200"],body[data-aos-duration="200"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.2s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="200"],body[data-aos-
delay="200"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="200"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="200"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration="250"],body[data-aos-duration="250"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.25s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="250"],body[data-aos-
delay="250"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="250"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="250"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration="300"],body[data-aos-duration="300"] [data-aos]{transition-
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delay="300"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="300"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="300"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.3s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="350"],body[data-aos-duration="350"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.35s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="350"],body[data-aos-
delay="350"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="350"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="350"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.35s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="400"],body[data-aos-duration="400"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.4s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="400"],body[data-aos-
delay="400"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="400"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="400"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.4s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="450"],body[data-aos-duration="450"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.45s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="450"],body[data-aos-
delay="450"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="450"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="450"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.45s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="500"],body[data-aos-duration="500"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.5s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="500"],body[data-aos-
delay="500"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
```

```
delay="500"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="500"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.5s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="550"],body[data-aos-duration="550"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.55s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="550"],body[data-aos-
delay="550"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="550"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="550"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.55s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="600"],body[data-aos-duration="600"] [data-aos]{transition-
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delay="600"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="600"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="600"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.6s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="650"],body[data-aos-duration="650"] [data-aos]{transition-
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delay="650"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="650"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="650"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration="700"],body[data-aos-duration="700"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.7s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="700"],body[data-aos-
delay="700"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="700"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="700"] [data-aos].aos-
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delay="750"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="750"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="750"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.75s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="800"],body[data-aos-duration="800"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.8s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="800"],body[data-aos-
delay="800"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="800"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="800"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration="850"],body[data-aos-duration="850"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.85s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="850"],body[data-aos-
delay="850"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="850"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="850"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.85s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="900"],body[data-aos-duration="900"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.9s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="900"],body[data-aos-
delay="900"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="900"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="900"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration="950"],body[data-aos-duration="950"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:.95s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="950"],body[data-aos-
delay="950"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="950"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="950"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:.95s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
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```



```
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delay="2900"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="2900"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="2900"] [data-aos].aos-
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duration:2.95s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="2950"],body[data-aos-
delay="2950"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
delay="2950"].aos-animate,body[data-aos-delay="2950"] [data-aos].aos-
animate{transition-delay:2.95s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
duration="3000"],body[data-aos-duration="3000"] [data-aos]{transition-
duration:3s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-delay="3000"],body[data-aos-
delay="3000"] [data-aos]{transition-delay:0}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
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animate{transition-delay:3s}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=linear],body[data-aos-easing=linear] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:cubic-bezier(.25,.25,.75,.75)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease],body[data-aos-easing=ease] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:ease}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in],body[data-aos-
easing=ease-in] [data-aos]{transition-timing-function:ease-in}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-out],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out]
[data-aos]{transition-timing-function:ease-out}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-in-out],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-out] [data-aos]{transition-
timing-function:ease-in-out}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-
back],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-back] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:cubic-bezier(.6,-.28,.735,.045)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-out-back],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out-back] [data-
aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.175,.885,.32,1.275)}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-out-back],body[data-aos-easing=ease-
in-out-back] [data-aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.68,-
.55,.265,1.55)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-sine],body[data-
aos-easing=ease-in-sine] [data-aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-
bezier(.47,0,.745,.715)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-out-
sine],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out-sine] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:cubic-bezier(.39,.575,.565,1)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-in-out-sine],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-out-sine] [data-
aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.445,.05,.55,.95)}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-quad],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-
quad] [data-aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-
bezier(.55,.085,.68,.53)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-out-
quad],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out-quad] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:cubic-bezier(.25,.46,.45,.94)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-in-out-quad],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-out-quad] [data-
aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.455,.03,.515,.955)}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-cubic],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-
cubic] [data-aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-
bezier(.55,.085,.68,.53)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-out-
cubic],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out-cubic] [data-aos]{transition-timing-
```

```

function:cubic-bezier(.25,.46,.45,.94)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-in-out-cubic],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-out-cubic][data-
aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.455,.03,.515,.955)}[data-
aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-in-quart],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-
quart][data-aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-
bezier(.55,.085,.68,.53)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-easing=ease-out-
quart],body[data-aos-easing=ease-out-quart][data-aos]{transition-timing-
function:cubic-bezier(.25,.46,.45,.94)}[data-aos][data-aos][data-aos-
easing=ease-in-out-quart],body[data-aos-easing=ease-in-out-quart][data-
aos]{transition-timing-function:cubic-bezier(.455,.03,.515,.955)}[data-
aos^=fade][data-aos^=fade]{opacity:0;transition-
property:opacity,transform}[data-aos^=fade][data-aos^=fade].aos-
animate{opacity:1;transform:translateZ(0)}[data-aos=fade-
up]{transform:translate3d(0,100px,0)}[data-aos=fade-
down]{transform:translate3d(0,-100px,0)}[data-aos=fade-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100px,0,0)}[data-aos=fade-
left]{transform:translate3d(100px,0,0)}[data-aos=fade-up-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100px,100px,0)}[data-aos=fade-up-
left]{transform:translate3d(100px,100px,0)}[data-aos=fade-down-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100px,-100px,0)}[data-aos=fade-down-
left]{transform:translate3d(100px,-100px,0)}[data-aos^=zoom][data-
aos^=zoom]{opacity:0;transition-property:opacity,transform}[data-
aos^=zoom][data-aos^=zoom].aos-animate{opacity:1;transform:translateZ(0)
scale(1)}[data-aos=zoom-in]{transform:scale(.6)}[data-aos=zoom-in-
up]{transform:translate3d(0,100px,0)scale(.6)}[data-aos=zoom-in-
down]{transform:translate3d(0,-100px,0)scale(.6)}[data-aos=zoom-in-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100px,0,0)scale(.6)}[data-aos=zoom-in-
left]{transform:translate3d(100px,0,0)scale(.6)}[data-aos=zoom-
out]{transform:scale(1.2)}[data-aos=zoom-out-
up]{transform:translate3d(0,100px,0)scale(1.2)}[data-aos=zoom-out-
down]{transform:translate3d(0,-100px,0)scale(1.2)}[data-aos=zoom-out-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100px,0,0)scale(1.2)}[data-aos=zoom-out-
left]{transform:translate3d(100px,0,0)scale(1.2)}[data-aos^=slide][data-
aos^=slide]{transition-property:transform}[data-aos^=slide][data-
aos^=slide].aos-animate{transform:translateZ(0)}[data-aos=slide-
up]{transform:translate3d(0,100%,0)}[data-aos=slide-
down]{transform:translate3d(0,-100%,0)}[data-aos=slide-
right]{transform:translate3d(-100%,0,0)}[data-aos=slide-
left]{transform:translate3d(100%,0,0)}[data-aos^=flip][data-
aos^=flip]{backface-visibility:hidden;transition-property:transform}[data-
aos=flip-left]{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateY(-100deg)}[data-aos=flip-
left].aos-animate{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateY(0)}[data-aos=flip-
right]{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateY(100deg)}[data-aos=flip-
right].aos-animate{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateY(0)}[data-aos=flip-
up]{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateX(-100deg)}[data-aos=flip-up].aos-
animate{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateX(0)}[data-aos=flip-
down]{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateX(100deg)}[data-aos=flip-down].aos-
animate{transform:perspective(2500px)rotateX(0)}

```

Bootstrap.mini.css

```
/*!
 * Bootstrap v4.2.1 (https://getbootstrap.com/)
 * Copyright 2011-2018 The Bootstrap Authors
 * Copyright 2011-2018 Twitter, Inc.
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */:root{--blue:#007bff;--indigo:#6610f2;--purple:#6f42c1;--pink:#e83e8c;--
red:#dc3545;--orange:#fd7e14;--yellow:#ffc107;--green:#28a745;--
teal:#20c997;--cyan:#17a2b8;--white:#fff;--gray:#6c757d;--gray-dark:#343a40;--
-primary:#007bff;--secondary:#6c757d;--success:#28a745;--info:#17a2b8;--
warning:#ffc107;--danger:#dc3545;--light:#f8f9fa;--dark:#343a40;--breakpoint-
xs:0;--breakpoint-sm:576px;--breakpoint-md:768px;--breakpoint-lg:992px;--
breakpoint-xl:1200px;--font-family-sans-serif:-apple-
system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,"Noto
Sans",sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol","Noto
Color Emoji";--font-family-monospace:SFMono-
Regular,Menlo,Monaco,Consolas,"Liberation Mono","Courier
New",monospace}*,::after,::before{box-sizing:border-box}html{font-
family:sans-serif;line-height:1.15;-webkit-text-size-adjust:100%;-webkit-tap-
highlight-
color:transparent}article,aside,figcaption,figure,footer,header,hgroup,main,n
av,section{display:block}body{margin:0;font-family:-apple-
system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,"Noto
Sans",sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol","Noto
Color Emoji";font-size:1rem;font-weight:400;line-
height:1.5;color:#212529;text-align:left;background-color:#fff}[tabindex="-
1"]:focus{outline:0!important}hr{box-sizing:content-
box;height:0;overflow:visible}h1,h2,h3,h4,h5,h6{margin-top:0;margin-
bottom:.5rem}p{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:1rem}abbr[data-original-
title],abbr[title]{text-decoration:underline;-webkit-text-
decoration:underline dotted;text-decoration:underline
dotted;cursor:help;border-bottom:0;text-decoration-skip-
ink:none}address{margin-bottom:1rem;font-style:normal;line-
height:inherit}dl,ol,ul{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:1rem}ol ol,ol ul,ul ol,ul
ul{margin-bottom:0}dt{font-weight:700}dd{margin-bottom:.5rem;margin-
left:0}blockquote{margin:0 0 1rem}b,strong{font-weight:bolder}small{font-
size:80%}sub,sup{position:relative;font-size:75%;line-height:0;vertical-
align:baseline}sub{bottom:-.25em}sup{top:-.5em}a{color:#007bff;text-
decoration:none;background-color:transparent}a:hover{color:#0056b3;text-
decoration:underline}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]){color:inherit;text-
decoration:none}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]):focus,a:not([href]):not([tabind
ex]):hover{color:inherit;text-
decoration:none}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]):focus{outline:0}code,kbd,pre,sa
mp{font-family:SFMono-Regular,Menlo,Monaco,Consolas,"Liberation
Mono","Courier New",monospace;font-size:1em}pre{margin-top:0;margin-
bottom:1rem;overflow:auto}figure{margin:0 0 1rem}img{vertical-
align:middle;border-style:none}svg{overflow:hidden;vertical-
align:middle}table{border-collapse:collapse}caption{padding-
top:.75rem;padding-bottom:.75rem;color:#6c757d;text-align:left;caption-
side:bottom}th{text-align:inherit}label{display:inline-block;margin-
bottom:.5rem}button{border-radius:0}button:focus{outline:1px
dotted;outline:5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-
color}button,input,optgroup,select,textarea{margin:0;font-
family:inherit;font-size:inherit;line-
```

```

height:inherit}button,input{overflow:visible}button,select{text-
transform:none}[type=button],[type=reset],[type=submit],button{-webkit-
appearance:button}[type=button]:-moz-focus-inner,[type=reset]:-moz-focus-
inner,[type=submit]:-moz-focus-inner,button::-moz-focus-
inner{padding:0;border-style:none}input[type=checkbox],input[type=radio]{box-
sizing:border-box;padding:0}input[type=date],input[type=datetime-
local],input[type=month],input[type=time]{-webkit-
appearance:listbox}textarea{overflow:auto;resize:vertical}fieldset{min-
width:0;padding:0;margin:0;border:0}legend{display:block;width:100%;max-
width:100%;padding:0;margin-bottom:.5rem;font-size:1.5rem;line-
height:inherit;color:inherit;white-space:normal}progress{vertical-
align:baseline}[type=number]:-webkit-inner-spin-button,[type=number]:-
webkit-outer-spin-button{height:auto}[type=search]{outline-offset:-2px;-
webkit-appearance:none}[type=search]:-webkit-search-decoration{-webkit-
appearance:none}:-webkit-file-upload-button{font:inherit;-webkit-
appearance:button}output{display:inline-block}summary{display:list-
item;cursor:pointer}template{display:none}[hidden]{display:none!important}.h1
,.h2,.h3,.h4,.h5,.h6,h1,h2,h3,h4,h5,h6{margin-bottom:.5rem;font-
family:inherit;font-weight:500;line-height:1.2;color:inherit}.h1,h1{font-
size:2.5rem}.h2,h2{font-size:2rem}.h3,h3{font-size:1.75rem}.h4,h4{font-
size:1.5rem}.h5,h5{font-size:1.25rem}.h6,h6{font-size:1rem}.lead{font-
size:1.25rem;font-weight:300}.display-1{font-size:6rem;font-weight:300;line-
height:1.2}.display-2{font-size:5.5rem;font-weight:300;line-
height:1.2}.display-3{font-size:4.5rem;font-weight:300;line-
height:1.2}.display-4{font-size:3.5rem;font-weight:300;line-
height:1.2}hr{margin-top:1rem;margin-bottom:1rem;border:0;border-top:1px
solid rgba(0,0,0,.1)}.small,small{font-size:80%;font-
weight:400}.mark,mark{padding:.2em;background-color:#fcf8e3}.list-
-unstyled{padding-left:0;list-style:none}.list-inline{padding-left:0;list-
style:none}.list-inline-item{display:inline-block}.list-inline-
item:not(:last-child){margin-right:.5rem}.initialism{font-size:90%;text-
transform:uppercase}.blockquote{margin-bottom:1rem;font-
size:1.25rem}.blockquote-footer{display:block;font-
size:80%;color:#6c757d}.blockquote-footer::before{content:"\2014\00A0"}.img-
fluid{max-width:100%;height:auto}.img-thumbnail{padding:.25rem;background-
color:#fff;border:1px solid #dee2e6;border-radius:.25rem;max-
width:100%;height:auto}.figure{display:inline-block}.figure-img{margin-
bottom:.5rem;line-height:1}.figure-caption{font-
size:90%;color:#6c757d}code{font-size:87.5%;color:#e83e8c;word-break:break-
word}a>code{color:inherit}kbd{padding:.2rem .4rem;font-
size:87.5%;color:#fff;background-color:#212529;border-radius:.2rem}kbd
kbd{padding:0;font-size:100%;font-weight:700}pre{display:block;font-
size:87.5%;color:#212529}pre code{font-size:inherit;color:inherit;word-
break:normal}.pre-scrollable{max-height:340px;overflow-
y:scroll}.container{width:100%;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-
right:auto;margin-left:auto}@media (min-width:576px){.container{max-
width:540px}}@media (min-width:768px){.container{max-width:720px}}@media
(min-width:992px){.container{max-width:960px}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.container{max-width:1140px}}.container-
fluid{width:100%;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-
right:auto;margin-left:auto}.row{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-
wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}.no-
gutters{margin-right:0;margin-left:0}.no-gutters>.col,.no-
gutters>[class*=col-]{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.col,.col-1,.col-
10,.col-11,.col-12,.col-2,.col-3,.col-4,.col-5,.col-6,.col-7,.col-8,.col-
9,.col-auto,.col-lg,.col-lg-1,.col-lg-10,.col-lg-11,.col-lg-12,.col-lg-
2,.col-lg-3,.col-lg-4,.col-lg-5,.col-lg-6,.col-lg-7,.col-lg-8,.col-lg-9,.col-

```

```
lg-auto, .col-md, .col-md-1, .col-md-10, .col-md-11, .col-md-12, .col-md-2, .col-md-3, .col-md-4, .col-md-5, .col-md-6, .col-md-7, .col-md-8, .col-md-9, .col-md-auto, .col-sm, .col-sm-1, .col-sm-10, .col-sm-11, .col-sm-12, .col-sm-2, .col-sm-3, .col-sm-4, .col-sm-5, .col-sm-6, .col-sm-7, .col-sm-8, .col-sm-9, .col-sm-auto, .col-xl, .col-xl-1, .col-xl-10, .col-xl-11, .col-xl-12, .col-xl-2, .col-xl-3, .col-xl-4, .col-xl-5, .col-xl-6, .col-xl-7, .col-xl-8, .col-xl-9, .col-xl-auto{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-auto{-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:100%}.col-1{-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-2{-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-3{-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-4{-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-5{-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-6{-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-7{-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-8{-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-9{-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-10{-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-11{-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-12{-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-first{-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-last{-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-0{-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-1{-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-2{-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-3{-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-4{-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-5{-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-6{-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-7{-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-8{-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-9{-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-10{-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-11{-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-12{-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-11{margin-left:91.666667%}@media (min-width:576px){.col-sm{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-sm-auto{-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:100%}.col-sm-1{-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-sm-2{-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-sm-3{-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-sm-4{-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-sm-5{-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-sm-6{-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-sm-7{-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-sm-8{-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-sm-9{-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-sm-10{-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-sm-11{-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-sm-12{-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-sm-first{-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-sm-last{-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-sm-0{-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-sm-1{-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-sm-2{-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-sm-3{-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-sm-4{-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-sm-5{-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-sm-6{-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-sm-7{-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-sm-8{-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-sm-9{-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-sm-10{-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-sm-11{-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-sm-12{-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-sm-0{margin-left:0}.offset-sm-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-sm-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-sm-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-sm-4{margin-
```

```
left:33.333333%}.offset-sm-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-sm-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-sm-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-sm-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-sm-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-sm-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-sm-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-width:768px){.col-md{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-md-auto{-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:100%}.col-md-1{-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-md-2{-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-md-3{-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-md-4{-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-md-5{-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-md-6{-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-md-7{-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-md-8{-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-md-9{-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-md-10{-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-md-11{-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-md-12{-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-md-first{-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-md-last{-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-md-0{-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-md-1{-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-md-2{-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-md-3{-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-md-4{-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-md-5{-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-md-6{-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-md-7{-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-md-8{-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-md-9{-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-md-10{-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-md-11{-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-md-12{-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-md-0{margin-left:0}.offset-md-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-md-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-md-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-md-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-md-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-md-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-md-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-md-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-md-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-md-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-md-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-width:992px){.col-lg{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-lg-auto{-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:100%}.col-lg-1{-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-lg-2{-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-lg-3{-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-lg-4{-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-lg-5{-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-lg-6{-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-lg-7{-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-lg-8{-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-lg-9{-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-lg-10{-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-lg-11{-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-lg-12{-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-lg-first{-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-lg-last{-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-lg-0{-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-lg-1{-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-lg-2{-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-lg-3{-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-lg-4{-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-lg-5{-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-lg-6{-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-lg-7{-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-lg-8{-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-lg-9{-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-lg-10{-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-lg-11{-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-lg-12{-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-lg-0{margin-left:0}.offset-lg-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-lg-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-lg-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-lg-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-lg-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-lg-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-lg-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-lg-8{margin-
```

```

left:66.666667%}.offset-lg-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-lg-10{margin-
left:83.333333%}.offset-lg-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.col-xl{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-
positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-xl-auto{-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0
auto;width:auto;max-width:100%}.col-xl-1{-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0
8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-xl-2{-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0
16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-xl-3{-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-
width:25%}.col-xl-4{-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-
width:33.333333%}.col-xl-5{-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-
width:41.666667%}.col-xl-6{-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-
xl-7{-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-
xl-8{-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-
xl-9{-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-xl-10{-ms-flex:0 0
83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-xl-11{-ms-flex:0 0
91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-xl-12{-ms-flex:0 0
100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-xl-first{-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-
1}.order-xl-last{-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-xl-0{-ms-flex-
order:0;order:0}.order-xl-1{-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-xl-2{-ms-flex-
order:2;order:2}.order-xl-3{-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-xl-4{-ms-flex-
order:4;order:4}.order-xl-5{-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-xl-6{-ms-flex-
order:6;order:6}.order-xl-7{-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-xl-8{-ms-flex-
order:8;order:8}.order-xl-9{-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-xl-10{-ms-flex-
order:10;order:10}.order-xl-11{-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-xl-12{-ms-
flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-xl-0{margin-left:0}.offset-xl-1{margin-
left:8.333333%}.offset-xl-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-xl-3{margin-
left:25%}.offset-xl-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-xl-5{margin-
left:41.666667%}.offset-xl-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-xl-7{margin-
left:58.333333%}.offset-xl-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-xl-9{margin-
left:75%}.offset-xl-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-xl-11{margin-
left:91.666667%}}.table{width:100%;margin-bottom:1rem;background-
color:transparent}.table td,.table th{padding:.75rem;vertical-
align:top;border-top:1px solid #dee2e6}.table thead th{vertical-
align:bottom;border-bottom:2px solid #dee2e6}.table tbody+tbody{border-
top:2px solid #dee2e6}.table .table{background-color:#fff}.table-sm
td,.table-sm th{padding:.3rem}.table-bordered{border:1px solid
#dee2e6}.table-bordered td,.table-bordered th{border:1px solid
#dee2e6}.table-bordered thead td,.table-bordered thead th{border-bottom-
width:2px}.table-borderless tbody+tbody,.table-borderless td,.table-
borderless th,.table-borderless thead th{border:0}.table-striped tbody
tr:nth-of-type(odd){background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.05)}.table-hover tbody
tr:hover{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-primary,.table-
primary>td,.table-primary>th{background-color:#b8daff}.table-primary
tbody+tbody,.table-primary td,.table-primary th,.table-primary thead
th{border-color:#7abaff}.table-hover .table-primary:hover{background-
color:#9fcdff}.table-hover .table-primary:hover>td,.table-hover .table-
primary:hover>th{background-color:#9fcdff}.table-secondary,.table-
secondary>td,.table-secondary>th{background-color:#d6d8db}.table-secondary
tbody+tbody,.table-secondary td,.table-secondary th,.table-secondary thead
th{border-color:#b3b7bb}.table-hover .table-secondary:hover{background-
color:#c8cbcf}.table-hover .table-secondary:hover>td,.table-hover .table-
secondary:hover>th{background-color:#c8cbcf}.table-success,.table-
success>td,.table-success>th{background-color:#c3e6cb}.table-success
tbody+tbody,.table-success td,.table-success th,.table-success thead
th{border-color:#8fd19e}.table-hover .table-success:hover{background-
color:#b1dfbb}.table-hover .table-success:hover>td,.table-hover .table-
success:hover>th{background-color:#b1dfbb}.table-info,.table-info>td,.table-
info>th{background-color:#bee5eb}.table-info tbody+tbody,.table-info

```

```

td,.table-info th,.table-info thead th{border-color:#86cfda}.table-hover
.table-info: hover{background-color:#abdde5}.table-hover .table-
info: hover>td,.table-hover .table-info: hover>th{background-
color:#abdde5}.table-warning,.table-warning>td,.table-warning>th{background-
color:#ffeeba}.table-warning tbody+tbody,.table-warning td,.table-warning
th,.table-warning thead th{border-color:#ffdf7e}.table-hover .table-
warning: hover{background-color:#ffe8a1}.table-hover .table-
warning: hover>td,.table-hover .table-warning: hover>th{background-
color:#ffe8a1}.table-danger,.table-danger>td,.table-danger>th{background-
color:#f5c6cb}.table-danger tbody+tbody,.table-danger td,.table-danger
th,.table-danger thead th{border-color:#ed969e}.table-hover .table-
danger: hover{background-color:#f1b0b7}.table-hover .table-
danger: hover>td,.table-hover .table-danger: hover>th{background-
color:#f1b0b7}.table-light,.table-light>td,.table-light>th{background-
color:#fdfdfe}.table-light tbody+tbody,.table-light td,.table-light
th,.table-light thead th{border-color:#fbfcfc}.table-hover .table-
light: hover{background-color:#ececfc6}.table-hover .table-
light: hover>td,.table-hover .table-light: hover>th{background-
color:#ececfc6}.table-dark,.table-dark>td,.table-dark>th{background-
color:#c6c8ca}.table-dark tbody+tbody,.table-dark td,.table-dark th,.table-
dark thead th{border-color:#95999c}.table-hover .table-dark: hover{background-
color:#b9bbbe}.table-hover .table-dark: hover>td,.table-hover .table-
dark: hover>th{background-color:#b9bbbe}.table-active,.table-active>td,.table-
active>th{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-hover .table-
active: hover{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-hover .table-
active: hover>td,.table-hover .table-active: hover>th{background-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table .thead-dark th{color:#fff;background-color:
#212529;border-color:#32383e}.table .thead-light
th{color:#495057;background-color:#e9ecef;border-color:#dee2e6}.table-
dark{color:#fff;background-color:#212529}.table-dark td,.table-dark
th,.table-dark thead th{border-color:#32383e}.table-dark.table-
bordered{border:0}.table-dark.table-striped tbody tr:nth-of-
type(odd){background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.05)}.table-dark.table-hover
tbody tr: hover{background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.075)}@media (max-
width:575.98px){.table-responsive-sm{display:block;width:100%;overflow-
x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-
scrollbar}.table-responsive-sm>.table-bordered{border:0}}@media (max-
width:767.98px){.table-responsive-md{display:block;width:100%;overflow-
x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-
scrollbar}.table-responsive-md>.table-bordered{border:0}}@media (max-
width:991.98px){.table-responsive-lg{display:block;width:100%;overflow-
x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-
scrollbar}.table-responsive-lg>.table-bordered{border:0}}@media (max-
width:1199.98px){.table-responsive-xl{display:block;width:100%;overflow-
x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-
scrollbar}.table-responsive-xl>.table-bordered{border:0}}.table-
responsive{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-overflow-
scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-
responsive>.table-bordered{border:0}.form-
control{display:block;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);padding:.375rem
.75rem;font-size:1rem;font-weight:400;line-
height:1.5;color:#495057;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-
box;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:.25rem;transition:border-color
.15s ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out}@media screen and (prefers-
reduced-motion:reduce){.form-control{transition:none}}.form-control::-ms-
expand{background-color:transparent;border:0}.form-
control:focus{color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border-

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color:#80bdff;outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.form-
control::-webkit-input-placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control::-
moz-placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control:-ms-input-
placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control::-ms-input-
placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-
control::placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control:disabled,.form-
control[readonly]{background-color:#e9ecef;opacity:1}select.form-
control:focus::-ms-value{color:#495057;background-color:#fff}.form-control-
file,.form-control-range{display:block;width:100%}.col-form-label{padding-
top:calc(.375rem + 1px);padding-bottom:calc(.375rem + 1px);margin-
bottom:0;font-size:inherit;line-height:1.5}.col-form-label-lg{padding-
top:calc(.5rem + 1px);padding-bottom:calc(.5rem + 1px);font-
size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5}.col-form-label-sm{padding-top:calc(.25rem +
1px);padding-bottom:calc(.25rem + 1px);font-size:.875rem;line-
height:1.5}.form-control-plaintext{display:block;width:100%;padding-
top:.375rem;padding-bottom:.375rem;margin-bottom:0;line-
height:1.5;color:#212529;background-color:transparent;border:solid
transparent;border-width:1px 0}.form-control-plaintext.form-control-lg,.form-
control-plaintext.form-control-sm{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.form-
control-sm{height:calc(1.8125rem + 2px);padding:.25rem .5rem;font-
size:.875rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.2rem}.form-control-
lg{height:calc(2.875rem + 2px);padding:.5rem 1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-
height:1.5;border-radius:.3rem}select.form-control[multiple],select.form-
control[size]{height:auto}textarea.form-control{height:auto}.form-
group{margin-bottom:1rem}.form-text{display:block;margin-top:.25rem}.form-
row{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-
wrap:wrap;margin-right:-5px;margin-left:-5px}.form-row>.col,.form-
row>[class*=col-]{padding-right:5px;padding-left:5px}.form-
check{position:relative;display:block;padding-left:1.25rem}.form-check-
input{position:absolute;margin-top:.3rem;margin-left:-1.25rem}.form-check-
input:disabled~.form-check-label{color:#6c757d}.form-check-label{margin-
bottom:0}.form-check-inline{display:-ms-inline-flexbox;display:inline-flex;-
ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;padding-left:0;margin-
right:.75rem}.form-check-inline .form-check-input{position:static;margin-
top:0;margin-right:.3125rem;margin-left:0}.valid-
feedback{display:none;width:100%;margin-top:.25rem;font-
size:80%;color:#28a745}.valid-tooltip{position:absolute;top:100%;z-
index:5;display:none;max-width:100%;padding:.25rem .5rem;margin-
top:.1rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5;color:#fff;background-
color:rgba(40,167,69,.9);border-radius:.25rem}.form-control.is-valid,.was-
validated .form-control:valid{border-color:#28a745;padding-
right:2.25rem;background-repeat:no-repeat;background-position:center right
calc(2.25rem / 4);background-size:calc(2.25rem / 2) calc(2.25rem /
2);background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath
fill='%2328a745' d='M2.3 6.73L6 4.53c-.4-1.04.46-1.4 1.1-.811.1 1.4 3.4-
3.8c.6-.63 1.6-.27 1.2.71-4 4.6c-.43.5-.8.4-1.1z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.form-
control.is-valid:focus,.was-validated .form-control:valid:focus{border-
color:#28a745;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.form-control.is-
valid~.valid-feedback,.form-control.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated
.form-control:valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated .form-
control:valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.was-validated textarea.form-
control:valid,textarea.form-control.is-valid{padding-
right:2.25rem;background-position:top calc(2.25rem / 4) right calc(2.25rem /
4)}.custom-select.is-valid,.was-validated .custom-select:valid{border-
color:#28a745;padding-
right:3.4375rem;background:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg

```

```
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 4 5'%3e%3cpath
fill='%23343a40' d='M2 0L0 2h4zm0 5L0 3h4z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e") no-repeat right
.75rem center/8px 10px,url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath
fill='%2328a745' d='M2.3 6.73L6 4.53c-.4-1.04.46-1.4 1.1-.811.1 1.4 3.4-
3.8c.6-.63 1.6-.27 1.2.71-4 4.6c-.43.5-.8.4-1.1.1z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e") no-repeat
center right 1.75rem/1.125rem 1.125rem}.custom-select.is-valid:focus,.was-
validated .custom-select:valid:focus{border-color:#28a745;box-shadow:0 0 0
.2rem rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.custom-select.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-
select.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-select:valid~.valid-
feedback,.was-validated .custom-select:valid~.valid-
tooltip{display:block}.form-control-file.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.form-
control-file.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated .form-control-
file:valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated .form-control-file:valid~.valid-
tooltip{display:block}.form-check-input.is-valid~.form-check-label,.was-
validated .form-check-input:valid~.form-check-label{color:#28a745}.form-
check-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.form-check-input.is-valid~.valid-
tooltip,.was-validated .form-check-input:valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated
.form-check-input:valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-
input.is-valid~.custom-control-label,.was-validated .custom-control-
input:valid~.custom-control-label{color:#28a745}.custom-control-input.is-
valid~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-
input:valid~.custom-control-label::before{border-color:#28a745}.custom-
control-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-control-input.is-valid~.valid-
tooltip,.was-validated .custom-control-input:valid~.valid-feedback,.was-
validated .custom-control-input:valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-
control-input.is-valid:checked~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated
.custom-control-input:valid:checked~.custom-control-label::before{border-
color:#34ce57;background-color:#34ce57}.custom-control-input.is-
valid:focus~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-
input:valid:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.custom-control-input.is-
valid:focus:not(:checked)~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated
.custom-control-input:valid:focus:not(:checked)~.custom-control-
label::before{border-color:#28a745}.custom-file-input.is-valid~.custom-file-
label,.was-validated .custom-file-input:valid~.custom-file-label{border-
color:#28a745}.custom-file-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-file-
input.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-file-input:valid~.valid-
feedback,.was-validated .custom-file-input:valid~.valid-
tooltip{display:block}.custom-file-input.is-valid:focus~.custom-file-
label,.was-validated .custom-file-input:valid:focus~.custom-file-
label{border-color:#28a745;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.invalid-feedback{display:none;width:100%;margin-
top:.25rem;font-size:80%;color:#dc3545}.invalid-
tooltip{position:absolute;top:100%;z-index:5;display:none;max-
width:100%;padding:.25rem .5rem;margin-top:.1rem;font-size:.875rem;line-
height:1.5;color:#fff;background-color:rgba(220,53,69,.9);border-
radius:.25rem}.form-control.is-invalid,.was-validated .form-
control:invalid{border-color:#dc3545;padding-right:2.25rem;background-
repeat:no-repeat;background-position:center right calc(2.25rem /
4);background-size:calc(2.25rem / 2) calc(2.25rem / 2);background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
fill='%23dc3545' viewBox='-2 -2 7 7'%3e%3cpath stroke='%23d9534f' d='M0 0L3
3'/%3e%3ccircle r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cx='3' r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cy='3'
r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cx='3' cy='3' r='.5'/%3e%3c/svg%3E")}.form-control.is-
invalid:focus,.was-validated .form-control:invalid:focus{border-
color:#dc3545;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.form-control.is-
```

```
invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-control.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .form-control:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-control:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.was-validated textarea.form-control:invalid,textarea.form-control.is-invalid{padding-right:2.25rem;background-position:top calc(2.25rem / 4) right calc(2.25rem / 4)}.custom-select.is-invalid,.was-validated .custom-select:invalid{border-color:#dc3545;padding-right:3.4375rem;background:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 4 5'%3e%3cpath fill='%23343a40' d='M2 0L0 2h4z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e") no-repeat right .75rem center/8px 10px,url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' fill='%23dc3545' viewBox='-2 -2 7 7'%3e%3cpath stroke='%23d9534f' d='M0 0l3 3'/%3e%3ccircle r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cx='3' r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cy='3' r='.5'/%3e%3ccircle cx='3' cy='3' r='.5'/%3e%3c/svg%3E") no-repeat center right 1.75rem/1.125rem 1.125rem}.custom-select.is-invalid:focus,.was-validated .custom-select:invalid:focus{border-color:#dc3545;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.custom-select.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-select.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-select:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-select:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.form-control-file.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-control-file.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .form-control-file:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-control-file:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.form-check-input.is-invalid~.form-check-label,.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-check-input.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-check-input.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.custom-control-label,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.custom-control-label{color:#dc3545}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.custom-control-label::before{border-color:#dc3545}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-input.is-invalid:checked~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid:checked~.custom-control-label::before{border-color:#e4606d;background-color:#e4606d}.custom-control-input.is-invalid:focus~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.custom-control-input.is-invalid:focus:not(:checked)~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid:focus:not(:checked)~.custom-control-label::before{border-color:#dc3545}.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.custom-file-label,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid~.custom-file-label{border-color:#dc3545}.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-file-input.is-invalid:focus~.custom-file-label,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid:focus~.custom-file-label{border-color:#dc3545;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.form-inline{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-flow:row wrap;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center}.form-inline .form-check{width:100%}@media (min-width:576px){.form-inline label{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-
```

```

align:center;align-items:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center;margin-bottom:0}.form-inline .form-group{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;-ms-flex-flow:row
wrap;flex-flow:row wrap;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;margin-
bottom:0}.form-inline .form-control{display:inline-block;width:auto;vertical-
align:middle}.form-inline .form-control-plaintext{display:inline-block}.form-
inline .custom-select,.form-inline .input-group{width:auto}.form-inline
.form-check{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:center;align-
items:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;width:auto;padding-
left:0}.form-inline .form-check-input{position:relative;margin-top:0;margin-
right:.25rem;margin-left:0}.form-inline .custom-control{-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center}.form-inline .custom-control-label{margin-
bottom:0}}.btn{display:inline-block;font-weight:400;color:#212529;text-
align:center;vertical-align:middle;-webkit-user-select:none;-moz-user-
select:none;-ms-user-select:none;user-select:none;background-
color:transparent;border:1px solid transparent;padding:.375rem .75rem;font-
size:1rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.25rem;transition:color .15s ease-in-
out,background-color .15s ease-in-out,border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-
shadow .15s ease-in-out}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.btn{transition:none}}.btn:hover{color:#212529;text-
decoration:none}.btn:focus,.btn:focus{outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.btn.disabled,.btn:disabled{opacity:.65}.btn:not(:disabl-
e):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.a.btn.disabled,fieldset:disabled
a.btn{pointer-events:none}.btn-primary{color:#fff;background-
color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-
color:#0069d9;border-color:#0062cc}.btn-primary:focus,.btn-primary:focus{box-
shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(38,143,255,.5)}.btn-primary.disabled,.btn-
primary:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-
color:#007bff}.btn-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-primary.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#0062cc;border-color:#005cbf}.btn-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-
primary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(38,143,255,.5)}.btn-secondary{color:#fff;background-
color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-
secondary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#5a6268;border-
color:#545b62}.btn-secondary:focus,.btn-secondary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0
.2rem rgba(130,138,145,.5)}.btn-secondary.disabled,.btn-
secondary:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-
color:#6c757d}.btn-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-secondary.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#545b62;border-color:#4e555b}.btn-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-
secondary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(130,138,145,.5)}.btn-success{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-
color:#28a745}.btn-success:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#218838;border-
color:#1e7e34}.btn-success:focus,.btn-success:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(72,180,97,.5)}.btn-success.disabled,.btn-
success:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-
color:#28a745}.btn-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-success.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#1e7e34;border-color:#1c7430}.btn-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-

```

```
success.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(72,180,97,.5)}.btn-
info{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-
info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#138496;border-color:#117a8b}.btn-
info.focus,.btn-info:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(58,176,195,.5)}.btn-
info.disabled,.btn-info:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-
color:#17a2b8}.btn-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-info.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#117a8b;border-color:#10707f}.btn-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-info.dropdown-
toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(58,176,195,.5)}.btn-
warning{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-
warning:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#e0a800;border-
color:#d39e00}.btn-warning.focus,.btn-warning:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(222,170,12,.5)}.btn-warning.disabled,.btn-
warning:disabled{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-
color:#ffc107}.btn-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-warning.dropdown-
toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#d39e00;border-color:#c69500}.btn-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-
warning.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(222,170,12,.5)}.btn-danger{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-
color:#dc3545}.btn-danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#c82333;border-
color:#bd2130}.btn-danger.focus,.btn-danger:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(225,83,97,.5)}.btn-danger.disabled,.btn-
danger:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-
color:#dc3545}.btn-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-danger.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#bd2130;border-color:#b21f2d}.btn-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-danger.dropdown-
toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(225,83,97,.5)}.btn-
light{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-
light:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#e2e6ea;border-color:#dae0e5}.btn-
light.focus,.btn-light:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(216,217,219,.5)}.btn-light.disabled,.btn-
light:disabled{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-
color:#f8f9fa}.btn-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-light.dropdown-
toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#dae0e5;border-color:#d3d9df}.btn-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-light.dropdown-
toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(216,217,219,.5)}.btn-
dark{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-
dark:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#23272b;border-color:#1d2124}.btn-
dark.focus,.btn-dark:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(82,88,93,.5)}.btn-
dark.disabled,.btn-dark:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-
color:#343a40}.btn-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#1d2124;border-color:#171a1d}.btn-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-
toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(82,88,93,.5)}.btn-outline-
primary{color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-outline-
primary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-
outline-primary.focus,.btn-outline-primary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
```

```
rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-outline-primary.disabled,.btn-outline-
primary:disabled{color:#007bff;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-
primary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-
color:#007bff}.btn-outline-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
primary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-
outline-secondary{color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-
secondary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-
color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-secondary:focus,.btn-outline-secondary:focus{box-
shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-outline-secondary.disabled,.btn-
outline-secondary:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent}.btn-
outline-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-
secondary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-
color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
secondary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-outline-success{color:#28a745;border-
color:#28a745}.btn-outline-success:hover{color:#fff;background-
color:#28a745;border-color:#28a745}.btn-outline-success:focus,.btn-outline-
success:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-outline-
success.disabled,.btn-outline-success:disabled{color:#28a745;background-
color:transparent}.btn-outline-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-
success.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-
color:#28a745}.btn-outline-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
success.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-
outline-info{color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-outline-
info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-
outline-info:focus,.btn-outline-info:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-outline-info.disabled,.btn-outline-
info:disabled{color:#17a2b8;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-info.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-outline-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
info.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-
outline-warning{color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-
warning:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-
color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-warning:focus,.btn-outline-warning:focus{box-
shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-outline-warning.disabled,.btn-
outline-warning:disabled{color:#ffc107;background-color:transparent}.btn-
outline-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-
warning.dropdown-toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-
color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
warning.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-
```

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outline-danger{color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-outline-
danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-
outline-danger.focus,.btn-outline-danger:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-outline-danger.disabled,.btn-outline-
danger:disabled{color:#dc3545;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-
danger.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-
color:#dc3545}.btn-outline-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
danger.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-
outline-light{color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-outline-
light:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-
outline-light.focus,.btn-outline-light:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-outline-light.disabled,.btn-outline-
light:disabled{color:#f8f9fa;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-light.dropdown-
toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-
outline-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
light.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-
outline-dark{color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-outline-
dark:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-
outline-dark.focus,.btn-outline-dark:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-outline-dark.disabled,.btn-outline-
dark:disabled{color:#343a40;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-dark.dropdown-
toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-outline-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-
dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-
dark.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-
link{font-weight:400;color:#f13a11}.btn-link:hover{color:#f13a11;font-
weight:700;text-decoration:underline}.btn-link.focus,.btn-link:focus{text-
decoration:underline;box-shadow:none}.btn-link.disabled,.btn-
link:disabled{color:#6c757d;pointer-events:none}.btn-group-lg>.btn,.btn-
lg{padding:.5rem 1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5;border-
radius:.3rem}.btn-group-sm>.btn,.btn-sm{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-
size:.875rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.2rem}.btn-
block{display:block;width:100%}.btn-block+.btn-block{margin-
top:.5rem}input[type=button].btn-block,input[type=reset].btn-
block,input[type=submit].btn-block{width:100%}.fade{transition:opacity .15s
linear}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.fade{transition:none}}.fade:not(.show){opacity:0}.collapse:~no
t(.show){display:none}.collapsing{position:relative;height:0;overflow:hidden;
transition:height .35s ease}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.collapsing{transition:none}}.dropdown,.dropleft,.dropright,.d
ropup{position:relative}.dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;margin-
left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em solid;border-
right:.3em solid transparent;border-bottom:0;border-left:.3em solid
transparent}.dropdown-toggle.empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropdown-
menu{position:absolute;top:100%;left:0;z-
index:1000;display:none;float:left;min-width:10rem;padding:.5rem
0;margin:.125rem 0 0;font-size:1rem;color:#212529;text-align:left;list-
style:none;background-color:#fff;background-clip;padding-box;border:1px solid

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rgba(0,0,0,.15);border-radius:.25rem}.dropdown-menu-
right{right:0;left:auto}@media (min-width:576px){.dropdown-menu-sm-
right{right:0;left:auto}}@media (min-width:768px){.dropdown-menu-md-
right{right:0;left:auto}}@media (min-width:992px){.dropdown-menu-lg-
right{right:0;left:auto}}@media (min-width:1200px){.dropdown-menu-xl-
right{right:0;left:auto}}.dropdown-menu-left{right:auto;left:0}@media (min-
width:576px){.dropdown-menu-sm-left{right:auto;left:0}}@media (min-
width:768px){.dropdown-menu-md-left{right:auto;left:0}}@media (min-
width:992px){.dropdown-menu-lg-left{right:auto;left:0}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.dropdown-menu-xl-left{right:auto;left:0}}.dropup .dropdown-
menu{top:auto;bottom:100%;margin-top:0;margin-bottom:.125rem}.dropup
.dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;margin-left:.255em;vertical-
align:.255em;content:"";border-top:0;border-right:.3em solid
transparent;border-bottom:.3em solid;border-left:.3em solid
transparent}.dropup .dropdown-toggle.empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropright
.dropdown-menu{top:0;right:auto;left:100%;margin-top:0;margin-
left:.125rem}.dropright .dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;margin-
left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em solid
transparent;border-right:0;border-bottom:.3em solid transparent;border-
left:.3em solid}.dropright .dropdown-toggle.empty::after{margin-
left:0}.dropright .dropdown-toggle::after{vertical-align:0}.dropleft
.dropdown-menu{top:0;right:100%;left:auto;margin-top:0;margin-
right:.125rem}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;margin-
left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:""}.dropleft .dropdown-
toggle::after{display:none}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle::before{display:inline-
block;margin-right:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em
solid transparent;border-right:.3em solid;border-bottom:.3em solid
transparent}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle.empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropleft
.dropdown-toggle::before{vertical-align:0}.dropdown-menu[x-
placement^=bottom],.dropdown-menu[x-placement^=left],.dropdown-menu[x-
placement^=right],.dropdown-menu[x-
placement^=top]{right:auto;bottom:auto}.dropdown-
divider{height:0;margin:.5rem 0;overflow:hidden;border-top:1px solid
#e9ecef}.dropdown-item{display:block;width:100%;padding:.25rem
1.5rem;clear:both;font-weight:400;color:#212529;text-align:inherit;white-
space:nowrap;background-color:transparent;border:0}.dropdown-item:first-
child{border-top-left-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-top-right-
radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.dropdown-item:last-child{border-bottom-right-
radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-bottom-left-radius:calc(.25rem -
1px)}.dropdown-item:focus,.dropdown-item:hover{color:#16181b;text-
decoration:none;background-color:#f8f9fa}.dropdown-item.active,.dropdown-
item:active{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-
color:#007bff}.dropdown-item.disabled,.dropdown-
item:disabled{color:#6c757d;pointer-events:none;background-
color:transparent}.dropdown-menu.show{display:block}.dropdown-
header{display:block;padding:.5rem 1.5rem;margin-bottom:0;font-
size:.875rem;color:#6c757d;white-space:nowrap}.dropdown-item-
text{display:block;padding:.25rem 1.5rem;color:#212529}.btn-group,.btn-group-
vertical{position:relative;display:-ms-inline-flexbox;display:inline-
flex;vertical-align:middle}.btn-group-vertical>.btn,.btn-
group>.btn{position:relative;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn:hover,.btn-group>.btn:hover{z-index:1}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn.active,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:active,.btn-group-
vertical>.btn:focus,.btn-group>.btn.active,.btn-group>.btn:active,.btn-
group>.btn:focus{z-index:1}.btn-toolbar{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-
start}.btn-toolbar .input-group{width:auto}.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:first-

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child), .btn-group>.btn:not(:first-child){margin-left:-1px}.btn-group>.btn-
group:not(:last-child)>.btn, .btn-group>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-
toggle){border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.btn-
group>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn, .btn-group>.btn:not(:first-
child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.dropdown-toggle-
split{padding-right:.5625rem;padding-left:.5625rem}.dropdown-toggle-
split::after,.dropright .dropdown-toggle-split::after,.dropup .dropdown-
toggle-split::after{margin-left:0}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle-
split::before{margin-right:0}.btn-group-sm>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,.btn-
sm+.dropdown-toggle-split{padding-right:.375rem;padding-left:.375rem}.btn-
group-lg>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,.btn-lg+.dropdown-toggle-split{padding-
right:.75rem;padding-left:.75rem}.btn-group-vertical{-ms-flex-
direction:column;flex-direction:column;-ms-flex-align:start;align-items:flex-
start;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group{width:100%}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-child),.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:first-
child){margin-top:-1px}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:last-
child)>.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-
toggle){border-bottom-right-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn,.btn-group-
vertical>.btn:not(:first-child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-
radius:0}.btn-group-toggle>.btn,.btn-group-toggle>.btn-group>.btn{margin-
bottom:0}.btn-group-toggle>.btn input[type=checkbox],.btn-group-toggle>.btn
input[type=radio],.btn-group-toggle>.btn-group>.btn
input[type=checkbox],.btn-group-toggle>.btn-group>.btn
input[type=radio]{position:absolute;clip:rect(0,0,0,0);pointer-
events:none}.input-group{position:relative;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-
ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-ms-flex-align:stretch;align-
items:stretch;width:100%}.input-group>.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-
select,.input-group>.form-control,.input-group>.form-control-
plaintext{position:relative;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;width:1%;margin-
bottom:0}.input-group>.custom-file+.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-
file+.custom-select,.input-group>.custom-file+.form-control,.input-
group>.custom-select+.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-select+.custom-
select,.input-group>.custom-select+.form-control,.input-group>.form-
control+.custom-file,.input-group>.form-control+.custom-select,.input-
group>.form-control+.form-control,.input-group>.form-control-
plaintext+.custom-file,.input-group>.form-control-plaintext+.custom-
select,.input-group>.form-control-plaintext+.form-control{margin-left:-
1px}.input-group>.custom-file .custom-file-input:focus~.custom-file-
label,.input-group>.custom-select:focus,.input-group>.form-control:focus{z-
index:3}.input-group>.custom-file .custom-file-input:focus{z-index:4}.input-
group>.custom-select:not(:last-child),.input-group>.form-control:not(:last-
child){border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-
group>.custom-select:not(:first-child),.input-group>.form-control:not(:first-
child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.input-
group>.custom-file{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center}.input-group>.custom-file:not(:last-child)
.custom-file-label,.input-group>.custom-file:not(:last-child) .custom-file-
label::after{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-
group>.custom-file:not(:first-child) .custom-file-label{border-top-left-
radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.input-group-append,.input-group-
prepend{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex}.input-group-append .btn,.input-
group-prepend .btn{position:relative;z-index:2}.input-group-append
.btn:focus,.input-group-prepend .btn:focus{z-index:3}.input-group-append
.btn+.btn,.input-group-append .btn+.input-group-text,.input-group-append
.input-group-text+.btn,.input-group-append .input-group-text+.input-group-

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text, .input-group-prepend .btn+.btn, .input-group-prepend .btn+.input-group-
text, .input-group-prepend .input-group-text+.btn, .input-group-prepend .input-
group-text+.input-group-text{margin-left:-1px}.input-group-prepend{margin-
right:-1px}.input-group-append{margin-left:-1px}.input-group-text{display:-
ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:center;align-
items:center;padding:.375rem .75rem;margin-bottom:0;font-size:1rem;font-
weight:400;line-height:1.5;color:#495057;text-align:center;white-
space:nowrap;background-color:#e9ecef;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-
radius:.25rem}.input-group-text input[type=checkbox],.input-group-text
input[type=radio]{margin-top:0}.input-group-lg>.custom-select,.input-group-
lg>.form-control:not(textarea){height:calc(2.875rem + 2px)}.input-group-
lg>.custom-select,.input-group-lg>.form-control,.input-group-lg>.input-group-
append>.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-group-append>.input-group-text,.input-
group-lg>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-group-
prepend>.input-group-text{padding:.5rem 1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-
height:1.5;border-radius:.3rem}.input-group-sm>.custom-select,.input-group-
sm>.form-control:not(textarea){height:calc(1.8125rem + 2px)}.input-group-
sm>.custom-select,.input-group-sm>.form-control,.input-group-sm>.input-group-
append>.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-append>.input-group-text,.input-
group-sm>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-
prepend>.input-group-text{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-size:.875rem;line-
height:1.5;border-radius:.2rem}.input-group-lg>.custom-select,.input-group-
sm>.custom-select{padding-right:1.75rem}.input-group>.input-group-
append:last-child>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle),.input-
group>.input-group-append:last-child>.input-group-text:not(:last-
child),.input-group>.input-group-append:not(:last-child)>.btn,.input-
group>.input-group-append:not(:last-child)>.input-group-text,.input-
group>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-prepend>.input-
group-text{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-
group>.input-group-append>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-append>.input-group-
text,.input-group>.input-group-prepend:first-child>.btn:not(:first-
child),.input-group>.input-group-prepend:first-child>.input-group-
text:not(:first-child),.input-group>.input-group-prepend:not(:first-
child)>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-prepend:not(:first-child)>.input-group-
text{border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.custom-
control{position:relative;display:block;min-height:1.5rem;padding-
left:1.5rem}.custom-control-inline{display:-ms-inline-flexbox;display:inline-
flex;margin-right:1rem}.custom-control-input{position:absolute;z-index:-
1;opacity:0}.custom-control-input:checked~.custom-control-
label::before{color:#fff;border-color:#007bff;background-
color:#007bff}.custom-control-input:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-
shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-control-
input:focus:not(:checked)~.custom-control-label::before{border-
color:#80bdff}.custom-control-input:not(:disabled):active~.custom-control-
label::before{color:#fff;background-color:#b3d7ff;border-
color:#b3d7ff}.custom-control-input:disabled~.custom-control-
label{color:#6c757d}.custom-control-input:disabled~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:#e9ecef}.custom-control-
label{position:relative;margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:top}.custom-control-
label::before{position:absolute;top:.25rem;left:-
1.5rem;display:block;width:1rem;height:1rem;pointer-
events:none;content:"";background-color:#fff;border:#adb5bd solid
1px}.custom-control-label::after{position:absolute;top:.25rem;left:-
1.5rem;display:block;width:1rem;height:1rem;content:"";background-repeat:no-
repeat;background-position:center center;background-size:50% 50%}.custom-
checkbox .custom-control-label::before{border-radius:.25rem}.custom-checkbox
.custom-control-input:checked~.custom-control-label::after{background-

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image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath fill='%23fff' d='M6.564.751-3.59 3.612-1.538-
1.55L0 4.26 2.974 7.25 8 2.193z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.custom-checkbox .custom-
control-input:indeterminate~.custom-control-label::before{border-
color:#007bff;background-color:#007bff}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-
input:indeterminate~.custom-control-label::after{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
viewBox='0 0 4 4'%3e%3cpath stroke='%23fff' d='M0
2h4'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-
input:disabled:checked~.custom-control-label::before{background-
color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-
input:disabled:indeterminate~.custom-control-label::before{background-
color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-radio .custom-control-label::before{border-
radius:50%}.custom-radio .custom-control-input:checked~.custom-control-
label::after{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3e%3ccircle r='3'
fill='%23fff'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.custom-radio .custom-control-
input:disabled:checked~.custom-control-label::before{background-
color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-switch{padding-left:2.25rem}.custom-switch
.custom-control-label::before{left:-2.25rem;width:1.75rem;pointer-
events:all;border-radius:.5rem}.custom-switch .custom-control-
label::after{top:calc(.25rem + 2px);left:calc(-2.25rem + 2px);width:calc(1rem
- 4px);height:calc(1rem - 4px);background-color:#adb5bd;border-
radius:.5rem;transition:background-color .15s ease-in-out,border-color .15s
ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out,-webkit-transform .15s ease-in-
out;transition:transform .15s ease-in-out,background-color .15s ease-in-
out,border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-
out;transition:transform .15s ease-in-out,background-color .15s ease-in-
out,border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out,-webkit-
transform .15s ease-in-out}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.custom-switch .custom-control-
label::after{transition:none}}.custom-switch .custom-control-
input:checked~.custom-control-label::after{background-color:#fff;-webkit-
transform:translateX(.75rem);transform:translateX(.75rem)}.custom-switch
.custom-control-input:disabled:checked~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-
select{display:inline-block;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem +
2px);padding:.375rem 1.75rem .375rem .75rem;font-weight:400;line-
height:1.5;color:#495057;vertical-
align:middle;background:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 4 5'%3e%3cpath
fill='%233443a40' d='M2 0L0 2h4zm0 5L0 3h4z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e") no-repeat right
.75rem center/8px 10px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-
radius:.25rem;-webkit-appearance:none;-moz-
appearance:none;appearance:none}.custom-select:focus{border-
color:#80bdff;outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(128,189,255,.5)}.custom-
select:focus::-ms-value{color:#495057;background-color:#fff}.custom-
select[multiple],.custom-select[size]:not([size="1"]){height:auto;padding-
right:.75rem;background-image:none}.custom-
select:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:#e9ecef}.custom-select::-ms-
expand{opacity:0}.custom-select-sm{height:calc(1.8125rem + 2px);padding-
top:.25rem;padding-bottom:.25rem;padding-left:.5rem;font-
size:.875rem}.custom-select-lg{height:calc(2.875rem + 2px);padding-
top:.5rem;padding-bottom:.5rem;padding-left:1rem;font-size:1.25rem}.custom-
file{position:relative;display:inline-block;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem +
2px);margin-bottom:0}.custom-file-input{position:relative;z-
index:2;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);margin:0;opacity:0}.custom-

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file-input:focus~.custom-file-label{border-color:#80bdff;box-shadow:0 0 0
.2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-file-input:disabled~.custom-file-
label{background-color:#e9ecef}.custom-file-input:lang(en)~.custom-file-
label::after{content:"Browse"}.custom-file-input~.custom-file-label[data-
browse]::after{content:attr(data-browse)}.custom-file-
label{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;left:0;z-index:1;height:calc(2.25rem +
2px);padding:.375rem .75rem;font-weight:400;line-
height:1.5;color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid
#ced4da;border-radius:.25rem}.custom-file-
label::after{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;z-
index:3;display:block;height:2.25rem;padding:.375rem .75rem;line-
height:1.5;color:#495057;content:"Browse";background-color:#e9ecef;border-
left:inherit;border-radius:0 .25rem .25rem 0}.custom-
range{width:100%;height:calc(1rem + .4rem);padding:0;background-
color:transparent;-webkit-appearance:none;-moz-
appearance:none;appearance:none}.custom-range:focus{outline:0}.custom-
range:focus::-webkit-slider-thumb{box-shadow:0 0 0 1px #fff,0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-range:focus::-moz-range-thumb{box-shadow:0 0 0
1px #fff,0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-range:focus::-ms-thumb{box-
shadow:0 0 0 1px #fff,0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-range::-moz-
focus-outer{border:0}.custom-range::-webkit-slider-
thumb{width:1rem;height:1rem;margin-top:-.25rem;background-
color:#007bff;border:0;border-radius:1rem;transition:background-color .15s
ease-in-out,border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;-
webkit-appearance:none;appearance:none}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.custom-range::-webkit-slider-thumb{transition:none}}.custom-
range::-webkit-slider-thumb:active{background-color:#b3d7ff}.custom-range::-
webkit-slider-runnable-
track{width:100%;height:.5rem;color:transparent;cursor:pointer;background-
color:#dee2e6;border-color:transparent;border-radius:1rem}.custom-range::-
moz-range-thumb{width:1rem;height:1rem;background-
color:#007bff;border:0;border-radius:1rem;transition:background-color .15s
ease-in-out,border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;-moz-
appearance:none;appearance:none}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.custom-range::-moz-range-thumb{transition:none}}.custom-
range::-moz-range-thumb:active{background-color:#b3d7ff}.custom-range::-moz-
range-
track{width:100%;height:.5rem;color:transparent;cursor:pointer;background-
color:#dee2e6;border-color:transparent;border-radius:1rem}.custom-range::-ms-
thumb{width:1rem;height:1rem;margin-top:0;margin-right:.2rem;margin-
left:.2rem;background-color:#007bff;border:0;border-
radius:1rem;transition:background-color .15s ease-in-out,border-color .15s
ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;appearance:none}@media screen and
(prefers-reduced-motion:reduce){.custom-range::-ms-
thumb{transition:none}}.custom-range::-ms-thumb:active{background-
color:#b3d7ff}.custom-range::-ms-
track{width:100%;height:.5rem;color:transparent;cursor:pointer;background-
color:transparent;border-color:transparent;border-width:.5rem}.custom-
range::-ms-fill-lower{background-color:#dee2e6;border-radius:1rem}.custom-
range::-ms-fill-upper{margin-right:15px;background-color:#dee2e6;border-
radius:1rem}.custom-range:disabled::-webkit-slider-thumb{background-
color:#adb5bd}.custom-range:disabled::-webkit-slider-runnable-
track{cursor:default}.custom-range:disabled::-moz-range-thumb{background-
color:#adb5bd}.custom-range:disabled::-moz-range-
track{cursor:default}.custom-range:disabled::-ms-thumb{background-
color:#adb5bd}.custom-control-label::before,.custom-file-label,.custom-
select{transition:background-color .15s ease-in-out,border-color .15s ease-

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in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.custom-control-label::before,.custom-file-label,.custom-
select{transition:none}}.nav{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-
wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;padding-left:0;margin-bottom:0;list-style:none}.nav-
link{display:block;padding:.5rem 1rem}.nav-link:focus,.nav-link:hover{text-
decoration:none}.nav-link.disabled{color:#6c757d;pointer-
events:none;cursor:default}.nav-tabs{border-bottom:1px solid #dee2e6}.nav-
tabs .nav-item{margin-bottom:-1px}.nav-tabs .nav-link{border:1px solid
transparent;border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-top-right-
radius:.25rem}.nav-tabs .nav-link:focus,.nav-tabs .nav-link:hover{border-
color:#e9ecef #e9ecef #dee2e6}.nav-tabs .nav-
link.disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent;border-
color:transparent}.nav-tabs .nav-item.show .nav-link,.nav-tabs .nav-
link.active{color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border-color:#dee2e6 #dee2e6
#fff}.nav-tabs .dropdown-menu{margin-top:-1px;border-top-left-
radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.nav-pills .nav-link{border-
radius:.25rem}.nav-pills .nav-link.active,.nav-pills .show>.nav-
link{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff}.nav-fill .nav-item{-ms-flex:1 1
auto;flex:1 1 auto;text-align:center}.nav-justified .nav-item{-ms-flex-
preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;text-
align:center}.tab-content>.tab-pane{display:none}.tab-
content>.active{display:block}.navbar{position:relative;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-content:space-
between;padding:.5rem 1rem}.navbar>.container,.navbar>.container-
fluid{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-ms-
flex-align:center;align-items:center;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-
content:space-between}.navbar-brand{display:inline-block;padding-
top:.3125rem;padding-bottom:.3125rem;margin-right:1rem;font-
size:1.25rem;line-height:inherit;white-space:nowrap}.navbar-
brand:focus,.navbar-brand:hover{text-decoration:none}.navbar-nav{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;padding-
left:0;margin-bottom:0;list-style:none}.navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:0;padding-left:0}.navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:static;float:none}.navbar-text{display:inline-block;padding-
top:.5rem;padding-bottom:.5rem}.navbar-collapse{-ms-flex-preferred-
size:100%;flex-basis:100%;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center}.navbar-toggler{padding:.25rem .75rem;font-
size:1.25rem;line-height:1;background-color:transparent;border:1px solid
transparent;border-radius:.25rem}.navbar-toggler:focus,.navbar-
toggler:hover{text-decoration:none}.navbar-
toggler:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.navbar-toggler-
icon{display:inline-block;width:1.5em;height:1.5em;vertical-
align:middle;content:"";background:no-repeat center center;background-
size:100% 100%}@media (max-width:575.98px){.navbar-expand-
sm>.container,.navbar-expand-sm>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-
left:0}}@media (min-width:576px){.navbar-expand-sm{-ms-flex-flow:row
nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-
start}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav{-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-
direction:row}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:.5rem;padding-left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-sm>.container,.navbar-expand-
sm>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-sm
.navbar-collapse{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-
flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-
toggler{display:none}}@media (max-width:767.98px){.navbar-expand-
md>.container,.navbar-expand-md>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-

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left:0}}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-expand-md{-ms-flex-flow:row
nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-
start}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav{-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-
direction:row}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:.5rem;padding-left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-md>.container,.navbar-expand-
md>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-md
.navbar-collapse{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-
flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-
toggler{display:none}}@media (max-width:991.98px){.navbar-expand-
lg>.container,.navbar-expand-lg>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-
left:0}}@media (min-width:992px){.navbar-expand-lg{-ms-flex-flow:row
nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-
start}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav{-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-
direction:row}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:.5rem;padding-left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-lg>.container,.navbar-expand-
lg>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-lg
.navbar-collapse{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-
flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-
toggler{display:none}}@media (max-width:1199.98px){.navbar-expand-
xl>.container,.navbar-expand-xl>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-
left:0}}@media (min-width:1200px){.navbar-expand-xl{-ms-flex-flow:row
nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-
start}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav{-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-
direction:row}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:.5rem;padding-left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-xl>.container,.navbar-expand-
xl>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-xl
.navbar-collapse{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-
flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-
toggler{display:none}}.navbar-expand{-ms-flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row
nowrap;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-start}.navbar-
expand>.container,.navbar-expand>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-
left:0}.navbar-expand .navbar-nav{-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-
direction:row}.navbar-expand .navbar-nav .dropdown-
menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-
right:.5rem;padding-left:.5rem}.navbar-expand>.container,.navbar-
expand>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand
.navbar-collapse{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-
flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand .navbar-
toggler{display:none}.navbar-light .navbar-
brand{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light .navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-light
.navbar-brand:hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-
link{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link:focus,.navbar-
light .navbar-nav .nav-link:hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.7)}.navbar-light .navbar-
nav .nav-link.disabled{color:rgba(0,0,0,.3)}.navbar-light .navbar-nav
.active>.nav-link,.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link.active,.navbar-light
.navbar-nav .nav-link.show,.navbar-light .navbar-nav .show>.nav-
link{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light .navbar-
toggler{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5);border-color:rgba(0,0,0,.1)}.navbar-light
.navbar-toggler-icon{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
viewBox='0 0 30 30' xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'%3e%3cpath
stroke='rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5)' stroke-width='2' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-
miterlimit='10' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4 23h22'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.navbar-light
.navbar-text{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.navbar-light .navbar-text
a{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light .navbar-text a:focus,.navbar-light

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.navbar-text a:hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-dark .navbar-
brand{color:#fff}.navbar-dark .navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-dark .navbar-
brand:hover{color:#fff}.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-
link{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)}.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-
link:focus,.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-
link:hover{color:rgba(255,255,255,.75)}.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-
link.disabled{color:rgba(255,255,255,.25)}.navbar-dark .navbar-nav
.active>.nav-link,.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link.active,.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav .nav-link.show,.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .show>.nav-
link{color:#fff}.navbar-dark .navbar-
toggler{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5);border-color:rgba(255,255,255,.1)}.navbar-
dark .navbar-toggler-icon{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
viewBox='0 0 30 30' xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'%3e%3cpath
stroke='rgba(255, 255, 255, 0.5)' stroke-width='2' stroke-linecap='round'
stroke-miterlimit='10' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4 23h22'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.navbar-
dark .navbar-text{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)}.navbar-dark .navbar-text
a{color:#fff}.navbar-dark .navbar-text a:focus,.navbar-dark .navbar-text
a:hover{color:#fff}.card{position:relative;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-
ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;min-width:0;word-wrap:break-
word;background-color:#fff;background-clip:border-box;border:1px solid
rgba(0,0,0,.125);border-radius:.25rem}.card>hr{margin-right:0;margin-
left:0}.card>.list-group:first-child .list-group-item:first-child{border-top-
left-radius:.25rem;border-top-right-radius:.25rem}.card>.list-group:last-
child .list-group-item:last-child{border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem;border-
bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.card-body{-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1
auto;padding:1.25rem}.card-title{margin-bottom:.75rem}.card-subtitle{margin-
top:-.375rem;margin-bottom:0}.card-text:last-child{margin-bottom:0}.card-
link:hover{text-decoration:none}.card-link+.card-link{margin-
left:1.25rem}.card-header{padding:.75rem 1.25rem;margin-
bottom:0;color:inherit;background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.03);border-bottom:1px
solid rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.card-header:first-child{border-radius:calc(.25rem -
1px) calc(.25rem - 1px) 0 0}.card-header+.list-group .list-group-item:first-
child{border-top:0}.card-footer{padding:.75rem 1.25rem;background-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.03);border-top:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.card-
footer:last-child{border-radius:0 0 calc(.25rem - 1px) calc(.25rem -
1px)}.card-header-tabs{margin-right:-.625rem;margin-bottom:-.75rem;margin-
left:-.625rem;border-bottom:0}.card-header-pills{margin-right:-
.625rem;margin-left:-.625rem}.card-img-
overlay{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;padding:1.25rem}.card
-img{width:100%;border-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-img-
top{width:100%;border-top-left-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-top-right-
radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-img-bottom{width:100%;border-bottom-right-
radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-bottom-left-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-
deck{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-
direction:column}.card-deck .card{margin-bottom:15px}@media (min-
width:576px){.card-deck{-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-flow:row wrap;margin-
right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}.card-deck .card{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex:1 0 0%;flex:1 0 0%;-ms-flex-
direction:column;flex-direction:column;margin-right:15px;margin-
bottom:0;margin-left:15px)}.card-group{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-
flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column}.card-group>.card{margin-
bottom:15px}@media (min-width:576px){.card-group{-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-
flow:row wrap}.card-group>.card{-ms-flex:1 0 0%;flex:1 0 0%;margin-
bottom:0}.card-group>.card+.card{margin-left:0;border-left:0}.card-
group>.card:first-child{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-
radius:0}.card-group>.card:first-child .card-header,.card-group>.card:first-
child .card-img-top{border-top-right-radius:0}.card-group>.card:first-child

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.card-footer, .card-group>.card:first-child .card-img-bottom{border-bottom-
right-radius:0}.card-group>.card:last-child{border-top-left-radius:0;border-
bottom-left-radius:0}.card-group>.card:last-child .card-header, .card-
group>.card:last-child .card-img-top{border-top-left-radius:0}.card-
group>.card:last-child .card-footer, .card-group>.card:last-child .card-img-
bottom{border-bottom-left-radius:0}.card-group>.card:only-child{border-
radius:.25rem}.card-group>.card:only-child .card-header, .card-
group>.card:only-child .card-img-top{border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-
top-right-radius:.25rem}.card-group>.card:only-child .card-footer, .card-
group>.card:only-child .card-img-bottom{border-bottom-right-
radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.card-group>.card:not(:first-
child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child){border-radius:0}.card-
group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child) .card-
footer, .card-group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child)
.card-header, .card-group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-
child) .card-img-bottom, .card-group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-
child):not(:only-child) .card-img-top{border-radius:0}}.card-columns
.card{margin-bottom:.75rem}@media (min-width:576px){.card-columns{-webkit-
column-count:3;-moz-column-count:3;column-count:3;-webkit-column-
gap:1.25rem;-moz-column-gap:1.25rem;column-
gap:1.25rem;orphans:1;widows:1}.card-columns .card{display:inline-
block;width:100%}}.accordion .card{overflow:hidden}.accordion
.card:not(:first-of-type) .card-header:first-child{border-radius:0}.accordion
.card:not(:first-of-type):not(:last-of-type){border-bottom:0;border-
radius:0}.accordion .card:first-of-type{border-bottom:0;border-bottom-right-
radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.accordion .card:last-of-type{border-
top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.accordion .card .card-
header{margin-bottom:-1px}.breadcrumb{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;padding:.75rem 1rem;margin-bottom:1rem;list-
style:none;background-color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.25rem}.breadcrumb-
item+.breadcrumb-item{padding-left:.5rem}.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-
item::before{display:inline-block;padding-
right:.5rem;color:#6c757d;content:"/"}.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-
item:hover::before{text-decoration:underline}.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-
item:hover::before{text-decoration:none}.breadcrumb-
item.active{color:#6c757d}.pagination{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;padding-left:0;list-style:none;border-
radius:.25rem}.page-link{position:relative;display:block;padding:.5rem
.75rem;margin-left:-1px;line-height:1.25;color:#007bff;background-
color:#fff;border:1px solid #dee2e6}.page-link:hover{z-
index:2;color:#0056b3;text-decoration:none;background-color:#e9ecef;border-
color:#dee2e6}.page-link:focus{z-index:2;outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.page-
link:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.page-item:first-child
.page-link{margin-left:0;border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-
radius:.25rem}.page-item:last-child .page-link{border-top-right-
radius:.25rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem}.page-item.active .page-
link{z-index:1;color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-
color:#007bff}.page-item.disabled .page-link{color:#6c757d;pointer-
events:none;cursor:auto;background-color:#fff;border-
color:#dee2e6}.pagination-lg .page-link{padding:.75rem 1.5rem;font-
size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5}.pagination-lg .page-item:first-child .page-
link{border-top-left-radius:.3rem;border-bottom-left-
radius:.3rem}.pagination-lg .page-item:last-child .page-link{border-top-
right-radius:.3rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.3rem}.pagination-sm .page-
link{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5}.pagination-sm
.page-item:first-child .page-link{border-top-left-radius:.2rem;border-bottom-

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left-radius:.2rem}.pagination-sm .page-item:last-child .page-link{border-top-
right-radius:.2rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.2rem}.badge{display:inline-
block;padding:.25em .4em;font-size:75%;font-weight:700;line-height:1;text-
align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:baseline;border-
radius:.25rem}a.badge:focus,a.badge:hover{text-
decoration:none}.badge:empty{display:none}.btn .badge{position:relative;top:-
1px}.badge-pill{padding-right:.6em;padding-left:.6em;border-
radius:10rem}.badge-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff}a.badge-
primary:focus,a.badge-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-
color:#0062cc}.badge-secondary{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d}a.badge-
secondary:focus,a.badge-secondary:hover{color:#fff;background-
color:#545b62}.badge-success{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745}a.badge-
success:focus,a.badge-success:hover{color:#fff;background-
color:#1e7e34}.badge-info{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8}a.badge-
info:focus,a.badge-info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#117a8b}.badge-
warning{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107}a.badge-warning:focus,a.badge-
warning:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#d39e00}.badge-
danger{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545}a.badge-danger:focus,a.badge-
danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#bd2130}.badge-
light{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa}a.badge-light:focus,a.badge-
light:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#dae0e5}.badge-
dark{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40}a.badge-dark:focus,a.badge-
dark:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#1d2124}.jumbotron{padding:2rem
1rem;margin-bottom:2rem;background-color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.3rem}@media
(min-width:576px){.jumbotron{padding:4rem 2rem}}.jumbotron-fluid{padding-
right:0;padding-left:0;border-
radius:0}.alert{position:relative;padding:.75rem 1.25rem;margin-
bottom:1rem;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:.25rem}.alert-
heading{color:inherit}.alert-link{font-weight:700}.alert-dismissible{padding-
right:4rem}.alert-dismissible
.close{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;padding:.75rem
1.25rem;color:inherit}.alert-primary{color:#004085;background-
color:#cce5ff;border-color:#b8daff}.alert-primary hr{border-top-
color:#9fcdff}.alert-primary .alert-link{color:#002752}.alert-
secondary{color:#383d41;background-color:#e2e3e5;border-color:#d6d8db}.alert-
secondary hr{border-top-color:#c8cbcf}.alert-secondary .alert-
link{color:#202326}.alert-success{color:#155724;background-
color:#d4edda;border-color:#c3e6cb}.alert-success hr{border-top-
color:#b1dfbb}.alert-success .alert-link{color:#0b2e13}.alert-
info{color:#0c5460;background-color:#d1ecf1;border-color:#bee5eb}.alert-info
hr{border-top-color:#abdde5}.alert-info .alert-link{color:#062c33}.alert-
warning{color:#856404;background-color:#fff3cd;border-color:#ffeeba}.alert-
warning hr{border-top-color:#ffe8a1}.alert-warning .alert-
link{color:#533f03}.alert-danger{color:#721c24;background-
color:#f8d7da;border-color:#f5c6cb}.alert-danger hr{border-top-
color:#f1b0b7}.alert-danger .alert-link{color:#491217}.alert-
light{color:#818182;background-color:#fefefe;border-color:#fdfdfe}.alert-
light hr{border-top-color:#ececfc6}.alert-light .alert-
link{color:#686868}.alert-dark{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#d6d8d9;border-
color:#c6c8ca}.alert-dark hr{border-top-color:#b9bbbe}.alert-dark .alert-
link{color:#040505}@-webkit-keyframes progress-bar-stripes{from{background-
position:1rem 0}to{background-position:0 0}}@keyframes progress-bar-
stripes{from{background-position:1rem 0}to{background-position:0
0}}.progress{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;height:1rem;overflow:hidden;font-size:.75rem;background-
color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.25rem}.progress-bar{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;-ms-

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flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;color:#fff;text-align:center;white-
space:nowrap;background-color:#007bff;transition:width .6s ease}@media screen
and (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce){.progress-bar{transition:none}}.progress-
bar-striped{background-image:linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-
size:1rem 1rem}.progress-bar-animated{-webkit-animation:progress-bar-stripes
1s linear infinite;animation:progress-bar-stripes 1s linear
infinite}.media{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:start;align-
items:flex-start}.media-body{-ms-flex:1;flex:1}.list-group{display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;padding-
left:0;margin-bottom:0}.list-group-item-action{width:100%;color:#495057;text-
align:inherit}.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#495057;text-decoration:none;background-
color:#f8f9fa}.list-group-item-action:active{color:#212529;background-
color:#e9ecef}.list-group-item{position:relative;display:block;padding:.75rem
1.25rem;margin-bottom:-1px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid
rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.list-group-item:first-child{border-top-left-
radius:.25rem;border-top-right-radius:.25rem}.list-group-item:last-
child{margin-bottom:0;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-
radius:.25rem}.list-group-item:focus,.list-group-item:hover{z-index:1;text-
decoration:none}.list-group-item.disabled,.list-group-
item:disabled{color:#6c757d;pointer-events:none;background-color:#fff}.list-
group-item.active{z-index:2;color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-
color:#007bff}.list-group-flush .list-group-item{border-right:0;border-
left:0;border-radius:0}.list-group-flush .list-group-item:last-child{margin-
bottom:-1px}.list-group-flush:first-child .list-group-item:first-
child{border-top:0}.list-group-flush:last-child .list-group-item:last-
child{margin-bottom:0;border-bottom:0}.list-group-item-
primary{color:#004085;background-color:#b8daff}.list-group-item-primary.list-
group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#004085;background-color:#9fcdfc}.list-group-item-
primary.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-
color:#004085;border-color:#004085}.list-group-item-
secondary{color:#383d41;background-color:#d6d8db}.list-group-item-
secondary.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-
item-action:hover{color:#383d41;background-color:#c8cbcf}.list-group-item-
secondary.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-
color:#383d41;border-color:#383d41}.list-group-item-
success{color:#155724;background-color:#c3e6cb}.list-group-item-success.list-
group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#155724;background-color:#b1dfbb}.list-group-item-
success.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-
color:#155724;border-color:#155724}.list-group-item-
info{color:#0c5460;background-color:#bee5eb}.list-group-item-info.list-group-
item-action:focus,.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#0c5460;background-color:#abdde5}.list-group-item-
info.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-
color:#0c5460;border-color:#0c5460}.list-group-item-
warning{color:#856404;background-color:#ffeeba}.list-group-item-warning.list-
group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#856404;background-color:#ffe8a1}.list-group-item-
warning.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-
color:#856404;border-color:#856404}.list-group-item-
danger{color:#721c24;background-color:#f5c6cb}.list-group-item-danger.list-
group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-
action:hover{color:#721c24;background-color:#f1b0b7}.list-group-item-

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danger.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-color:#721c24;border-color:#721c24}.list-group-item-light{color:#818182;background-color:#fdfdfe}.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#818182;background-color:#ecec6f}.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-color:#818182;border-color:#818182}.list-group-item-dark{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#c6c8ca}.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#b9bbbe}.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action.active{color:#fff;background-color:#1b1e21;border-color:#1b1e21}.close{float:right;font-size:1.5rem;font-weight:700;line-height:1;color:#000;text-shadow:0 1px 0 #fff;opacity:.5}.close:hover{color:#000;text-decoration:none}.close:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.close:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):focus,.close:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):hover{opacity:.75}button.close{padding:0;background-color:transparent;border:0;-webkit-appearance:none;-moz-appearance:none;appearance:none}a.close.disabled{pointer-events:none}.toast{max-width:350px;overflow:hidden;font-size:.875rem;background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.85);background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.1);border-radius:.25rem;box-shadow:0 .25rem .75rem rgba(0,0,0,.1);-webkit-backdrop-filter:blur(10px);backdrop-filter:blur(10px);opacity:0}.toast:not(:last-child){margin-bottom:.75rem}.toast.showing{opacity:1}.toast.show{display:block;opacity:1}.toast.hide{display:none}.toast-header{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;padding:.25rem .75rem;color:#6c757d;background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.85);background-clip:padding-box;border-bottom:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.05)}.toast-body{padding:.75rem}.modal-open{overflow:hidden}.modal-open .modal{overflow-x:hidden;overflow-y:auto}.modal{position:fixed;top:0;left:0;z-index:1050;display:none;width:100%;height:100%;overflow:hidden;outline:0}.modal-dialog{position:relative;width:auto;margin:.5rem;pointer-events:none}.modal.fade .modal-dialog{transition:-webkit-transform .3s ease-out;transition:transform .3s ease-out;transition:transform .3s ease-out,-webkit-transform .3s ease-out;-webkit-transform:translate(0,-50px);transform:translate(0,-50px)}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce){.modal.fade .modal-dialog{transition:none}}.modal.show .modal-dialog{-webkit-transform:none;transform:none}.modal-dialog-centered{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;min-height:calc(100% - (.5rem * 2))}.modal-dialog-centered::before{display:block;height:calc(100vh - (.5rem * 2));content:""}.modal-content{position:relative;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;width:100%;pointer-events:auto;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-radius:.3rem;outline:0}.modal-backdrop{position:fixed;top:0;left:0;z-index:1040;width:100vw;height:100vh;background-color:#000}.modal-backdrop.fade{opacity:0}.modal-backdrop.show{opacity:.5}.modal-header{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:start;align-items:flex-start;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-content:space-between;padding:1rem 1rem;border-bottom:1px solid #e9ecef;border-top-left-radius:.3rem;border-top-right-radius:.3rem}.modal-header .close{padding:1rem 1rem;margin:-1rem -1rem -1rem auto}.modal-title{margin-bottom:0;line-height:1.5}.modal-body{position:relative;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;padding:1rem}.modal-footer{display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-

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align:center;align-items:center;-ms-flex-pack:end;justify-content:flex-
end;padding:1rem;border-top:1px solid #e9ecef;border-bottom-right-
radius:.3rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.3rem}.modal-footer>:not(:first-
child){margin-left:.25rem}.modal-footer>:not(:last-child){margin-
right:.25rem}.modal-scrollbar-measure{position:absolute;top:-
9999px;width:50px;height:50px;overflow:scroll}@media (min-
width:576px){.modal-dialog{max-width:500px;margin:1.75rem auto}.modal-dialog-
centered{min-height:calc(100% - (1.75rem * 2))}.modal-dialog-
centered::before{height:calc(100vh - (1.75rem * 2))}.modal-sm{max-
width:300px}}@media (min-width:992px){.modal-lg,.modal-xl{max-
width:800px}}@media (min-width:1200px){.modal-xl{max-
width:1140px}}.tooltip{position:absolute;z-
index:1070;display:block;margin:0;font-family:-apple-
system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,"Noto
Sans",sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol","Noto
Color Emoji";font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;text-
align:left;text-align:start;text-decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-
transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-break:normal;word-
spacing:normal;white-space:normal;line-break:auto;font-size:.875rem;word-
wrap:break-word;opacity:0}.tooltip.show{opacity:.9}.tooltip
.arrow{position:absolute;display:block;width:.8rem;height:.4rem}.tooltip
.arrow::before{position:absolute;content:"";border-color:transparent;border-
style:solid}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top],.bs-tooltip-top{padding:.4rem
0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-top
.arrow{bottom:0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::before,.bs-
tooltip-top .arrow::before{top:0;border-width:.4rem .4rem 0;border-top-
color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right],.bs-tooltip-right{padding:0
.4rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-right
.arrow{left:0;width:.4rem;height:.8rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right]
.arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-right .arrow::before{right:0;border-width:.4rem
.4rem 0;border-right-color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-
placement^=bottom],.bs-tooltip-bottom{padding:.4rem 0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-bottom .arrow{top:0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-bottom
.arrow::before{bottom:0;border-width:0 .4rem .4rem;border-bottom-
color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left],.bs-tooltip-left{padding:0
.4rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-left
.arrow{right:0;width:.4rem;height:.8rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left]
.arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-left .arrow::before{left:0;border-width:.4rem 0
.4rem .4rem;border-left-color:#000}.tooltip-inner{max-
width:200px;padding:.25rem .5rem;color:#fff;text-align:center;background-
color:#000;border-radius:.25rem}.popover{position:absolute;top:0;left:0;z-
index:1060;display:block;max-width:276px;font-family:-apple-
system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,"Noto
Sans",sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol","Noto
Color Emoji";font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;text-
align:left;text-align:start;text-decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-
transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-break:normal;word-
spacing:normal;white-space:normal;line-break:auto;font-size:.875rem;word-
wrap:break-word;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px
solid rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-radius:.3rem}.popover
.arrow{position:absolute;display:block;width:1rem;height:.5rem;margin:0
.3rem}.popover .arrow::after,.popover
.arrow::before{position:absolute;display:block;content:"";border-
color:transparent;border-style:solid}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top],.bs-
popover-top{margin-bottom:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top]
.arrow,.bs-popover-top .arrow{bottom:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -1)}.bs-popover-

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auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top]
.arrow::before, .bs-popover-top .arrow::after, .bs-popover-top
.arrow::before{border-width:.5rem .5rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top]
.arrow::before, .bs-popover-top .arrow::before{bottom:0;border-top-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::after, .bs-
popover-top .arrow::after{bottom:1px;border-top-color:#fff}.bs-popover-
auto[x-placement^=right], .bs-popover-right{margin-left:.5rem}.bs-popover-
auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow, .bs-popover-right .arrow{left:calc((.5rem +
1px) * -1);width:.5rem;height:1rem;margin:.3rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=right] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=right]
.arrow::before, .bs-popover-right .arrow::after, .bs-popover-right
.arrow::before{border-width:.5rem .5rem .5rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=right] .arrow::before, .bs-popover-right
.arrow::before{left:0;border-right-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=right] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-right
.arrow::after{left:1px;border-right-color:#fff}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=bottom], .bs-popover-bottom{margin-top:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .arrow, .bs-popover-bottom .arrow{top:calc((.5rem + 1px) *
-1)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .arrow::before, .bs-popover-bottom .arrow::after, .bs-
popover-bottom .arrow::before{border-width:0 .5rem .5rem .5rem}.bs-popover-
auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow::before, .bs-popover-bottom
.arrow::before{top:0;border-bottom-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-bottom
.arrow::after{top:1px;border-bottom-color:#fff}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=bottom] .popover-header::before, .bs-popover-bottom .popover-
header::before{position:absolute;top:0;left:50%;display:block;width:1rem;marg
in-left:-.5rem;content:"";border-bottom:1px solid #f7f7f7}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=left], .bs-popover-left{margin-right:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=left] .arrow, .bs-popover-left .arrow{right:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -
1);width:.5rem;height:1rem;margin:.3rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left]
.arrow::after, .bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow::before, .bs-popover-
left .arrow::after, .bs-popover-left .arrow::before{border-width:.5rem 0 .5rem
.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow::before, .bs-popover-left
.arrow::before{right:0;border-left-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=left] .arrow::after, .bs-popover-left
.arrow::after{right:1px;border-left-color:#fff}.popover-header{padding:.5rem
.75rem;margin-bottom:0;font-size:1rem;color:inherit;background-
color:#f7f7f7;border-bottom:1px solid #ebeb;border-top-left-
radius:calc(.3rem - 1px);border-top-right-radius:calc(.3rem - 1px)}.popover-
header:empty{display:none}.popover-body{padding:.5rem
.75rem;color:#212529}.carousel{position:relative}.carousel.pointer-event{-ms-
touch-action:pan-y;touch-action:pan-y}.carousel-
inner{position:relative;width:100%;overflow:hidden}.carousel-
inner::after{display:block;clear:both;content:""}.carousel-
item{position:relative;display:none;float:left;width:100%;margin-right:-
100%;-webkit-backface-visibility:hidden;backface-
visibility:hidden;transition:-webkit-transform .6s ease-in-
out;transition:transform .6s ease-in-out;transition:transform .6s ease-in-
out,-webkit-transform .6s ease-in-out}@media screen and (prefers-reduced-
motion:reduce){.carousel-item{transition:none}}.carousel-item-next, .carousel-
item-prev, .carousel-item.active{display:block}.active.carousel-item-
right, .carousel-item-next:not(.carousel-item-left){-webkit-
transform:translateX(100%);transform:translateX(100%)}.active.carousel-item-
left, .carousel-item-prev:not(.carousel-item-right){-webkit-
transform:translateX(-100%);transform:translateX(-100%)}.carousel-fade
.carousel-item{opacity:0;transition-property:opacity;-webkit-

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transform:none;transform:none}.carousel-fade .carousel-item-next.carousel-
item-left,.carousel-fade .carousel-item-prev.carousel-item-right,.carousel-
fade .carousel-item.active{z-index:1;opacity:1}.carousel-fade
.active.carousel-item-left,.carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-right{z-
index:0;opacity:0;transition:0s .6s opacity}@media screen and (prefers-
reduced-motion:reduce){.carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-left,.carousel-
fade .active.carousel-item-right{transition:none}}.carousel-control-
next,.carousel-control-prev{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;z-
index:1;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-align:center;align-
items:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center;width:15%;color:#fff;text-
align:center;opacity:.5;transition:opacity .15s ease}@media screen and
(prefers-reduced-motion:reduce){.carousel-control-next,.carousel-control-
prev{transition:none}}.carousel-control-next:focus,.carousel-control-
next:hover,.carousel-control-prev:focus,.carousel-control-
prev:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;outline:0;opacity:.9}.carousel-
control-prev{left:0}.carousel-control-next{right:0}.carousel-control-next-
icon,.carousel-control-prev-icon{display:inline-
block;width:20px;height:20px;background:transparent no-repeat center
center;background-size:100% 100%}.carousel-control-prev-icon{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
fill='%23fff' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath d='M5.25 0l-4 4 4 4 1.5-1.5-2.5-2.5
2.5-2.5-1.5-1.5z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.carousel-control-next-icon{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
fill='%23fff' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath d='M2.75 0l-1.5 1.5 2.5 2.5-2.5 2.5
1.5 1.5 4-4-4-4z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")}.carousel-
indicators{position:absolute;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:15;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;padding-
left:0;margin-right:15%;margin-left:15%;list-style:none}.carousel-indicators
li{box-sizing:content-box;-ms-flex:0 1 auto;flex:0 1
auto;width:30px;height:3px;margin-right:3px;margin-left:3px;text-indent:-
999px;cursor:pointer;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-
box;border-top:10px solid transparent;border-bottom:10px solid
transparent;opacity:.5;transition:opacity .6s ease}@media screen and
(prefers-reduced-motion:reduce){.carousel-indicators
li{transition:none}}.carousel-indicators .active{opacity:1}.carousel-
caption{position:absolute;right:15%;bottom:20px;left:15%;z-index:10;padding-
top:20px;padding-bottom:20px;color:#fff;text-align:center}@-webkit-keyframes
spinner-border{to{-webkit-
transform:rotate(360deg);transform:rotate(360deg)}}@keyframes spinner-
border{to{-webkit-
transform:rotate(360deg);transform:rotate(360deg)}}.spinner-
border{display:inline-block;width:2rem;height:2rem;vertical-align:text-
bottom;border:.25em solid currentColor;border-right-color:transparent;border-
radius:50%;-webkit-animation:spinner-border .75s linear
infinite;animation:spinner-border .75s linear infinite}.spinner-border-
sm{width:1rem;height:1rem;border-width:.2em}@-webkit-keyframes spinner-
grow{0%{-webkit-
transform:scale(0);transform:scale(0)}50%{opacity:1}}@keyframes spinner-
grow{0%{-webkit-
transform:scale(0);transform:scale(0)}50%{opacity:1}}.spinner-
grow{display:inline-block;width:2rem;height:2rem;vertical-align:text-
bottom;background-color:currentColor;border-radius:50%;opacity:0;-webkit-
animation:spinner-grow .75s linear infinite;animation:spinner-grow .75s
linear infinite}.spinner-grow-sm{width:1rem;height:1rem}.align-
baseline{vertical-align:baseline!important}.align-top{vertical-
align:top!important}.align-middle{vertical-align:middle!important}.align-

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bottom{vertical-align:bottom!important}.align-text-bottom{vertical-align:text-bottom!important}.align-text-top{vertical-align:text-top!important}.bg-primary{background-color:#007bff!important}.a.bg-primary:focus,.a.bg-primary:hover,.button.bg-primary:focus,.button.bg-primary:hover{background-color:#0062cc!important}.bg-secondary{background-color:#6c757d!important}.a.bg-secondary:focus,.a.bg-secondary:hover,.button.bg-secondary:focus,.button.bg-secondary:hover{background-color:#545b62!important}.bg-success{background-color:#28a745!important}.a.bg-success:focus,.a.bg-success:hover,.button.bg-success:focus,.button.bg-success:hover{background-color:#1e7e34!important}.bg-info{background-color:#17a2b8!important}.a.bg-info:focus,.a.bg-info:hover,.button.bg-info:focus,.button.bg-info:hover{background-color:#117a8b!important}.bg-warning{background-color:#ffc107!important}.a.bg-warning:focus,.a.bg-warning:hover,.button.bg-warning:focus,.button.bg-warning:hover{background-color:#d39e00!important}.bg-danger{background-color:#dc3545!important}.a.bg-danger:focus,.a.bg-danger:hover,.button.bg-danger:focus,.button.bg-danger:hover{background-color:#bd2130!important}.bg-light{background-color:#f8f9fa!important}.a.bg-light:focus,.a.bg-light:hover,.button.bg-light:focus,.button.bg-light:hover{background-color:#dae0e5!important}.bg-dark{background-color:#343a40!important}.a.bg-dark:focus,.a.bg-dark:hover,.button.bg-dark:focus,.button.bg-dark:hover{background-color:#1d2124!important}.bg-white{background-color:#fff!important}.bg-transparent{background-color:transparent!important}.border{border:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-top{border-top:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-right{border-right:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-bottom{border-bottom:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-left{border-left:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-0{border:0!important}.border-top-0{border-top:0!important}.border-right-0{border-right:0!important}.border-bottom-0{border-bottom:0!important}.border-left-0{border-left:0!important}.border-primary{border-color:#007bff!important}.border-secondary{border-color:#6c757d!important}.border-success{border-color:#28a745!important}.border-info{border-color:#17a2b8!important}.border-warning{border-color:#ffc107!important}.border-danger{border-color:#dc3545!important}.border-light{border-color:#f8f9fa!important}.border-dark{border-color:#343a40!important}.border-white{border-color:#fff!important}.rounded{border-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-top{border-top-left-radius:.25rem!important;border-top-right-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-right{border-top-right-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-bottom{border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-left{border-top-left-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-circle{border-radius:50%!important}.rounded-pill{border-radius:50rem!important}.rounded-0{border-radius:0!important}.clearfix::after{display:block;clear:both;content:""}.d-none{display:none!important}.d-inline{display:inline!important}.d-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-block{display:block!important}.d-table{display:table!important}.d-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-flex{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-inline-flex{display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}@media (min-width:576px){.d-sm-none{display:none!important}.d-sm-inline{display:inline!important}.d-sm-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-sm-block{display:block!important}.d-sm-table{display:table!important}.d-sm-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-sm-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-sm-flex{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-sm-inline-flex{display:-ms-
```

```

inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-
width:768px){.d-md-none{display:none!important}.d-md-
inline{display:inline!important}.d-md-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}.d-md-block{display:block!important}.d-md-
table{display:table!important}.d-md-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-
md-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-md-flex{display:-ms-
flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-md-inline-flex{display:-ms-
inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-
width:992px){.d-lg-none{display:none!important}.d-lg-
inline{display:inline!important}.d-lg-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}.d-lg-block{display:block!important}.d-lg-
table{display:table!important}.d-lg-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-
lg-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-lg-flex{display:-ms-
flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-lg-inline-flex{display:-ms-
inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.d-xl-none{display:none!important}.d-xl-
inline{display:inline!important}.d-xl-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}.d-xl-block{display:block!important}.d-xl-
table{display:table!important}.d-xl-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-
xl-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-xl-flex{display:-ms-
flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-xl-inline-flex{display:-ms-
inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media print{.d-
print-none{display:none!important}.d-print-
inline{display:inline!important}.d-print-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}.d-print-block{display:block!important}.d-print-
table{display:table!important}.d-print-table-row{display:table-
row!important}.d-print-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-print-
flex{display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-print-inline-
flex{display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-
flex!important}}.embed-
responsive{position:relative;display:block;width:100%;padding:0;overflow:hidd
en}.embed-responsive::before{display:block;content:""}.embed-responsive
.embed-responsive-item,.embed-responsive embed,.embed-responsive
iframe,.embed-responsive object,.embed-responsive
video{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;left:0;width:100%;height:100%;border:0
}.embed-responsive-21by9::before{padding-top:42.857143%}.embed-responsive-
16by9::before{padding-top:56.25%}.embed-responsive-3by4::before{padding-
top:133.333333%}.embed-responsive-1by1::before{padding-top:100%}.flex-row{-
ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-column{-
ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-row-
reverse{-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-
reverse!important}.flex-column-reverse{-ms-flex-direction:column-
reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-wrap{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-nowrap{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-
wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.flex-fill{-ms-
flex:1 1 auto!important;flex:1 1 auto!important}.flex-grow-0{-ms-flex-
positive:0!important;flex-grow:0!important}.flex-grow-1{-ms-flex-
positive:1!important;flex-grow:1!important}.flex-shrink-0{-ms-flex-
negative:0!important;flex-shrink:0!important}.flex-shrink-1{-ms-flex-
negative:1!important;flex-shrink:1!important}.justify-content-start{-ms-flex-
pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-
end{-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-
content-center{-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-
content:center!important}.justify-content-between{-ms-flex-
pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-between!important}.justify-
content-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-

```

```
around!important}).align-items-start{-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-
items:flex-start!important}.align-items-end{-ms-flex-
align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-center{-ms-
flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-
baseline{-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-
items:baseline!important}.align-items-stretch{-ms-flex-
align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-start{-
ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-
content-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-
end!important}.align-content-center{-ms-flex-line-
pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-between{-
ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-
between!important}.align-content-around{-ms-flex-line-
pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-
content-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-
content:stretch!important}.align-self-auto{-ms-flex-item-
align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-start{-ms-flex-
item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-end{-
ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-
center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-
self:center!important}.align-self-baseline{-ms-flex-item-
align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-stretch{-
ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}@media
(min-width:576px){.flex-sm-row{-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-
direction:row!important}.flex-sm-column{-ms-flex-
direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-sm-row-
reverse{-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-
reverse!important}.flex-sm-column-reverse{-ms-flex-direction:column-
reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-sm-wrap{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-sm-nowrap{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-sm-wrap-reverse{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.flex-sm-
fill{-ms-flex:1 1 auto!important;flex:1 1 auto!important}.flex-sm-grow-0{-ms-
flex-positive:0!important;flex-grow:0!important}.flex-sm-grow-1{-ms-flex-
positive:1!important;flex-grow:1!important}.flex-sm-shrink-0{-ms-flex-
negative:0!important;flex-shrink:0!important}.flex-sm-shrink-1{-ms-flex-
negative:1!important;flex-shrink:1!important}.justify-content-sm-start{-ms-
flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-
content-sm-end{-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-
end!important}.justify-content-sm-center{-ms-flex-
pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-sm-
between{-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-
between!important}.justify-content-sm-around{-ms-flex-
pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-
items-sm-start{-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-
start!important}.align-items-sm-end{-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-
items:flex-end!important}.align-items-sm-center{-ms-flex-
align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-sm-
baseline{-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-
items:baseline!important}.align-items-sm-stretch{-ms-flex-
align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-sm-
start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-
start!important}.align-content-sm-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-
content:flex-end!important}.align-content-sm-center{-ms-flex-line-
pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-sm-
between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-
between!important}.align-content-sm-around{-ms-flex-line-
```

```
pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-
content-sm-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-
content:stretch!important}.align-self-sm-auto{-ms-flex-item-
align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-sm-start{-ms-flex-
item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-sm-
end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-
self-sm-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-
self:center!important}.align-self-sm-baseline{-ms-flex-item-
align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-sm-
stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-
self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.flex-md-row{-ms-flex-
direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-md-column{-ms-
flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-md-row-
reverse{-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-
reverse!important}.flex-md-column-reverse{-ms-flex-direction:column-
reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-md-wrap{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-md-nowrap{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-md-wrap-reverse{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.flex-md-
fill{-ms-flex:1 1 auto!important;flex:1 1 auto!important}.flex-md-grow-0{-ms-
flex-positive:0!important;flex-grow:0!important}.flex-md-grow-1{-ms-flex-
positive:1!important;flex-grow:1!important}.flex-md-shrink-0{-ms-flex-
negative:0!important;flex-shrink:0!important}.flex-md-shrink-1{-ms-flex-
negative:1!important;flex-shrink:1!important}.justify-content-md-start{-ms-
flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-
content-md-end{-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-
end!important}.justify-content-md-center{-ms-flex-
pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-md-
between{-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-
between!important}.justify-content-md-around{-ms-flex-
pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-
items-md-start{-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-
start!important}.align-items-md-end{-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-
items:flex-end!important}.align-items-md-center{-ms-flex-
align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-md-
baseline{-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-
items:baseline!important}.align-items-md-stretch{-ms-flex-
align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-md-
start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-
start!important}.align-content-md-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-
content:flex-end!important}.align-content-md-center{-ms-flex-line-
pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-md-
between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-
between!important}.align-content-md-around{-ms-flex-line-
pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-
content-md-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-
content:stretch!important}.align-self-md-auto{-ms-flex-item-
align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-md-start{-ms-flex-
item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-md-
end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-
self-md-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-
self:center!important}.align-self-md-baseline{-ms-flex-item-
align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-md-
stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-
self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.flex-lg-row{-ms-flex-
direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-lg-column{-ms-
flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-lg-row-
```

```

reverse{-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-
reverse!important}.flex-lg-column-reverse{-ms-flex-direction:column-
reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-lg-wrap{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-lg-nowrap{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-lg-wrap-reverse{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.flex-lg-
fill{-ms-flex:1 1 auto!important;flex:1 1 auto!important}.flex-lg-grow-0{-ms-
flex-positive:0!important;flex-grow:0!important}.flex-lg-grow-1{-ms-flex-
positive:1!important;flex-grow:1!important}.flex-lg-shrink-0{-ms-flex-
negative:0!important;flex-shrink:0!important}.flex-lg-shrink-1{-ms-flex-
negative:1!important;flex-shrink:1!important}.justify-content-lg-start{-ms-
flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-
content-lg-end{-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-
end!important}.justify-content-lg-center{-ms-flex-
pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-lg-
between{-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-
between!important}.justify-content-lg-around{-ms-flex-
pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-
items-lg-start{-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-
start!important}.align-items-lg-end{-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-
items:flex-end!important}.align-items-lg-center{-ms-flex-
align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-lg-
baseline{-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-
items:baseline!important}.align-items-lg-stretch{-ms-flex-
align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-lg-
start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-
start!important}.align-content-lg-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-
content:flex-end!important}.align-content-lg-center{-ms-flex-line-
pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-lg-
between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-
between!important}.align-content-lg-around{-ms-flex-line-
pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-
content-lg-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-
content:stretch!important}.align-self-lg-auto{-ms-flex-item-
align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-lg-start{-ms-flex-
item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-lg-
end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-
self-lg-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-
self:center!important}.align-self-lg-baseline{-ms-flex-item-
align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-lg-
stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-
self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.flex-xl-row{-ms-flex-
direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-xl-column{-ms-
flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-xl-row-
reverse{-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-
reverse!important}.flex-xl-column-reverse{-ms-flex-direction:column-
reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-xl-wrap{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-xl-nowrap{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-xl-wrap-reverse{-ms-
flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.flex-xl-
fill{-ms-flex:1 1 auto!important;flex:1 1 auto!important}.flex-xl-grow-0{-ms-
flex-positive:0!important;flex-grow:0!important}.flex-xl-grow-1{-ms-flex-
positive:1!important;flex-grow:1!important}.flex-xl-shrink-0{-ms-flex-
negative:0!important;flex-shrink:0!important}.flex-xl-shrink-1{-ms-flex-
negative:1!important;flex-shrink:1!important}.justify-content-xl-start{-ms-
flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-
content-xl-end{-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-

```

```

end!important}.justify-content-xl-center{-ms-flex-
pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-xl-
between{-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-
between!important}.justify-content-xl-around{-ms-flex-
pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-
items-xl-start{-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-
start!important}.align-items-xl-end{-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-
items:flex-end!important}.align-items-xl-center{-ms-flex-
align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-xl-
baseline{-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-
items:baseline!important}.align-items-xl-stretch{-ms-flex-
align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-xl-
start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-
start!important}.align-content-xl-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-
content:flex-end!important}.align-content-xl-center{-ms-flex-line-
pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-xl-
between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-
between!important}.align-content-xl-around{-ms-flex-line-
pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-
content-xl-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-
content:stretch!important}.align-self-xl-auto{-ms-flex-item-
align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-xl-start{-ms-flex-
item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-xl-
end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-
self-xl-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-
self:center!important}.align-self-xl-baseline{-ms-flex-item-
align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-xl-
stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-
self:stretch!important}.float-left{float:left!important}.float-
right{float:right!important}.float-none{float:none!important}@media (min-
width:576px){.float-sm-left{float:left!important}.float-sm-
right{float:right!important}.float-sm-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-
width:768px){.float-md-left{float:left!important}.float-md-
right{float:right!important}.float-md-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-
width:992px){.float-lg-left{float:left!important}.float-lg-
right{float:right!important}.float-lg-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.float-xl-left{float:left!important}.float-xl-
right{float:right!important}.float-xl-none{float:none!important}}.overflow-
auto{overflow:auto!important}.overflow-
hidden{overflow:hidden!important}.position-
static{position:static!important}.position-
relative{position:relative!important}.position-
absolute{position:absolute!important}.position-
fixed{position:fixed!important}.position-sticky{position:-webkit-
sticky!important;position:sticky!important}.fixed-
top{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;left:0;z-index:1030}.fixed-
bottom{position:fixed;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1030}@supports
((position:-webkit-sticky) or (position:sticky)){.sticky-top{position:-
webkit-sticky;position:sticky;top:0;z-index:1020}}.sr-
only{position:absolute;width:1px;height:1px;padding:0;overflow:hidden;clip:re-
ct(0,0,0,0);white-space:nowrap;border:0}.sr-only-focusable:active,.sr-only-
focusable:focus{position:static;width:auto;height:auto;overflow:visible;clip:
auto;white-space:normal}.shadow-sm{box-shadow:0 .125rem .25rem
rgba(0,0,0,.075)!important}.shadow{box-shadow:0 .5rem 1rem
rgba(0,0,0,.15)!important}.shadow-lg{box-shadow:0 1rem 3rem
rgba(0,0,0,.175)!important}.shadow-none{box-shadow:none!important}.w-
25{width:25%!important}.w-50{width:50%!important}.w-

```

```
75{width:75%!important}.w-100{width:100%!important}.w-
auto{width:auto!important}.h-25{height:25%!important}.h-
50{height:50%!important}.h-75{height:75%!important}.h-
100{height:100%!important}.h-auto{height:auto!important}.mw-100{max-
width:100%!important}.mh-100{max-height:100%!important}.min-vw-100{min-
width:100vw!important}.min-vh-100{min-height:100vh!important}.vw-
100{width:100vw!important}.vh-100{height:100vh!important}.m-
0{margin:0!important}.mt-0,.my-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-0,.mx-0{margin-
right:0!important}.mb-0,.my-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-0,.mx-0{margin-
left:0!important}.m-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-1,.my-1{margin-
top:.25rem!important}.mr-1,.mx-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-1,.my-
1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-1,.mx-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-
2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-2,.my-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-2,.mx-
2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-2,.my-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-
2,.mx-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-3,.my-
3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-3,.mx-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-
3,.my-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-3,.mx-3{margin-
left:1rem!important}.m-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-4,.my-4{margin-
top:1.5rem!important}.mr-4,.mx-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-4,.my-
4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-4,.mx-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-
5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-5,.my-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-5,.mx-
5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-5,.my-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-
5,.mx-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-0{padding:0!important}.pt-0,.py-
0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-0,.px-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-0,.py-
0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-0,.px-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-
1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-1,.py-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-
1,.px-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-1,.py-1{padding-
bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-1,.px-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-
2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-2,.py-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-2,.px-
2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-2,.py-2{padding-
bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-2,.px-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-
3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-3,.py-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-3,.px-
3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-3,.py-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-
3,.px-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-4,.py-
4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-4,.px-4{padding-
right:1.5rem!important}.pb-4,.py-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-4,.px-
4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-5,.py-
5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-5,.px-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-
5,.py-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-5,.px-5{padding-
left:3rem!important}.m-n1{margin:-.25rem!important}.mt-n1,.my-n1{margin-top:-
.25rem!important}.mr-n1,.mx-n1{margin-right:-.25rem!important}.mb-n1,.my-
n1{margin-bottom:-.25rem!important}.ml-n1,.mx-n1{margin-left:-
.25rem!important}.m-n2{margin:-.5rem!important}.mt-n2,.my-n2{margin-top:-
.5rem!important}.mr-n2,.mx-n2{margin-right:-.5rem!important}.mb-n2,.my-
n2{margin-bottom:-.5rem!important}.ml-n2,.mx-n2{margin-left:-
.5rem!important}.m-n3{margin:-1rem!important}.mt-n3,.my-n3{margin-top:-
1rem!important}.mr-n3,.mx-n3{margin-right:-1rem!important}.mb-n3,.my-
n3{margin-bottom:-1rem!important}.ml-n3,.mx-n3{margin-left:-
1rem!important}.m-n4{margin:-1.5rem!important}.mt-n4,.my-n4{margin-top:-
1.5rem!important}.mr-n4,.mx-n4{margin-right:-1.5rem!important}.mb-n4,.my-
n4{margin-bottom:-1.5rem!important}.ml-n4,.mx-n4{margin-left:-
1.5rem!important}.m-n5{margin:-3rem!important}.mt-n5,.my-n5{margin-top:-
3rem!important}.mr-n5,.mx-n5{margin-right:-3rem!important}.mb-n5,.my-
n5{margin-bottom:-3rem!important}.ml-n5,.mx-n5{margin-left:-
3rem!important}.m-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-auto,.my-auto{margin-
top:auto!important}.mr-auto,.mx-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-
auto,.my-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-auto,.mx-auto{margin-
```

```
left:auto!important}@media (min-width:576px){.m-sm-0{margin:0!important}.mt-sm-0,.my-sm-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-sm-0,.mx-sm-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-sm-0,.my-sm-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-sm-0,.mx-sm-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-sm-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-sm-1,.my-sm-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-sm-1,.mx-sm-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-sm-1,.my-sm-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-sm-1,.mx-sm-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-sm-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-sm-2,.my-sm-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-sm-2,.mx-sm-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-sm-2,.my-sm-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-sm-2,.mx-sm-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-sm-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-sm-3,.my-sm-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-sm-3,.mx-sm-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-sm-3,.my-sm-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-sm-3,.mx-sm-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-sm-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-sm-4,.my-sm-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-sm-4,.mx-sm-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-sm-4,.my-sm-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-sm-4,.mx-sm-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-sm-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-sm-5,.my-sm-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-sm-5,.mx-sm-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-sm-5,.my-sm-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-sm-5,.mx-sm-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-sm-0{padding:0!important}.pt-sm-0,.py-sm-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-sm-0,.px-sm-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-sm-0,.py-sm-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-sm-0,.px-sm-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-sm-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-sm-1,.py-sm-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-sm-1,.px-sm-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-sm-1,.py-sm-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-sm-1,.px-sm-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-sm-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-sm-2,.py-sm-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-sm-2,.px-sm-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-sm-2,.py-sm-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-sm-2,.px-sm-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-sm-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-sm-3,.py-sm-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-sm-3,.px-sm-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-sm-3,.py-sm-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-sm-3,.px-sm-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-sm-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-sm-4,.py-sm-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-sm-4,.px-sm-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-sm-4,.py-sm-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-sm-4,.px-sm-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-sm-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-sm-5,.py-sm-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-sm-5,.px-sm-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-sm-5,.py-sm-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-sm-5,.px-sm-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-sm-n1{margin:-.25rem!important}.mt-sm-n1,.my-sm-n1{margin-top:-.25rem!important}.mr-sm-n1,.mx-sm-n1{margin-right:-.25rem!important}.mb-sm-n1,.my-sm-n1{margin-bottom:-.25rem!important}.ml-sm-n1,.mx-sm-n1{margin-left:-.25rem!important}.m-sm-n2{margin:-.5rem!important}.mt-sm-n2,.my-sm-n2{margin-top:-.5rem!important}.mr-sm-n2,.mx-sm-n2{margin-right:-.5rem!important}.mb-sm-n2,.my-sm-n2{margin-bottom:-.5rem!important}.ml-sm-n2,.mx-sm-n2{margin-left:-.5rem!important}.m-sm-n3{margin:-1rem!important}.mt-sm-n3,.my-sm-n3{margin-top:-1rem!important}.mr-sm-n3,.mx-sm-n3{margin-right:-1rem!important}.mb-sm-n3,.my-sm-n3{margin-bottom:-1rem!important}.ml-sm-n3,.mx-sm-n3{margin-left:-1rem!important}.m-sm-n4{margin:-1.5rem!important}.mt-sm-n4,.my-sm-n4{margin-top:-1.5rem!important}.mr-sm-n4,.mx-sm-n4{margin-right:-1.5rem!important}.mb-sm-n4,.my-sm-n4{margin-bottom:-1.5rem!important}.ml-sm-n4,.mx-sm-n4{margin-left:-1.5rem!important}.m-sm-n5{margin:-3rem!important}.mt-sm-n5,.my-sm-n5{margin-top:-3rem!important}.mr-sm-n5,.mx-sm-n5{margin-right:-3rem!important}.mb-sm-n5,.my-sm-n5{margin-bottom:-3rem!important}.ml-sm-n5,.mx-sm-n5{margin-left:-3rem!important}.m-sm-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-sm-auto,.my-sm-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-sm-auto,.mx-sm-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-
```

```
sm-auto, .my-sm-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-sm-auto, .mx-sm-
auto{margin-left:auto!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.m-md-
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md-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-md-0, .my-md-0{margin-
bottom:0!important}.ml-md-0, .mx-md-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-md-
1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-md-1, .my-md-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-
md-1, .mx-md-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-md-1, .my-md-1{margin-
bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-md-1, .mx-md-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-md-
2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-md-2, .my-md-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-md-
2, .mx-md-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-md-2, .my-md-2{margin-
bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-md-2, .mx-md-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-md-
3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-md-3, .my-md-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-md-
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bottom:1rem!important}.ml-md-3, .mx-md-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-md-
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bottom:3rem!important}.ml-md-5, .mx-md-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-md-
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left:1.5rem!important}.p-md-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-md-5, .py-md-
5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-md-5, .px-md-5{padding-
right:3rem!important}.pb-md-5, .py-md-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-md-
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right:-.25rem!important}.mb-md-n1, .my-md-n1{margin-bottom:-
.25rem!important}.ml-md-n1, .mx-md-n1{margin-left:-.25rem!important}.m-md-
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.5rem!important}.mr-md-n2, .mx-md-n2{margin-right:-.5rem!important}.mb-md-
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top:-1rem!important}.mr-md-n3, .mx-md-n3{margin-right:-1rem!important}.mb-md-
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md-n4, .my-md-n4{margin-bottom:-1.5rem!important}.ml-md-n4, .mx-md-n4{margin-
left:-1.5rem!important}.m-md-n5{margin:-3rem!important}.mt-md-n5, .my-md-
n5{margin-top:-3rem!important}.mr-md-n5, .mx-md-n5{margin-right:-
3rem!important}.mb-md-n5, .my-md-n5{margin-bottom:-3rem!important}.ml-md-
n5, .mx-md-n5{margin-left:-3rem!important}.m-md-
auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-md-auto, .my-md-auto{margin-
```

```
top:auto!important}.mr-md-auto,.mx-md-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-
md-auto,.my-md-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-md-auto,.mx-md-
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bottom:0!important}.ml-lg-0,.mx-lg-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-lg-
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lg-1,.mx-lg-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-lg-1,.my-lg-1{margin-
bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-lg-1,.mx-lg-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-lg-
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bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-lg-2,.mx-lg-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-lg-
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bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-lg-4,.mx-lg-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-lg-
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bottom:3rem!important}.ml-lg-5,.mx-lg-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-lg-
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lg-2,.px-lg-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-lg-
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3,.px-lg-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-lg-3,.py-lg-3{padding-
bottom:1rem!important}.pl-lg-3,.px-lg-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-lg-
4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-lg-4,.py-lg-4{padding-
top:1.5rem!important}.pr-lg-4,.px-lg-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-lg-
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left:1.5rem!important}.p-lg-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-lg-5,.py-lg-
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lg-n1,.my-lg-n1{margin-top:-.25rem!important}.mr-lg-n1,.mx-lg-n1{margin-
right:-.25rem!important}.mb-lg-n1,.my-lg-n1{margin-bottom:-
.25rem!important}.ml-lg-n1,.mx-lg-n1{margin-left:-.25rem!important}.m-lg-
n2{margin:-.5rem!important}.mt-lg-n2,.my-lg-n2{margin-top:-
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top:-1rem!important}.mr-lg-n3,.mx-lg-n3{margin-right:-1rem!important}.mb-lg-
n3,.my-lg-n3{margin-bottom:-1rem!important}.ml-lg-n3,.mx-lg-n3{margin-left:-
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top:-1.5rem!important}.mr-lg-n4,.mx-lg-n4{margin-right:-1.5rem!important}.mb-
lg-n4,.my-lg-n4{margin-bottom:-1.5rem!important}.ml-lg-n4,.mx-lg-n4{margin-
left:-1.5rem!important}.m-lg-n5{margin:-3rem!important}.mt-lg-n5,.my-lg-
n5{margin-top:-3rem!important}.mr-lg-n5,.mx-lg-n5{margin-right:-
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n5,.mx-lg-n5{margin-left:-3rem!important}.m-lg-
```

```

auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-lg-auto, .my-lg-auto{margin-
top:auto!important}.mr-lg-auto, .mx-lg-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-
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auto{margin-left:auto!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.m-xl-
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bottom:0!important}.ml-xl-0, .mx-xl-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-xl-
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xl-1, .mx-xl-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-xl-1, .my-xl-1{margin-
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bottom:1rem!important}.ml-xl-3, .mx-xl-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-xl-
4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-xl-4, .my-xl-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-
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top:.25rem!important}.pr-xl-1, .px-xl-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-xl-
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left:.25rem!important}.p-xl-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-xl-2, .py-xl-
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right:.5rem!important}.pb-xl-2, .py-xl-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-
xl-2, .px-xl-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-xl-
3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-xl-3, .py-xl-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-xl-
3, .px-xl-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-xl-3, .py-xl-3{padding-
bottom:1rem!important}.pl-xl-3, .px-xl-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-xl-
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top:1.5rem!important}.pr-xl-4, .px-xl-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-xl-
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left:1.5rem!important}.p-xl-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-xl-5, .py-xl-
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xl-n1, .my-xl-n1{margin-top:-.25rem!important}.mr-xl-n1, .mx-xl-n1{margin-
right:-.25rem!important}.mb-xl-n1, .my-xl-n1{margin-bottom:-
.25rem!important}.ml-xl-n1, .mx-xl-n1{margin-left:-.25rem!important}.m-xl-
n2{margin:-.5rem!important}.mt-xl-n2, .my-xl-n2{margin-top:-
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top:-1.5rem!important}.mr-xl-n4, .mx-xl-n4{margin-right:-1.5rem!important}.mb-
xl-n4, .my-xl-n4{margin-bottom:-1.5rem!important}.ml-xl-n4, .mx-xl-n4{margin-
left:-1.5rem!important}.m-xl-n5{margin:-3rem!important}.mt-xl-n5, .my-xl-
n5{margin-top:-3rem!important}.mr-xl-n5, .mx-xl-n5{margin-right:-
3rem!important}.mb-xl-n5, .my-xl-n5{margin-bottom:-3rem!important}.ml-xl-

```

```

n5, .mx-xl-n5{margin-left:-3rem!important}.m-xl-
auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-xl-auto, .my-xl-auto{margin-
top:auto!important}.mr-xl-auto, .mx-xl-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-
xl-auto, .my-xl-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-xl-auto, .mx-xl-
auto{margin-left:auto!important}}.text-monospace{font-family:SFMono-
Regular, Menlo, Monaco, Consolas, "Liberation Mono", "Courier
New", monospace}.text-justify{text-align:justify!important}.text-wrap{white-
space:normal!important}.text-nowrap{white-space:nowrap!important}.text-
truncate{overflow:hidden;text-overflow:ellipsis;white-space:nowrap}.text-
left{text-align:left!important}.text-right{text-align:right!important}.text-
center{text-align:center!important}@media (min-width:576px){.text-sm-
left{text-align:left!important}.text-sm-right{text-
align:right!important}.text-sm-center{text-align:center!important}}@media
(min-width:768px){.text-md-left{text-align:left!important}.text-md-
right{text-align:right!important}.text-md-center{text-
align:center!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.text-lg-left{text-
align:left!important}.text-lg-right{text-align:right!important}.text-lg-
center{text-align:center!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.text-xl-
left{text-align:left!important}.text-xl-right{text-
align:right!important}.text-xl-center{text-align:center!important}}.text-
lowercase{text-transform:lowercase!important}.text-uppercase{text-
transform:uppercase!important}.text-capitalize{text-
transform:capitalize!important}.font-weight-light{font-
weight:300!important}.font-weight-lighter{font-
weight:lighter!important}.font-weight-normal{font-weight:400!important}.font-
weight-bold{font-weight:700!important}.font-weight-bolder{font-
weight:bolder!important}.font-italic{font-style:italic!important}.text-
white{color:#fff!important}.text-primary{color:#007bff!important}.a.text-
primary:focus, a.text-primary:hover{color:#0056b3!important}.text-
secondary{color:#6c757d!important}.a.text-secondary:focus, a.text-
secondary:hover{color:#494f54!important}.text-
success{color:#28a745!important}.a.text-
success:focus, a.text-
success:hover{color:#19692c!important}.text-
info{color:#17a2b8!important}.a.text-
info:focus, a.text-
info:hover{color:#0f6674!important}.text-
warning{color:#ffc107!important}.a.text-
warning:focus, a.text-
warning:hover{color:#ba8b00!important}.text-
danger{color:#dc3545!important}.a.text-
danger:focus, a.text-
danger:hover{color:#a71d2a!important}.text-
light{color:#f8f9fa!important}.a.text-
light:focus, a.text-
light:hover{color:#cbd3da!important}.text-
dark{color:#343a40!important}.a.text-
dark:focus, a.text-
dark:hover{color:#121416!important}.text-body{color:#212529!important}.text-
muted{color:#6c757d!important}.text-black-
50{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5)!important}.text-white-
50{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)!important}.text-hide{font:0/0
a;color:transparent;text-shadow:none;background-
color:transparent;border:0}.text-decoration-none{text-
decoration:none!important}.text-
reset{color:inherit!important}.visible{visibility:visible!important}.invisibl
e{visibility:hidden!important}@media print{*,::after,::before{text-
shadow:none!important;box-shadow:none!important}a:not(.btn){text-
decoration:underline}abbr[title]::after{content:" (" attr(title)
")"}pre{white-space:pre-wrap!important}blockquote,pre{border:1px solid
#adb5bd;page-break-inside:avoid}thead{display:table-header-group}img,tr{page-
break-inside:avoid}h2,h3,p{orphans:3;widows:3}h2,h3{page-break-
after:avoid}@page{size:a3}body{min-width:992px!important}.container{min-

```

```
width:992px!important}.navbar{display:none}.badge{border:1px solid
#000}.table{border-collapse:collapse!important}.table td,.table
th{background-color:#fff!important}.table-bordered td,.table-bordered
th{border:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.table-dark{color:inherit}.table-dark
tbody+tbody,.table-dark td,.table-dark th,.table-dark thead th{border-
color:#dee2e6}.table .thead-dark th{color:inherit;border-color:#dee2e6}}
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.min.css.map */
```

Font-awesome.min.css

```
/*!
 * Font Awesome 4.7.0 by @davegandy - http://fontawesome.io - @fontawesome
 * License - http://fontawesome.io/license (Font: SIL OFL 1.1, CSS: MIT
 License)
 */
@font-face{font-family:'FontAwesome';src:url('../fonts/fontawesome-
webfont.eot?v=4.7.0');src:url('../fonts/fontawesome-
webfont.eot?#iefix&v=4.7.0') format('embedded-
opentype'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.woff2?v=4.7.0')
format('woff2'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.woff?v=4.7.0')
format('woff'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.ttf?v=4.7.0')
format('truetype'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-
webfont.svg?v=4.7.0#fontawesomeregular') format('svg');font-
weight:normal;font-style:normal}.fa{display:inline-block;font:normal normal
normal 14px/1 FontAwesome;font-size:inherit;text-rendering:auto;-webkit-font-
smoothing:antialiased;-moz-osx-font-smoothing:grayscale}.fa-lg{font-
size:1.33333333em;line-height:.75em;vertical-align:-15%}.fa-2x{font-
size:2em}.fa-3x{font-size:3em}.fa-4x{font-size:4em}.fa-5x{font-size:5em}.fa-
fw{width:1.28571429em;text-align:center}.fa-ul{padding-left:0;margin-
left:2.14285714em;list-style-type:none}.fa-ul>li{position:relative}.fa-
li{position:absolute;left:-
2.14285714em;width:2.14285714em;top:.14285714em;text-align:center}.fa-li.fa-
lg{left:-1.85714286em}.fa-border{padding:.2em .25em .15em;border:solid .08em
#eee;border-radius:.1em}.fa-pull-left{float:left}.fa-pull-
right{float:right}.fa.fa-pull-left{margin-right:.3em}.fa.fa-pull-
right{margin-left:.3em}.pull-right{float:right}.pull-
left{float:left}.fa.pull-left{margin-right:.3em}.fa.pull-right{margin-
left:.3em}.fa-spin{-webkit-animation:fa-spin 2s infinite linear;animation:fa-
spin 2s infinite linear}.fa-pulse{-webkit-animation:fa-spin 1s infinite
steps(8);animation:fa-spin 1s infinite steps(8)}@-webkit-keyframes fa-
spin{0%{-webkit-transform:rotate(0deg);transform:rotate(0deg)}100%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(359deg);transform:rotate(359deg)}}@keyframes fa-spin{0%{-
webkit-transform:rotate(0deg);transform:rotate(0deg)}100%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(359deg);transform:rotate(359deg)}}.fa-rotate-90{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=1)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(90deg);-ms-
transform:rotate(90deg);transform:rotate(90deg)}.fa-rotate-180{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=2)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(180deg);-ms-
transform:rotate(180deg);transform:rotate(180deg)}.fa-rotate-270{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=3)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(270deg);-ms-
transform:rotate(270deg);transform:rotate(270deg)}.fa-flip-horizontal{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=0, mirror=1)";-
webkit-transform:scale(-1, 1);-ms-transform:scale(-1, 1);transform:scale(-1,
1)}.fa-flip-vertical{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=2, mirror=1)";-
webkit-transform:scale(1, -1);-ms-transform:scale(1, -1);transform:scale(1, -
1)}:root .fa-rotate-90,:root .fa-rotate-180,:root .fa-rotate-270,:root .fa-
flip-horizontal,:root .fa-flip-vertical{filter:none}.fa-
stack{position:relative;display:inline-block;width:2em;height:2em;line-
height:2em;vertical-align:middle}.fa-stack-1x,.fa-stack-
2x{position:absolute;left:0;width:100%;text-align:center}.fa-stack-1x{line-
height:inherit}.fa-stack-2x{font-size:2em}.fa-inverse{color:#fff}.fa-
```

```
glass:before{content:"\f000"}.fa-music:before{content:"\f001"}.fa-
search:before{content:"\f002"}.fa-envelope-o:before{content:"\f003"}.fa-
heart:before{content:"\f004"}.fa-star:before{content:"\f005"}.fa-star-
o:before{content:"\f006"}.fa-user:before{content:"\f007"}.fa-
film:before{content:"\f008"}.fa-th-large:before{content:"\f009"}.fa-
th:before{content:"\f00a"}.fa-th-list:before{content:"\f00b"}.fa-
check:before{content:"\f00c"}.fa-remove:before,.fa-close:before,.fa-
times:before{content:"\f00d"}.fa-search-plus:before{content:"\f00e"}.fa-
search-minus:before{content:"\f010"}.fa-power-off:before{content:"\f011"}.fa-
signal:before{content:"\f012"}.fa-gear:before,.fa-
cog:before{content:"\f013"}.fa-trash-o:before{content:"\f014"}.fa-
home:before{content:"\f015"}.fa-file-o:before{content:"\f016"}.fa-clock-
o:before{content:"\f017"}.fa-road:before{content:"\f018"}.fa-
download:before{content:"\f019"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-
down:before{content:"\f01a"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-up:before{content:"\f01b"}.fa-
inbox:before{content:"\f01c"}.fa-play-circle-o:before{content:"\f01d"}.fa-
rotate-right:before,.fa-repeat:before{content:"\f01e"}.fa-
refresh:before{content:"\f021"}.fa-list-alt:before{content:"\f022"}.fa-
lock:before{content:"\f023"}.fa-flag:before{content:"\f024"}.fa-
headphones:before{content:"\f025"}.fa-volume-off:before{content:"\f026"}.fa-
volume-down:before{content:"\f027"}.fa-volume-up:before{content:"\f028"}.fa-
qrcode:before{content:"\f029"}.fa-barcode:before{content:"\f02a"}.fa-
tag:before{content:"\f02b"}.fa-tags:before{content:"\f02c"}.fa-
book:before{content:"\f02d"}.fa-bookmark:before{content:"\f02e"}.fa-
print:before{content:"\f02f"}.fa-camera:before{content:"\f030"}.fa-
font:before{content:"\f031"}.fa-bold:before{content:"\f032"}.fa-
italic:before{content:"\f033"}.fa-text-height:before{content:"\f034"}.fa-
text-width:before{content:"\f035"}.fa-align-left:before{content:"\f036"}.fa-
align-center:before{content:"\f037"}.fa-align-
right:before{content:"\f038"}.fa-align-justify:before{content:"\f039"}.fa-
list:before{content:"\f03a"}.fa-dedent:before,.fa-
outdent:before{content:"\f03b"}.fa-indent:before{content:"\f03c"}.fa-video-
camera:before{content:"\f03d"}.fa-photo:before,.fa-image:before,.fa-picture-
o:before{content:"\f03e"}.fa-pencil:before{content:"\f040"}.fa-map-
marker:before{content:"\f041"}.fa-adjust:before{content:"\f042"}.fa-
tint:before{content:"\f043"}.fa-edit:before,.fa-pencil-square-
o:before{content:"\f044"}.fa-share-square-o:before{content:"\f045"}.fa-check-
square-o:before{content:"\f046"}.fa-arrows:before{content:"\f047"}.fa-step-
backward:before{content:"\f048"}.fa-fast-backward:before{content:"\f049"}.fa-
backward:before{content:"\f04a"}.fa-play:before{content:"\f04b"}.fa-
pause:before{content:"\f04c"}.fa-stop:before{content:"\f04d"}.fa-
forward:before{content:"\f04e"}.fa-fast-forward:before{content:"\f050"}.fa-
step-forward:before{content:"\f051"}.fa-eject:before{content:"\f052"}.fa-
chevron-left:before{content:"\f053"}.fa-chevron-
right:before{content:"\f054"}.fa-plus-circle:before{content:"\f055"}.fa-
minus-circle:before{content:"\f056"}.fa-times-
circle:before{content:"\f057"}.fa-check-circle:before{content:"\f058"}.fa-
question-circle:before{content:"\f059"}.fa-info-
circle:before{content:"\f05a"}.fa-crosshairs:before{content:"\f05b"}.fa-
times-circle-o:before{content:"\f05c"}.fa-check-circle-
o:before{content:"\f05d"}.fa-ban:before{content:"\f05e"}.fa-arrow-
left:before{content:"\f060"}.fa-arrow-right:before{content:"\f061"}.fa-arrow-
up:before{content:"\f062"}.fa-arrow-down:before{content:"\f063"}.fa-mail-
forward:before,.fa-share:before{content:"\f064"}.fa-
expand:before{content:"\f065"}.fa-compress:before{content:"\f066"}.fa-
plus:before{content:"\f067"}.fa-minus:before{content:"\f068"}.fa-
asterisk:before{content:"\f069"}.fa-exclamation-
```

```
circle:before{content:"\f06a"}.fa-gift:before{content:"\f06b"}.fa-leaf:before{content:"\f06c"}.fa-fire:before{content:"\f06d"}.fa-eye:before{content:"\f06e"}.fa-eye-slash:before{content:"\f070"}.fa-warning:before,.fa-exclamation-triangle:before{content:"\f071"}.fa-plane:before{content:"\f072"}.fa-calendar:before{content:"\f073"}.fa-random:before{content:"\f074"}.fa-comment:before{content:"\f075"}.fa-magnet:before{content:"\f076"}.fa-chevron-up:before{content:"\f077"}.fa-chevron-down:before{content:"\f078"}.fa-retweet:before{content:"\f079"}.fa-shopping-cart:before{content:"\f07a"}.fa-folder:before{content:"\f07b"}.fa-folder-open:before{content:"\f07c"}.fa-arrows-v:before{content:"\f07d"}.fa-arrows-h:before{content:"\f07e"}.fa-bar-chart-o:before,.fa-bar-chart:before{content:"\f080"}.fa-twitter-square:before{content:"\f081"}.fa-facebook-square:before{content:"\f082"}.fa-camera-retro:before{content:"\f083"}.fa-key:before{content:"\f084"}.fa-gears:before,.fa-cogs:before{content:"\f085"}.fa-comments:before{content:"\f086"}.fa-thumbs-o-up:before{content:"\f087"}.fa-thumbs-o-down:before{content:"\f088"}.fa-star-half:before{content:"\f089"}.fa-heart-o:before{content:"\f08a"}.fa-sign-out:before{content:"\f08b"}.fa-linkedin-square:before{content:"\f08c"}.fa-thumb-tack:before{content:"\f08d"}.fa-external-link:before{content:"\f08e"}.fa-sign-in:before{content:"\f090"}.fa-trophy:before{content:"\f091"}.fa-github-square:before{content:"\f092"}.fa-upload:before{content:"\f093"}.fa-lemon-o:before{content:"\f094"}.fa-phone:before{content:"\f095"}.fa-square-o:before{content:"\f096"}.fa-bookmark-o:before{content:"\f097"}.fa-phone-square:before{content:"\f098"}.fa-twitter:before{content:"\f099"}.fa-facebook-f:before,.fa-facebook:before{content:"\f09a"}.fa-github:before{content:"\f09b"}.fa-unlock:before{content:"\f09c"}.fa-credit-card:before{content:"\f09d"}.fa-feed:before,.fa-rss:before{content:"\f09e"}.fa-hdd-o:before{content:"\f0a0"}.fa-bullhorn:before{content:"\f0a1"}.fa-bell:before{content:"\f0f3"}.fa-certificate:before{content:"\f0a3"}.fa-hand-o-right:before{content:"\f0a4"}.fa-hand-o-left:before{content:"\f0a5"}.fa-hand-o-up:before{content:"\f0a6"}.fa-hand-o-down:before{content:"\f0a7"}.fa-arrow-circle-left:before{content:"\f0a8"}.fa-arrow-circle-right:before{content:"\f0a9"}.fa-arrow-circle-up:before{content:"\f0aa"}.fa-arrow-circle-down:before{content:"\f0ab"}.fa-globe:before{content:"\f0ac"}.fa-wrench:before{content:"\f0ad"}.fa-tasks:before{content:"\f0ae"}.fa-filter:before{content:"\f0b0"}.fa-briefcase:before{content:"\f0b1"}.fa-arrows-alt:before{content:"\f0b2"}.fa-group:before,.fa-users:before{content:"\f0c0"}.fa-chain:before,.fa-link:before{content:"\f0c1"}.fa-cloud:before{content:"\f0c2"}.fa-flask:before{content:"\f0c3"}.fa-cut:before,.fa-scissors:before{content:"\f0c4"}.fa-copy:before,.fa-files-o:before{content:"\f0c5"}.fa-paperclip:before{content:"\f0c6"}.fa-save:before,.fa-floppy-o:before{content:"\f0c7"}.fa-square:before{content:"\f0c8"}.fa-navicon:before,.fa-reorder:before,.fa-bars:before{content:"\f0c9"}.fa-list-ul:before{content:"\f0ca"}.fa-list-ol:before{content:"\f0cb"}.fa-strikethrough:before{content:"\f0cc"}.fa-underline:before{content:"\f0cd"}.fa-table:before{content:"\f0ce"}.fa-magic:before{content:"\f0d0"}.fa-truck:before{content:"\f0d1"}.fa-pinterest:before{content:"\f0d2"}.fa-pinterest-square:before{content:"\f0d3"}.fa-google-plus-square:before{content:"\f0d4"}.fa-google-plus:before{content:"\f0d5"}.fa-money:before{content:"\f0d6"}.fa-caret-down:before{content:"\f0d7"}.fa-caret-up:before{content:"\f0d8"}.fa-caret-left:before{content:"\f0d9"}.fa-caret-right:before{content:"\f0da"}.fa-columns:before{content:"\f0db"}.fa-
```

unsorted:before, .fa-sort:before{content:"\f0dc"}.fa-sort-down:before, .fa-sort-desc:before{content:"\f0dd"}.fa-sort-up:before, .fa-sort-asc:before{content:"\f0de"}.fa-envelope:before{content:"\f0e0"}.fa-linkedin:before{content:"\f0e1"}.fa-rotate-left:before, .fa-undo:before{content:"\f0e2"}.fa-legal:before, .fa-gavel:before{content:"\f0e3"}.fa-dashboard:before, .fa-tachometer:before{content:"\f0e4"}.fa-comment-o:before{content:"\f0e5"}.fa-comments-o:before{content:"\f0e6"}.fa-flash:before, .fa-bolt:before{content:"\f0e7"}.fa-sitemap:before{content:"\f0e8"}.fa-umbrella:before{content:"\f0e9"}.fa-paste:before, .fa-clipboard:before{content:"\f0ea"}.fa-lightbulb-o:before{content:"\f0eb"}.fa-exchange:before{content:"\f0ec"}.fa-cloud-download:before{content:"\f0ed"}.fa-cloud-upload:before{content:"\f0ee"}.fa-user-md:before{content:"\f0f0"}.fa-stethoscope:before{content:"\f0f1"}.fa-suitcase:before{content:"\f0f2"}.fa-bell-o:before{content:"\f0a2"}.fa-coffee:before{content:"\f0f4"}.fa-cutlery:before{content:"\f0f5"}.fa-file-text-o:before{content:"\f0f6"}.fa-building-o:before{content:"\f0f7"}.fa-hospital-o:before{content:"\f0f8"}.fa-ambulance:before{content:"\f0f9"}.fa-medkit:before{content:"\f0fa"}.fa-fighter-jet:before{content:"\f0fb"}.fa-beer:before{content:"\f0fc"}.fa-h-square:before{content:"\f0fd"}.fa-plus-square:before{content:"\f0fe"}.fa-angle-double-left:before{content:"\f100"}.fa-angle-double-right:before{content:"\f101"}.fa-angle-double-up:before{content:"\f102"}.fa-angle-double-down:before{content:"\f103"}.fa-angle-left:before{content:"\f104"}.fa-angle-right:before{content:"\f105"}.fa-angle-up:before{content:"\f106"}.fa-angle-down:before{content:"\f107"}.fa-desktop:before{content:"\f108"}.fa-laptop:before{content:"\f109"}.fa-tablet:before{content:"\f10a"}.fa-mobile-phone:before, .fa-mobile:before{content:"\f10b"}.fa-circle-o:before{content:"\f10c"}.fa-quote-left:before{content:"\f10d"}.fa-quote-right:before{content:"\f10e"}.fa-spinner:before{content:"\f110"}.fa-circle:before{content:"\f111"}.fa-mail-reply:before, .fa-reply:before{content:"\f112"}.fa-github-alt:before{content:"\f113"}.fa-folder-o:before{content:"\f114"}.fa-folder-open-o:before{content:"\f115"}.fa-smile-o:before{content:"\f118"}.fa-frown-o:before{content:"\f119"}.fa-meh-o:before{content:"\f11a"}.fa-gamepad:before{content:"\f11b"}.fa-keyboard-o:before{content:"\f11c"}.fa-flag-o:before{content:"\f11d"}.fa-flag-checkered:before{content:"\f11e"}.fa-terminal:before{content:"\f120"}.fa-code:before{content:"\f121"}.fa-mail-reply-all:before, .fa-reply-all:before{content:"\f122"}.fa-star-half-empty:before, .fa-star-half-full:before, .fa-star-half-o:before{content:"\f123"}.fa-location-arrow:before{content:"\f124"}.fa-crop:before{content:"\f125"}.fa-code-fork:before{content:"\f126"}.fa-unlink:before, .fa-chain-broken:before{content:"\f127"}.fa-question:before{content:"\f128"}.fa-info:before{content:"\f129"}.fa-exclamation:before{content:"\f12a"}.fa-superscript:before{content:"\f12b"}.fa-subscript:before{content:"\f12c"}.fa-eraser:before{content:"\f12d"}.fa-puzzle-piece:before{content:"\f12e"}.fa-microphone:before{content:"\f130"}.fa-microphone-slash:before{content:"\f131"}.fa-shield:before{content:"\f132"}.fa-calendar-o:before{content:"\f133"}.fa-fire-extinguisher:before{content:"\f134"}.fa-rocket:before{content:"\f135"}.fa-maxcdn:before{content:"\f136"}.fa-chevron-circle-left:before{content:"\f137"}.fa-chevron-circle-right:before{content:"\f138"}.fa-chevron-circle-up:before{content:"\f139"}.fa-chevron-circle-down:before{content:"\f13a"}.fa-html5:before{content:"\f13b"}.fa-css3:before{content:"\f13c"}.fa-anchor:before{content:"\f13d"}.fa-unlock-alt:before{content:"\f13e"}.fa-bullseye:before{content:"\f140"}.fa-ellipsis-h:before{content:"\f141"}.fa-

```
ellipsis-v:before{content:"\f142"}.fa-rss-square:before{content:"\f143"}.fa-
play-circle:before{content:"\f144"}.fa-ticket:before{content:"\f145"}.fa-
minus-square:before{content:"\f146"}.fa-minus-square-
o:before{content:"\f147"}.fa-level-up:before{content:"\f148"}.fa-level-
down:before{content:"\f149"}.fa-check-square:before{content:"\f14a"}.fa-
pencil-square:before{content:"\f14b"}.fa-external-link-
square:before{content:"\f14c"}.fa-share-square:before{content:"\f14d"}.fa-
compass:before{content:"\f14e"}.fa-toggle-down:before,.fa-caret-square-o-
down:before{content:"\f150"}.fa-toggle-up:before,.fa-caret-square-o-
up:before{content:"\f151"}.fa-toggle-right:before,.fa-caret-square-o-
right:before{content:"\f152"}.fa-euro:before,.fa-
eur:before{content:"\f153"}.fa-gbp:before{content:"\f154"}.fa-
dollar:before,.fa-usd:before{content:"\f155"}.fa-rupee:before,.fa-
inr:before{content:"\f156"}.fa-cny:before,.fa-rmb:before,.fa-yen:before,.fa-
jpy:before{content:"\f157"}.fa-ruble:before,.fa-rouble:before,.fa-
rub:before{content:"\f158"}.fa-won:before,.fa-krw:before{content:"\f159"}.fa-
bitcoin:before,.fa-btc:before{content:"\f15a"}.fa-
file:before{content:"\f15b"}.fa-file-text:before{content:"\f15c"}.fa-sort-
alpha-asc:before{content:"\f15d"}.fa-sort-alpha-
desc:before{content:"\f15e"}.fa-sort-amount-asc:before{content:"\f160"}.fa-
sort-amount-desc:before{content:"\f161"}.fa-sort-numeric-
asc:before{content:"\f162"}.fa-sort-numeric-desc:before{content:"\f163"}.fa-
thumbs-up:before{content:"\f164"}.fa-thumbs-down:before{content:"\f165"}.fa-
youtube-square:before{content:"\f166"}.fa-youtube:before{content:"\f167"}.fa-
xing:before{content:"\f168"}.fa-xing-square:before{content:"\f169"}.fa-
youtube-play:before{content:"\f16a"}.fa-dropbox:before{content:"\f16b"}.fa-
stack-overflow:before{content:"\f16c"}.fa-
instagram:before{content:"\f16d"}.fa-flickr:before{content:"\f16e"}.fa-
adn:before{content:"\f170"}.fa-bitbucket:before{content:"\f171"}.fa-
bitbucket-square:before{content:"\f172"}.fa-
tumblr:before{content:"\f173"}.fa-tumblr-square:before{content:"\f174"}.fa-
long-arrow-down:before{content:"\f175"}.fa-long-arrow-
up:before{content:"\f176"}.fa-long-arrow-left:before{content:"\f177"}.fa-
long-arrow-right:before{content:"\f178"}.fa-apple:before{content:"\f179"}.fa-
windows:before{content:"\f17a"}.fa-android:before{content:"\f17b"}.fa-
linux:before{content:"\f17c"}.fa-dribbble:before{content:"\f17d"}.fa-
skype:before{content:"\f17e"}.fa-foursquare:before{content:"\f180"}.fa-
trello:before{content:"\f181"}.fa-female:before{content:"\f182"}.fa-
male:before{content:"\f183"}.fa-gittip:before,.fa-
gratipay:before{content:"\f184"}.fa-sun-o:before{content:"\f185"}.fa-moon-
o:before{content:"\f186"}.fa-archive:before{content:"\f187"}.fa-
bug:before{content:"\f188"}.fa-vk:before{content:"\f189"}.fa-
weibo:before{content:"\f18a"}.fa-renren:before{content:"\f18b"}.fa-
pagelines:before{content:"\f18c"}.fa-stack-
exchange:before{content:"\f18d"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-
right:before{content:"\f18e"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-
left:before{content:"\f190"}.fa-toggle-left:before,.fa-caret-square-o-
left:before{content:"\f191"}.fa-dot-circle-o:before{content:"\f192"}.fa-
wheelchair:before{content:"\f193"}.fa-vimeo-
square:before{content:"\f194"}.fa-turkish-lira:before,.fa-
try:before{content:"\f195"}.fa-plus-square-o:before{content:"\f196"}.fa-
space-shuttle:before{content:"\f197"}.fa-slack:before{content:"\f198"}.fa-
envelope-square:before{content:"\f199"}.fa-
wordpress:before{content:"\f19a"}.fa-openid:before{content:"\f19b"}.fa-
institution:before,.fa-bank:before,.fa-university:before{content:"\f19c"}.fa-
mortar-board:before,.fa-graduation-cap:before{content:"\f19d"}.fa-
yahoo:before{content:"\f19e"}.fa-google:before{content:"\f1a0"}.fa-
```

```
reddit:before{content:"\f1a1"}.fa-reddit-square:before{content:"\f1a2"}.fa-
stumbleupon-circle:before{content:"\f1a3"}.fa-
stumbleupon:before{content:"\f1a4"}.fa-delicious:before{content:"\f1a5"}.fa-
digg:before{content:"\f1a6"}.fa-pied-piper-pp:before{content:"\f1a7"}.fa-
pied-piper-alt:before{content:"\f1a8"}.fa-drupal:before{content:"\f1a9"}.fa-
joomla:before{content:"\f1aa"}.fa-language:before{content:"\f1ab"}.fa-
fax:before{content:"\f1ac"}.fa-building:before{content:"\f1ad"}.fa-
child:before{content:"\f1ae"}.fa-paw:before{content:"\f1b0"}.fa-
spoon:before{content:"\f1b1"}.fa-cube:before{content:"\f1b2"}.fa-
cubes:before{content:"\f1b3"}.fa-behance:before{content:"\f1b4"}.fa-behance-
square:before{content:"\f1b5"}.fa-steam:before{content:"\f1b6"}.fa-steam-
square:before{content:"\f1b7"}.fa-recycle:before{content:"\f1b8"}.fa-
automobile:before,.fa-car:before{content:"\f1b9"}.fa-cab:before,.fa-
taxi:before{content:"\f1ba"}.fa-tree:before{content:"\f1bb"}.fa-
spotify:before{content:"\f1bc"}.fa-deviantart:before{content:"\f1bd"}.fa-
soundcloud:before{content:"\f1be"}.fa-database:before{content:"\f1c0"}.fa-
file-pdf-o:before{content:"\f1c1"}.fa-file-word-o:before{content:"\f1c2"}.fa-
file-excel-o:before{content:"\f1c3"}.fa-file-powerpoint-
o:before{content:"\f1c4"}.fa-file-photo-o:before,.fa-file-picture-
o:before,.fa-file-image-o:before{content:"\f1c5"}.fa-file-zip-o:before,.fa-
file-archive-o:before{content:"\f1c6"}.fa-file-sound-o:before,.fa-file-audio-
o:before{content:"\f1c7"}.fa-file-movie-o:before,.fa-file-video-
o:before{content:"\f1c8"}.fa-file-code-o:before{content:"\f1c9"}.fa-
vine:before{content:"\f1ca"}.fa-codepen:before{content:"\f1cb"}.fa-
jsfiddle:before{content:"\f1cc"}.fa-life-bouy:before,.fa-life-
buoy:before,.fa-life-saver:before,.fa-support:before,.fa-life-
ring:before{content:"\f1cd"}.fa-circle-o-notch:before{content:"\f1ce"}.fa-
ra:before,.fa-resistance:before,.fa-rebel:before{content:"\f1d0"}.fa-
ge:before,.fa-empire:before{content:"\f1d1"}.fa-git-
square:before{content:"\f1d2"}.fa-git:before{content:"\f1d3"}.fa-y-
combinator-square:before,.fa-yc-square:before,.fa-hacker-
news:before{content:"\f1d4"}.fa-tencent-weibo:before{content:"\f1d5"}.fa-
qq:before{content:"\f1d6"}.fa-wechat:before,.fa-
weixin:before{content:"\f1d7"}.fa-send:before,.fa-paper-
plane:before{content:"\f1d8"}.fa-send-o:before,.fa-paper-plane-
o:before{content:"\f1d9"}.fa-history:before{content:"\f1da"}.fa-circle-
thin:before{content:"\f1db"}.fa-header:before{content:"\f1dc"}.fa-
paragraph:before{content:"\f1dd"}.fa-sliders:before{content:"\f1de"}.fa-
share-alt:before{content:"\f1e0"}.fa-share-alt-
square:before{content:"\f1e1"}.fa-bomb:before{content:"\f1e2"}.fa-soccer-
ball-o:before,.fa-futbol-o:before{content:"\f1e3"}.fa-
tty:before{content:"\f1e4"}.fa-binoculars:before{content:"\f1e5"}.fa-
plug:before{content:"\f1e6"}.fa-slideshare:before{content:"\f1e7"}.fa-
twitch:before{content:"\f1e8"}.fa-yelp:before{content:"\f1e9"}.fa-newspaper-
o:before{content:"\f1ea"}.fa-wifi:before{content:"\f1eb"}.fa-
calculator:before{content:"\f1ec"}.fa-paypal:before{content:"\f1ed"}.fa-
google-wallet:before{content:"\f1ee"}.fa-cc-visa:before{content:"\f1f0"}.fa-
cc-mastercard:before{content:"\f1f1"}.fa-cc-
discover:before{content:"\f1f2"}.fa-cc-amex:before{content:"\f1f3"}.fa-cc-
paypal:before{content:"\f1f4"}.fa-cc-stripe:before{content:"\f1f5"}.fa-bell-
slash:before{content:"\f1f6"}.fa-bell-slash-o:before{content:"\f1f7"}.fa-
trash:before{content:"\f1f8"}.fa-copyright:before{content:"\f1f9"}.fa-
at:before{content:"\f1fa"}.fa-eyedropper:before{content:"\f1fb"}.fa-paint-
brush:before{content:"\f1fc"}.fa-birthday-cake:before{content:"\f1fd"}.fa-
area-chart:before{content:"\f1fe"}.fa-pie-chart:before{content:"\f200"}.fa-
line-chart:before{content:"\f201"}.fa-lastfm:before{content:"\f202"}.fa-
lastfm-square:before{content:"\f203"}.fa-toggle-
```

off:before{content:"\f204"}.fa-toggle-on:before{content:"\f205"}.fa-bicycle:before{content:"\f206"}.fa-bus:before{content:"\f207"}.fa-ioxhost:before{content:"\f208"}.fa-angellist:before{content:"\f209"}.fa-cc:before{content:"\f20a"}.fa-shekel:before,.fa-sheqel:before,.fa-ils:before{content:"\f20b"}.fa-meanpath:before{content:"\f20c"}.fa-buysellads:before{content:"\f20d"}.fa-connectdevelop:before{content:"\f20e"}.fa-dashcube:before{content:"\f210"}.fa-forumbee:before{content:"\f211"}.fa-leanpub:before{content:"\f212"}.fa-sellsy:before{content:"\f213"}.fa-shirtsinbulk:before{content:"\f214"}.fa-simplybuilt:before{content:"\f215"}.fa-skyatlas:before{content:"\f216"}.fa-cart-plus:before{content:"\f217"}.fa-cart-arrow-down:before{content:"\f218"}.fa-diamond:before{content:"\f219"}.fa-ship:before{content:"\f21a"}.fa-user-secret:before{content:"\f21b"}.fa-motorcycle:before{content:"\f21c"}.fa-street-view:before{content:"\f21d"}.fa-heartbeat:before{content:"\f21e"}.fa-venus:before{content:"\f221"}.fa-mars:before{content:"\f222"}.fa-mercury:before{content:"\f223"}.fa-intersex:before,.fa-transgender:before{content:"\f224"}.fa-transgender-alt:before{content:"\f225"}.fa-venus-double:before{content:"\f226"}.fa-mars-double:before{content:"\f227"}.fa-venus-mars:before{content:"\f228"}.fa-mars-stroke:before{content:"\f229"}.fa-mars-stroke-v:before{content:"\f22a"}.fa-mars-stroke-h:before{content:"\f22b"}.fa-neuter:before{content:"\f22c"}.fa-genderless:before{content:"\f22d"}.fa-facebook-official:before{content:"\f230"}.fa-pinterest-p:before{content:"\f231"}.fa-whatsapp:before{content:"\f232"}.fa-server:before{content:"\f233"}.fa-user-plus:before{content:"\f234"}.fa-user-times:before{content:"\f235"}.fa-hotel:before,.fa-bed:before{content:"\f236"}.fa-viacoin:before{content:"\f237"}.fa-train:before{content:"\f238"}.fa-subway:before{content:"\f239"}.fa-medium:before{content:"\f23a"}.fa-yc:before,.fa-y-combinator:before{content:"\f23b"}.fa-optin-monster:before{content:"\f23c"}.fa-opencart:before{content:"\f23d"}.fa-expeditedssl:before{content:"\f23e"}.fa-battery-4:before,.fa-battery:before,.fa-battery-full:before{content:"\f240"}.fa-battery-3:before,.fa-battery-three-quarters:before{content:"\f241"}.fa-battery-2:before,.fa-battery-half:before{content:"\f242"}.fa-battery-1:before,.fa-battery-quarter:before{content:"\f243"}.fa-battery-0:before,.fa-battery-empty:before{content:"\f244"}.fa-mouse-pointer:before{content:"\f245"}.fa-i-cursor:before{content:"\f246"}.fa-object-group:before{content:"\f247"}.fa-object-ungroup:before{content:"\f248"}.fa-sticky-note:before{content:"\f249"}.fa-sticky-note-o:before{content:"\f24a"}.fa-cc-jcb:before{content:"\f24b"}.fa-cc-diners-club:before{content:"\f24c"}.fa-clone:before{content:"\f24d"}.fa-balance-scale:before{content:"\f24e"}.fa-hourglass-o:before{content:"\f250"}.fa-hourglass-1:before,.fa-hourglass-start:before{content:"\f251"}.fa-hourglass-2:before,.fa-hourglass-half:before{content:"\f252"}.fa-hourglass-3:before,.fa-hourglass-end:before{content:"\f253"}.fa-hourglass:before{content:"\f254"}.fa-hand-grab-o:before,.fa-hand-rock-o:before{content:"\f255"}.fa-hand-stop-o:before,.fa-hand-paper-o:before{content:"\f256"}.fa-hand-scissors-o:before{content:"\f257"}.fa-hand-lizard-o:before{content:"\f258"}.fa-hand-spock-o:before{content:"\f259"}.fa-hand-pointer-o:before{content:"\f25a"}.fa-hand-peace-o:before{content:"\f25b"}.fa-trademark:before{content:"\f25c"}.fa-registered:before{content:"\f25d"}.fa-creative-commons:before{content:"\f25e"}.fa-gg:before{content:"\f260"}.fa-gg-circle:before{content:"\f261"}.fa-tripadvisor:before{content:"\f262"}.fa-odnoklassniki:before{content:"\f263"}.fa-odnoklassniki-square:before{content:"\f264"}.fa-get-pocket:before{content:"\f265"}.fa-wikipedia-w:before{content:"\f266"}.fa-safari:before{content:"\f267"}.fa-

```
chrome:before{content:"\f268"}.fa-firefox:before{content:"\f269"}.fa-
opera:before{content:"\f26a"}.fa-internet-
explorer:before{content:"\f26b"}.fa-tv:before,.fa-
television:before{content:"\f26c"}.fa-contao:before{content:"\f26d"}.fa-
500px:before{content:"\f26e"}.fa-amazon:before{content:"\f270"}.fa-calendar-
plus-o:before{content:"\f271"}.fa-calendar-minus-
o:before{content:"\f272"}.fa-calendar-times-o:before{content:"\f273"}.fa-
calendar-check-o:before{content:"\f274"}.fa-
industry:before{content:"\f275"}.fa-map-pin:before{content:"\f276"}.fa-map-
signs:before{content:"\f277"}.fa-map-o:before{content:"\f278"}.fa-
map:before{content:"\f279"}.fa-commenting:before{content:"\f27a"}.fa-
commenting-o:before{content:"\f27b"}.fa-houzz:before{content:"\f27c"}.fa-
vimeo:before{content:"\f27d"}.fa-black-tie:before{content:"\f27e"}.fa-
fonticons:before{content:"\f280"}.fa-reddit-alien:before{content:"\f281"}.fa-
edge:before{content:"\f282"}.fa-credit-card-alt:before{content:"\f283"}.fa-
codiepie:before{content:"\f284"}.fa-modx:before{content:"\f285"}.fa-fort-
awesome:before{content:"\f286"}.fa-usb:before{content:"\f287"}.fa-product-
hunt:before{content:"\f288"}.fa-mixcloud:before{content:"\f289"}.fa-
scribd:before{content:"\f28a"}.fa-pause-circle:before{content:"\f28b"}.fa-
pause-circle-o:before{content:"\f28c"}.fa-stop-
circle:before{content:"\f28d"}.fa-stop-circle-o:before{content:"\f28e"}.fa-
shopping-bag:before{content:"\f290"}.fa-shopping-
basket:before{content:"\f291"}.fa-hashtag:before{content:"\f292"}.fa-
bluetooth:before{content:"\f293"}.fa-bluetooth-b:before{content:"\f294"}.fa-
percent:before{content:"\f295"}.fa-gitlab:before{content:"\f296"}.fa-
wpbeginner:before{content:"\f297"}.fa-wpforms:before{content:"\f298"}.fa-
envira:before{content:"\f299"}.fa-universal-
access:before{content:"\f29a"}.fa-wheelchair-alt:before{content:"\f29b"}.fa-
question-circle-o:before{content:"\f29c"}.fa-
blind:before{content:"\f29d"}.fa-audio-
description:before{content:"\f29e"}.fa-volume-control-
phone:before{content:"\f2a0"}.fa-braille:before{content:"\f2a1"}.fa-
assistive-listening-systems:before{content:"\f2a2"}.fa-asl-
interpreting:before,.fa-american-sign-language-
interpreting:before{content:"\f2a3"}.fa-deafness:before,.fa-hard-of-
hearing:before,.fa-deaf:before{content:"\f2a4"}.fa-
glide:before{content:"\f2a5"}.fa-glide-g:before{content:"\f2a6"}.fa-
signing:before,.fa-sign-language:before{content:"\f2a7"}.fa-low-
vision:before{content:"\f2a8"}.fa-viadeo:before{content:"\f2a9"}.fa-viadeo-
square:before{content:"\f2aa"}.fa-snapchat:before{content:"\f2ab"}.fa-
snapchat-ghost:before{content:"\f2ac"}.fa-snapchat-
square:before{content:"\f2ad"}.fa-pied-piper:before{content:"\f2ae"}.fa-
first-order:before{content:"\f2b0"}.fa-yoast:before{content:"\f2b1"}.fa-
themeisle:before{content:"\f2b2"}.fa-google-plus-circle:before,.fa-google-
plus-official:before{content:"\f2b3"}.fa-fa:before,.fa-font-
awesome:before{content:"\f2b4"}.fa-handshake-o:before{content:"\f2b5"}.fa-
envelope-open:before{content:"\f2b6"}.fa-envelope-open-
o:before{content:"\f2b7"}.fa-linode:before{content:"\f2b8"}.fa-address-
book:before{content:"\f2b9"}.fa-address-book-o:before{content:"\f2ba"}.fa-
vcard:before,.fa-address-card:before{content:"\f2bb"}.fa-vcard-o:before,.fa-
address-card-o:before{content:"\f2bc"}.fa-user-
circle:before{content:"\f2bd"}.fa-user-circle-o:before{content:"\f2be"}.fa-
user-o:before{content:"\f2c0"}.fa-id-badge:before{content:"\f2c1"}.fa-
drivers-license:before,.fa-id-card:before{content:"\f2c2"}.fa-drivers-
license-o:before,.fa-id-card-o:before{content:"\f2c3"}.fa-
quora:before{content:"\f2c4"}.fa-free-code-camp:before{content:"\f2c5"}.fa-
telegram:before{content:"\f2c6"}.fa-thermometer-4:before,.fa-
```

```
thermometer:before, .fa-thermometer-full:before{content:"\f2c7"}.fa-thermometer-3:before, .fa-thermometer-three-quarters:before{content:"\f2c8"}.fa-thermometer-2:before, .fa-thermometer-half:before{content:"\f2c9"}.fa-thermometer-1:before, .fa-thermometer-quarter:before{content:"\f2ca"}.fa-thermometer-0:before, .fa-thermometer-empty:before{content:"\f2cb"}.fa-shower:before{content:"\f2cc"}.fa-bathtub:before, .fa-s15:before, .fa-bath:before{content:"\f2cd"}.fa-podcast:before{content:"\f2ce"}.fa-window-maximize:before{content:"\f2d0"}.fa-window-minimize:before{content:"\f2d1"}.fa-window-restore:before{content:"\f2d2"}.fa-times-rectangle:before, .fa-window-close:before{content:"\f2d3"}.fa-times-rectangle-o:before, .fa-window-close-o:before{content:"\f2d4"}.fa-bandcamp:before{content:"\f2d5"}.fa-grav:before{content:"\f2d6"}.fa-etsy:before{content:"\f2d7"}.fa-imdb:before{content:"\f2d8"}.fa-ravelry:before{content:"\f2d9"}.fa-eercast:before{content:"\f2da"}.fa-microchip:before{content:"\f2db"}.fa-snowflake-o:before{content:"\f2dc"}.fa-superpowers:before{content:"\f2dd"}.fa-wpexplorer:before{content:"\f2de"}.fa-meetup:before{content:"\f2e0"}.sr-only{position:absolute;width:1px;height:1px;padding:0;margin:-1px;overflow:hidden;clip:rect(0, 0, 0, 0);border:0}.sr-only-focusable:active, .sr-only-focusable:focus{position:static;width:auto;height:auto;margin:0;overflow:visible;clip:auto}
```

Service.css

```
@charset "UTF-8";

/*!
 * Bootstrap v5.1.3 (https://getbootstrap.com/)
 * Copyright 2011-2021 The Bootstrap Authors
 * Copyright 2011-2021 Twitter, Inc.
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/main/LICENSE)
 */

:root {
  --bs-blue: #0d6efd;
  --bs-indigo: #6610f2;
  --bs-purple: #6f42c1;
  --bs-pink: #d63384;
  --bs-red: #dc3545;
  --bs-orange: #fd7e14;
  --bs-yellow: #ffc107;
  --bs-green: #198754;
  --bs-teal: #20c997;
  --bs-cyan: #0dcaf0;
  --bs-white: #fff;
  --bs-gray: #6c757d;
  --bs-gray-dark: #343a40;
  --bs-gray-100: #f8f9fa;
  --bs-gray-200: #e9ecef;
  --bs-gray-300: #dee2e6;
  --bs-gray-400: #ced4da;
  --bs-gray-500: #adb5bd;
  --bs-gray-600: #6c757d;
  --bs-gray-700: #495057;
  --bs-gray-800: #343a40;
  --bs-gray-900: #212529;
  --bs-primary: #0d6efd;
  --bs-secondary: #6c757d;
  --bs-success: #198754;
  --bs-info: #0dcaf0;
  --bs-warning: #ffc107;
  --bs-danger: #dc3545;
  --bs-light: #f8f9fa;
  --bs-dark: #212529;
  --bs-primary-rgb: 13, 110, 253;
  --bs-secondary-rgb: 108, 117, 125;
  --bs-success-rgb: 25, 135, 84;
  --bs-info-rgb: 13, 202, 240;
  --bs-warning-rgb: 255, 193, 7;
  --bs-danger-rgb: 220, 53, 69;
  --bs-light-rgb: 248, 249, 250;
  --bs-dark-rgb: 33, 37, 41;
  --bs-white-rgb: 255, 255, 255;
  --bs-black-rgb: 0, 0, 0;
  --bs-body-color-rgb: 33, 37, 41;
  --bs-body-bg-rgb: 255, 255, 255;
  --bs-font-sans-serif: system-ui, -apple-system, "Segoe UI", Roboto,
  "Helvetica Neue", Arial, "Noto Sans", "Liberation Sans", sans-serif, "Apple
```

```

Color Emoji", "Segoe UI Emoji", "Segoe UI Symbol", "Noto Color Emoji";
  --bs-font-monospace: SFMono-Regular, Menlo, Monaco, Consolas, "Liberation
Mono", "Courier New", monospace;
  --bs-gradient: linear-gradient(180deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, 0.15),
rgba(255, 255, 255, 0));
  --bs-body-font-family: var(--bs-font-sans-serif);
  --bs-body-font-size: 1rem;
  --bs-body-font-weight: 400;
  --bs-body-line-height: 1.5;
  --bs-body-color: #212529;
  --bs-body-bg: #fff
}

*,
::after,
::before {
  box-sizing: border-box
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:no-preference) {
  :root {
    scroll-behavior: smooth
  }
}

body {
  margin: 0;
  font-family: var(--bs-body-font-family);
  font-size: var(--bs-body-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--bs-body-font-weight);
  line-height: var(--bs-body-line-height);
  color: var(--bs-body-color);
  text-align: var(--bs-body-text-align);
  background-color: var(--bs-body-bg);
  -webkit-text-size-adjust: 100%;
  -webkit-tap-highlight-color: transparent
}

hr {
  margin: 1rem 0;
  color: inherit;
  background-color: currentColor;
  border: 0;
  opacity: .25
}

hr:not([size]) {
  height: 1px
}

.h1,
.h2,
.h3,
.h4,
.h5,
.h6,
h1,

```

```

h2,
h3,
h4,
h5,
h6 {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: .5rem;
  font-weight: 500;
  line-height: 1.2
}

.h1,
h1 {
  font-size: calc(1.375rem + 1.5vw)
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .h1,
  h1 {
    font-size: 2.5rem
  }
}

.h2,
h2 {
  font-size: calc(1.325rem + .9vw)
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .h2,
  h2 {
    font-size: 2rem
  }
}

.h3,
h3 {
  font-size: calc(1.3rem + .6vw)
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .h3,
  h3 {
    font-size: 1.75rem
  }
}

.h4,
h4 {
  font-size: calc(1.275rem + .3vw)
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .h4,
  h4 {
    font-size: 1.5rem
  }
}

```

```

}

.h5,
h5 {
  font-size: 1.25rem
}

.h6,
h6 {
  font-size: 1rem
}

p {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 1rem
}

abbr[data-bs-original-title],
abbr[title] {
  -webkit-text-decoration: underline dotted;
  text-decoration: underline dotted;
  cursor: help;
  -webkit-text-decoration-skip-ink: none;
  text-decoration-skip-ink: none
}

address {
  margin-bottom: 1rem;
  font-style: normal;
  line-height: inherit
}

ol,
ul {
  padding-left: 2rem
}

dl,
ol,
ul {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 1rem
}

ol ol,
ol ul,
ul ol,
ul ul {
  margin-bottom: 0
}

dt {
  font-weight: 700
}

dd {
  margin-bottom: .5rem;

```

```
margin-left: 0
}

blockquote {
margin: 0 0 1rem
}

b,
strong {
font-weight: bolder
}

.small,
small {
font-size: .875em
}

.mark,
mark {
padding: .2em;
background-color: #fcf8e3
}

sub,
sup {
position: relative;
font-size: .75em;
line-height: 0;
vertical-align: baseline
}

sub {
bottom: -.25em
}

sup {
top: -.5em
}

a {
color: #0d6efd;
text-decoration: underline
}

a:hover {
color: #0a58ca
}

a:not([href]):not([class]),
a:not([href]):not([class]):hover {
color: inherit;
text-decoration: none
}

code,
kbd,
pre,
```

```

samp {
  font-family: var(--bs-font-monospace);
  font-size: 1em;
  direction: ltr;
  unicode-bidi: bidi-override
}

pre {
  display: block;
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 1rem;
  overflow: auto;
  font-size: .875em
}

pre code {
  font-size: inherit;
  color: inherit;
  word-break: normal
}

code {
  font-size: .875em;
  color: #d63384;
  word-wrap: break-word
}

a>code {
  color: inherit
}

kbd {
  padding: .2rem .4rem;
  font-size: .875em;
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #212529;
  border-radius: .2rem
}

kbd kbd {
  padding: 0;
  font-size: 1em;
  font-weight: 700
}

figure {
  margin: 0 0 1rem
}

img,
svg {
  vertical-align: middle
}

table {
  caption-side: bottom;
  border-collapse: collapse
}

```

```

}

caption {
  padding-top: .5rem;
  padding-bottom: .5rem;
  color: #6c757d;
  text-align: left
}

th {
  text-align: inherit;
  text-align: -webkit-match-parent
}

tbody,
td,
tfoot,
th,
thead,
tr {
  border-color: inherit;
  border-style: solid;
  border-width: 0
}

label {
  display: inline-block
}

button {
  border-radius: 0
}

button:focus:not(:focus-visible) {
  outline: 0
}

button,
input,
optgroup,
select,
textarea {
  margin: 0;
  font-family: inherit;
  font-size: inherit;
  line-height: inherit
}

button,
select {
  text-transform: none
}

[role=button] {
  cursor: pointer
}

```

```

select {
  word-wrap: normal
}

select:disabled {
  opacity: 1
}

[list]::-webkit-calendar-picker-indicator {
  display: none
}

[type=button],
[type=reset],
[type=submit],
button {
  -webkit-appearance: button
}

[type=button]:not(:disabled),
[type=reset]:not(:disabled),
[type=submit]:not(:disabled),
button:not(:disabled) {
  cursor: pointer
}

::-moz-focus-inner {
  padding: 0;
  border-style: none
}

textarea {
  resize: vertical
}

fieldset {
  min-width: 0;
  padding: 0;
  margin: 0;
  border: 0
}

legend {
  float: left;
  width: 100%;
  padding: 0;
  margin-bottom: .5rem;
  font-size: calc(1.275rem + .3vw);
  line-height: inherit
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  legend {
    font-size: 1.5rem
  }
}

```

```

legend+* {
  clear: left
}

::-webkit-datetime-edit-day-field,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-fields-wrapper,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-hour-field,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-minute,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-month-field,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-text,
::-webkit-datetime-edit-year-field {
  padding: 0
}

::-webkit-inner-spin-button {
  height: auto
}

[type=search] {
  outline-offset: -2px;
  -webkit-appearance: textfield
}

::-webkit-search-decoration {
  -webkit-appearance: none
}

::-webkit-color-swatch-wrapper {
  padding: 0
}

::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  font: inherit
}

::file-selector-button {
  font: inherit
}

::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  font: inherit;
  -webkit-appearance: button
}

output {
  display: inline-block
}

iframe {
  border: 0
}

summary {
  display: list-item;
  cursor: pointer
}

```

```

progress {
  vertical-align: baseline
}

[hidden] {
  display: none!important
}

.lead {
  font-size: 1.25rem;
  font-weight: 300
}

.display-1 {
  font-size: calc(1.625rem + 4.5vw);
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .display-1 {
    font-size: 5rem
  }
}

.display-2 {
  font-size: calc(1.575rem + 3.9vw);
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .display-2 {
    font-size: 4.5rem
  }
}

.display-3 {
  font-size: calc(1.525rem + 3.3vw);
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .display-3 {
    font-size: 4rem
  }
}

.display-4 {
  font-size: calc(1.475rem + 2.7vw);
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .display-4 {

```

```

        font-size: 3.5rem
    }
}

.display-5 {
    font-size: calc(1.425rem + 2.1vw);
    font-weight: 300;
    line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .display-5 {
        font-size: 3rem
    }
}

.display-6 {
    font-size: calc(1.375rem + 1.5vw);
    font-weight: 300;
    line-height: 1.2
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .display-6 {
        font-size: 2.5rem
    }
}

.list-unstyled {
    padding-left: 0;
    list-style: none
}

.list-inline {
    padding-left: 0;
    list-style: none
}

.list-inline-item {
    display: inline-block
}

.list-inline-item:not(:last-child) {
    margin-right: .5rem
}

.initialism {
    font-size: .875em;
    text-transform: uppercase
}

.blockquote {
    margin-bottom: 1rem;
    font-size: 1.25rem
}

.blockquote>:last-child {

```

```

margin-bottom: 0
}

.blockquote-footer {
margin-top: -1rem;
margin-bottom: 1rem;
font-size: .875em;
color: #6c757d
}

.blockquote-footer::before {
content: "—"
}

.img-fluid {
max-width: 100%;
height: auto
}

.img-thumbnail {
padding: .25rem;
background-color: #fff;
border: 1px solid #dee2e6;
border-radius: .25rem;
max-width: 100%;
height: auto
}

.figure {
display: inline-block
}

.figure-img {
margin-bottom: .5rem;
line-height: 1
}

.figure-caption {
font-size: .875em;
color: #6c757d
}

.container,
.container-fluid,
.container-lg,
.container-md,
.container-sm,
.container-xl,
.container-xxl {
width: 100%;
padding-right: var(--bs-gutter-x, .75rem);
padding-left: var(--bs-gutter-x, .75rem);
margin-right: auto;
margin-left: auto
}

@media (min-width:576px) {

```

```

    .container,
    .container-sm {
        max-width: 540px
    }
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
    .container,
    .container-md,
    .container-sm {
        max-width: 720px
    }
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
    .container,
    .container-lg,
    .container-md,
    .container-sm {
        max-width: 960px
    }
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .container,
    .container-lg,
    .container-md,
    .container-sm,
    .container-xl {
        max-width: 1140px
    }
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
    .container,
    .container-lg,
    .container-md,
    .container-sm,
    .container-xl,
    .container-xxl {
        max-width: 1320px
    }
}

.row {
    --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem;
    --bs-gutter-y: 0;
    display: flex;
    flex-wrap: wrap;
    margin-top: calc(-1 * var(--bs-gutter-y));
    margin-right: calc(-.5 * var(--bs-gutter-x));
    margin-left: calc(-.5 * var(--bs-gutter-x))
}

.row>* {
    flex-shrink: 0;
    width: 100%;

```

```

max-width: 100%;
padding-right: calc(var(--bs-gutter-x) * .5);
padding-left: calc(var(--bs-gutter-x) * .5);
margin-top: var(--bs-gutter-y)
}

.col {
  flex: 1 0 0%
}

.row-cols-auto>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}

.row-cols-1>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}

.row-cols-2>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}

.row-cols-3>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.3333333333%
}

.row-cols-4>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}

.row-cols-5>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 20%
}

.row-cols-6>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 16.6666666667%
}

.col-auto {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}

.col-1 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 8.333333333%
}

.col-2 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;

```

```
width: 16.66666667%
}

.col-3 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}

.col-4 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.33333333%
}

.col-5 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 41.66666667%
}

.col-6 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}

.col-7 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 58.33333333%
}

.col-8 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 66.66666667%
}

.col-9 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 75%
}

.col-10 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 83.33333333%
}

.col-11 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 91.66666667%
}

.col-12 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}

.offset-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%
}
```

```
.offset-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%
}

.offset-3 {
  margin-left: 25%
}

.offset-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%
}

.offset-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%
}

.offset-6 {
  margin-left: 50%
}

.offset-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%
}

.offset-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%
}

.offset-9 {
  margin-left: 75%
}

.offset-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%
}

.offset-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%
}

.g-0,
.gx-0 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0
}

.g-0,
.gy-0 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0
}

.g-1,
.gx-1 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
}

.g-1,
.gy-1 {
```

```

    --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
  }

.g-2,
.gx-2 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
}

.g-2,
.gy-2 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
}

.g-3,
.gx-3 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
}

.g-3,
.gy-3 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
}

.g-4,
.gx-4 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
}

.g-4,
.gy-4 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
}

.g-5,
.gx-5 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
}

.g-5,
.gy-5 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .col-sm {
    flex: 1 0 0%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-auto>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: auto
  }
  .row-cols-sm-1>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 100%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-2>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;

```

```

    width: 50%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-3>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 33.3333333333%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-4>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-5>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 20%
  }
  .row-cols-sm-6>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.6666666667%
  }
  .col-sm-auto {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: auto
  }
  .col-sm-1 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 8.333333333%
  }
  .col-sm-2 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.666666667%
  }
  .col-sm-3 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .col-sm-4 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 33.333333333%
  }
  .col-sm-5 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 41.666666667%
  }
  .col-sm-6 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 50%
  }
  .col-sm-7 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 58.333333333%
  }
  .col-sm-8 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 66.666666667%
  }
  .col-sm-9 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 75%
  }

```

```

}
.col-sm-10 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 83.33333333%
}
.col-sm-11 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 91.66666667%
}
.col-sm-12 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.offset-sm-0 {
  margin-left: 0
}
.offset-sm-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%
}
.offset-sm-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%
}
.offset-sm-3 {
  margin-left: 25%
}
.offset-sm-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%
}
.offset-sm-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%
}
.offset-sm-6 {
  margin-left: 50%
}
.offset-sm-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%
}
.offset-sm-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%
}
.offset-sm-9 {
  margin-left: 75%
}
.offset-sm-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%
}
.offset-sm-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%
}
}
.g-sm-0,
.gx-sm-0 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0
}
.g-sm-0,
.gy-sm-0 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0
}
}

```

```

.g-sm-1,
.gx-sm-1 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
}
.g-sm-1,
.gy-sm-1 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
}
.g-sm-2,
.gx-sm-2 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
}
.g-sm-2,
.gy-sm-2 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
}
.g-sm-3,
.gx-sm-3 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
}
.g-sm-3,
.gy-sm-3 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
}
.g-sm-4,
.gx-sm-4 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
}
.g-sm-4,
.gy-sm-4 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
}
.g-sm-5,
.gx-sm-5 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
}
.g-sm-5,
.gy-sm-5 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
}
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
.col-md {
  flex: 1 0 0%
}
.row-cols-md-auto>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}
.row-cols-md-1>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.row-cols-md-2>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}

```

```

}
.row-cols-md-3>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.3333333333%
}
.row-cols-md-4>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}
.row-cols-md-5>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 20%
}
.row-cols-md-6>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 16.6666666667%
}
.col-md-auto {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}
.col-md-1 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 8.333333333%
}
.col-md-2 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 16.666666667%
}
.col-md-3 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}
.col-md-4 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.333333333%
}
.col-md-5 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 41.666666667%
}
.col-md-6 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}
.col-md-7 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 58.333333333%
}
.col-md-8 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 66.666666667%
}
.col-md-9 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 75%
}
}

```

```

.col-md-10 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 83.33333333%
}
.col-md-11 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 91.66666667%
}
.col-md-12 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.offset-md-0 {
  margin-left: 0
}
.offset-md-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%
}
.offset-md-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%
}
.offset-md-3 {
  margin-left: 25%
}
.offset-md-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%
}
.offset-md-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%
}
.offset-md-6 {
  margin-left: 50%
}
.offset-md-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%
}
.offset-md-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%
}
.offset-md-9 {
  margin-left: 75%
}
.offset-md-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%
}
.offset-md-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%
}
.g-md-0,
.gx-md-0 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0
}
.g-md-0,
.gy-md-0 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0
}
.g-md-1,

```

```

.gx-md-1 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
}
.g-md-1,
.gy-md-1 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
}
.g-md-2,
.gx-md-2 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
}
.g-md-2,
.gy-md-2 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
}
.g-md-3,
.gx-md-3 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
}
.g-md-3,
.gy-md-3 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
}
.g-md-4,
.gx-md-4 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
}
.g-md-4,
.gy-md-4 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
}
.g-md-5,
.gx-md-5 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
}
.g-md-5,
.gy-md-5 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
}
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
.col-lg {
  flex: 1 0 0%
}
.row-cols-lg-auto>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}
.row-cols-lg-1>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.row-cols-lg-2>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}
}

```

```

.row-cols-lg-3>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.3333333333%
}
.row-cols-lg-4>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}
.row-cols-lg-5>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 20%
}
.row-cols-lg-6>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 16.6666666667%
}
.col-lg-auto {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}
.col-lg-1 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 8.333333333%
}
.col-lg-2 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 16.666666667%
}
.col-lg-3 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 25%
}
.col-lg-4 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 33.333333333%
}
.col-lg-5 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 41.666666667%
}
.col-lg-6 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}
.col-lg-7 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 58.333333333%
}
.col-lg-8 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 66.666666667%
}
.col-lg-9 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 75%
}
.col-lg-10 {

```

```

    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 83.33333333%
  }
  .col-lg-11 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 91.66666667%
  }
  .col-lg-12 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 100%
  }
  .offset-lg-0 {
    margin-left: 0
  }
  .offset-lg-1 {
    margin-left: 8.33333333%
  }
  .offset-lg-2 {
    margin-left: 16.66666667%
  }
  .offset-lg-3 {
    margin-left: 25%
  }
  .offset-lg-4 {
    margin-left: 33.33333333%
  }
  .offset-lg-5 {
    margin-left: 41.66666667%
  }
  .offset-lg-6 {
    margin-left: 50%
  }
  .offset-lg-7 {
    margin-left: 58.33333333%
  }
  .offset-lg-8 {
    margin-left: 66.66666667%
  }
  .offset-lg-9 {
    margin-left: 75%
  }
  .offset-lg-10 {
    margin-left: 83.33333333%
  }
  .offset-lg-11 {
    margin-left: 91.66666667%
  }
  .g-lg-0,
  .gx-lg-0 {
    --bs-gutter-x: 0
  }
  .g-lg-0,
  .gy-lg-0 {
    --bs-gutter-y: 0
  }
  .g-lg-1,
  .gx-lg-1 {

```

```

        --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
    }
    .g-lg-1,
    .gy-lg-1 {
        --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
    }
    .g-lg-2,
    .gx-lg-2 {
        --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
    }
    .g-lg-2,
    .gy-lg-2 {
        --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
    }
    .g-lg-3,
    .gx-lg-3 {
        --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
    }
    .g-lg-3,
    .gy-lg-3 {
        --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
    }
    .g-lg-4,
    .gx-lg-4 {
        --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
    }
    .g-lg-4,
    .gy-lg-4 {
        --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
    }
    .g-lg-5,
    .gx-lg-5 {
        --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
    }
    .g-lg-5,
    .gy-lg-5 {
        --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
    }
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .col-xl {
        flex: 1 0 0%
    }
    .row-cols-xl-auto>* {
        flex: 0 0 auto;
        width: auto
    }
    .row-cols-xl-1>* {
        flex: 0 0 auto;
        width: 100%
    }
    .row-cols-xl-2>* {
        flex: 0 0 auto;
        width: 50%
    }
    .row-cols-xl-3>* {

```

```
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 33.3333333333%
  }
  .row-cols-xl-4>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .row-cols-xl-5>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 20%
  }
  .row-cols-xl-6>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.6666666667%
  }
  .col-xl-auto {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: auto
  }
  .col-xl-1 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 8.33333333%
  }
  .col-xl-2 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.66666667%
  }
  .col-xl-3 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .col-xl-4 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 33.33333333%
  }
  .col-xl-5 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 41.66666667%
  }
  .col-xl-6 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 50%
  }
  .col-xl-7 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 58.33333333%
  }
  .col-xl-8 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 66.66666667%
  }
  .col-xl-9 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 75%
  }
  .col-xl-10 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
```

```

    width: 83.33333333%
  }
  .col-xl-11 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 91.66666667%
  }
  .col-xl-12 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 100%
  }
  .offset-xl-0 {
    margin-left: 0
  }
  .offset-xl-1 {
    margin-left: 8.33333333%
  }
  .offset-xl-2 {
    margin-left: 16.66666667%
  }
  .offset-xl-3 {
    margin-left: 25%
  }
  .offset-xl-4 {
    margin-left: 33.33333333%
  }
  .offset-xl-5 {
    margin-left: 41.66666667%
  }
  .offset-xl-6 {
    margin-left: 50%
  }
  .offset-xl-7 {
    margin-left: 58.33333333%
  }
  .offset-xl-8 {
    margin-left: 66.66666667%
  }
  .offset-xl-9 {
    margin-left: 75%
  }
  .offset-xl-10 {
    margin-left: 83.33333333%
  }
  .offset-xl-11 {
    margin-left: 91.66666667%
  }
  .g-xl-0,
  .gx-xl-0 {
    --bs-gutter-x: 0
  }
  .g-xl-0,
  .gy-xl-0 {
    --bs-gutter-y: 0
  }
  .g-xl-1,
  .gx-xl-1 {
    --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
  }

```

```

}
.g-xl-1,
.gy-xl-1 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
}
.g-xl-2,
.gx-xl-2 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
}
.g-xl-2,
.gy-xl-2 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
}
.g-xl-3,
.gx-xl-3 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
}
.g-xl-3,
.gy-xl-3 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
}
.g-xl-4,
.gx-xl-4 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
}
.g-xl-4,
.gy-xl-4 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
}
.g-xl-5,
.gx-xl-5 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
}
.g-xl-5,
.gy-xl-5 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
}
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
.col-xxl {
  flex: 1 0 0%
}
.row-cols-xxl-auto>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: auto
}
.row-cols-xxl-1>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.row-cols-xxl-2>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 50%
}
.row-cols-xxl-3>* {
  flex: 0 0 auto;

```

```

    width: 33.3333333333%
  }
  .row-cols-xxl-4>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .row-cols-xxl-5>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 20%
  }
  .row-cols-xxl-6>* {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.6666666667%
  }
  .col-xxl-auto {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: auto
  }
  .col-xxl-1 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 8.333333333%
  }
  .col-xxl-2 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 16.666666667%
  }
  .col-xxl-3 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 25%
  }
  .col-xxl-4 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 33.333333333%
  }
  .col-xxl-5 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 41.666666667%
  }
  .col-xxl-6 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 50%
  }
  .col-xxl-7 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 58.333333333%
  }
  .col-xxl-8 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 66.666666667%
  }
  .col-xxl-9 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 75%
  }
  .col-xxl-10 {
    flex: 0 0 auto;
    width: 83.333333333%
  }

```

```

}
.col-xxl-11 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 91.66666667%
}
.col-xxl-12 {
  flex: 0 0 auto;
  width: 100%
}
.offset-xxl-0 {
  margin-left: 0
}
.offset-xxl-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%
}
.offset-xxl-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%
}
.offset-xxl-3 {
  margin-left: 25%
}
.offset-xxl-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%
}
.offset-xxl-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%
}
.offset-xxl-6 {
  margin-left: 50%
}
.offset-xxl-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%
}
.offset-xxl-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%
}
.offset-xxl-9 {
  margin-left: 75%
}
.offset-xxl-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%
}
.offset-xxl-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%
}
}
.g-xxl-0,
.gx-xxl-0 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0
}
.g-xxl-0,
.gy-xxl-0 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0
}
.g-xxl-1,
.gx-xxl-1 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.25rem
}
}

```

```

.g-xxl-1,
.gy-xxl-1 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.25rem
}
.g-xxl-2,
.gx-xxl-2 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 0.5rem
}
.g-xxl-2,
.gy-xxl-2 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 0.5rem
}
.g-xxl-3,
.gx-xxl-3 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1rem
}
.g-xxl-3,
.gy-xxl-3 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1rem
}
.g-xxl-4,
.gx-xxl-4 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 1.5rem
}
.g-xxl-4,
.gy-xxl-4 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 1.5rem
}
.g-xxl-5,
.gx-xxl-5 {
  --bs-gutter-x: 3rem
}
.g-xxl-5,
.gy-xxl-5 {
  --bs-gutter-y: 3rem
}
}

.table {
  --bs-table-bg: transparent;
  --bs-table-accent-bg: transparent;
  --bs-table-striped-color: #212529;
  --bs-table-striped-bg: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.05);
  --bs-table-active-color: #212529;
  --bs-table-active-bg: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.1);
  --bs-table-hover-color: #212529;
  --bs-table-hover-bg: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.075);
  width: 100%;
  margin-bottom: 1rem;
  color: #212529;
  vertical-align: top;
  border-color: #dee2e6
}

.table>:not(caption)>*>* {
  padding: .5rem .5rem;
  background-color: var(--bs-table-bg);
}

```

```

border-bottom-width: 1px;
box-shadow: inset 0 0 0 9999px var(--bs-table-accent-bg)
}

.table>tbody {
  vertical-align: inherit
}

.table>thead {
  vertical-align: bottom
}

.table>:not(:first-child) {
  border-top: 2px solid currentColor
}

.caption-top {
  caption-side: top
}

.table-sm>:not(caption)>*>* {
  padding: .25rem .25rem
}

.table-bordered>:not(caption)>* {
  border-width: 1px 0
}

.table-bordered>:not(caption)>*>* {
  border-width: 0 1px
}

.table-borderless>:not(caption)>*>* {
  border-bottom-width: 0
}

.table-borderless>:not(:first-child) {
  border-top-width: 0
}

.table-striped>tbody>tr:nth-of-type(odd)>* {
  --bs-table-accent-bg: var(--bs-table-striped-bg);
  color: var(--bs-table-striped-color)
}

.table-active {
  --bs-table-accent-bg: var(--bs-table-active-bg);
  color: var(--bs-table-active-color)
}

.table-hover>tbody>tr: hover>* {
  --bs-table-accent-bg: var(--bs-table-hover-bg);
  color: var(--bs-table-hover-color)
}

.table-primary {
  --bs-table-bg: #cfe2ff;

```

```

--bs-table-striped-bg: #c5d7f2;
--bs-table-striped-color: #000;
--bs-table-active-bg: #bacbe6;
--bs-table-active-color: #000;
--bs-table-hover-bg: #bfd1ec;
--bs-table-hover-color: #000;
color: #000;
border-color: #bacbe6
}

.table-secondary {
--bs-table-bg: #e2e3e5;
--bs-table-striped-bg: #d7d8da;
--bs-table-striped-color: #000;
--bs-table-active-bg: #cbccce;
--bs-table-active-color: #000;
--bs-table-hover-bg: #d1d2d4;
--bs-table-hover-color: #000;
color: #000;
border-color: #cbccce
}

.table-success {
--bs-table-bg: #d1e7dd;
--bs-table-striped-bg: #c7dbd2;
--bs-table-striped-color: #000;
--bs-table-active-bg: #bcd0c7;
--bs-table-active-color: #000;
--bs-table-hover-bg: #c1d6cc;
--bs-table-hover-color: #000;
color: #000;
border-color: #bcd0c7
}

.table-info {
--bs-table-bg: #cfff4fc;
--bs-table-striped-bg: #c5e8ef;
--bs-table-striped-color: #000;
--bs-table-active-bg: #badce3;
--bs-table-active-color: #000;
--bs-table-hover-bg: #bfe2e9;
--bs-table-hover-color: #000;
color: #000;
border-color: #badce3
}

.table-warning {
--bs-table-bg: #fff3cd;
--bs-table-striped-bg: #f2e7c3;
--bs-table-striped-color: #000;
--bs-table-active-bg: #e6dbb9;
--bs-table-active-color: #000;
--bs-table-hover-bg: #ece1be;
--bs-table-hover-color: #000;
color: #000;
border-color: #e6dbb9
}

```

```

.table-danger {
  --bs-table-bg: #f8d7da;
  --bs-table-striped-bg: #eccccf;
  --bs-table-striped-color: #000;
  --bs-table-active-bg: #dfc2c4;
  --bs-table-active-color: #000;
  --bs-table-hover-bg: #e5c7ca;
  --bs-table-hover-color: #000;
  color: #000;
  border-color: #dfc2c4
}

.table-light {
  --bs-table-bg: #f8f9fa;
  --bs-table-striped-bg: #ecedee;
  --bs-table-striped-color: #000;
  --bs-table-active-bg: #dfe0e1;
  --bs-table-active-color: #000;
  --bs-table-hover-bg: #e5e6e7;
  --bs-table-hover-color: #000;
  color: #000;
  border-color: #dfe0e1
}

.table-dark {
  --bs-table-bg: #212529;
  --bs-table-striped-bg: #2c3034;
  --bs-table-striped-color: #fff;
  --bs-table-active-bg: #373b3e;
  --bs-table-active-color: #fff;
  --bs-table-hover-bg: #323539;
  --bs-table-hover-color: #fff;
  color: #fff;
  border-color: #373b3e
}

.table-responsive {
  overflow-x: auto;
  -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
}

@media (max-width:575.98px) {
  .table-responsive-sm {
    overflow-x: auto;
    -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
  }
}

@media (max-width:767.98px) {
  .table-responsive-md {
    overflow-x: auto;
    -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
  }
}

@media (max-width:991.98px) {

```

```

.table-responsive-lg {
  overflow-x: auto;
  -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
}
}

@media (max-width:1199.98px) {
  .table-responsive-xl {
    overflow-x: auto;
    -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
  }
}

@media (max-width:1399.98px) {
  .table-responsive-xxl {
    overflow-x: auto;
    -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch
  }
}

.form-label {
  margin-bottom: .5rem
}

.col-form-label {
  padding-top: calc(.375rem + 1px);
  padding-bottom: calc(.375rem + 1px);
  margin-bottom: 0;
  font-size: inherit;
  line-height: 1.5
}

.col-form-label-lg {
  padding-top: calc(.5rem + 1px);
  padding-bottom: calc(.5rem + 1px);
  font-size: 1.25rem
}

.col-form-label-sm {
  padding-top: calc(.25rem + 1px);
  padding-bottom: calc(.25rem + 1px);
  font-size: .875rem
}

.form-text {
  margin-top: .25rem;
  font-size: .875em;
  color: #6c757d
}

.form-control {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
  padding: .375rem .75rem;
  font-size: 1rem;
  font-weight: 400;
  line-height: 1.5;

```

```

    color: #212529;
    background-color: #fff;
    background-clip: padding-box;
    border: 1px solid #ced4da;
    -webkit-appearance: none;
    -moz-appearance: none;
    appearance: none;
    border-radius: .25rem;
    transition: border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .form-control {
        transition: none
    }
}

.form-control[type=file] {
    overflow: hidden
}

.form-control[type=file]:not(:disabled):not([readonly]) {
    cursor: pointer
}

.form-control:focus {
    color: #212529;
    background-color: #fff;
    border-color: #86b7fe;
    outline: 0;
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.form-control::-webkit-date-and-time-value {
    height: 1.5em
}

.form-control::-moz-placeholder {
    color: #6c757d;
    opacity: 1
}

.form-control::placeholder {
    color: #6c757d;
    opacity: 1
}

.form-control:disabled,
.form-control[readonly] {
    background-color: #e9ecef;
    opacity: 1
}

.form-control::-webkit-file-upload-button {
    padding: .375rem .75rem;
    margin: -.375rem -.75rem;
    -webkit-margin-end: .75rem;

```

```

margin-inline-end: .75rem;
color: #212529;
background-color: #e9ecef;
pointer-events: none;
border-color: inherit;
border-style: solid;
border-width: 0;
border-inline-end-width: 1px;
border-radius: 0;
-webkit-transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-
in-out, border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

.form-control::file-selector-button {
padding: .375rem .75rem;
margin: -.375rem -.75rem;
-webkit-margin-end: .75rem;
margin-inline-end: .75rem;
color: #212529;
background-color: #e9ecef;
pointer-events: none;
border-color: inherit;
border-style: solid;
border-width: 0;
border-inline-end-width: 1px;
border-radius: 0;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
.form-control::-webkit-file-upload-button {
-webkit-transition: none;
transition: none
}
.form-control::file-selector-button {
transition: none
}
}

.form-control:hover:not(:disabled):not([readonly])::-webkit-file-upload-
button {
background-color: #dde0e3
}

.form-control:hover:not(:disabled):not([readonly])::file-selector-button {
background-color: #dde0e3
}

.form-control::-webkit-file-upload-button {
padding: .375rem .75rem;
margin: -.375rem -.75rem;
-webkit-margin-end: .75rem;
margin-inline-end: .75rem;
color: #212529;

```

```

background-color: #e9ecef;
pointer-events: none;
border-color: inherit;
border-style: solid;
border-width: 0;
border-inline-end-width: 1px;
border-radius: 0;
-webkit-transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-
in-out, border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .form-control::-webkit-file-upload-button {
    -webkit-transition: none;
    transition: none
  }
}

.form-control:hover:not(:disabled):not([readonly])::-webkit-file-upload-
button {
  background-color: #dde0e3
}

.form-control-plaintext {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
  padding: .375rem 0;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  line-height: 1.5;
  color: #212529;
  background-color: transparent;
  border: solid transparent;
  border-width: 1px 0
}

.form-control-plaintext.form-control-lg,
.form-control-plaintext.form-control-sm {
  padding-right: 0;
  padding-left: 0
}

.form-control-sm {
  min-height: calc(1.5em + .5rem + 2px);
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  font-size: .875rem;
  border-radius: .2rem
}

.form-control-sm::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  margin: -.25rem -.5rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: .5rem;
  margin-inline-end: .5rem
}

```

```

.form-control-sm::file-selector-button {
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  margin: -.25rem -.5rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: .5rem;
  margin-inline-end: .5rem
}

.form-control-sm::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  margin: -.25rem -.5rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: .5rem;
  margin-inline-end: .5rem
}

.form-control-lg {
  min-height: calc(1.5em + 1rem + 2px);
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  font-size: 1.25rem;
  border-radius: .3rem
}

.form-control-lg::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  margin: -.5rem -1rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: 1rem;
  margin-inline-end: 1rem
}

.form-control-lg::file-selector-button {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  margin: -.5rem -1rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: 1rem;
  margin-inline-end: 1rem
}

.form-control-lg::-webkit-file-upload-button {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  margin: -.5rem -1rem;
  -webkit-margin-end: 1rem;
  margin-inline-end: 1rem
}

textarea.form-control {
  min-height: calc(1.5em + .75rem + 2px)
}

textarea.form-control-sm {
  min-height: calc(1.5em + .5rem + 2px)
}

textarea.form-control-lg {
  min-height: calc(1.5em + 1rem + 2px)
}

.form-control-color {
  width: 3rem;
  height: auto;
}

```

```

padding: .375rem
}

.form-control-color:not(:disabled):not([readonly]) {
  cursor: pointer
}

.form-control-color::-moz-color-swatch {
  height: 1.5em;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.form-control-color::-webkit-color-swatch {
  height: 1.5em;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.form-select {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
  padding: .375rem 2.25rem .375rem .75rem;
  -moz-padding-start: calc(0.75rem - 3px);
  font-size: 1rem;
  font-weight: 400;
  line-height: 1.5;
  color: #212529;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'%3e%3cpath fill='none'
stroke='%23343a40' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-linejoin='round' stroke-
width='2' d='M2 5 6 6 6 2'%3e%3c/svg%3e");
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  background-position: right .75rem center;
  background-size: 16px 12px;
  border: 1px solid #ced4da;
  border-radius: .25rem;
  transition: border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
  -webkit-appearance: none;
  -moz-appearance: none;
  appearance: none
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .form-select {
    transition: none
  }
}

.form-select:focus {
  border-color: #86b7fe;
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.form-select[multiple],
.form-select[size]:not([size="1"]) {
  padding-right: .75rem;

```

```

    background-image: none
}

.form-select:disabled {
    background-color: #e9ecef
}

.form-select:-moz-focusring {
    color: transparent;
    text-shadow: 0 0 0 #212529
}

.form-select-sm {
    padding-top: .25rem;
    padding-bottom: .25rem;
    padding-left: .5rem;
    font-size: .875rem;
    border-radius: .2rem
}

.form-select-lg {
    padding-top: .5rem;
    padding-bottom: .5rem;
    padding-left: 1rem;
    font-size: 1.25rem;
    border-radius: .3rem
}

.form-check {
    display: block;
    min-height: 1.5rem;
    padding-left: 1.5em;
    margin-bottom: .125rem
}

.form-check .form-check-input {
    float: left;
    margin-left: -1.5em
}

.form-check-input {
    width: 1em;
    height: 1em;
    margin-top: .25em;
    vertical-align: top;
    background-color: #fff;
    background-repeat: no-repeat;
    background-position: center;
    background-size: contain;
    border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
    -webkit-appearance: none;
    -moz-appearance: none;
    appearance: none;
    -webkit-print-color-adjust: exact;
    color-adjust: exact
}

```

```

.form-check-input[type=checkbox] {
  border-radius: .25em
}

.form-check-input[type=radio] {
  border-radius: 50%
}

.form-check-input:active {
  filter: brightness(90%)
}

.form-check-input:focus {
  border-color: #86b7fe;
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.form-check-input:checked {
  background-color: #0d6efd;
  border-color: #0d6efd
}

.form-check-input:checked[type=checkbox] {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 20 20'%3e%3cpath fill='none'
stroke='%23fff' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-linejoin='round' stroke-
width='3' d='M6 10 13 3 16-6'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.form-check-input:checked[type=radio] {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3e%3ccircle r='2'
fill='%23fff'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.form-check-input[type=checkbox]:indeterminate {
  background-color: #0d6efd;
  border-color: #0d6efd;
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 20 20'%3e%3cpath fill='none'
stroke='%23fff' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-linejoin='round' stroke-
width='3' d='M6 10h8'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.form-check-input:disabled {
  pointer-events: none;
  filter: none;
  opacity: .5
}

.form-check-input:disabled~.form-check-label,
.form-check-input[disabled]~.form-check-label {
  opacity: .5
}

.form-switch {

```

```

padding-left: 2.5em
}

.form-switch .form-check-input {
width: 2em;
margin-left: -2.5em;
background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3e%3ccircle r='3'
fill='rgba%280, 0, 0, 0.25%29'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
background-position: left center;
border-radius: 2em;
transition: background-position .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
.form-switch .form-check-input {
transition: none
}
}

.form-switch .form-check-input:focus {
background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3e%3ccircle r='3'
fill='%2386b7fe'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.form-switch .form-check-input:checked {
background-position: right center;
background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3e%3ccircle r='3'
fill='%23fff'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.form-check-inline {
display: inline-block;
margin-right: 1rem
}

.btn-check {
position: absolute;
clip: rect(0, 0, 0, 0);
pointer-events: none
}

.btn-check:disabled+.btn,
.btn-check[disabled]+.btn {
pointer-events: none;
filter: none;
opacity: .65
}

.form-range {
width: 100%;
height: 1.5rem;
padding: 0;
background-color: transparent;
-webkit-appearance: none;

```

```

    -moz-appearance: none;
    appearance: none
}

.form-range:focus {
    outline: 0
}

.form-range:focus::-webkit-slider-thumb {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 1px #fff, 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.form-range:focus::-moz-range-thumb {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 1px #fff, 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.form-range::-moz-focus-outer {
    border: 0
}

.form-range::-webkit-slider-thumb {
    width: 1rem;
    height: 1rem;
    margin-top: -.25rem;
    background-color: #0d6efd;
    border: 0;
    border-radius: 1rem;
    -webkit-transition: background-color .15s ease-in-out, border-color .15s
ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
    transition: background-color .15s ease-in-out, border-color .15s ease-in-
out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
    -webkit-appearance: none;
    appearance: none
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .form-range::-webkit-slider-thumb {
        -webkit-transition: none;
        transition: none
    }
}

.form-range::-webkit-slider-thumb:active {
    background-color: #b6d4fe
}

.form-range::-webkit-slider-runnable-track {
    width: 100%;
    height: .5rem;
    color: transparent;
    cursor: pointer;
    background-color: #dee2e6;
    border-color: transparent;
    border-radius: 1rem
}

.form-range::-moz-range-thumb {

```

```

width: 1rem;
height: 1rem;
background-color: #0d6efd;
border: 0;
border-radius: 1rem;
-moz-transition: background-color .15s ease-in-out, border-color .15s
ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
transition: background-color .15s ease-in-out, border-color .15s ease-in-
out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out;
-moz-appearance: none;
appearance: none
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .form-range::-moz-range-thumb {
    -moz-transition: none;
    transition: none
  }
}

.form-range::-moz-range-thumb:active {
  background-color: #b6d4fe
}

.form-range::-moz-range-track {
  width: 100%;
  height: .5rem;
  color: transparent;
  cursor: pointer;
  background-color: #dee2e6;
  border-color: transparent;
  border-radius: 1rem
}

.form-range:disabled {
  pointer-events: none
}

.form-range:disabled::-webkit-slider-thumb {
  background-color: #adb5bd
}

.form-range:disabled::-moz-range-thumb {
  background-color: #adb5bd
}

.form-floating {
  position: relative
}

.form-floating>.form-control,
.form-floating>.form-select {
  height: calc(3.5rem + 2px);
  line-height: 1.25
}

.form-floating>label {

```

```

position: absolute;
top: 0;
left: 0;
height: 100%;
padding: 1rem .75rem;
pointer-events: none;
border: 1px solid transparent;
transform-origin: 0 0;
transition: opacity .1s ease-in-out, transform .1s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .form-floating>label {
    transition: none
  }
}

.form-floating>.form-control {
  padding: 1rem .75rem
}

.form-floating>.form-control::-moz-placeholder {
  color: transparent
}

.form-floating>.form-control::placeholder {
  color: transparent
}

.form-floating>.form-control:not(:-moz-placeholder-shown) {
  padding-top: 1.625rem;
  padding-bottom: .625rem
}

.form-floating>.form-control:focus,
.form-floating>.form-control:not(:placeholder-shown) {
  padding-top: 1.625rem;
  padding-bottom: .625rem
}

.form-floating>.form-control:-webkit-autofill {
  padding-top: 1.625rem;
  padding-bottom: .625rem
}

.form-floating>.form-select {
  padding-top: 1.625rem;
  padding-bottom: .625rem
}

.form-floating>.form-control:not(:-moz-placeholder-shown)~label {
  opacity: .65;
  transform: scale(.85) translateY(-.5rem) translateX(.15rem)
}

.form-floating>.form-control:focus~label,
.form-floating>.form-control:not(:placeholder-shown)~label,

```

```

.form-floating>.form-select~label {
  opacity: .65;
  transform: scale(.85) translateY(-.5rem) translateX(.15rem)
}

.form-floating>.form-control:-webkit-autofill~label {
  opacity: .65;
  transform: scale(.85) translateY(-.5rem) translateX(.15rem)
}

.input-group {
  position: relative;
  display: flex;
  flex-wrap: wrap;
  align-items: stretch;
  width: 100%
}

.input-group>.form-control,
.input-group>.form-select {
  position: relative;
  flex: 1 1 auto;
  width: 1%;
  min-width: 0
}

.input-group>.form-control:focus,
.input-group>.form-select:focus {
  z-index: 3
}

.input-group .btn {
  position: relative;
  z-index: 2
}

.input-group .btn:focus {
  z-index: 3
}

.input-group-text {
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  padding: .375rem .75rem;
  font-size: 1rem;
  font-weight: 400;
  line-height: 1.5;
  color: #212529;
  text-align: center;
  white-space: nowrap;
  background-color: #e9ecef;
  border: 1px solid #ced4da;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.input-group-lg>.btn,
.input-group-lg>.form-control,

```

```

.input-group-lg>.form-select,
.input-group-lg>.input-group-text {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  font-size: 1.25rem;
  border-radius: .3rem
}

.input-group-sm>.btn,
.input-group-sm>.form-control,
.input-group-sm>.form-select,
.input-group-sm>.input-group-text {
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  font-size: .875rem;
  border-radius: .2rem
}

.input-group-lg>.form-select,
.input-group-sm>.form-select {
  padding-right: 3rem
}

.input-group:not(.has-validation)>.dropdown-toggle:nth-last-child(n+3),
.input-group:not(.has-validation)>:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-
toggle):not(.dropdown-menu) {
  border-top-right-radius: 0;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0
}

.input-group.has-validation>.dropdown-toggle:nth-last-child(n+4),
.input-group.has-validation>:nth-last-child(n+3):not(.dropdown-
toggle):not(.dropdown-menu) {
  border-top-right-radius: 0;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0
}

.input-group>:not(:first-child):not(.dropdown-menu):not(.valid-
tooltip):not(.valid-feedback):not(.invalid-tooltip):not(.invalid-feedback) {
  margin-left: -1px;
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}

.valid-feedback {
  display: none;
  width: 100%;
  margin-top: .25rem;
  font-size: .875em;
  color: #198754
}

.valid-tooltip {
  position: absolute;
  top: 100%;
  z-index: 5;
  display: none;
  max-width: 100%;
  padding: .25rem .5rem;

```

```

margin-top: .1rem;
font-size: .875rem;
color: #fff;
background-color: rgba(25, 135, 84, .9);
border-radius: .25rem
}

.is-valid~.valid-feedback,
.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,
.was-validated :valid~.valid-feedback,
.was-validated :valid~.valid-tooltip {
  display: block
}

.form-control.is-valid,
.was-validated .form-control:valid {
  border-color: #198754;
  padding-right: calc(1.5em + .75rem);
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath
fill='%23198754' d='M2.3 6.73L6 4.53c-.4-1.04.46-1.4 1.1-.81l1.1 1.4 3.4-
3.8c.6-.63 1.6-.27 1.2.71-4 4.6c-.43.5-.8.4-1.1.1z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  background-position: right calc(.375em + .1875rem) center;
  background-size: calc(.75em + .375rem) calc(.75em + .375rem)
}

.form-control.is-valid:focus,
.was-validated .form-control:valid:focus {
  border-color: #198754;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(25, 135, 84, .25)
}

.was-validated textarea.form-control:valid,
textarea.form-control.is-valid {
  padding-right: calc(1.5em + .75rem);
  background-position: top calc(.375em + .1875rem) right calc(.375em +
.1875rem)
}

.form-select.is-valid,
.was-validated .form-select:valid {
  border-color: #198754
}

.form-select.is-valid:not([multiple]):not([size]),
.form-select.is-valid:not([multiple])[size="1"],
.was-validated .form-select:valid:not([multiple]):not([size]),
.was-validated .form-select:valid:not([multiple])[size="1"] {
  padding-right: 4.125rem;
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'%3e%3cpath fill='none'
stroke='%23343a40' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-linejoin='round' stroke-
width='2' d='M2 5l6 6'/%3e%3c/svg%3e"), url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3e%3cpath
fill='%23198754' d='M2.3 6.73L6 4.53c-.4-1.04.46-1.4 1.1-.81l1.1 1.4 3.4-
3.8c.6-.63 1.6-.27 1.2.71-4 4.6c-.43.5-.8.4-1.1.1z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");

```

```

background-position: right .75rem center, center right 2.25rem;
background-size: 16px 12px, calc(.75em + .375rem) calc(.75em + .375rem)
}

.form-select.is-valid:focus,
.was-validated .form-select:valid:focus {
border-color: #198754;
box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(25, 135, 84, .25)
}

.form-check-input.is-valid,
.was-validated .form-check-input:valid {
border-color: #198754
}

.form-check-input.is-valid:checked,
.was-validated .form-check-input:valid:checked {
background-color: #198754
}

.form-check-input.is-valid:focus,
.was-validated .form-check-input:valid:focus {
box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(25, 135, 84, .25)
}

.form-check-input.is-valid~.form-check-label,
.was-validated .form-check-input:valid~.form-check-label {
color: #198754
}

.form-check-inline .form-check-input~.valid-feedback {
margin-left: .5em
}

.input-group .form-control.is-valid,
.input-group .form-select.is-valid,
.was-validated .input-group .form-control:valid,
.was-validated .input-group .form-select:valid {
z-index: 1
}

.input-group .form-control.is-valid:focus,
.input-group .form-select.is-valid:focus,
.was-validated .input-group .form-control:valid:focus,
.was-validated .input-group .form-select:valid:focus {
z-index: 3
}

.invalid-feedback {
display: none;
width: 100%;
margin-top: .25rem;
font-size: .875em;
color: #dc3545
}

.invalid-tooltip {

```

```

position: absolute;
top: 100%;
z-index: 5;
display: none;
max-width: 100%;
padding: .25rem .5rem;
margin-top: .1rem;
font-size: .875rem;
color: #fff;
background-color: rgba(220, 53, 69, .9);
border-radius: .25rem
}

.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,
.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,
.was-validated :invalid~.invalid-feedback,
.was-validated :invalid~.invalid-tooltip {
display: block
}

.form-control.is-invalid,
.was-validated .form-control:invalid {
border-color: #dc3545;
padding-right: calc(1.5em + .75rem);
background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 12 12' width='12' height='12'
fill='none' stroke='%23dc3545'%3e%3ccircle cx='6' cy='6' r='4.5'/%3e%3cpath
stroke-linejoin='round' d='M5.8 3.6h.4L6 6.5z'/%3e%3ccircle cx='6' cy='8.2'
r='.6' fill='%23dc3545' stroke='none'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
background-repeat: no-repeat;
background-position: right calc(.375em + .1875rem) center;
background-size: calc(.75em + .375rem) calc(.75em + .375rem)
}

.form-control.is-invalid:focus,
.was-validated .form-control:invalid:focus {
border-color: #dc3545;
box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(220, 53, 69, .25)
}

.was-validated textarea.form-control:invalid,
textarea.form-control.is-invalid {
padding-right: calc(1.5em + .75rem);
background-position: top calc(.375em + .1875rem) right calc(.375em +
.1875rem)
}

.form-select.is-invalid,
.was-validated .form-select:invalid {
border-color: #dc3545
}

.form-select.is-invalid:not([multiple]):not([size]),
.form-select.is-invalid:not([multiple])[size="1"],
.was-validated .form-select:invalid:not([multiple]):not([size]),
.was-validated .form-select:invalid:not([multiple])[size="1"] {
padding-right: 4.125rem;
}

```

```

        background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'%3e%3cpath fill='none'
stroke='%23343a40' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-linejoin='round' stroke-
width='2' d='M2 5l6 6 6-6'/%3e%3c/svg%3e"), url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 12 12' width='12' height='12'
fill='none' stroke='%23dc3545'%3e%3ccircle cx='6' cy='6' r='4.5'/%3e%3cpath
stroke-linejoin='round' d='M5.8 3.6h.4L6 6.5z'/%3e%3ccircle cx='6' cy='8.2'
r='.6' fill='%23dc3545' stroke='none'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
        background-position: right .75rem center, center right 2.25rem;
        background-size: 16px 12px, calc(.75em + .375rem) calc(.75em + .375rem)
    }

.form-select.is-invalid:focus,
.was-validated .form-select:invalid:focus {
    border-color: #dc3545;
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(220, 53, 69, .25)
}

.form-check-input.is-invalid,
.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid {
    border-color: #dc3545
}

.form-check-input.is-invalid:checked,
.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid:checked {
    background-color: #dc3545
}

.form-check-input.is-invalid:focus,
.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(220, 53, 69, .25)
}

.form-check-input.is-invalid~.form-check-label,
.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.form-check-label {
    color: #dc3545
}

.form-check-inline .form-check-input~.invalid-feedback {
    margin-left: .5em
}

.input-group .form-control.is-invalid,
.input-group .form-select.is-invalid,
.was-validated .input-group .form-control:invalid,
.was-validated .input-group .form-select:invalid {
    z-index: 2
}

.input-group .form-control.is-invalid:focus,
.input-group .form-select.is-invalid:focus,
.was-validated .input-group .form-control:invalid:focus,
.was-validated .input-group .form-select:invalid:focus {
    z-index: 3
}

.btn {

```

```

display: inline-block;
font-weight: 400;
line-height: 1.5;
color: #212529;
text-align: center;
text-decoration: none;
vertical-align: middle;
cursor: pointer;
-webkit-user-select: none;
-moz-user-select: none;
user-select: none;
background-color: transparent;
border: 1px solid transparent;
padding: .375rem .75rem;
font-size: 1rem;
border-radius: .25rem;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .btn {
    transition: none
  }
}

.btn:hover {
  color: #212529
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn,
.btn:focus {
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.btn.disabled,
.btn:disabled,
fieldset:disabled .btn {
  pointer-events: none;
  opacity: .65
}

.btn-primary {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0d6efd;
  border-color: #0d6efd
}

.btn-primary:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0b5ed7;
  border-color: #0a58ca
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-primary,
.btn-primary:focus {

```

```

    color: #fff;
    background-color: #0b5ed7;
    border-color: #0a58ca;
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(49, 132, 253, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-primary,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-primary,
.btn-primary.active,
.btn-primary:active,
.show>.btn-primary.dropdown-toggle {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #0a58ca;
    border-color: #0a53be
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-primary:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-primary:focus,
.btn-primary.active:focus,
.btn-primary:active:focus,
.show>.btn-primary.dropdown-toggle:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(49, 132, 253, .5)
}

.btn-primary.disabled,
.btn-primary:disabled {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #0d6efd;
    border-color: #0d6efd
}

.btn-secondary {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #6c757d;
    border-color: #6c757d
}

.btn-secondary:hover {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #5c636a;
    border-color: #565e64
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-secondary,
.btn-secondary:focus {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #5c636a;
    border-color: #565e64;
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(130, 138, 145, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-secondary,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-secondary,
.btn-secondary.active,
.btn-secondary:active,
.show>.btn-secondary.dropdown-toggle {
    color: #fff;

```

```

    background-color: #565e64;
    border-color: #51585e
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-secondary:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-secondary:focus,
.btn-secondary.active:focus,
.btn-secondary:active:focus,
.show>.btn-secondary.dropdown-toggle:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(130, 138, 145, .5)
}

.btn-secondary.disabled,
.btn-secondary.disabled {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #6c757d;
    border-color: #6c757d
}

.btn-success {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #198754;
    border-color: #198754
}

.btn-success:hover {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #157347;
    border-color: #146c43
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-success,
.btn-success:focus {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #157347;
    border-color: #146c43;
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(60, 153, 110, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-success,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-success,
.btn-success.active,
.btn-success:active,
.show>.btn-success.dropdown-toggle {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #146c43;
    border-color: #13653f
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-success:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-success:focus,
.btn-success.active:focus,
.btn-success:active:focus,
.show>.btn-success.dropdown-toggle:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(60, 153, 110, .5)
}

```

```

.btn-success.disabled,
.btn-success:disabled {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #198754;
  border-color: #198754
}

.btn-info {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #0dcaf0;
  border-color: #0dcaf0
}

.btn-info:hover {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #31d2f2;
  border-color: #25cff2
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-info,
.btn-info:focus {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #31d2f2;
  border-color: #25cff2;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(11, 172, 204, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-info,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-info,
.btn-info.active,
.btn-info:active,
.show>.btn-info.dropdown-toggle {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #3dd5f3;
  border-color: #25cff2
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-info:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-info:focus,
.btn-info.active:focus,
.btn-info:active:focus,
.show>.btn-info.dropdown-toggle:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(11, 172, 204, .5)
}

.btn-info.disabled,
.btn-info:disabled {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #0dcaf0;
  border-color: #0dcaf0
}

.btn-warning {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffc107;
  border-color: #ffc107
}

```

```

.btn-warning:hover {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffca2c;
  border-color: #ffc720
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-warning,
.btn-warning:focus {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffca2c;
  border-color: #ffc720;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(217, 164, 6, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-warning,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-warning,
.btn-warning.active,
.btn-warning:active,
.show>.btn-warning.dropdown-toggle {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffcd39;
  border-color: #ffc720
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-warning:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-warning:focus,
.btn-warning.active:focus,
.btn-warning:active:focus,
.show>.btn-warning.dropdown-toggle:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(217, 164, 6, .5)
}

.btn-warning.disabled,
.btn-warning:disabled {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffc107;
  border-color: #ffc107
}

.btn-danger {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #dc3545;
  border-color: #dc3545
}

.btn-danger:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #bb2d3b;
  border-color: #b02a37
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-danger,
.btn-danger:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #bb2d3b;
  border-color: #b02a37;
}

```

```

        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(225, 83, 97, .5)
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-danger,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-danger,
    .btn-danger.active,
    .btn-danger:active,
    .show>.btn-danger.dropdown-toggle {
        color: #fff;
        background-color: #b02a37;
        border-color: #a52834
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-danger:focus,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-danger:focus,
    .btn-danger.active:focus,
    .btn-danger:active:focus,
    .show>.btn-danger.dropdown-toggle:focus {
        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(225, 83, 97, .5)
    }

    .btn-danger.disabled,
    .btn-danger:disabled {
        color: #fff;
        background-color: #dc3545;
        border-color: #dc3545
    }

    .btn-light {
        color: #000;
        background-color: #f8f9fa;
        border-color: #f8f9fa
    }

    .btn-light:hover {
        color: #000;
        background-color: #f9fafb;
        border-color: #f9fafb
    }

    .btn-check:focus+.btn-light,
    .btn-light:focus {
        color: #000;
        background-color: #f9fafb;
        border-color: #f9fafb;
        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(211, 212, 213, .5)
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-light,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-light,
    .btn-light.active,
    .btn-light:active,
    .show>.btn-light.dropdown-toggle {
        color: #000;
        background-color: #f9fafb;
        border-color: #f9fafb
    }
}

```

```

.btn-check:active+.btn-light:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-light:focus,
.btn-light.active:focus,
.btn-light:active:focus,
.show>.btn-light.dropdown-toggle:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(211, 212, 213, .5)
}

.btn-light.disabled,
.btn-light:disabled {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #f8f9fa;
  border-color: #f8f9fa
}

.btn-dark {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #212529;
  border-color: #212529
}

.btn-dark:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #1c1f23;
  border-color: #1a1e21
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-dark,
.btn-dark:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #1c1f23;
  border-color: #1a1e21;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(66, 70, 73, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-dark,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-dark,
.btn-dark.active,
.btn-dark:active,
.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-toggle {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #1a1e21;
  border-color: #191c1f
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-dark:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-dark:focus,
.btn-dark.active:focus,
.btn-dark:active:focus,
.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-toggle:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(66, 70, 73, .5)
}

.btn-dark.disabled,
.btn-dark:disabled {
  color: #fff;

```

```

    background-color: #212529;
    border-color: #212529
}

.btn-outline-primary {
    color: #0d6efd;
    border-color: #0d6efd
}

.btn-outline-primary:hover {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #0d6efd;
    border-color: #0d6efd
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-primary,
.btn-outline-primary:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-primary,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-primary,
.btn-outline-primary.active,
.btn-outline-primary.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-primary:active {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #0d6efd;
    border-color: #0d6efd
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-primary:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-primary:focus,
.btn-outline-primary.active:focus,
.btn-outline-primary.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-primary:active:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .5)
}

.btn-outline-primary.disabled,
.btn-outline-primary:disabled {
    color: #0d6efd;
    background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-secondary {
    color: #6c757d;
    border-color: #6c757d
}

.btn-outline-secondary:hover {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #6c757d;
    border-color: #6c757d
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-secondary,
.btn-outline-secondary:focus {

```

```

        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(108, 117, 125, .5)
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-outline-secondary,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-secondary,
    .btn-outline-secondary.active,
    .btn-outline-secondary.dropdown-toggle.show,
    .btn-outline-secondary:active {
        color: #fff;
        background-color: #6c757d;
        border-color: #6c757d
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-outline-secondary:focus,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-secondary:focus,
    .btn-outline-secondary.active:focus,
    .btn-outline-secondary.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
    .btn-outline-secondary:active:focus {
        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(108, 117, 125, .5)
    }

    .btn-outline-secondary.disabled,
    .btn-outline-secondary:disabled {
        color: #6c757d;
        background-color: transparent
    }

    .btn-outline-success {
        color: #198754;
        border-color: #198754
    }

    .btn-outline-success:hover {
        color: #fff;
        background-color: #198754;
        border-color: #198754
    }

    .btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-success,
    .btn-outline-success:focus {
        box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(25, 135, 84, .5)
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-outline-success,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-success,
    .btn-outline-success.active,
    .btn-outline-success.dropdown-toggle.show,
    .btn-outline-success:active {
        color: #fff;
        background-color: #198754;
        border-color: #198754
    }

    .btn-check:active+.btn-outline-success:focus,
    .btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-success:focus,
    .btn-outline-success.active:focus,
    .btn-outline-success.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,

```

```

.btn-outline-success:active:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(25, 135, 84, .5)
}

.btn-outline-success.disabled,
.btn-outline-success:disabled {
  color: #198754;
  background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-info {
  color: #0dcaf0;
  border-color: #0dcaf0
}

.btn-outline-info:hover {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #0dcaf0;
  border-color: #0dcaf0
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-info,
.btn-outline-info:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 202, 240, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-info,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-info,
.btn-outline-info.active,
.btn-outline-info.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-info:active {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #0dcaf0;
  border-color: #0dcaf0
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-info:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-info:focus,
.btn-outline-info.active:focus,
.btn-outline-info.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-info:active:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 202, 240, .5)
}

.btn-outline-info.disabled,
.btn-outline-info:disabled {
  color: #0dcaf0;
  background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-warning {
  color: #ffc107;
  border-color: #ffc107
}

.btn-outline-warning:hover {
  color: #000;

```

```

background-color: #ffc107;
border-color: #ffc107
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-warning,
.btn-outline-warning:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(255, 193, 7, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-warning,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-warning,
.btn-outline-warning.active,
.btn-outline-warning.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-warning:active {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #ffc107;
  border-color: #ffc107
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-warning:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-warning:focus,
.btn-outline-warning.active:focus,
.btn-outline-warning.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-warning:active:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(255, 193, 7, .5)
}

.btn-outline-warning.disabled,
.btn-outline-warning:disabled {
  color: #ffc107;
  background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-danger {
  color: #dc3545;
  border-color: #dc3545
}

.btn-outline-danger:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #dc3545;
  border-color: #dc3545
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-danger,
.btn-outline-danger:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(220, 53, 69, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-danger,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-danger,
.btn-outline-danger.active,
.btn-outline-danger.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-danger:active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #dc3545;
  border-color: #dc3545
}

```

```

}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-danger:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-danger:focus,
.btn-outline-danger.active:focus,
.btn-outline-danger.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-danger:active:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(220, 53, 69, .5)
}

.btn-outline-danger.disabled,
.btn-outline-danger:disabled {
  color: #dc3545;
  background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-light {
  color: #f8f9fa;
  border-color: #f8f9fa
}

.btn-outline-light:hover {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #f8f9fa;
  border-color: #f8f9fa
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-light,
.btn-outline-light:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(248, 249, 250, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-light,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-light,
.btn-outline-light.active,
.btn-outline-light.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-light:active {
  color: #000;
  background-color: #f8f9fa;
  border-color: #f8f9fa
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-light:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-light:focus,
.btn-outline-light.active:focus,
.btn-outline-light.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-light:active:focus {
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(248, 249, 250, .5)
}

.btn-outline-light.disabled,
.btn-outline-light:disabled {
  color: #f8f9fa;
  background-color: transparent
}

.btn-outline-dark {

```

```

    color: #212529;
    border-color: #212529
}

.btn-outline-dark:hover {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #212529;
    border-color: #212529
}

.btn-check:focus+.btn-outline-dark,
.btn-outline-dark:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(33, 37, 41, .5)
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-dark,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-dark,
.btn-outline-dark.active,
.btn-outline-dark.dropdown-toggle.show,
.btn-outline-dark:active {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #212529;
    border-color: #212529
}

.btn-check:active+.btn-outline-dark:focus,
.btn-check:checked+.btn-outline-dark:focus,
.btn-outline-dark.active:focus,
.btn-outline-dark.dropdown-toggle.show:focus,
.btn-outline-dark:active:focus {
    box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(33, 37, 41, .5)
}

.btn-outline-dark.disabled,
.btn-outline-dark:disabled {
    color: #212529;
    background-color: transparent
}

.btn-link {
    font-weight: 400;
    color: #0d6efd;
    text-decoration: underline
}

.btn-link:hover {
    color: #0a58ca
}

.btn-link.disabled,
.btn-link:disabled {
    color: #6c757d
}

.btn-group-lg>.btn,
.btn-lg {
    padding: .5rem 1rem;

```

```

    font-size: 1.25rem;
    border-radius: .3rem
}

.btn-group-sm>.btn,
.btn-sm {
    padding: .25rem .5rem;
    font-size: .875rem;
    border-radius: .2rem
}

.fade {
    transition: opacity .15s linear
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .fade {
        transition: none
    }
}

.fade:not(.show) {
    opacity: 0
}

.collapse:not(.show) {
    display: none
}

.collapsing {
    height: 0;
    overflow: hidden;
    transition: height .35s ease
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .collapsing {
        transition: none
    }
}

.collapsing.collapse-horizontal {
    width: 0;
    height: auto;
    transition: width .35s ease
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .collapsing.collapse-horizontal {
        transition: none
    }
}

.dropdown,
.dropleft,
.dropright,
.dropstart,
.dropup {

```

```

    position: relative
  }

.dropdown-toggle {
  white-space: nowrap
}

.dropdown-toggle::after {
  display: inline-block;
  margin-left: .255em;
  vertical-align: .255em;
  content: "";
  border-top: .3em solid;
  border-right: .3em solid transparent;
  border-bottom: 0;
  border-left: .3em solid transparent
}

.dropdown-toggle.empty::after {
  margin-left: 0
}

.dropdown-menu {
  position: absolute;
  z-index: 1000;
  display: none;
  min-width: 10rem;
  padding: .5rem 0;
  margin: 0;
  font-size: 1rem;
  color: #212529;
  text-align: left;
  list-style: none;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-clip: padding-box;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.dropdown-menu[data-bs-popover] {
  top: 100%;
  left: 0;
  margin-top: .125rem
}

.dropdown-menu-start {
  --bs-position: start
}

.dropdown-menu-start[data-bs-popover] {
  right: auto;
  left: 0
}

.dropdown-menu-end {
  --bs-position: end
}

```

```

.dropdown-menu-end[data-bs-popover] {
  right: 0;
  left: auto
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .dropdown-menu-sm-start {
    --bs-position: start
  }
  .dropdown-menu-sm-start[data-bs-popover] {
    right: auto;
    left: 0
  }
  .dropdown-menu-sm-end {
    --bs-position: end
  }
  .dropdown-menu-sm-end[data-bs-popover] {
    right: 0;
    left: auto
  }
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
  .dropdown-menu-md-start {
    --bs-position: start
  }
  .dropdown-menu-md-start[data-bs-popover] {
    right: auto;
    left: 0
  }
  .dropdown-menu-md-end {
    --bs-position: end
  }
  .dropdown-menu-md-end[data-bs-popover] {
    right: 0;
    left: auto
  }
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
  .dropdown-menu-lg-start {
    --bs-position: start
  }
  .dropdown-menu-lg-start[data-bs-popover] {
    right: auto;
    left: 0
  }
  .dropdown-menu-lg-end {
    --bs-position: end
  }
  .dropdown-menu-lg-end[data-bs-popover] {
    right: 0;
    left: auto
  }
}

```

```

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .dropdown-menu-xl-start {
    --bs-position: start
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xl-start[data-bs-popover] {
    right: auto;
    left: 0
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xl-end {
    --bs-position: end
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xl-end[data-bs-popover] {
    right: 0;
    left: auto
  }
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
  .dropdown-menu-xxl-start {
    --bs-position: start
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xxl-start[data-bs-popover] {
    right: auto;
    left: 0
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xxl-end {
    --bs-position: end
  }
  .dropdown-menu-xxl-end[data-bs-popover] {
    right: 0;
    left: auto
  }
}

.dropdown .dropdown-menu[data-bs-popover] {
  top: auto;
  bottom: 100%;
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: .125rem
}

.dropdown .dropdown-toggle::after {
  display: inline-block;
  margin-left: .255em;
  vertical-align: .255em;
  content: "";
  border-top: 0;
  border-right: .3em solid transparent;
  border-bottom: .3em solid;
  border-left: .3em solid transparent
}

.dropdown .dropdown-toggle:empty::after {
  margin-left: 0
}

.dropdown .dropdown-menu[data-bs-popover] {

```

```

    top: 0;
    right: auto;
    left: 100%;
    margin-top: 0;
    margin-left: .125rem
}

.dropend .dropdown-toggle::after {
    display: inline-block;
    margin-left: .255em;
    vertical-align: .255em;
    content: "";
    border-top: .3em solid transparent;
    border-right: 0;
    border-bottom: .3em solid transparent;
    border-left: .3em solid
}

.dropend .dropdown-toggle:empty::after {
    margin-left: 0
}

.dropend .dropdown-toggle::after {
    vertical-align: 0
}

.dropstart .dropdown-menu[data-bs-popover] {
    top: 0;
    right: 100%;
    left: auto;
    margin-top: 0;
    margin-right: .125rem
}

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle::after {
    display: inline-block;
    margin-left: .255em;
    vertical-align: .255em;
    content: ""
}

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle::after {
    display: none
}

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle::before {
    display: inline-block;
    margin-right: .255em;
    vertical-align: .255em;
    content: "";
    border-top: .3em solid transparent;
    border-right: .3em solid;
    border-bottom: .3em solid transparent
}

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle:empty::after {
    margin-left: 0
}

```

```

}

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle::before {
  vertical-align: 0
}

.dropdown-divider {
  height: 0;
  margin: .5rem 0;
  overflow: hidden;
  border-top: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .15)
}

.dropdown-item {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
  padding: .25rem 1rem;
  clear: both;
  font-weight: 400;
  color: #212529;
  text-align: inherit;
  text-decoration: none;
  white-space: nowrap;
  background-color: transparent;
  border: 0
}

.dropdown-item:focus,
.dropdown-item:hover {
  color: #1e2125;
  background-color: #e9ecef
}

.dropdown-item.active,
.dropdown-item:active {
  color: #fff;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #0d6efd
}

.dropdown-item.disabled,
.dropdown-item:disabled {
  color: #adb5bd;
  pointer-events: none;
  background-color: transparent
}

.dropdown-menu.show {
  display: block
}

.dropdown-header {
  display: block;
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  font-size: .875rem;
  color: #6c757d;

```

```

    white-space: nowrap
  }

.dropdown-item-text {
  display: block;
  padding: .25rem 1rem;
  color: #212529
}

.dropdown-menu-dark {
  color: #dee2e6;
  background-color: #343a40;
  border-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .15)
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item {
  color: #dee2e6
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item:focus,
.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .15)
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item.active,
.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item:active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0d6efd
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item.disabled,
.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item:disabled {
  color: #adb5bd
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-divider {
  border-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .15)
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-item-text {
  color: #dee2e6
}

.dropdown-menu-dark .dropdown-header {
  color: #adb5bd
}

.btn-group,
.btn-group-vertical {
  position: relative;
  display: inline-flex;
  vertical-align: middle
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn,
.btn-group>.btn {

```

```

    position: relative;
    flex: 1 1 auto
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn-check:checked+.btn,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn-check:focus+.btn,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn.active,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn:active,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn:focus,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn:hover,
.btn-group>.btn-check:checked+.btn,
.btn-group>.btn-check:focus+.btn,
.btn-group>.btn.active,
.btn-group>.btn:active,
.btn-group>.btn:focus,
.btn-group>.btn:hover {
    z-index: 1
}

.btn-toolbar {
    display: flex;
    flex-wrap: wrap;
    justify-content: flex-start
}

.btn-toolbar .input-group {
    width: auto
}

.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:first-child),
.btn-group>.btn:not(:first-child) {
    margin-left: -1px
}

.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:last-child)>.btn,
.btn-group>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle) {
    border-top-right-radius: 0;
    border-bottom-right-radius: 0
}

.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn,
.btn-group>.btn:nth-child(n+3),
.btn-group>:not(.btn-check)+.btn {
    border-top-left-radius: 0;
    border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}

.dropdown-toggle-split {
    padding-right: .5625rem;
    padding-left: .5625rem
}

.dropdown-toggle-split::after,
.dropend .dropdown-toggle-split::after,
.dropup .dropdown-toggle-split::after {
    margin-left: 0
}

```

```

.dropstart .dropdown-toggle-split::before {
  margin-right: 0
}

.btn-group-sm>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,
.btn-sm+.dropdown-toggle-split {
  padding-right: .375rem;
  padding-left: .375rem
}

.btn-group-lg>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,
.btn-lg+.dropdown-toggle-split {
  padding-right: .75rem;
  padding-left: .75rem
}

.btn-group-vertical {
  flex-direction: column;
  align-items: flex-start;
  justify-content: center
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group {
  width: 100%
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-child),
.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:first-child) {
  margin-top: -1px
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:last-child)>.btn,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle) {
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}

.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn,
.btn-group-vertical>.btn~.btn {
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
  border-top-right-radius: 0
}

.nav {
  display: flex;
  flex-wrap: wrap;
  padding-left: 0;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  list-style: none
}

.nav-link {
  display: block;
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  color: #0d6efd;

```

```

    text-decoration: none;
    transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .nav-link {
        transition: none
    }
}

.nav-link:focus,
.nav-link:hover {
    color: #0a58ca
}

.nav-link.disabled {
    color: #6c757d;
    pointer-events: none;
    cursor: default
}

.nav-tabs {
    border-bottom: 1px solid #dee2e6
}

.nav-tabs .nav-link {
    margin-bottom: -1px;
    background: 0 0;
    border: 1px solid transparent;
    border-top-left-radius: .25rem;
    border-top-right-radius: .25rem
}

.nav-tabs .nav-link:focus,
.nav-tabs .nav-link:hover {
    border-color: #e9ecef #e9ecef #dee2e6;
    isolation: isolate
}

.nav-tabs .nav-link.disabled {
    color: #6c757d;
    background-color: transparent;
    border-color: transparent
}

.nav-tabs .nav-item.show .nav-link,
.nav-tabs .nav-link.active {
    color: #495057;
    background-color: #fff;
    border-color: #dee2e6 #dee2e6 #fff
}

.nav-tabs .dropdown-menu {
    margin-top: -1px;
    border-top-left-radius: 0;
    border-top-right-radius: 0
}

```

```

}

.nav-pills .nav-link {
  background: 0 0;
  border: 0;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.nav-pills .nav-link.active,
.nav-pills .show>.nav-link {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0d6efd
}

.nav-fill .nav-item,
.nav-fill>.nav-link {
  flex: 1 1 auto;
  text-align: center
}

.nav-justified .nav-item,
.nav-justified>.nav-link {
  flex-basis: 0;
  flex-grow: 1;
  text-align: center
}

.nav-fill .nav-item .nav-link,
.nav-justified .nav-item .nav-link {
  width: 100%
}

.tab-content>.tab-pane {
  display: none
}

.tab-content>.active {
  display: block
}

.navbar {
  position: relative;
  display: flex;
  flex-wrap: wrap;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: space-between;
  padding-top: .5rem;
  padding-bottom: .5rem
}

.navbar>.container,
.navbar>.container-fluid,
.navbar>.container-lg,
.navbar>.container-md,
.navbar>.container-sm,
.navbar>.container-xl,
.navbar>.container-xxl {

```

```

display: flex;
flex-wrap: inherit;
align-items: center;
justify-content: space-between
}

.navbar-brand {
padding-top: .3125rem;
padding-bottom: .3125rem;
margin-right: 1rem;
font-size: 1.25rem;
text-decoration: none;
white-space: nowrap
}

.navbar-nav {
display: flex;
flex-direction: column;
padding-left: 0;
margin-bottom: 0;
list-style: none
}

.navbar-nav .nav-link {
padding-right: 0;
padding-left: 0
}

.navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
position: static
}

.navbar-text {
padding-top: .5rem;
padding-bottom: .5rem
}

.navbar-collapse {
flex-basis: 100%;
flex-grow: 1;
align-items: center
}

.navbar-toggler {
padding: .25rem .75rem;
font-size: 1.25rem;
line-height: 1;
background-color: transparent;
border: 1px solid transparent;
border-radius: .25rem;
transition: box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
.navbar-toggler {
transition: none
}
}

```

```

}

.navbar-toggler:hover {
  text-decoration: none
}

.navbar-toggler:focus {
  text-decoration: none;
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem
}

.navbar-toggler-icon {
  display: inline-block;
  width: 1.5em;
  height: 1.5em;
  vertical-align: middle;
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  background-position: center;
  background-size: 100%
}

.navbar-nav-scroll {
  max-height: var(--bs-scroll-height, 75vh);
  overflow-y: auto
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .navbar-expand-sm {
    flex-wrap: nowrap;
    justify-content: flex-start
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav {
    flex-direction: row
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
    position: absolute
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .nav-link {
    padding-right: .5rem;
    padding-left: .5rem
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav-scroll {
    overflow: visible
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-collapse {
    display: flex!important;
    flex-basis: auto
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .navbar-toggler {
    display: none
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .offcanvas-header {
    display: none
  }
  .navbar-expand-sm .offcanvas {
    position: inherit;

```

```

        bottom: 0;
        z-index: 1000;
        flex-grow: 1;
        visibility: visible!important;
        background-color: transparent;
        border-right: 0;
        border-left: 0;
        transition: none;
        transform: none
    }
    .navbar-expand-sm .offcanvas-bottom,
    .navbar-expand-sm .offcanvas-top {
        height: auto;
        border-top: 0;
        border-bottom: 0
    }
    .navbar-expand-sm .offcanvas-body {
        display: flex;
        flex-grow: 0;
        padding: 0;
        overflow-y: visible
    }
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
    .navbar-expand-md {
        flex-wrap: nowrap;
        justify-content: flex-start
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav {
        flex-direction: row
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
        position: absolute
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .nav-link {
        padding-right: .5rem;
        padding-left: .5rem
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav-scroll {
        overflow: visible
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-collapse {
        display: flex!important;
        flex-basis: auto
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .navbar-toggler {
        display: none
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .offcanvas-header {
        display: none
    }
    .navbar-expand-md .offcanvas {
        position: inherit;
        bottom: 0;
        z-index: 1000;
        flex-grow: 1;

```

```

visibility: visible!important;
background-color: transparent;
border-right: 0;
border-left: 0;
transition: none;
transform: none
}
.navbar-expand-md .offcanvas-bottom,
.navbar-expand-md .offcanvas-top {
height: auto;
border-top: 0;
border-bottom: 0
}
.navbar-expand-md .offcanvas-body {
display: flex;
flex-grow: 0;
padding: 0;
overflow-y: visible
}
}
}
@media (min-width:992px) {
.navbar-expand-lg {
flex-wrap: nowrap;
justify-content: flex-start
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav {
flex-direction: row
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
position: absolute
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .nav-link {
padding-right: .5rem;
padding-left: .5rem
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav-scroll {
overflow: visible
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-collapse {
display: flex!important;
flex-basis: auto
}
.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-toggler {
display: none
}
.navbar-expand-lg .offcanvas-header {
display: none
}
.navbar-expand-lg .offcanvas {
position: inherit;
bottom: 0;
z-index: 1000;
flex-grow: 1;
visibility: visible!important;
background-color: transparent;
border-right: 0;

```

```

border-left: 0;
transition: none;
transform: none
}
.navbar-expand-lg .offcanvas-bottom,
.navbar-expand-lg .offcanvas-top {
height: auto;
border-top: 0;
border-bottom: 0
}
.navbar-expand-lg .offcanvas-body {
display: flex;
flex-grow: 0;
padding: 0;
overflow-y: visible
}
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
.navbar-expand-xl {
flex-wrap: nowrap;
justify-content: flex-start
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav {
flex-direction: row
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
position: absolute
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .nav-link {
padding-right: .5rem;
padding-left: .5rem
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav-scroll {
overflow: visible
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-collapse {
display: flex!important;
flex-basis: auto
}
.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-toggler {
display: none
}
.navbar-expand-xl .offcanvas-header {
display: none
}
.navbar-expand-xl .offcanvas {
position: inherit;
bottom: 0;
z-index: 1000;
flex-grow: 1;
visibility: visible!important;
background-color: transparent;
border-right: 0;
border-left: 0;
transition: none;
transform: none
}
}

```

```

}
.navbar-expand-xl .offcanvas-bottom,
.navbar-expand-xl .offcanvas-top {
  height: auto;
  border-top: 0;
  border-bottom: 0
}
.navbar-expand-xl .offcanvas-body {
  display: flex;
  flex-grow: 0;
  padding: 0;
  overflow-y: visible
}
}
}
@media (min-width:1400px) {
  .navbar-expand-xxl {
    flex-wrap: nowrap;
    justify-content: flex-start
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-nav {
    flex-direction: row
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
    position: absolute
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-nav .nav-link {
    padding-right: .5rem;
    padding-left: .5rem
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-nav-scroll {
    overflow: visible
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-collapse {
    display: flex!important;
    flex-basis: auto
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .navbar-toggler {
    display: none
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .offcanvas-header {
    display: none
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .offcanvas {
    position: inherit;
    bottom: 0;
    z-index: 1000;
    flex-grow: 1;
    visibility: visible!important;
    background-color: transparent;
    border-right: 0;
    border-left: 0;
    transition: none;
    transform: none
  }
  .navbar-expand-xxl .offcanvas-bottom,
  .navbar-expand-xxl .offcanvas-top {

```

```

        height: auto;
        border-top: 0;
        border-bottom: 0
    }
    .navbar-expand-xxl .offcanvas-body {
        display: flex;
        flex-grow: 0;
        padding: 0;
        overflow-y: visible
    }
}

.navbar-expand {
    flex-wrap: nowrap;
    justify-content: flex-start
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-nav {
    flex-direction: row
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu {
    position: absolute
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-nav .nav-link {
    padding-right: .5rem;
    padding-left: .5rem
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-nav-scroll {
    overflow: visible
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-collapse {
    display: flex!important;
    flex-basis: auto
}

.navbar-expand .navbar-toggler {
    display: none
}

.navbar-expand .offcanvas-header {
    display: none
}

.navbar-expand .offcanvas {
    position: inherit;
    bottom: 0;
    z-index: 1000;
    flex-grow: 1;
    visibility: visible!important;
    background-color: transparent;
    border-right: 0;
    border-left: 0;
    transition: none;
}

```

```

    transform: none
  }

.navbar-expand .offcanvas-bottom,
.navbar-expand .offcanvas-top {
  height: auto;
  border-top: 0;
  border-bottom: 0
}

.navbar-expand .offcanvas-body {
  display: flex;
  flex-grow: 0;
  padding: 0;
  overflow-y: visible
}

.navbar-light .navbar-brand {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .9)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-brand:focus,
.navbar-light .navbar-brand:hover {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .9)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .55)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link:focus,
.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link:hover {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .7)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link.disabled {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .3)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-nav .nav-link.active,
.navbar-light .navbar-nav .show>.nav-link {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .9)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-toggler {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .55);
  border-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .1)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-toggler-icon {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 30 30'%3e%3cpath
stroke='rgba%280, 0, 0, 0.55%29' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-
miterlimit='10' stroke-width='2' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4 23h22'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.navbar-light .navbar-text {

```

```

    color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .55)
}

.navbar-light .navbar-text a,
.navbar-light .navbar-text a:focus,
.navbar-light .navbar-text a:hover {
    color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .9)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-brand {
    color: #fff
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-brand:focus,
.navbar-dark .navbar-brand:hover {
    color: #fff
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link {
    color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .55)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link:focus,
.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link:hover {
    color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .75)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link.disabled {
    color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .25)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .nav-link.active,
.navbar-dark .navbar-nav .show>.nav-link {
    color: #fff
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-toggler {
    color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .55);
    border-color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .1)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-toggler-icon {
    background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 30 30'%3e%3cpath
stroke='rgba%28255, 255, 255, 0.55%29' stroke-linecap='round' stroke-
miterlimit='10' stroke-width='2' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4 23h22'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-text {
    color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .55)
}

.navbar-dark .navbar-text a,
.navbar-dark .navbar-text a:focus,
.navbar-dark .navbar-text a:hover {
    color: #fff
}

```

```

.card {
  position: relative;
  display: flex;
  flex-direction: column;
  min-width: 0;
  word-wrap: break-word;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-clip: border-box;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.card>hr {
  margin-right: 0;
  margin-left: 0
}

.card>.list-group {
  border-top: inherit;
  border-bottom: inherit
}

.card>.list-group:first-child {
  border-top-width: 0;
  border-top-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
  border-top-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card>.list-group:last-child {
  border-bottom-width: 0;
  border-bottom-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
  border-bottom-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card>.card-header+.list-group,
.card>.list-group+.card-footer {
  border-top: 0
}

.card-body {
  flex: 1 1 auto;
  padding: 1rem 1rem
}

.card-title {
  margin-bottom: .5rem
}

.card-subtitle {
  margin-top: -.25rem;
  margin-bottom: 0
}

.card-text:last-child {
  margin-bottom: 0
}

```

```

.card-link+.card-link {
  margin-left: 1rem
}

.card-header {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  background-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .03);
  border-bottom: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .125)
}

.card-header:first-child {
  border-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px) calc(.25rem - 1px) 0 0
}

.card-footer {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  background-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .03);
  border-top: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .125)
}

.card-footer:last-child {
  border-radius: 0 0 calc(.25rem - 1px) calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card-header-tabs {
  margin-right: -.5rem;
  margin-bottom: -.5rem;
  margin-left: -.5rem;
  border-bottom: 0
}

.card-header-pills {
  margin-right: -.5rem;
  margin-left: -.5rem
}

.card-img-overlay {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  left: 0;
  padding: 1rem;
  border-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card-img,
.card-img-bottom,
.card-img-top {
  width: 100%
}

.card-img,
.card-img-top {
  border-top-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);

```

```

border-top-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card-img,
.card-img-bottom {
border-bottom-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
border-bottom-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.card-group>.card {
margin-bottom: .75rem
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
.card-group {
display: flex;
flex-flow: row wrap
}
.card-group>.card {
flex: 1 0 0%;
margin-bottom: 0
}
.card-group>.card+.card {
margin-left: 0;
border-left: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:last-child) {
border-top-right-radius: 0;
border-bottom-right-radius: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:last-child) .card-header,
.card-group>.card:not(:last-child) .card-img-top {
border-top-right-radius: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:last-child) .card-footer,
.card-group>.card:not(:last-child) .card-img-bottom {
border-bottom-right-radius: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:first-child) {
border-top-left-radius: 0;
border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:first-child) .card-header,
.card-group>.card:not(:first-child) .card-img-top {
border-top-left-radius: 0
}
.card-group>.card:not(:first-child) .card-footer,
.card-group>.card:not(:first-child) .card-img-bottom {
border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}
}

.accordion-button {
position: relative;
display: flex;
align-items: center;
width: 100%;

```

```

padding: 1rem 1.25rem;
font-size: 1rem;
color: #212529;
text-align: left;
background-color: #fff;
border: 0;
border-radius: 0;
overflow-anchor: none;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out, border-radius
.15s ease
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .accordion-button {
    transition: none
  }
}

.accordion-button:not(.collapsed) {
  color: #0c63e4;
  background-color: #e7f1ff;
  box-shadow: inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .125)
}

.accordion-button:not(.collapsed)::after {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'
fill='%230c63e4'%3e%3cpath fill-rule='evenodd' d='M1.646 4.646a.5.5 0 0 1
.708 0L8 10.29315.646-5.647a.5.5 0 0 1 .708.7081-6 6a.5.5 0 0 1-.708 01-6-
6a.5.5 0 0 1 0-.708z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
  transform: rotate(-180deg)
}

.accordion-button::after {
  flex-shrink: 0;
  width: 1.25rem;
  height: 1.25rem;
  margin-left: auto;
  content: "";
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'
fill='%23212529'%3e%3cpath fill-rule='evenodd' d='M1.646 4.646a.5.5 0 0 1
.708 0L8 10.29315.646-5.647a.5.5 0 0 1 .708.7081-6 6a.5.5 0 0 1-.708 01-6-
6a.5.5 0 0 1 0-.708z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e");
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  background-size: 1.25rem;
  transition: transform .2s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .accordion-button::after {
    transition: none
  }
}

.accordion-button:hover {

```

```

    z-index: 2
}

.accordion-button:focus {
  z-index: 3;
  border-color: #86b7fe;
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.accordion-header {
  margin-bottom: 0
}

.accordion-item {
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .125)
}

.accordion-item:first-of-type {
  border-top-left-radius: .25rem;
  border-top-right-radius: .25rem
}

.accordion-item:first-of-type .accordion-button {
  border-top-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
  border-top-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.accordion-item:not(:first-of-type) {
  border-top: 0
}

.accordion-item:last-of-type {
  border-bottom-right-radius: .25rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem
}

.accordion-item:last-of-type .accordion-button.collapsed {
  border-bottom-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
  border-bottom-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.accordion-item:last-of-type .accordion-collapse {
  border-bottom-right-radius: .25rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem
}

.accordion-body {
  padding: 1rem 1.25rem
}

.accordion-flush .accordion-collapse {
  border-width: 0
}

.accordion-flush .accordion-item {

```

```

border-right: 0;
border-left: 0;
border-radius: 0
}

.accordion-flush .accordion-item:first-child {
border-top: 0
}

.accordion-flush .accordion-item:last-child {
border-bottom: 0
}

.accordion-flush .accordion-item .accordion-button {
border-radius: 0
}

.breadcrumb {
display: flex;
flex-wrap: wrap;
padding: 0 0;
margin-bottom: 1rem;
list-style: none
}

.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-item {
padding-left: .5rem
}

.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-item::before {
float: left;
padding-right: .5rem;
color: #6c757d;
content: var(--bs-breadcrumb-divider, "/")
}

.breadcrumb-item.active {
color: #6c757d
}

.pagination {
display: flex;
padding-left: 0;
list-style: none
}

.page-link {
position: relative;
display: block;
color: #0d6efd;
text-decoration: none;
background-color: #fff;
border: 1px solid #dee2e6;
transition: color .15s ease-in-out, background-color .15s ease-in-out,
border-color .15s ease-in-out, box-shadow .15s ease-in-out
}

```

```

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .page-link {
    transition: none
  }
}

.page-link:hover {
  z-index: 2;
  color: #0a58ca;
  background-color: #e9ecef;
  border-color: #dee2e6
}

.page-link:focus {
  z-index: 3;
  color: #0a58ca;
  background-color: #e9ecef;
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25)
}

.page-item:not(:first-child) .page-link {
  margin-left: -1px
}

.page-item.active .page-link {
  z-index: 3;
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0d6efd;
  border-color: #0d6efd
}

.page-item.disabled .page-link {
  color: #6c757d;
  pointer-events: none;
  background-color: #fff;
  border-color: #dee2e6
}

.page-link {
  padding: .375rem .75rem
}

.page-item:first-child .page-link {
  border-top-left-radius: .25rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem
}

.page-item:last-child .page-link {
  border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
  border-bottom-right-radius: .25rem
}

.pagination-lg .page-link {
  padding: .75rem 1.5rem;
  font-size: 1.25rem
}

```

```

.pagination-lg .page-item:first-child .page-link {
  border-top-left-radius: .3rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: .3rem
}

.pagination-lg .page-item:last-child .page-link {
  border-top-right-radius: .3rem;
  border-bottom-right-radius: .3rem
}

.pagination-sm .page-link {
  padding: .25rem .5rem;
  font-size: .875rem
}

.pagination-sm .page-item:first-child .page-link {
  border-top-left-radius: .2rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: .2rem
}

.pagination-sm .page-item:last-child .page-link {
  border-top-right-radius: .2rem;
  border-bottom-right-radius: .2rem
}

.badge {
  display: inline-block;
  padding: .35em .65em;
  font-size: .75em;
  font-weight: 700;
  line-height: 1;
  color: #fff;
  text-align: center;
  white-space: nowrap;
  vertical-align: baseline;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.badge:empty {
  display: none
}

.btn .badge {
  position: relative;
  top: -1px
}

.alert {
  position: relative;
  padding: 1rem 1rem;
  margin-bottom: 1rem;
  border: 1px solid transparent;
  border-radius: .25rem
}

.alert-heading {

```

```

    color: inherit
}

.alert-link {
    font-weight: 700
}

.alert-dismissible {
    padding-right: 3rem
}

.alert-dismissible .btn-close {
    position: absolute;
    top: 0;
    right: 0;
    z-index: 2;
    padding: 1.25rem 1rem
}

.alert-primary {
    color: #084298;
    background-color: #cfe2ff;
    border-color: #b6d4fe
}

.alert-primary .alert-link {
    color: #06357a
}

.alert-secondary {
    color: #41464b;
    background-color: #e2e3e5;
    border-color: #d3d6d8
}

.alert-secondary .alert-link {
    color: #34383c
}

.alert-success {
    color: #0f5132;
    background-color: #d1e7dd;
    border-color: #badbcc
}

.alert-success .alert-link {
    color: #0c4128
}

.alert-info {
    color: #055160;
    background-color: #cfe2ff;
    border-color: #b6d4fe
}

.alert-info .alert-link {
    color: #04414d
}

```

```

}

.alert-warning {
  color: #664d03;
  background-color: #fff3cd;
  border-color: #ffecb5
}

.alert-warning .alert-link {
  color: #523e02
}

.alert-danger {
  color: #842029;
  background-color: #f8d7da;
  border-color: #f5c2c7
}

.alert-danger .alert-link {
  color: #6a1a21
}

.alert-light {
  color: #636464;
  background-color: #fefefe;
  border-color: #fdfdfe
}

.alert-light .alert-link {
  color: #4f5050
}

.alert-dark {
  color: #141619;
  background-color: #d3d3d4;
  border-color: #bcbebf
}

.alert-dark .alert-link {
  color: #101214
}

@-webkit-keyframes progress-bar-stripes {
  0% {
    background-position-x: 1rem
  }
}

@keyframes progress-bar-stripes {
  0% {
    background-position-x: 1rem
  }
}

.progress {
  display: flex;
  height: 1rem;

```

```

    overflow: hidden;
    font-size: .75rem;
    background-color: #e9ecef;
    border-radius: .25rem
}

.progress-bar {
    display: flex;
    flex-direction: column;
    justify-content: center;
    overflow: hidden;
    color: #fff;
    text-align: center;
    white-space: nowrap;
    background-color: #0d6efd;
    transition: width .6s ease
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .progress-bar {
        transition: none
    }
}

.progress-bar-striped {
    background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%,
transparent 25%, transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255,
255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%, transparent);
    background-size: 1rem 1rem
}

.progress-bar-animated {
    -webkit-animation: 1s linear infinite progress-bar-stripes;
    animation: 1s linear infinite progress-bar-stripes
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .progress-bar-animated {
        -webkit-animation: none;
        animation: none
    }
}

.list-group {
    display: flex;
    flex-direction: column;
    padding-left: 0;
    margin-bottom: 0;
    border-radius: .25rem
}

.list-group-numbered {
    list-style-type: none;
    counter-reset: section
}

.list-group-numbered>li::before {

```

```

    content: counters(section, ".") ". ";
    counter-increment: section
}

.list-group-item-action {
  width: 100%;
  color: #495057;
  text-align: inherit
}

.list-group-item-action:focus,
.list-group-item-action:hover {
  z-index: 1;
  color: #495057;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #f8f9fa
}

.list-group-item-action:active {
  color: #212529;
  background-color: #e9ecef
}

.list-group-item {
  position: relative;
  display: block;
  padding: .5rem 1rem;
  color: #212529;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .125)
}

.list-group-item:first-child {
  border-top-left-radius: inherit;
  border-top-right-radius: inherit
}

.list-group-item:last-child {
  border-bottom-right-radius: inherit;
  border-bottom-left-radius: inherit
}

.list-group-item.disabled,
.list-group-item:disabled {
  color: #6c757d;
  pointer-events: none;
  background-color: #fff
}

.list-group-item.active {
  z-index: 2;
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0d6efd;
  border-color: #0d6efd
}

```

```

.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
  border-top-width: 0
}

.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
  margin-top: -1px;
  border-top-width: 1px
}

.list-group-horizontal {
  flex-direction: row
}

.list-group-horizontal>.list-group-item:first-child {
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
  border-top-right-radius: 0
}

.list-group-horizontal>.list-group-item:last-child {
  border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 0
}

.list-group-horizontal>.list-group-item.active {
  margin-top: 0
}

.list-group-horizontal>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
  border-top-width: 1px;
  border-left-width: 0
}

.list-group-horizontal>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
  margin-left: -1px;
  border-left-width: 1px
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .list-group-horizontal-sm {
    flex-direction: row
  }
  .list-group-horizontal-sm>.list-group-item:first-child {
    border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
    border-top-right-radius: 0
  }
  .list-group-horizontal-sm>.list-group-item:last-child {
    border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
    border-bottom-left-radius: 0
  }
  .list-group-horizontal-sm>.list-group-item.active {
    margin-top: 0
  }
  .list-group-horizontal-sm>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
    border-top-width: 1px;
    border-left-width: 0
  }
  .list-group-horizontal-sm>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {

```

```

        margin-left: -1px;
        border-left-width: 1px
    }
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
    .list-group-horizontal-md {
        flex-direction: row
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-md>.list-group-item:first-child {
        border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
        border-top-right-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-md>.list-group-item:last-child {
        border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
        border-bottom-left-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-md>.list-group-item.active {
        margin-top: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-md>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
        border-top-width: 1px;
        border-left-width: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-md>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
        margin-left: -1px;
        border-left-width: 1px
    }
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
    .list-group-horizontal-lg {
        flex-direction: row
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-lg>.list-group-item:first-child {
        border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
        border-top-right-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-lg>.list-group-item:last-child {
        border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
        border-bottom-left-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-lg>.list-group-item.active {
        margin-top: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-lg>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
        border-top-width: 1px;
        border-left-width: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-lg>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
        margin-left: -1px;
        border-left-width: 1px
    }
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .list-group-horizontal-xl {

```

```

        flex-direction: row
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xl>.list-group-item:first-child {
        border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
        border-top-right-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xl>.list-group-item:last-child {
        border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
        border-bottom-left-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xl>.list-group-item.active {
        margin-top: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xl>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
        border-top-width: 1px;
        border-left-width: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xl>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
        margin-left: -1px;
        border-left-width: 1px
    }
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl {
        flex-direction: row
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl>.list-group-item:first-child {
        border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem;
        border-top-right-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl>.list-group-item:last-child {
        border-top-right-radius: .25rem;
        border-bottom-left-radius: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl>.list-group-item.active {
        margin-top: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl>.list-group-item+.list-group-item {
        border-top-width: 1px;
        border-left-width: 0
    }
    .list-group-horizontal-xxl>.list-group-item+.list-group-item.active {
        margin-left: -1px;
        border-left-width: 1px
    }
}

.list-group-flush {
    border-radius: 0
}

.list-group-flush>.list-group-item {
    border-width: 0 0 1px
}

.list-group-flush>.list-group-item:last-child {

```

```
border-bottom-width: 0
}

.list-group-item-primary {
  color: #084298;
  background-color: #cfe2ff
}

.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action:focus,
.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action:hover {
  color: #084298;
  background-color: #bacbe6
}

.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action.active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #084298;
  border-color: #084298
}

.list-group-item-secondary {
  color: #41464b;
  background-color: #e2e3e5
}

.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action:focus,
.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action:hover {
  color: #41464b;
  background-color: #cbccce
}

.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action.active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #41464b;
  border-color: #41464b
}

.list-group-item-success {
  color: #0f5132;
  background-color: #d1e7dd
}

.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action:focus,
.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action:hover {
  color: #0f5132;
  background-color: #bcd0c7
}

.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action.active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #0f5132;
  border-color: #0f5132
}

.list-group-item-info {
  color: #055160;
  background-color: #c9f4fc
}
```

```
}  
  
.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action:focus,  
.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action:hover {  
  color: #055160;  
  background-color: #badce3  
}  
  
.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action.active {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #055160;  
  border-color: #055160  
}  
  
.list-group-item-warning {  
  color: #664d03;  
  background-color: #fff3cd  
}  
  
.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action:focus,  
.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action:hover {  
  color: #664d03;  
  background-color: #e6dbb9  
}  
  
.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action.active {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #664d03;  
  border-color: #664d03  
}  
  
.list-group-item-danger {  
  color: #842029;  
  background-color: #f8d7da  
}  
  
.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action:focus,  
.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action:hover {  
  color: #842029;  
  background-color: #dfc2c4  
}  
  
.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action.active {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #842029;  
  border-color: #842029  
}  
  
.list-group-item-light {  
  color: #636464;  
  background-color: #fefefe  
}  
  
.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:focus,  
.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:hover {  
  color: #636464;  
  background-color: #e5e5e5
```

```

}

.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action.active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #636464;
  border-color: #636464
}

.list-group-item-dark {
  color: #141619;
  background-color: #d3d3d4
}

.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:focus,
.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action: hover {
  color: #141619;
  background-color: #bebebf
}

.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action.active {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #141619;
  border-color: #141619
}

.btn-close {
  box-sizing: content-box;
  width: 1em;
  height: 1em;
  padding: .25em .25em;
  color: #000;
  background: transparent url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'
fill='%23000'%3e%3cpath d='M.293.293a1 1 0 011.414 0L8 6.586 14.293.293a1 1 0
111.414 1.414L9.414 8.16.293 6.293a1 1 0 01-1.414 1.414L8 9.414-6.293 6.293a1
1 0 01-1.414-1.414L6.586 8 .293 1.707a1 1 0 010-1.414z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
  center/1em auto no-repeat;
  border: 0;
  border-radius: .25rem;
  opacity: .5
}

.btn-close: hover {
  color: #000;
  text-decoration: none;
  opacity: .75
}

.btn-close: focus {
  outline: 0;
  box-shadow: 0 0 0 .25rem rgba(13, 110, 253, .25);
  opacity: 1
}

.btn-close.disabled,
.btn-close: disabled {
  pointer-events: none;
}

```

```

    -webkit-user-select: none;
    -moz-user-select: none;
    user-select: none;
    opacity: .25
}

.btn-close-white {
    filter: invert(1) grayscale(100%) brightness(200%)
}

.toast {
    width: 350px;
    max-width: 100%;
    font-size: .875rem;
    pointer-events: auto;
    background-color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .85);
    background-clip: padding-box;
    border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .1);
    box-shadow: 0 .5rem 1rem rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
    border-radius: .25rem
}

.toast.showing {
    opacity: 0
}

.toast:not(.show) {
    display: none
}

.toast-container {
    width: -webkit-max-content;
    width: -moz-max-content;
    width: max-content;
    max-width: 100%;
    pointer-events: none
}

.toast-container>:not(:last-child) {
    margin-bottom: .75rem
}

.toast-header {
    display: flex;
    align-items: center;
    padding: .5rem .75rem;
    color: #6c757d;
    background-color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .85);
    background-clip: padding-box;
    border-bottom: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
    border-top-left-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px);
    border-top-right-radius: calc(.25rem - 1px)
}

.toast-header .btn-close {
    margin-right: -.375rem;
    margin-left: .75rem
}

```

```

}

.toast-body {
  padding: .75rem;
  word-wrap: break-word
}

.modal {
  position: fixed;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1055;
  display: none;
  width: 100%;
  height: 100%;
  overflow-x: hidden;
  overflow-y: auto;
  outline: 0
}

.modal-dialog {
  position: relative;
  width: auto;
  margin: .5rem;
  pointer-events: none
}

.modal.fade .modal-dialog {
  transition: transform .3s ease-out;
  transform: translate(0, -50px)
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .modal.fade .modal-dialog {
    transition: none
  }
}

.modal.show .modal-dialog {
  transform: none
}

.modal.modal-static .modal-dialog {
  transform: scale(1.02)
}

.modal-dialog-scrollable {
  height: calc(100% - 1rem)
}

.modal-dialog-scrollable .modal-content {
  max-height: 100%;
  overflow: hidden
}

.modal-dialog-scrollable .modal-body {
  overflow-y: auto
}

```

```

}

.modal-dialog-centered {
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  min-height: calc(100% - 1rem)
}

.modal-content {
  position: relative;
  display: flex;
  flex-direction: column;
  width: 100%;
  pointer-events: auto;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-clip: padding-box;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  border-radius: .3rem;
  outline: 0
}

.modal-backdrop {
  position: fixed;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1050;
  width: 100vw;
  height: 100vh;
  background-color: #000
}

.modal-backdrop.fade {
  opacity: 0
}

.modal-backdrop.show {
  opacity: .5
}

.modal-header {
  display: flex;
  flex-shrink: 0;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: space-between;
  padding: 1rem 1rem;
  border-bottom: 1px solid #dee2e6;
  border-top-left-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px);
  border-top-right-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px)
}

.modal-header .btn-close {
  padding: .5rem .5rem;
  margin: -.5rem -.5rem -.5rem auto
}

.modal-title {
  margin-bottom: 0;

```

```

    line-height: 1.5
  }

.modal-body {
  position: relative;
  flex: 1 1 auto;
  padding: 1rem
}

.modal-footer {
  display: flex;
  flex-wrap: wrap;
  flex-shrink: 0;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: flex-end;
  padding: .75rem;
  border-top: 1px solid #dee2e6;
  border-bottom-right-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px);
  border-bottom-left-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px)
}

.modal-footer>* {
  margin: .25rem
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .modal-dialog {
    max-width: 500px;
    margin: 1.75rem auto
  }
  .modal-dialog-scrollable {
    height: calc(100% - 3.5rem)
  }
  .modal-dialog-centered {
    min-height: calc(100% - 3.5rem)
  }
  .modal-sm {
    max-width: 300px
  }
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
  .modal-lg,
  .modal-xl {
    max-width: 800px
  }
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .modal-xl {
    max-width: 1140px
  }
}

.modal-fullscreen {
  width: 100vw;
  max-width: none;
}

```

```

    height: 100%;
    margin: 0
}

.modal-fullscreen .modal-content {
    height: 100%;
    border: 0;
    border-radius: 0
}

.modal-fullscreen .modal-header {
    border-radius: 0
}

.modal-fullscreen .modal-body {
    overflow-y: auto
}

.modal-fullscreen .modal-footer {
    border-radius: 0
}

@media (max-width:575.98px) {
    .modal-fullscreen-sm-down {
        width: 100vw;
        max-width: none;
        height: 100%;
        margin: 0
    }
    .modal-fullscreen-sm-down .modal-content {
        height: 100%;
        border: 0;
        border-radius: 0
    }
    .modal-fullscreen-sm-down .modal-header {
        border-radius: 0
    }
    .modal-fullscreen-sm-down .modal-body {
        overflow-y: auto
    }
    .modal-fullscreen-sm-down .modal-footer {
        border-radius: 0
    }
}

@media (max-width:767.98px) {
    .modal-fullscreen-md-down {
        width: 100vw;
        max-width: none;
        height: 100%;
        margin: 0
    }
    .modal-fullscreen-md-down .modal-content {
        height: 100%;
        border: 0;
        border-radius: 0
    }
}

```

```

.modal-fullscreen-md-down .modal-header {
  border-radius: 0
}
.modal-fullscreen-md-down .modal-body {
  overflow-y: auto
}
.modal-fullscreen-md-down .modal-footer {
  border-radius: 0
}
}

@media (max-width:991.98px) {
  .modal-fullscreen-lg-down {
    width: 100vw;
    max-width: none;
    height: 100%;
    margin: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-lg-down .modal-content {
    height: 100%;
    border: 0;
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-lg-down .modal-header {
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-lg-down .modal-body {
    overflow-y: auto
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-lg-down .modal-footer {
    border-radius: 0
  }
}

@media (max-width:1199.98px) {
  .modal-fullscreen-xl-down {
    width: 100vw;
    max-width: none;
    height: 100%;
    margin: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xl-down .modal-content {
    height: 100%;
    border: 0;
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xl-down .modal-header {
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xl-down .modal-body {
    overflow-y: auto
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xl-down .modal-footer {
    border-radius: 0
  }
}
}

```

```

@media (max-width:1399.98px) {
  .modal-fullscreen-xxl-down {
    width: 100vw;
    max-width: none;
    height: 100%;
    margin: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xxl-down .modal-content {
    height: 100%;
    border: 0;
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xxl-down .modal-header {
    border-radius: 0
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xxl-down .modal-body {
    overflow-y: auto
  }
  .modal-fullscreen-xxl-down .modal-footer {
    border-radius: 0
  }
}

.tooltip {
  position: absolute;
  z-index: 1080;
  display: block;
  margin: 0;
  font-family: var(--bs-font-sans-serif);
  font-style: normal;
  font-weight: 400;
  line-height: 1.5;
  text-align: left;
  text-align: start;
  text-decoration: none;
  text-shadow: none;
  text-transform: none;
  letter-spacing: normal;
  word-break: normal;
  word-spacing: normal;
  white-space: normal;
  line-break: auto;
  font-size: .875rem;
  word-wrap: break-word;
  opacity: 0
}

.tooltip.show {
  opacity: .9
}

.tooltip .tooltip-arrow {
  position: absolute;
  display: block;
  width: .8rem;
  height: .4rem
}

```

```

.tooltip .tooltip-arrow::before {
  position: absolute;
  content: "";
  border-color: transparent;
  border-style: solid
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=top],
.bs-tooltip-top {
  padding: .4rem 0
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=top] .tooltip-arrow,
.bs-tooltip-top .tooltip-arrow {
  bottom: 0
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=top] .tooltip-arrow::before,
.bs-tooltip-top .tooltip-arrow::before {
  top: -1px;
  border-width: .4rem .4rem 0;
  border-top-color: #000
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=right],
.bs-tooltip-end {
  padding: 0 .4rem
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=right] .tooltip-arrow,
.bs-tooltip-end .tooltip-arrow {
  left: 0;
  width: .4rem;
  height: .8rem
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=right] .tooltip-arrow::before,
.bs-tooltip-end .tooltip-arrow::before {
  right: -1px;
  border-width: .4rem .4rem .4rem 0;
  border-right-color: #000
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom],
.bs-tooltip-bottom {
  padding: .4rem 0
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom] .tooltip-arrow,
.bs-tooltip-bottom .tooltip-arrow {
  top: 0
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom] .tooltip-arrow::before,
.bs-tooltip-bottom .tooltip-arrow::before {
  bottom: -1px;

```

```

border-width: 0 .4rem .4rem;
border-bottom-color: #000
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=left],
.bs-tooltip-start {
padding: 0 .4rem
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=left] .tooltip-arrow,
.bs-tooltip-start .tooltip-arrow {
right: 0;
width: .4rem;
height: .8rem
}

.bs-tooltip-auto[data-popper-placement^=left] .tooltip-arrow::before,
.bs-tooltip-start .tooltip-arrow::before {
left: -1px;
border-width: .4rem 0 .4rem .4rem;
border-left-color: #000
}

.tooltip-inner {
max-width: 200px;
padding: .25rem .5rem;
color: #fff;
text-align: center;
background-color: #000;
border-radius: .25rem
}

.popover {
position: absolute;
top: 0;
left: 0;
z-index: 1070;
display: block;
max-width: 276px;
font-family: var(--bs-font-sans-serif);
font-style: normal;
font-weight: 400;
line-height: 1.5;
text-align: left;
text-align: start;
text-decoration: none;
text-shadow: none;
text-transform: none;
letter-spacing: normal;
word-break: normal;
word-spacing: normal;
white-space: normal;
line-break: auto;
font-size: .875rem;
word-wrap: break-word;
background-color: #fff;
background-clip: padding-box;

```

```

border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
border-radius: .3rem
}

.popover .popover-arrow {
  position: absolute;
  display: block;
  width: 1rem;
  height: .5rem
}

.popover .popover-arrow::after,
.popover .popover-arrow::before {
  position: absolute;
  display: block;
  content: "";
  border-color: transparent;
  border-style: solid
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=top]>.popover-arrow,
.bs-popover-top>.popover-arrow {
  bottom: calc(-.5rem - 1px)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=top]>.popover-arrow::before,
.bs-popover-top>.popover-arrow::before {
  bottom: 0;
  border-width: .5rem .5rem 0;
  border-top-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=top]>.popover-arrow::after,
.bs-popover-top>.popover-arrow::after {
  bottom: 1px;
  border-width: .5rem .5rem 0;
  border-top-color: #fff
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=right]>.popover-arrow,
.bs-popover-end>.popover-arrow {
  left: calc(-.5rem - 1px);
  width: .5rem;
  height: 1rem
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=right]>.popover-arrow::before,
.bs-popover-end>.popover-arrow::before {
  left: 0;
  border-width: .5rem .5rem .5rem 0;
  border-right-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=right]>.popover-arrow::after,
.bs-popover-end>.popover-arrow::after {
  left: 1px;
  border-width: .5rem .5rem .5rem 0;
}

```

```

border-right-color: #fff
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom]>.popover-arrow,
.bs-popover-bottom>.popover-arrow {
  top: calc(-.5rem - 1px)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom]>.popover-arrow::before,
.bs-popover-bottom>.popover-arrow::before {
  top: 0;
  border-width: 0 .5rem .5rem .5rem;
  border-bottom-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom]>.popover-arrow::after,
.bs-popover-bottom>.popover-arrow::after {
  top: 1px;
  border-width: 0 .5rem .5rem .5rem;
  border-bottom-color: #fff
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=bottom] .popover-header::before,
.bs-popover-bottom .popover-header::before {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 50%;
  display: block;
  width: 1rem;
  margin-left: -.5rem;
  content: "";
  border-bottom: 1px solid #f0f0f0
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=left]>.popover-arrow,
.bs-popover-start>.popover-arrow {
  right: calc(-.5rem - 1px);
  width: .5rem;
  height: 1rem
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=left]>.popover-arrow::before,
.bs-popover-start>.popover-arrow::before {
  right: 0;
  border-width: .5rem 0 .5rem .5rem;
  border-left-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25)
}

.bs-popover-auto[data-popper-placement^=left]>.popover-arrow::after,
.bs-popover-start>.popover-arrow::after {
  right: 1px;
  border-width: .5rem 0 .5rem .5rem;
  border-left-color: #fff
}

.popover-header {
  padding: .5rem 1rem;

```

```

margin-bottom: 0;
font-size: 1rem;
background-color: #f0f0f0;
border-bottom: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
border-top-left-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px);
border-top-right-radius: calc(.3rem - 1px)
}

.popover-header:empty {
  display: none
}

.popover-body {
  padding: 1rem 1rem;
  color: #212529
}

.carousel {
  position: relative
}

.carousel.pointer-event {
  touch-action: pan-y
}

.carousel-inner {
  position: relative;
  width: 100%;
  overflow: hidden
}

.carousel-inner::after {
  display: block;
  clear: both;
  content: ""
}

.carousel-item {
  position: relative;
  display: none;
  float: left;
  width: 100%;
  margin-right: -100%;
  -webkit-backface-visibility: hidden;
  backface-visibility: hidden;
  transition: transform .6s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .carousel-item {
    transition: none
  }
}

.carousel-item-next,
.carousel-item-prev,
.carousel-item.active {

```

```

    display: block
}

.active.carousel-item-end,
.carousel-item-next:not(.carousel-item-start) {
    transform: translateX(100%)
}

.active.carousel-item-start,
.carousel-item-prev:not(.carousel-item-end) {
    transform: translateX(-100%)
}

.carousel-fade .carousel-item {
    opacity: 0;
    transition-property: opacity;
    transform: none
}

.carousel-fade .carousel-item-next.carousel-item-start,
.carousel-fade .carousel-item-prev.carousel-item-end,
.carousel-fade .carousel-item.active {
    z-index: 1;
    opacity: 1
}

.carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-end,
.carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-start {
    z-index: 0;
    opacity: 0;
    transition: opacity 0s .6s
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
    .carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-end,
    .carousel-fade .active.carousel-item-start {
        transition: none
    }
}

.carousel-control-next,
.carousel-control-prev {
    position: absolute;
    top: 0;
    bottom: 0;
    z-index: 1;
    display: flex;
    align-items: center;
    justify-content: center;
    width: 15%;
    padding: 0;
    color: #fff;
    text-align: center;
    background: 0 0;
    border: 0;
    opacity: .5;
    transition: opacity .15s ease
}

```

```

}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .carousel-control-next,
  .carousel-control-prev {
    transition: none
  }
}

.carousel-control-next:focus,
.carousel-control-next:hover,
.carousel-control-prev:focus,
.carousel-control-prev:hover {
  color: #fff;
  text-decoration: none;
  outline: 0;
  opacity: .9
}

.carousel-control-prev {
  left: 0
}

.carousel-control-next {
  right: 0
}

.carousel-control-next-icon,
.carousel-control-prev-icon {
  display: inline-block;
  width: 2rem;
  height: 2rem;
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  background-position: 50%;
  background-size: 100% 100%
}

.carousel-control-prev-icon {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'
fill='%23fff'%3e%3cpath d='M11.354 1.646a.5.5 0 0 1 0 .708L5.707 8.15.647
5.646a.5.5 0 0 1-.708.708l-6-6a.5.5 0 0 1 0-.708l6-6a.5.5 0 0 1 .708
0z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.carousel-control-next-icon {
  background-image: url("data:image/svg+xml,%3csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 16 16'
fill='%23fff'%3e%3cpath d='M4.646 1.646a.5.5 0 0 1 .708 0l6-6a.5.5 0 0 1 0
.708l-6 6a.5.5 0 0 1-.708-.708L10.293 8 4.646 2.354a.5.5 0 0 1 0-
.708z'/%3e%3c/svg%3e")
}

.carousel-indicators {
  position: absolute;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;

```

```

left: 0;
z-index: 2;
display: flex;
justify-content: center;
padding: 0;
margin-right: 15%;
margin-bottom: 1rem;
margin-left: 15%;
list-style: none
}

.carousel-indicators [data-bs-target] {
  box-sizing: content-box;
  flex: 0 1 auto;
  width: 30px;
  height: 3px;
  padding: 0;
  margin-right: 3px;
  margin-left: 3px;
  text-indent: -999px;
  cursor: pointer;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-clip: padding-box;
  border: 0;
  border-top: 10px solid transparent;
  border-bottom: 10px solid transparent;
  opacity: .5;
  transition: opacity .6s ease
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .carousel-indicators [data-bs-target] {
    transition: none
  }
}

.carousel-indicators .active {
  opacity: 1
}

.carousel-caption {
  position: absolute;
  right: 15%;
  bottom: 1.25rem;
  left: 15%;
  padding-top: 1.25rem;
  padding-bottom: 1.25rem;
  color: #fff;
  text-align: center
}

.carousel-dark .carousel-control-next-icon,
.carousel-dark .carousel-control-prev-icon {
  filter: invert(1) grayscale(100)
}

.carousel-dark .carousel-indicators [data-bs-target] {

```

```

    background-color: #000
  }

.carousel-dark .carousel-caption {
  color: #000
}

@-webkit-keyframes spinner-border {
  to {
    transform: rotate(360deg)
  }
}

@keyframes spinner-border {
  to {
    transform: rotate(360deg)
  }
}

.spinner-border {
  display: inline-block;
  width: 2rem;
  height: 2rem;
  vertical-align: -.125em;
  border: .25em solid currentColor;
  border-right-color: transparent;
  border-radius: 50%;
  -webkit-animation: .75s linear infinite spinner-border;
  animation: .75s linear infinite spinner-border
}

.spinner-border-sm {
  width: 1rem;
  height: 1rem;
  border-width: .2em
}

@-webkit-keyframes spinner-grow {
  0% {
    transform: scale(0)
  }
  50% {
    opacity: 1;
    transform: none
  }
}

@keyframes spinner-grow {
  0% {
    transform: scale(0)
  }
  50% {
    opacity: 1;
    transform: none
  }
}

```

```

.spinner-grow {
  display: inline-block;
  width: 2rem;
  height: 2rem;
  vertical-align: -.125em;
  background-color: currentColor;
  border-radius: 50%;
  opacity: 0;
  -webkit-animation: .75s linear infinite spinner-grow;
  animation: .75s linear infinite spinner-grow
}

.spinner-grow-sm {
  width: 1rem;
  height: 1rem
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .spinner-border,
  .spinner-grow {
    -webkit-animation-duration: 1.5s;
    animation-duration: 1.5s
  }
}

.offcanvas {
  position: fixed;
  bottom: 0;
  z-index: 1045;
  display: flex;
  flex-direction: column;
  max-width: 100%;
  visibility: hidden;
  background-color: #fff;
  background-clip: padding-box;
  outline: 0;
  transition: transform .3s ease-in-out
}

@media (prefers-reduced-motion:reduce) {
  .offcanvas {
    transition: none
  }
}

.offcanvas-backdrop {
  position: fixed;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1040;
  width: 100vw;
  height: 100vh;
  background-color: #000
}

.offcanvas-backdrop.fade {
  opacity: 0
}

```

```

}

.offcanvas-backdrop.show {
  opacity: .5
}

.offcanvas-header {
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: space-between;
  padding: 1rem 1rem
}

.offcanvas-header .btn-close {
  padding: .5rem .5rem;
  margin-top: -.5rem;
  margin-right: -.5rem;
  margin-bottom: -.5rem
}

.offcanvas-title {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  line-height: 1.5
}

.offcanvas-body {
  flex-grow: 1;
  padding: 1rem 1rem;
  overflow-y: auto
}

.offcanvas-start {
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  width: 400px;
  border-right: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  transform: translateX(-100%)
}

.offcanvas-end {
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  width: 400px;
  border-left: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  transform: translateX(100%)
}

.offcanvas-top {
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  left: 0;
  height: 30vh;
  max-height: 100%;
  border-bottom: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  transform: translateY(-100%)
}

```

```

.offcanvas-bottom {
  right: 0;
  left: 0;
  height: 30vh;
  max-height: 100%;
  border-top: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  transform: translateY(100%)
}

.offcanvas.show {
  transform: none
}

.placeholder {
  display: inline-block;
  min-height: 1em;
  vertical-align: middle;
  cursor: wait;
  background-color: currentColor;
  opacity: .5
}

.placeholder.btn::before {
  display: inline-block;
  content: ""
}

.placeholder-xs {
  min-height: .6em
}

.placeholder-sm {
  min-height: .8em
}

.placeholder-lg {
  min-height: 1.2em
}

.placeholder-glow .placeholder {
  -webkit-animation: placeholder-glow 2s ease-in-out infinite;
  animation: placeholder-glow 2s ease-in-out infinite
}

@-webkit-keyframes placeholder-glow {
  50% {
    opacity: .2
  }
}

@keyframes placeholder-glow {
  50% {
    opacity: .2
  }
}

.placeholder-wave {

```

```

    -webkit-mask-image: linear-gradient(130deg, #000 55%, rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.8)
75%, #000 95%);
    mask-image: linear-gradient(130deg, #000 55%, rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.8) 75%,
#000 95%);
    -webkit-mask-size: 200% 100%;
    mask-size: 200% 100%;
    -webkit-animation: placeholder-wave 2s linear infinite;
    animation: placeholder-wave 2s linear infinite
}

@-webkit-keyframes placeholder-wave {
  100% {
    -webkit-mask-position: -200% 0%;
    mask-position: -200% 0%
  }
}

@keyframes placeholder-wave {
  100% {
    -webkit-mask-position: -200% 0%;
    mask-position: -200% 0%
  }
}

.clearfix::after {
  display: block;
  clear: both;
  content: ""
}

.link-primary {
  color: #0d6efd
}

.link-primary:focus,
.link-primary:hover {
  color: #0a58ca
}

.link-secondary {
  color: #6c757d
}

.link-secondary:focus,
.link-secondary:hover {
  color: #565e64
}

.link-success {
  color: #198754
}

.link-success:focus,
.link-success:hover {
  color: #146c43
}

```

```
.link-info {
  color: #0dcaf0
}

.link-info:focus,
.link-info:hover {
  color: #3dd5f3
}

.link-warning {
  color: #ffc107
}

.link-warning:focus,
.link-warning:hover {
  color: #ffcd39
}

.link-danger {
  color: #dc3545
}

.link-danger:focus,
.link-danger:hover {
  color: #b02a37
}

.link-light {
  color: #f8f9fa
}

.link-light:focus,
.link-light:hover {
  color: #f9fafb
}

.link-dark {
  color: #212529
}

.link-dark:focus,
.link-dark:hover {
  color: #1a1e21
}

.ratio {
  position: relative;
  width: 100%
}

.ratio::before {
  display: block;
  padding-top: var(--bs-aspect-ratio);
  content: ""
}

.ratio>* {
```

```

position: absolute;
top: 0;
left: 0;
width: 100%;
height: 100%
}

.ratio-1x1 {
  --bs-aspect-ratio: 100%
}

.ratio-4x3 {
  --bs-aspect-ratio: 75%
}

.ratio-16x9 {
  --bs-aspect-ratio: 56.25%
}

.ratio-21x9 {
  --bs-aspect-ratio: 42.8571428571%
}

.fixed-top {
  position: fixed;
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1030
}

.fixed-bottom {
  position: fixed;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1030
}

.sticky-top {
  position: -webkit-sticky;
  position: sticky;
  top: 0;
  z-index: 1020
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .sticky-sm-top {
    position: -webkit-sticky;
    position: sticky;
    top: 0;
    z-index: 1020
  }
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
  .sticky-md-top {

```

```

        position: -webkit-sticky;
        position: sticky;
        top: 0;
        z-index: 1020
    }
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
    .sticky-lg-top {
        position: -webkit-sticky;
        position: sticky;
        top: 0;
        z-index: 1020
    }
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
    .sticky-xl-top {
        position: -webkit-sticky;
        position: sticky;
        top: 0;
        z-index: 1020
    }
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
    .sticky-xxl-top {
        position: -webkit-sticky;
        position: sticky;
        top: 0;
        z-index: 1020
    }
}

.hstack {
    display: flex;
    flex-direction: row;
    align-items: center;
    align-self: stretch
}

.vstack {
    display: flex;
    flex: 1 1 auto;
    flex-direction: column;
    align-self: stretch
}

.visually-hidden,
.visually-hidden-focusable:not(:focus):not(:focus-within) {
    position: absolute!important;
    width: 1px!important;
    height: 1px!important;
    padding: 0!important;
    margin: -1px!important;
    overflow: hidden!important;
    clip: rect(0, 0, 0, 0)!important;
}

```

```
white-space: nowrap!important;
border: 0!important
}

.stretched-link::after {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1;
  content: ""
}

.text-truncate {
  overflow: hidden;
  text-overflow: ellipsis;
  white-space: nowrap
}

.vr {
  display: inline-block;
  align-self: stretch;
  width: 1px;
  min-height: 1em;
  background-color: currentColor;
  opacity: .25
}

.align-baseline {
  vertical-align: baseline!important
}

.align-top {
  vertical-align: top!important
}

.align-middle {
  vertical-align: middle!important
}

.align-bottom {
  vertical-align: bottom!important
}

.align-text-bottom {
  vertical-align: text-bottom!important
}

.align-text-top {
  vertical-align: text-top!important
}

.float-start {
  float: left!important
}
```

```
.float-end {
  float: right!important
}

.float-none {
  float: none!important
}

.opacity-0 {
  opacity: 0!important
}

.opacity-25 {
  opacity: .25!important
}

.opacity-50 {
  opacity: .5!important
}

.opacity-75 {
  opacity: .75!important
}

.opacity-100 {
  opacity: 1!important
}

.overflow-auto {
  overflow: auto!important
}

.overflow-hidden {
  overflow: hidden!important
}

.overflow-visible {
  overflow: visible!important
}

.overflow-scroll {
  overflow: scroll!important
}

.d-inline {
  display: inline!important
}

.d-inline-block {
  display: inline-block!important
}

.d-block {
  display: block!important
}

.d-grid {
```

```
    display: grid!important
  }

.d-table {
  display: table!important
}

.d-table-row {
  display: table-row!important
}

.d-table-cell {
  display: table-cell!important
}

.d-flex {
  display: flex!important
}

.d-inline-flex {
  display: inline-flex!important
}

.d-none {
  display: none!important
}

.shadow {
  box-shadow: 0 .5rem 1rem rgba(0, 0, 0, .15)!important
}

.shadow-sm {
  box-shadow: 0 .125rem .25rem rgba(0, 0, 0, .075)!important
}

.shadow-lg {
  box-shadow: 0 1rem 3rem rgba(0, 0, 0, .175)!important
}

.shadow-none {
  box-shadow: none!important
}

.position-static {
  position: static!important
}

.position-relative {
  position: relative!important
}

.position-absolute {
  position: absolute!important
}

.position-fixed {
  position: fixed!important
}
```

```
}  
  
.position-sticky {  
  position: -webkit-sticky!important;  
  position: sticky!important  
}  
  
.top-0 {  
  top: 0!important  
}  
  
.top-50 {  
  top: 50%!important  
}  
  
.top-100 {  
  top: 100%!important  
}  
  
.bottom-0 {  
  bottom: 0!important  
}  
  
.bottom-50 {  
  bottom: 50%!important  
}  
  
.bottom-100 {  
  bottom: 100%!important  
}  
  
.start-0 {  
  left: 0!important  
}  
  
.start-50 {  
  left: 50%!important  
}  
  
.start-100 {  
  left: 100%!important  
}  
  
.end-0 {  
  right: 0!important  
}  
  
.end-50 {  
  right: 50%!important  
}  
  
.end-100 {  
  right: 100%!important  
}  
  
.translate-middle {  
  transform: translate(-50%, -50%)!important  
}
```

```
}  
  
.translate-middle-x {  
  transform: translateX(-50%)!important  
}  
  
.translate-middle-y {  
  transform: translateY(-50%)!important  
}  
  
.border {  
  border: 1px solid #dee2e6!important  
}  
  
.border-0 {  
  border: 0!important  
}  
  
.border-top {  
  border-top: 1px solid #dee2e6!important  
}  
  
.border-top-0 {  
  border-top: 0!important  
}  
  
.border-end {  
  border-right: 1px solid #dee2e6!important  
}  
  
.border-end-0 {  
  border-right: 0!important  
}  
  
.border-bottom {  
  border-bottom: 1px solid #dee2e6!important  
}  
  
.border-bottom-0 {  
  border-bottom: 0!important  
}  
  
.border-start {  
  border-left: 1px solid #dee2e6!important  
}  
  
.border-start-0 {  
  border-left: 0!important  
}  
  
.border-primary {  
  border-color: #0d6efd!important  
}  
  
.border-secondary {  
  border-color: #6c757d!important  
}  
}
```

```
.border-success {
  border-color: #198754!important
}

.border-info {
  border-color: #0dcaf0!important
}

.border-warning {
  border-color: #ffc107!important
}

.border-danger {
  border-color: #dc3545!important
}

.border-light {
  border-color: #f8f9fa!important
}

.border-dark {
  border-color: #212529!important
}

.border-white {
  border-color: #fff!important
}

.border-1 {
  border-width: 1px!important
}

.border-2 {
  border-width: 2px!important
}

.border-3 {
  border-width: 3px!important
}

.border-4 {
  border-width: 4px!important
}

.border-5 {
  border-width: 5px!important
}

.w-25 {
  width: 25%!important
}

.w-50 {
  width: 50%!important
}
```

```
.w-75 {
  width: 75%!important
}

.w-100 {
  width: 100%!important
}

.w-auto {
  width: auto!important
}

.mw-100 {
  max-width: 100%!important
}

.vw-100 {
  width: 100vw!important
}

.min-vw-100 {
  min-width: 100vw!important
}

.h-25 {
  height: 25%!important
}

.h-50 {
  height: 50%!important
}

.h-75 {
  height: 75%!important
}

.h-100 {
  height: 100%!important
}

.h-auto {
  height: auto!important
}

.mh-100 {
  max-height: 100%!important
}

.vh-100 {
  height: 100vh!important
}

.min-vh-100 {
  min-height: 100vh!important
}

.flex-fill {
```

```
    flex: 1 1 auto!important
  }

  .flex-row {
    flex-direction: row!important
  }

  .flex-column {
    flex-direction: column!important
  }

  .flex-row-reverse {
    flex-direction: row-reverse!important
  }

  .flex-column-reverse {
    flex-direction: column-reverse!important
  }

  .flex-grow-0 {
    flex-grow: 0!important
  }

  .flex-grow-1 {
    flex-grow: 1!important
  }

  .flex-shrink-0 {
    flex-shrink: 0!important
  }

  .flex-shrink-1 {
    flex-shrink: 1!important
  }

  .flex-wrap {
    flex-wrap: wrap!important
  }

  .flex-nowrap {
    flex-wrap: nowrap!important
  }

  .flex-wrap-reverse {
    flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
  }

  .gap-0 {
    gap: 0!important
  }

  .gap-1 {
    gap: .25rem!important
  }

  .gap-2 {
    gap: .5rem!important
  }
}
```

```
}  
  
.gap-3 {  
  gap: 1rem!important  
}  
  
.gap-4 {  
  gap: 1.5rem!important  
}  
  
.gap-5 {  
  gap: 3rem!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-start {  
  justify-content: flex-start!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-end {  
  justify-content: flex-end!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-center {  
  justify-content: center!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-between {  
  justify-content: space-between!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-around {  
  justify-content: space-around!important  
}  
  
.justify-content-evenly {  
  justify-content: space-evenly!important  
}  
  
.align-items-start {  
  align-items: flex-start!important  
}  
  
.align-items-end {  
  align-items: flex-end!important  
}  
  
.align-items-center {  
  align-items: center!important  
}  
  
.align-items-baseline {  
  align-items: baseline!important  
}  
  
.align-items-stretch {  
  align-items: stretch!important  
}
```

```
.align-content-start {
  align-content: flex-start!important
}

.align-content-end {
  align-content: flex-end!important
}

.align-content-center {
  align-content: center!important
}

.align-content-between {
  align-content: space-between!important
}

.align-content-around {
  align-content: space-around!important
}

.align-content-stretch {
  align-content: stretch!important
}

.align-self-auto {
  align-self: auto!important
}

.align-self-start {
  align-self: flex-start!important
}

.align-self-end {
  align-self: flex-end!important
}

.align-self-center {
  align-self: center!important
}

.align-self-baseline {
  align-self: baseline!important
}

.align-self-stretch {
  align-self: stretch!important
}

.order-first {
  order: -1!important
}

.order-0 {
  order: 0!important
}
```

```
.order-1 {
  order: 1!important
}

.order-2 {
  order: 2!important
}

.order-3 {
  order: 3!important
}

.order-4 {
  order: 4!important
}

.order-5 {
  order: 5!important
}

.order-last {
  order: 6!important
}

.m-0 {
  margin: 0!important
}

.m-1 {
  margin: .25rem!important
}

.m-2 {
  margin: .5rem!important
}

.m-3 {
  margin: 1rem!important
}

.m-4 {
  margin: 1.5rem!important
}

.m-5 {
  margin: 3rem!important
}

.m-auto {
  margin: auto!important
}

.mx-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important;
  margin-left: 0!important
}
```

```
.mx-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important;
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}

.mx-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important;
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}

.mx-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important;
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}

.mx-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}

.mx-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important;
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}

.mx-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important;
  margin-left: auto!important
}

.my-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important;
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}

.my-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}

.my-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}

.my-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}

.my-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}

.my-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important;
```

```
margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}

.my-auto {
margin-top: auto!important;
margin-bottom: auto!important
}

.mt-0 {
margin-top: 0!important
}

.mt-1 {
margin-top: .25rem!important
}

.mt-2 {
margin-top: .5rem!important
}

.mt-3 {
margin-top: 1rem!important
}

.mt-4 {
margin-top: 1.5rem!important
}

.mt-5 {
margin-top: 3rem!important
}

.mt-auto {
margin-top: auto!important
}

.me-0 {
margin-right: 0!important
}

.me-1 {
margin-right: .25rem!important
}

.me-2 {
margin-right: .5rem!important
}

.me-3 {
margin-right: 1rem!important
}

.me-4 {
margin-right: 1.5rem!important
}

.me-5 {
```

```
    margin-right: 3rem!important
  }

.me-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important
}

.mb-0 {
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}

.mb-1 {
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}

.mb-2 {
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}

.mb-3 {
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}

.mb-4 {
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}

.mb-5 {
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}

.mb-auto {
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}

.ms-0 {
  margin-left: 0!important
}

.ms-1 {
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}

.ms-2 {
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}

.ms-3 {
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}

.ms-4 {
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}

.ms-5 {
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
```

```
}  
  
.ms-auto {  
  margin-left: auto!important  
}  
  
.p-0 {  
  padding: 0!important  
}  
  
.p-1 {  
  padding: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.p-2 {  
  padding: .5rem!important  
}  
  
.p-3 {  
  padding: 1rem!important  
}  
  
.p-4 {  
  padding: 1.5rem!important  
}  
  
.p-5 {  
  padding: 3rem!important  
}  
  
.px-0 {  
  padding-right: 0!important;  
  padding-left: 0!important  
}  
  
.px-1 {  
  padding-right: .25rem!important;  
  padding-left: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.px-2 {  
  padding-right: .5rem!important;  
  padding-left: .5rem!important  
}  
  
.px-3 {  
  padding-right: 1rem!important;  
  padding-left: 1rem!important  
}  
  
.px-4 {  
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important;  
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important  
}  
  
.px-5 {  
  padding-right: 3rem!important;  
}
```

```
padding-left: 3rem!important
}

.py-0 {
padding-top: 0!important;
padding-bottom: 0!important
}

.py-1 {
padding-top: .25rem!important;
padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}

.py-2 {
padding-top: .5rem!important;
padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}

.py-3 {
padding-top: 1rem!important;
padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}

.py-4 {
padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}

.py-5 {
padding-top: 3rem!important;
padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}

.pt-0 {
padding-top: 0!important
}

.pt-1 {
padding-top: .25rem!important
}

.pt-2 {
padding-top: .5rem!important
}

.pt-3 {
padding-top: 1rem!important
}

.pt-4 {
padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}

.pt-5 {
padding-top: 3rem!important
}
```

```
.pe-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}

.pe-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}

.pe-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}

.pe-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important
}

.pe-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important
}

.pe-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important
}

.pb-0 {
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}

.pb-1 {
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}

.pb-2 {
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}

.pb-3 {
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}

.pb-4 {
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}

.pb-5 {
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}

.ps-0 {
  padding-left: 0!important
}

.ps-1 {
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}

.ps-2 {
```

```
padding-left: .5rem!important
}

.ps-3 {
padding-left: 1rem!important
}

.ps-4 {
padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}

.ps-5 {
padding-left: 3rem!important
}

.font-monospace {
font-family: var(--bs-font-monospace)!important
}

.fs-1 {
font-size: calc(1.375rem + 1.5vw)!important
}

.fs-2 {
font-size: calc(1.325rem + .9vw)!important
}

.fs-3 {
font-size: calc(1.3rem + .6vw)!important
}

.fs-4 {
font-size: calc(1.275rem + .3vw)!important
}

.fs-5 {
font-size: 1.25rem!important
}

.fs-6 {
font-size: 1rem!important
}

.fst-italic {
font-style: italic!important
}

.fst-normal {
font-style: normal!important
}

.fw-light {
font-weight: 300!important
}

.fw-lighter {
font-weight: lighter!important
}
```

```
}  
  
.fw-normal {  
  font-weight: 400!important  
}  
  
.fw-bold {  
  font-weight: 700!important  
}  
  
.fw-bolder {  
  font-weight: bolder!important  
}  
  
.lh-1 {  
  line-height: 1!important  
}  
  
.lh-sm {  
  line-height: 1.25!important  
}  
  
.lh-base {  
  line-height: 1.5!important  
}  
  
.lh-lg {  
  line-height: 2!important  
}  
  
.text-start {  
  text-align: left!important  
}  
  
.text-end {  
  text-align: right!important  
}  
  
.text-center {  
  text-align: center!important  
}  
  
.text-decoration-none {  
  text-decoration: none!important  
}  
  
.text-decoration-underline {  
  text-decoration: underline!important  
}  
  
.text-decoration-line-through {  
  text-decoration: line-through!important  
}  
  
.text-lowercase {  
  text-transform: lowercase!important  
}  
}
```

```
.text-uppercase {
  text-transform: uppercase!important
}

.text-capitalize {
  text-transform: capitalize!important
}

.text-wrap {
  white-space: normal!important
}

.text-nowrap {
  white-space: nowrap!important
}

.text-break {
  word-wrap: break-word!important;
  word-break: break-word!important
}

.text-primary {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-primary-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-secondary {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-secondary-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-success {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-success-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-info {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-info-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-warning {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-warning-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-danger {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-danger-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-light {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-light-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}
```

```
.text-dark {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-dark-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-black {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-black-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-white {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-white-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-body {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(var(--bs-body-color-rgb), var(--bs-text-opacity))!important
}

.text-muted {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: #6c757d!important
}

.text-black-50 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .5)!important
}

.text-white-50 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: rgba(255, 255, 255, .5)!important
}

.text-reset {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1;
  color: inherit!important
}

.text-opacity-25 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 0.25
}

.text-opacity-50 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 0.5
}

.text-opacity-75 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 0.75
}

.text-opacity-100 {
  --bs-text-opacity: 1
}

.bg-primary {
```

```

    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-primary-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-secondary {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-secondary-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-success {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-success-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-info {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-info-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-warning {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-warning-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-danger {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-danger-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-light {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-light-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-dark {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-dark-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-black {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-black-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-white {
    --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
    background-color: rgba(var(--bs-white-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

```

```

}

.bg-body {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
  background-color: rgba(var(--bs-body-bg-rgb), var(--bs-bg-
opacity))!important
}

.bg-transparent {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 1;
  background-color: transparent!important
}

.bg-opacity-10 {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 0.1
}

.bg-opacity-25 {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 0.25
}

.bg-opacity-50 {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 0.5
}

.bg-opacity-75 {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 0.75
}

.bg-opacity-100 {
  --bs-bg-opacity: 1
}

.bg-gradient {
  background-image: var(--bs-gradient)!important
}

.user-select-all {
  -webkit-user-select: all!important;
  -moz-user-select: all!important;
  user-select: all!important
}

.user-select-auto {
  -webkit-user-select: auto!important;
  -moz-user-select: auto!important;
  user-select: auto!important
}

.user-select-none {
  -webkit-user-select: none!important;
  -moz-user-select: none!important;
  user-select: none!important
}

.pe-none {
  pointer-events: none!important
}

```

```
}  
  
.pe-auto {  
  pointer-events: auto!important  
}  
  
.rounded {  
  border-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-0 {  
  border-radius: 0!important  
}  
  
.rounded-1 {  
  border-radius: .2rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-2 {  
  border-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-3 {  
  border-radius: .3rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-circle {  
  border-radius: 50%!important  
}  
  
.rounded-pill {  
  border-radius: 50rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-top {  
  border-top-left-radius: .25rem!important;  
  border-top-right-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-end {  
  border-top-right-radius: .25rem!important;  
  border-bottom-right-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-bottom {  
  border-bottom-right-radius: .25rem!important;  
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.rounded-start {  
  border-bottom-left-radius: .25rem!important;  
  border-top-left-radius: .25rem!important  
}  
  
.visible {  
  visibility: visible!important  
}
```

```

.invisible {
  visibility: hidden!important
}

@media (min-width:576px) {
  .float-sm-start {
    float: left!important
  }
  .float-sm-end {
    float: right!important
  }
  .float-sm-none {
    float: none!important
  }
  .d-sm-inline {
    display: inline!important
  }
  .d-sm-inline-block {
    display: inline-block!important
  }
  .d-sm-block {
    display: block!important
  }
  .d-sm-grid {
    display: grid!important
  }
  .d-sm-table {
    display: table!important
  }
  .d-sm-table-row {
    display: table-row!important
  }
  .d-sm-table-cell {
    display: table-cell!important
  }
  .d-sm-flex {
    display: flex!important
  }
  .d-sm-inline-flex {
    display: inline-flex!important
  }
  .d-sm-none {
    display: none!important
  }
  .flex-sm-fill {
    flex: 1 1 auto!important
  }
  .flex-sm-row {
    flex-direction: row!important
  }
  .flex-sm-column {
    flex-direction: column!important
  }
  .flex-sm-row-reverse {
    flex-direction: row-reverse!important
  }
}

```

```

.flex-sm-column-reverse {
  flex-direction: column-reverse!important
}
.flex-sm-grow-0 {
  flex-grow: 0!important
}
.flex-sm-grow-1 {
  flex-grow: 1!important
}
.flex-sm-shrink-0 {
  flex-shrink: 0!important
}
.flex-sm-shrink-1 {
  flex-shrink: 1!important
}
.flex-sm-wrap {
  flex-wrap: wrap!important
}
.flex-sm-nowrap {
  flex-wrap: nowrap!important
}
.flex-sm-wrap-reverse {
  flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
}
.gap-sm-0 {
  gap: 0!important
}
.gap-sm-1 {
  gap: .25rem!important
}
.gap-sm-2 {
  gap: .5rem!important
}
.gap-sm-3 {
  gap: 1rem!important
}
.gap-sm-4 {
  gap: 1.5rem!important
}
.gap-sm-5 {
  gap: 3rem!important
}
.justify-content-sm-start {
  justify-content: flex-start!important
}
.justify-content-sm-end {
  justify-content: flex-end!important
}
.justify-content-sm-center {
  justify-content: center!important
}
.justify-content-sm-between {
  justify-content: space-between!important
}
.justify-content-sm-around {
  justify-content: space-around!important
}

```

```

.justify-content-sm-evenly {
  justify-content: space-evenly!important
}
.align-items-sm-start {
  align-items: flex-start!important
}
.align-items-sm-end {
  align-items: flex-end!important
}
.align-items-sm-center {
  align-items: center!important
}
.align-items-sm-baseline {
  align-items: baseline!important
}
.align-items-sm-stretch {
  align-items: stretch!important
}
.align-content-sm-start {
  align-content: flex-start!important
}
.align-content-sm-end {
  align-content: flex-end!important
}
.align-content-sm-center {
  align-content: center!important
}
.align-content-sm-between {
  align-content: space-between!important
}
.align-content-sm-around {
  align-content: space-around!important
}
.align-content-sm-stretch {
  align-content: stretch!important
}
.align-self-sm-auto {
  align-self: auto!important
}
.align-self-sm-start {
  align-self: flex-start!important
}
.align-self-sm-end {
  align-self: flex-end!important
}
.align-self-sm-center {
  align-self: center!important
}
.align-self-sm-baseline {
  align-self: baseline!important
}
.align-self-sm-stretch {
  align-self: stretch!important
}
.order-sm-first {
  order: -1!important
}

```

```
.order-sm-0 {
  order: 0!important
}
.order-sm-1 {
  order: 1!important
}
.order-sm-2 {
  order: 2!important
}
.order-sm-3 {
  order: 3!important
}
.order-sm-4 {
  order: 4!important
}
.order-sm-5 {
  order: 5!important
}
.order-sm-last {
  order: 6!important
}
.m-sm-0 {
  margin: 0!important
}
.m-sm-1 {
  margin: .25rem!important
}
.m-sm-2 {
  margin: .5rem!important
}
.m-sm-3 {
  margin: 1rem!important
}
.m-sm-4 {
  margin: 1.5rem!important
}
.m-sm-5 {
  margin: 3rem!important
}
.m-sm-auto {
  margin: auto!important
}
.mx-sm-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important;
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.mx-sm-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important;
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.mx-sm-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important;
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.mx-sm-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important;
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}
```

```

}
.mx-sm-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.mx-sm-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important;
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
.mx-sm-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important;
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.my-sm-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important;
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.my-sm-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.my-sm-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.my-sm-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.my-sm-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.my-sm-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.my-sm-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important;
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.mt-sm-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important
}
.mt-sm-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important
}
.mt-sm-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important
}
.mt-sm-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important
}
.mt-sm-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.mt-sm-5 {

```

```
    margin-top: 3rem!important
  }
  .mt-sm-auto {
    margin-top: auto!important
  }
  .me-sm-0 {
    margin-right: 0!important
  }
  .me-sm-1 {
    margin-right: .25rem!important
  }
  .me-sm-2 {
    margin-right: .5rem!important
  }
  .me-sm-3 {
    margin-right: 1rem!important
  }
  .me-sm-4 {
    margin-right: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .me-sm-5 {
    margin-right: 3rem!important
  }
  .me-sm-auto {
    margin-right: auto!important
  }
  .mb-sm-0 {
    margin-bottom: 0!important
  }
  .mb-sm-1 {
    margin-bottom: .25rem!important
  }
  .mb-sm-2 {
    margin-bottom: .5rem!important
  }
  .mb-sm-3 {
    margin-bottom: 1rem!important
  }
  .mb-sm-4 {
    margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .mb-sm-5 {
    margin-bottom: 3rem!important
  }
  .mb-sm-auto {
    margin-bottom: auto!important
  }
  .ms-sm-0 {
    margin-left: 0!important
  }
  .ms-sm-1 {
    margin-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .ms-sm-2 {
    margin-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .ms-sm-3 {
```

```

    margin-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .ms-sm-4 {
    margin-left: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .ms-sm-5 {
    margin-left: 3rem!important
  }
  .ms-sm-auto {
    margin-left: auto!important
  }
  .p-sm-0 {
    padding: 0!important
  }
  .p-sm-1 {
    padding: .25rem!important
  }
  .p-sm-2 {
    padding: .5rem!important
  }
  .p-sm-3 {
    padding: 1rem!important
  }
  .p-sm-4 {
    padding: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .p-sm-5 {
    padding: 3rem!important
  }
  .px-sm-0 {
    padding-right: 0!important;
    padding-left: 0!important
  }
  .px-sm-1 {
    padding-right: .25rem!important;
    padding-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .px-sm-2 {
    padding-right: .5rem!important;
    padding-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .px-sm-3 {
    padding-right: 1rem!important;
    padding-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .px-sm-4 {
    padding-right: 1.5rem!important;
    padding-left: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .px-sm-5 {
    padding-right: 3rem!important;
    padding-left: 3rem!important
  }
  .py-sm-0 {
    padding-top: 0!important;
    padding-bottom: 0!important
  }
}

```

```
.py-sm-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.py-sm-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.py-sm-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.py-sm-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.py-sm-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.pt-sm-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important
}
.pt-sm-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important
}
.pt-sm-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important
}
.pt-sm-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important
}
.pt-sm-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.pt-sm-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important
}
.pe-sm-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}
.pe-sm-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}
.pe-sm-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}
.pe-sm-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important
}
.pe-sm-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.pe-sm-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important
}
.pb-sm-0 {
```

```

padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.pb-sm-1 {
padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.pb-sm-2 {
padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.pb-sm-3 {
padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.pb-sm-4 {
padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.pb-sm-5 {
padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.ps-sm-0 {
padding-left: 0!important
}
.ps-sm-1 {
padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.ps-sm-2 {
padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.ps-sm-3 {
padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.ps-sm-4 {
padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ps-sm-5 {
padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.text-sm-start {
text-align: left!important
}
.text-sm-end {
text-align: right!important
}
.text-sm-center {
text-align: center!important
}
}

@media (min-width:768px) {
.float-md-start {
float: left!important
}
.float-md-end {
float: right!important
}
.float-md-none {
float: none!important
}
.d-md-inline {

```

```
    display: inline!important
  }
  .d-md-inline-block {
    display: inline-block!important
  }
  .d-md-block {
    display: block!important
  }
  .d-md-grid {
    display: grid!important
  }
  .d-md-table {
    display: table!important
  }
  .d-md-table-row {
    display: table-row!important
  }
  .d-md-table-cell {
    display: table-cell!important
  }
  .d-md-flex {
    display: flex!important
  }
  .d-md-inline-flex {
    display: inline-flex!important
  }
  .d-md-none {
    display: none!important
  }
  .flex-md-fill {
    flex: 1 1 auto!important
  }
  .flex-md-row {
    flex-direction: row!important
  }
  .flex-md-column {
    flex-direction: column!important
  }
  .flex-md-row-reverse {
    flex-direction: row-reverse!important
  }
  .flex-md-column-reverse {
    flex-direction: column-reverse!important
  }
  .flex-md-grow-0 {
    flex-grow: 0!important
  }
  .flex-md-grow-1 {
    flex-grow: 1!important
  }
  .flex-md-shrink-0 {
    flex-shrink: 0!important
  }
  .flex-md-shrink-1 {
    flex-shrink: 1!important
  }
  .flex-md-wrap {
```

```

    flex-wrap: wrap!important
  }
  .flex-md-nowrap {
    flex-wrap: nowrap!important
  }
  .flex-md-wrap-reverse {
    flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
  }
  .gap-md-0 {
    gap: 0!important
  }
  .gap-md-1 {
    gap: .25rem!important
  }
  .gap-md-2 {
    gap: .5rem!important
  }
  .gap-md-3 {
    gap: 1rem!important
  }
  .gap-md-4 {
    gap: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .gap-md-5 {
    gap: 3rem!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-start {
    justify-content: flex-start!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-end {
    justify-content: flex-end!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-center {
    justify-content: center!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-between {
    justify-content: space-between!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-around {
    justify-content: space-around!important
  }
  .justify-content-md-evenly {
    justify-content: space-evenly!important
  }
  .align-items-md-start {
    align-items: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-items-md-end {
    align-items: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-items-md-center {
    align-items: center!important
  }
  .align-items-md-baseline {
    align-items: baseline!important
  }
  .align-items-md-stretch {

```

```
    align-items: stretch!important
  }
  .align-content-md-start {
    align-content: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-content-md-end {
    align-content: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-content-md-center {
    align-content: center!important
  }
  .align-content-md-between {
    align-content: space-between!important
  }
  .align-content-md-around {
    align-content: space-around!important
  }
  .align-content-md-stretch {
    align-content: stretch!important
  }
  .align-self-md-auto {
    align-self: auto!important
  }
  .align-self-md-start {
    align-self: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-self-md-end {
    align-self: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-self-md-center {
    align-self: center!important
  }
  .align-self-md-baseline {
    align-self: baseline!important
  }
  .align-self-md-stretch {
    align-self: stretch!important
  }
  .order-md-first {
    order: -1!important
  }
  .order-md-0 {
    order: 0!important
  }
  .order-md-1 {
    order: 1!important
  }
  .order-md-2 {
    order: 2!important
  }
  .order-md-3 {
    order: 3!important
  }
  .order-md-4 {
    order: 4!important
  }
  .order-md-5 {
```

```

    order: 5!important
  }
  .order-md-last {
    order: 6!important
  }
  .m-md-0 {
    margin: 0!important
  }
  .m-md-1 {
    margin: .25rem!important
  }
  .m-md-2 {
    margin: .5rem!important
  }
  .m-md-3 {
    margin: 1rem!important
  }
  .m-md-4 {
    margin: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .m-md-5 {
    margin: 3rem!important
  }
  .m-md-auto {
    margin: auto!important
  }
  .mx-md-0 {
    margin-right: 0!important;
    margin-left: 0!important
  }
  .mx-md-1 {
    margin-right: .25rem!important;
    margin-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .mx-md-2 {
    margin-right: .5rem!important;
    margin-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .mx-md-3 {
    margin-right: 1rem!important;
    margin-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .mx-md-4 {
    margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
    margin-left: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .mx-md-5 {
    margin-right: 3rem!important;
    margin-left: 3rem!important
  }
  .mx-md-auto {
    margin-right: auto!important;
    margin-left: auto!important
  }
  .my-md-0 {
    margin-top: 0!important;
    margin-bottom: 0!important
  }

```

```

}
.my-md-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.my-md-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.my-md-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.my-md-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.my-md-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.my-md-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important;
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.mt-md-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important
}
.mt-md-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important
}
.mt-md-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important
}
.mt-md-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important
}
.mt-md-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.mt-md-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important
}
.mt-md-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important
}
.me-md-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important
}
.me-md-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important
}
.me-md-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important
}
.me-md-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important
}

```

```
}
.me-md-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.me-md-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important
}
.me-md-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important
}
.mb-md-0 {
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.mb-md-1 {
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.mb-md-2 {
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.mb-md-3 {
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.mb-md-4 {
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.mb-md-5 {
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.mb-md-auto {
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.ms-md-0 {
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.ms-md-1 {
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.ms-md-2 {
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.ms-md-3 {
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}
.ms-md-4 {
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ms-md-5 {
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
.ms-md-auto {
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.p-md-0 {
  padding: 0!important
}
.p-md-1 {
  padding: .25rem!important
}
```

```

}
.p-md-2 {
  padding: .5rem!important
}
.p-md-3 {
  padding: 1rem!important
}
.p-md-4 {
  padding: 1.5rem!important
}
.p-md-5 {
  padding: 3rem!important
}
.px-md-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important;
  padding-left: 0!important
}
.px-md-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important;
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.px-md-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important;
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.px-md-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important;
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.px-md-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.px-md-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important;
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.py-md-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important;
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.py-md-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.py-md-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.py-md-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.py-md-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
}

```

```
.py-md-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.pt-md-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important
}
.pt-md-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important
}
.pt-md-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important
}
.pt-md-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important
}
.pt-md-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.pt-md-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important
}
.pe-md-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}
.pe-md-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}
.pe-md-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}
.pe-md-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important
}
.pe-md-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.pe-md-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important
}
.pb-md-0 {
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.pb-md-1 {
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.pb-md-2 {
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.pb-md-3 {
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.pb-md-4 {
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.pb-md-5 {
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
```

```

}
.ps-md-0 {
  padding-left: 0!important
}
.ps-md-1 {
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.ps-md-2 {
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.ps-md-3 {
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.ps-md-4 {
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ps-md-5 {
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.text-md-start {
  text-align: left!important
}
.text-md-end {
  text-align: right!important
}
.text-md-center {
  text-align: center!important
}
}
}

@media (min-width:992px) {
  .float-lg-start {
    float: left!important
  }
  .float-lg-end {
    float: right!important
  }
  .float-lg-none {
    float: none!important
  }
  .d-lg-inline {
    display: inline!important
  }
  .d-lg-inline-block {
    display: inline-block!important
  }
  .d-lg-block {
    display: block!important
  }
  .d-lg-grid {
    display: grid!important
  }
  .d-lg-table {
    display: table!important
  }
  .d-lg-table-row {
    display: table-row!important
  }
}

```

```

}
.d-lg-table-cell {
    display: table-cell!important
}
.d-lg-flex {
    display: flex!important
}
.d-lg-inline-flex {
    display: inline-flex!important
}
.d-lg-none {
    display: none!important
}
.flex-lg-fill {
    flex: 1 1 auto!important
}
.flex-lg-row {
    flex-direction: row!important
}
.flex-lg-column {
    flex-direction: column!important
}
.flex-lg-row-reverse {
    flex-direction: row-reverse!important
}
.flex-lg-column-reverse {
    flex-direction: column-reverse!important
}
.flex-lg-grow-0 {
    flex-grow: 0!important
}
.flex-lg-grow-1 {
    flex-grow: 1!important
}
.flex-lg-shrink-0 {
    flex-shrink: 0!important
}
.flex-lg-shrink-1 {
    flex-shrink: 1!important
}
.flex-lg-wrap {
    flex-wrap: wrap!important
}
.flex-lg-nowrap {
    flex-wrap: nowrap!important
}
.flex-lg-wrap-reverse {
    flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
}
.gap-lg-0 {
    gap: 0!important
}
.gap-lg-1 {
    gap: .25rem!important
}
.gap-lg-2 {
    gap: .5rem!important
}

```

```

}
.gap-lg-3 {
  gap: 1rem!important
}
.gap-lg-4 {
  gap: 1.5rem!important
}
.gap-lg-5 {
  gap: 3rem!important
}
.justify-content-lg-start {
  justify-content: flex-start!important
}
.justify-content-lg-end {
  justify-content: flex-end!important
}
.justify-content-lg-center {
  justify-content: center!important
}
.justify-content-lg-between {
  justify-content: space-between!important
}
.justify-content-lg-around {
  justify-content: space-around!important
}
.justify-content-lg-evenly {
  justify-content: space-evenly!important
}
.align-items-lg-start {
  align-items: flex-start!important
}
.align-items-lg-end {
  align-items: flex-end!important
}
.align-items-lg-center {
  align-items: center!important
}
.align-items-lg-baseline {
  align-items: baseline!important
}
.align-items-lg-stretch {
  align-items: stretch!important
}
.align-content-lg-start {
  align-content: flex-start!important
}
.align-content-lg-end {
  align-content: flex-end!important
}
.align-content-lg-center {
  align-content: center!important
}
.align-content-lg-between {
  align-content: space-between!important
}
.align-content-lg-around {
  align-content: space-around!important
}

```

```

}
.align-content-lg-stretch {
  align-content: stretch!important
}
.align-self-lg-auto {
  align-self: auto!important
}
.align-self-lg-start {
  align-self: flex-start!important
}
.align-self-lg-end {
  align-self: flex-end!important
}
.align-self-lg-center {
  align-self: center!important
}
.align-self-lg-baseline {
  align-self: baseline!important
}
.align-self-lg-stretch {
  align-self: stretch!important
}
}
.order-lg-first {
  order: -1!important
}
}
.order-lg-0 {
  order: 0!important
}
}
.order-lg-1 {
  order: 1!important
}
}
.order-lg-2 {
  order: 2!important
}
}
.order-lg-3 {
  order: 3!important
}
}
.order-lg-4 {
  order: 4!important
}
}
.order-lg-5 {
  order: 5!important
}
}
.order-lg-last {
  order: 6!important
}
}
.m-lg-0 {
  margin: 0!important
}
}
.m-lg-1 {
  margin: .25rem!important
}
}
.m-lg-2 {
  margin: .5rem!important
}
}
.m-lg-3 {
  margin: 1rem!important
}
}

```

```

}
.m-lg-4 {
  margin: 1.5rem!important
}
.m-lg-5 {
  margin: 3rem!important
}
.m-lg-auto {
  margin: auto!important
}
.mx-lg-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important;
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.mx-lg-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important;
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.mx-lg-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important;
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.mx-lg-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important;
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}
.mx-lg-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.mx-lg-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important;
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
.mx-lg-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important;
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.my-lg-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important;
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.my-lg-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.my-lg-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.my-lg-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.my-lg-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}

```

```
}
.my-lg-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.my-lg-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important;
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.mt-lg-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important
}
.mt-lg-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important
}
.mt-lg-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important
}
.mt-lg-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important
}
.mt-lg-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.mt-lg-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important
}
.mt-lg-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important
}
.me-lg-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important
}
.me-lg-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important
}
.me-lg-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important
}
.me-lg-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important
}
.me-lg-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.me-lg-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important
}
.me-lg-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important
}
.mb-lg-0 {
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.mb-lg-1 {
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
}
```

```
.mb-lg-2 {
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.mb-lg-3 {
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.mb-lg-4 {
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.mb-lg-5 {
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.mb-lg-auto {
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.ms-lg-0 {
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.ms-lg-1 {
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.ms-lg-2 {
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.ms-lg-3 {
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}
.ms-lg-4 {
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ms-lg-5 {
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
.ms-lg-auto {
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.p-lg-0 {
  padding: 0!important
}
.p-lg-1 {
  padding: .25rem!important
}
.p-lg-2 {
  padding: .5rem!important
}
.p-lg-3 {
  padding: 1rem!important
}
.p-lg-4 {
  padding: 1.5rem!important
}
.p-lg-5 {
  padding: 3rem!important
}
.px-lg-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important;
  padding-left: 0!important
}
```

```

}
.px-lg-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important;
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.px-lg-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important;
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.px-lg-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important;
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.px-lg-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.px-lg-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important;
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.py-lg-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important;
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.py-lg-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.py-lg-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.py-lg-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.py-lg-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.py-lg-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.pt-lg-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important
}
.pt-lg-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important
}
.pt-lg-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important
}
.pt-lg-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important
}
}

```

```
.pt-lg-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.pt-lg-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important
}
.pe-lg-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}
.pe-lg-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}
.pe-lg-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}
.pe-lg-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important
}
.pe-lg-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.pe-lg-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important
}
.pb-lg-0 {
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.pb-lg-1 {
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.pb-lg-2 {
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.pb-lg-3 {
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.pb-lg-4 {
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.pb-lg-5 {
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.ps-lg-0 {
  padding-left: 0!important
}
.ps-lg-1 {
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.ps-lg-2 {
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.ps-lg-3 {
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.ps-lg-4 {
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
}
```

```

.ps-lg-5 {
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.text-lg-start {
  text-align: left!important
}
.text-lg-end {
  text-align: right!important
}
.text-lg-center {
  text-align: center!important
}
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
.float-xl-start {
  float: left!important
}
.float-xl-end {
  float: right!important
}
.float-xl-none {
  float: none!important
}
.d-xl-inline {
  display: inline!important
}
.d-xl-inline-block {
  display: inline-block!important
}
.d-xl-block {
  display: block!important
}
.d-xl-grid {
  display: grid!important
}
.d-xl-table {
  display: table!important
}
.d-xl-table-row {
  display: table-row!important
}
.d-xl-table-cell {
  display: table-cell!important
}
.d-xl-flex {
  display: flex!important
}
.d-xl-inline-flex {
  display: inline-flex!important
}
.d-xl-none {
  display: none!important
}
.flex-xl-fill {
  flex: 1 1 auto!important
}
}

```

```

.flex-xl-row {
  flex-direction: row!important
}
.flex-xl-column {
  flex-direction: column!important
}
.flex-xl-row-reverse {
  flex-direction: row-reverse!important
}
.flex-xl-column-reverse {
  flex-direction: column-reverse!important
}
.flex-xl-grow-0 {
  flex-grow: 0!important
}
.flex-xl-grow-1 {
  flex-grow: 1!important
}
.flex-xl-shrink-0 {
  flex-shrink: 0!important
}
.flex-xl-shrink-1 {
  flex-shrink: 1!important
}
.flex-xl-wrap {
  flex-wrap: wrap!important
}
.flex-xl-nowrap {
  flex-wrap: nowrap!important
}
.flex-xl-wrap-reverse {
  flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
}
.gap-xl-0 {
  gap: 0!important
}
.gap-xl-1 {
  gap: .25rem!important
}
.gap-xl-2 {
  gap: .5rem!important
}
.gap-xl-3 {
  gap: 1rem!important
}
.gap-xl-4 {
  gap: 1.5rem!important
}
.gap-xl-5 {
  gap: 3rem!important
}
.justify-content-xl-start {
  justify-content: flex-start!important
}
.justify-content-xl-end {
  justify-content: flex-end!important
}

```

```
.justify-content-xl-center {
  justify-content: center!important
}
.justify-content-xl-between {
  justify-content: space-between!important
}
.justify-content-xl-around {
  justify-content: space-around!important
}
.justify-content-xl-evenly {
  justify-content: space-evenly!important
}
.align-items-xl-start {
  align-items: flex-start!important
}
.align-items-xl-end {
  align-items: flex-end!important
}
.align-items-xl-center {
  align-items: center!important
}
.align-items-xl-baseline {
  align-items: baseline!important
}
.align-items-xl-stretch {
  align-items: stretch!important
}
.align-content-xl-start {
  align-content: flex-start!important
}
.align-content-xl-end {
  align-content: flex-end!important
}
.align-content-xl-center {
  align-content: center!important
}
.align-content-xl-between {
  align-content: space-between!important
}
.align-content-xl-around {
  align-content: space-around!important
}
.align-content-xl-stretch {
  align-content: stretch!important
}
.align-self-xl-auto {
  align-self: auto!important
}
.align-self-xl-start {
  align-self: flex-start!important
}
.align-self-xl-end {
  align-self: flex-end!important
}
.align-self-xl-center {
  align-self: center!important
}
}
```

```

.align-self-xl-baseline {
  align-self: baseline!important
}
.align-self-xl-stretch {
  align-self: stretch!important
}
.order-xl-first {
  order: -1!important
}
.order-xl-0 {
  order: 0!important
}
.order-xl-1 {
  order: 1!important
}
.order-xl-2 {
  order: 2!important
}
.order-xl-3 {
  order: 3!important
}
.order-xl-4 {
  order: 4!important
}
.order-xl-5 {
  order: 5!important
}
.order-xl-last {
  order: 6!important
}
.m-xl-0 {
  margin: 0!important
}
.m-xl-1 {
  margin: .25rem!important
}
.m-xl-2 {
  margin: .5rem!important
}
.m-xl-3 {
  margin: 1rem!important
}
.m-xl-4 {
  margin: 1.5rem!important
}
.m-xl-5 {
  margin: 3rem!important
}
.m-xl-auto {
  margin: auto!important
}
.mx-xl-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important;
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.mx-xl-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important;

```

```

    margin-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .mx-xl-2 {
    margin-right: .5rem!important;
    margin-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .mx-xl-3 {
    margin-right: 1rem!important;
    margin-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .mx-xl-4 {
    margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
    margin-left: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .mx-xl-5 {
    margin-right: 3rem!important;
    margin-left: 3rem!important
  }
  .mx-xl-auto {
    margin-right: auto!important;
    margin-left: auto!important
  }
  .my-xl-0 {
    margin-top: 0!important;
    margin-bottom: 0!important
  }
  .my-xl-1 {
    margin-top: .25rem!important;
    margin-bottom: .25rem!important
  }
  .my-xl-2 {
    margin-top: .5rem!important;
    margin-bottom: .5rem!important
  }
  .my-xl-3 {
    margin-top: 1rem!important;
    margin-bottom: 1rem!important
  }
  .my-xl-4 {
    margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
    margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .my-xl-5 {
    margin-top: 3rem!important;
    margin-bottom: 3rem!important
  }
  .my-xl-auto {
    margin-top: auto!important;
    margin-bottom: auto!important
  }
  .mt-xl-0 {
    margin-top: 0!important
  }
  .mt-xl-1 {
    margin-top: .25rem!important
  }
  .mt-xl-2 {

```

```
    margin-top: .5rem!important
  }
  .mt-xl-3 {
    margin-top: 1rem!important
  }
  .mt-xl-4 {
    margin-top: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .mt-xl-5 {
    margin-top: 3rem!important
  }
  .mt-xl-auto {
    margin-top: auto!important
  }
  .me-xl-0 {
    margin-right: 0!important
  }
  .me-xl-1 {
    margin-right: .25rem!important
  }
  .me-xl-2 {
    margin-right: .5rem!important
  }
  .me-xl-3 {
    margin-right: 1rem!important
  }
  .me-xl-4 {
    margin-right: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .me-xl-5 {
    margin-right: 3rem!important
  }
  .me-xl-auto {
    margin-right: auto!important
  }
  .mb-xl-0 {
    margin-bottom: 0!important
  }
  .mb-xl-1 {
    margin-bottom: .25rem!important
  }
  .mb-xl-2 {
    margin-bottom: .5rem!important
  }
  .mb-xl-3 {
    margin-bottom: 1rem!important
  }
  .mb-xl-4 {
    margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .mb-xl-5 {
    margin-bottom: 3rem!important
  }
  .mb-xl-auto {
    margin-bottom: auto!important
  }
  .ms-xl-0 {
```

```

    margin-left: 0!important
  }
  .ms-xl-1 {
    margin-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .ms-xl-2 {
    margin-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .ms-xl-3 {
    margin-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .ms-xl-4 {
    margin-left: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .ms-xl-5 {
    margin-left: 3rem!important
  }
  .ms-xl-auto {
    margin-left: auto!important
  }
  .p-xl-0 {
    padding: 0!important
  }
  .p-xl-1 {
    padding: .25rem!important
  }
  .p-xl-2 {
    padding: .5rem!important
  }
  .p-xl-3 {
    padding: 1rem!important
  }
  .p-xl-4 {
    padding: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .p-xl-5 {
    padding: 3rem!important
  }
  .px-xl-0 {
    padding-right: 0!important;
    padding-left: 0!important
  }
  .px-xl-1 {
    padding-right: .25rem!important;
    padding-left: .25rem!important
  }
  .px-xl-2 {
    padding-right: .5rem!important;
    padding-left: .5rem!important
  }
  .px-xl-3 {
    padding-right: 1rem!important;
    padding-left: 1rem!important
  }
  .px-xl-4 {
    padding-right: 1.5rem!important;
    padding-left: 1.5rem!important
  }

```

```

}
.px-xl-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important;
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.py-xl-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important;
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.py-xl-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.py-xl-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.py-xl-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.py-xl-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.py-xl-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.pt-xl-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important
}
.pt-xl-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important
}
.pt-xl-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important
}
.pt-xl-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important
}
.pt-xl-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.pt-xl-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important
}
.pe-xl-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}
.pe-xl-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}
.pe-xl-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}
.pe-xl-3 {

```

```

        padding-right: 1rem!important
    }
    .pe-xl-4 {
        padding-right: 1.5rem!important
    }
    .pe-xl-5 {
        padding-right: 3rem!important
    }
    .pb-xl-0 {
        padding-bottom: 0!important
    }
    .pb-xl-1 {
        padding-bottom: .25rem!important
    }
    .pb-xl-2 {
        padding-bottom: .5rem!important
    }
    .pb-xl-3 {
        padding-bottom: 1rem!important
    }
    .pb-xl-4 {
        padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
    }
    .pb-xl-5 {
        padding-bottom: 3rem!important
    }
    .ps-xl-0 {
        padding-left: 0!important
    }
    .ps-xl-1 {
        padding-left: .25rem!important
    }
    .ps-xl-2 {
        padding-left: .5rem!important
    }
    .ps-xl-3 {
        padding-left: 1rem!important
    }
    .ps-xl-4 {
        padding-left: 1.5rem!important
    }
    .ps-xl-5 {
        padding-left: 3rem!important
    }
    .text-xl-start {
        text-align: left!important
    }
    .text-xl-end {
        text-align: right!important
    }
    .text-xl-center {
        text-align: center!important
    }
}

@media (min-width:1400px) {
    .float-xxl-start {

```

```
    float: left!important
  }
  .float-xxl-end {
    float: right!important
  }
  .float-xxl-none {
    float: none!important
  }
  .d-xxl-inline {
    display: inline!important
  }
  .d-xxl-inline-block {
    display: inline-block!important
  }
  .d-xxl-block {
    display: block!important
  }
  .d-xxl-grid {
    display: grid!important
  }
  .d-xxl-table {
    display: table!important
  }
  .d-xxl-table-row {
    display: table-row!important
  }
  .d-xxl-table-cell {
    display: table-cell!important
  }
  .d-xxl-flex {
    display: flex!important
  }
  .d-xxl-inline-flex {
    display: inline-flex!important
  }
  .d-xxl-none {
    display: none!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-fill {
    flex: 1 1 auto!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-row {
    flex-direction: row!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-column {
    flex-direction: column!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-row-reverse {
    flex-direction: row-reverse!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-column-reverse {
    flex-direction: column-reverse!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-grow-0 {
    flex-grow: 0!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-grow-1 {
```

```

    flex-grow: 1!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-shrink-0 {
    flex-shrink: 0!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-shrink-1 {
    flex-shrink: 1!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-wrap {
    flex-wrap: wrap!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-nowrap {
    flex-wrap: nowrap!important
  }
  .flex-xxl-wrap-reverse {
    flex-wrap: wrap-reverse!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-0 {
    gap: 0!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-1 {
    gap: .25rem!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-2 {
    gap: .5rem!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-3 {
    gap: 1rem!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-4 {
    gap: 1.5rem!important
  }
  .gap-xxl-5 {
    gap: 3rem!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-start {
    justify-content: flex-start!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-end {
    justify-content: flex-end!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-center {
    justify-content: center!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-between {
    justify-content: space-between!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-around {
    justify-content: space-around!important
  }
  .justify-content-xxl-evenly {
    justify-content: space-evenly!important
  }
  .align-items-xxl-start {
    align-items: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-items-xxl-end {

```

```

    align-items: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-items-xxl-center {
    align-items: center!important
  }
  .align-items-xxl-baseline {
    align-items: baseline!important
  }
  .align-items-xxl-stretch {
    align-items: stretch!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-start {
    align-content: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-end {
    align-content: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-center {
    align-content: center!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-between {
    align-content: space-between!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-around {
    align-content: space-around!important
  }
  .align-content-xxl-stretch {
    align-content: stretch!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-auto {
    align-self: auto!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-start {
    align-self: flex-start!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-end {
    align-self: flex-end!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-center {
    align-self: center!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-baseline {
    align-self: baseline!important
  }
  .align-self-xxl-stretch {
    align-self: stretch!important
  }
  .order-xxl-first {
    order: -1!important
  }
  .order-xxl-0 {
    order: 0!important
  }
  .order-xxl-1 {
    order: 1!important
  }
  .order-xxl-2 {

```

```

    order: 2!important
}
.order-xxl-3 {
    order: 3!important
}
.order-xxl-4 {
    order: 4!important
}
.order-xxl-5 {
    order: 5!important
}
.order-xxl-last {
    order: 6!important
}
.m-xxl-0 {
    margin: 0!important
}
.m-xxl-1 {
    margin: .25rem!important
}
.m-xxl-2 {
    margin: .5rem!important
}
.m-xxl-3 {
    margin: 1rem!important
}
.m-xxl-4 {
    margin: 1.5rem!important
}
.m-xxl-5 {
    margin: 3rem!important
}
.m-xxl-auto {
    margin: auto!important
}
.mx-xxl-0 {
    margin-right: 0!important;
    margin-left: 0!important
}
.mx-xxl-1 {
    margin-right: .25rem!important;
    margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.mx-xxl-2 {
    margin-right: .5rem!important;
    margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.mx-xxl-3 {
    margin-right: 1rem!important;
    margin-left: 1rem!important
}
.mx-xxl-4 {
    margin-right: 1.5rem!important;
    margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.mx-xxl-5 {
    margin-right: 3rem!important;

```

```
    margin-left: 3rem!important
  }
.mx-xxl-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important;
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.my-xxl-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important;
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.my-xxl-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.my-xxl-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.my-xxl-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.my-xxl-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.my-xxl-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important;
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.my-xxl-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important;
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.mt-xxl-0 {
  margin-top: 0!important
}
.mt-xxl-1 {
  margin-top: .25rem!important
}
.mt-xxl-2 {
  margin-top: .5rem!important
}
.mt-xxl-3 {
  margin-top: 1rem!important
}
.mt-xxl-4 {
  margin-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.mt-xxl-5 {
  margin-top: 3rem!important
}
.mt-xxl-auto {
  margin-top: auto!important
}
.me-xxl-0 {
  margin-right: 0!important
```

```
}
.me-xxl-1 {
  margin-right: .25rem!important
}
.me-xxl-2 {
  margin-right: .5rem!important
}
.me-xxl-3 {
  margin-right: 1rem!important
}
.me-xxl-4 {
  margin-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.me-xxl-5 {
  margin-right: 3rem!important
}
.me-xxl-auto {
  margin-right: auto!important
}
.mb-xxl-0 {
  margin-bottom: 0!important
}
.mb-xxl-1 {
  margin-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.mb-xxl-2 {
  margin-bottom: .5rem!important
}
.mb-xxl-3 {
  margin-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.mb-xxl-4 {
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.mb-xxl-5 {
  margin-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.mb-xxl-auto {
  margin-bottom: auto!important
}
.ms-xxl-0 {
  margin-left: 0!important
}
.ms-xxl-1 {
  margin-left: .25rem!important
}
.ms-xxl-2 {
  margin-left: .5rem!important
}
.ms-xxl-3 {
  margin-left: 1rem!important
}
.ms-xxl-4 {
  margin-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ms-xxl-5 {
  margin-left: 3rem!important
}
```

```

}
.ms-xxl-auto {
  margin-left: auto!important
}
.p-xxl-0 {
  padding: 0!important
}
.p-xxl-1 {
  padding: .25rem!important
}
.p-xxl-2 {
  padding: .5rem!important
}
.p-xxl-3 {
  padding: 1rem!important
}
.p-xxl-4 {
  padding: 1.5rem!important
}
.p-xxl-5 {
  padding: 3rem!important
}
.px-xxl-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important;
  padding-left: 0!important
}
.px-xxl-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important;
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.px-xxl-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important;
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.px-xxl-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important;
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.px-xxl-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.px-xxl-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important;
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.py-xxl-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important;
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.py-xxl-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.py-xxl-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}

```

```
}
.py-xxl-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.py-xxl-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.py-xxl-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important;
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.pt-xxl-0 {
  padding-top: 0!important
}
.pt-xxl-1 {
  padding-top: .25rem!important
}
.pt-xxl-2 {
  padding-top: .5rem!important
}
.pt-xxl-3 {
  padding-top: 1rem!important
}
.pt-xxl-4 {
  padding-top: 1.5rem!important
}
.pt-xxl-5 {
  padding-top: 3rem!important
}
.pe-xxl-0 {
  padding-right: 0!important
}
.pe-xxl-1 {
  padding-right: .25rem!important
}
.pe-xxl-2 {
  padding-right: .5rem!important
}
.pe-xxl-3 {
  padding-right: 1rem!important
}
.pe-xxl-4 {
  padding-right: 1.5rem!important
}
.pe-xxl-5 {
  padding-right: 3rem!important
}
.pb-xxl-0 {
  padding-bottom: 0!important
}
.pb-xxl-1 {
  padding-bottom: .25rem!important
}
.pb-xxl-2 {
  padding-bottom: .5rem!important
}
```

```

}
.pb-xxl-3 {
  padding-bottom: 1rem!important
}
.pb-xxl-4 {
  padding-bottom: 1.5rem!important
}
.pb-xxl-5 {
  padding-bottom: 3rem!important
}
.ps-xxl-0 {
  padding-left: 0!important
}
.ps-xxl-1 {
  padding-left: .25rem!important
}
.ps-xxl-2 {
  padding-left: .5rem!important
}
.ps-xxl-3 {
  padding-left: 1rem!important
}
.ps-xxl-4 {
  padding-left: 1.5rem!important
}
.ps-xxl-5 {
  padding-left: 3rem!important
}
.text-xxl-start {
  text-align: left!important
}
.text-xxl-end {
  text-align: right!important
}
.text-xxl-center {
  text-align: center!important
}
}

@media (min-width:1200px) {
  .fs-1 {
    font-size: 2.5rem!important
  }
  .fs-2 {
    font-size: 2rem!important
  }
  .fs-3 {
    font-size: 1.75rem!important
  }
  .fs-4 {
    font-size: 1.5rem!important
  }
}

@media print {
  .d-print-inline {
    display: inline!important
  }
}

```

```
}  
.d-print-inline-block {  
    display: inline-block!important  
}  
.d-print-block {  
    display: block!important  
}  
.d-print-grid {  
    display: grid!important  
}  
.d-print-table {  
    display: table!important  
}  
.d-print-table-row {  
    display: table-row!important  
}  
.d-print-table-cell {  
    display: table-cell!important  
}  
.d-print-flex {  
    display: flex!important  
}  
.d-print-inline-flex {  
    display: inline-flex!important  
}  
.d-print-none {  
    display: none!important  
}  
}  
  
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.min.css.map */
```

Style.css

```
/*
Tooplate 2119 Gymso Fitness
https://www.tooplate.com/view/2119-gymso-fitness
*/

@font-face {
  font-family: 'Plain';
  src: url('../fonts/Plain-Regular.woff2') format('woff2'),
url('../fonts/Plain-Regular.woff') format('woff');
  font-weight: normal;
  font-style: normal;
}

@font-face {
  font-family: 'Plain';
  src: url('../fonts/Plain-Light.woff2') format('woff2'),
url('../fonts/Plain-Light.woff') format('woff');
  font-weight: 300;
  font-style: normal;
}

@font-face {
  font-family: 'Plain';
  src: url('../fonts/Plain-Bold.woff2') format('woff2'),
url('../fonts/Plain-Bold.woff') format('woff');
  font-weight: bold;
  font-style: normal;
}

:root {
  --primary-color: #f13a11;
  --white-color: #ffffff;
  --dark-color: #171819;
  --about-bg-color: #f9f9f9;
  --gray-color: #909090;
  --link-color: #404040;
  --p-color: #666262;
  --base-font-family: 'Plain', sans-serif;
  --font-weight-bold: bold;
  --font-weight-normal: normal;
  --font-weight-light: 300;
  --font-weight-thin: 100;
  --h1-font-size: 48px;
  --h2-font-size: 36px;
  --h3-font-size: 28px;
  --h4-font-size: 24px;
  --h5-font-size: 22px;
  --h6-font-size: 22px;
  --p-font-size: 18px;
  --base-font-size: 16px;
  --menu-font-size: 14px;
}
```

```

    --border-radius-large: 100%;
    --border-radius-small: 2px;
}

body {
    background: var(--white-color);
    font-family: var(--base-font-family);
}

/*-----
   TYPOGRAPHY
   -----*/

h1,
h2,
h3,
h4,
h5,
h6 {
    font-weight: var(--font-weight-thin);
    line-height: normal;
}

h1 {
    font-size: var(--h1-font-size);
    font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
    letter-spacing: -1px;
    text-transform: uppercase;
    margin: 60px 0;
}

h2 {
    font-size: var(--h2-font-size);
    font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
    letter-spacing: -2px;
}

h3 {
    font-size: var(--h3-font-size);
    font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
    letter-spacing: -1px;
    margin: 0;
}

h4 {
    font-size: var(--h4-font-size);
}

h5 {
    font-size: var(--h5-font-size);
}

h6 {
    color: var(--gray-color);
    font-size: var(--h6-font-size);
    line-height: inherit;
}

```

```

margin: 0;
}

p {
  color: var(--p-color);
  font-size: var(--p-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-light);
  line-height: 1.5em;
}

b,
strong {
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
  letter-spacing: 0;
}

.section {
  padding: 7rem 0;
}

/* BUTTON */

.custom-btn {
  background: transparent;
  border-radius: var(--border-radius-small);
  padding: 14px 24px;
  color: var(--white-color);
  font-size: var(--menu-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-normal);
  text-transform: uppercase;
  letter-spacing: 0.5px;
  white-space: nowrap;
  transition: all 0.3s ease;
}

.custom-btn:hover {
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

.custom-btn:focus {
  box-shadow: none;
}

.custom-btn.bordered:hover,
.custom-btn.bordered:focus,
.custom-btn.bg-color:hover,
.custom-btn.bg-color:focus {
  background: var(--white-color);
  border-color: transparent;
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

.bordered {
  border: 1px solid var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

```

```

.custom-btn.sub-bordered:hover,
.custom-btn.sub-bordered:focus,
.custom-btn.bg-color:hover,
.custom-btn.bg-color:focus {
  background: var(--white-color);
  border-color: transparent;
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

.sub-bordered {
  border-color: transparent;
}

.bg-color {
  background: var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--white-color);
}

/* Signup */

.booking {
  background-image: url('../images/signup-bg.jpg');
  background-size: cover;
  background-position: top;
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  vertical-align: middle;
  min-height: 100vh;
  position: relative;
}

.booking_box {
  width: 1050px;
  height: 600px;
  position: absolute;
  top: 50%;
  left: 50%;
  transform: translate(-50%, -50%);
  background: #fff;
  border-radius: 10px;
  box-shadow: 1px 4px 22px -8px #0004;
  display: flex;
  overflow: hidden;
}

.booking_box .left {
  width: 41%;
  height: 100%;
  padding: 25px 25px;
}

.booking_box .right {
  width: 59%;
  height: 100%;
}

```

```

/* Signup */

img {
  width: 100%;
}

.login {
  background-image: url('../images/signup-bg.jpg');
  background-size: cover;
  background-position: top;
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  vertical-align: middle;
  min-height: 120vh;
  position: relative;
  opacity: 0.45;
}

.login_box {
  width: 1050px;
  height: 600px;
  position: absolute;
  top: 65%;
  left: 50%;
  transform: translate(-50%, -50%);
  background: #fff;
  border-radius: 10px;
  box-shadow: 1px 4px 22px -8px #0004;
  display: flex;
  overflow: hidden;
}

.login_box .left {
  width: 41%;
  height: 100%;
  padding: 25px 25px;
}

.login_box .right {
  width: 59%;
  height: 100%;
}

.signup {
  background-image: url('../images/signup-bg.jpg');
  background-size: cover;
  background-position: top;
  background-repeat: no-repeat;
  vertical-align: middle;
  min-height: 190vh;
  position: relative;
  opacity: 0.45;
}

.signup_box {
  width: 1050px;
  height: 1050px;
  position: absolute;
}

```

```

top: 102%;
left: 50%;
transform: translate(-50%, -50%);
background: #fff;
border-radius: 10px;
box-shadow: 1px 4px 22px -8px #0004;
display: flex;
overflow: hidden;
}

.signup_box .left, .dashboard_box .left {
width: 41%;
height: 100%;
padding: 25px 25px;
}

.signup_box .right, .dashboard_box .right {
width: 59%;
height: 100%
}

.left .top_link a, .left-display .top_link a, .display .top_link a {
color: #f13a11;
font-weight: 500;
}

.left .top_link a:hover, .left-display .top_link a:hover, .display .top_link
a:hover {
text-decoration: underline;
text-decoration-offset: 0.25rem;
text-decoration-thickness: 2px;
}

.left .top_link, .left-display .top_link, .display .top_link {
height: 20px
}

.left .contact {
display: flex;
align-items: center;
justify-content: center;
align-self: center;
height: 100%;
width: 73%;
margin: auto;
}

.left .contact.signup_form{
display: flex;
align-items: center;
justify-content: center;
align-self: center;
height: 100%;
width: 100%;
margin: auto;
flex-direction: column;
}

```

```

}

.left .contact, .display .contact {
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  align-self: center;
  height: 100%;
  width: 100%;
  margin: auto;
}

.display .contact {
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  align-self: center;
  height: 20%;
  width: 60%;
  margin: auto;
}

.display .contact{
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  align-self: center;
  height: 20%;
  width: 60%;
  margin: auto;
  flex-direction: column;
}

.display .contact.mdb{
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  align-self: center;
  height: 40%;
  width: 60%;
  margin: auto;
  flex-direction: column;
}

.display .contact.mdb-list{
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  align-self: center;
  height: 100%;
  width: 60%;
  margin: auto;
  flex-direction: column;
}

.display .contact.slot{
  display: flex;

```

```

    align-items: center;
    justify-content: center;
    align-self: center;
    height: 50%;
    width: 60%;
    margin: auto;
    flex-direction: column;
}

.left .contact.dashboard-sec, .display .contact.dashboard-sec{
    display: flex;
    height: 100%;
    width: 100%;
}

.dashboard, .display-dashboard, .display_booking, .display-dashboard.mdb
{
    background-image: url('../images/signup-bg.jpg');
    background-size: cover;
    background-position: top;
    background-repeat: no-repeat;
    vertical-align: middle;
    position: relative;
    opacity: 0.45;
}

.dashboard {
    min-height: 155vh;
}

.display-dashboard {
    min-height: 105vh;
}

.display-dashboard.mdb {
    min-height: 125vh;
}

.display_booking {
    min-height: 135vh;
}

.dashboard_box, .display_box, .booking_box {
    position: absolute;
    left: 50%;
    transform: translate(-50%, -50%);
    background: #fff;
    border-radius: 10px;
    box-shadow: 1px 4px 22px -8px #0004;
    display: flex;
    overflow: hidden;
}

.contact.booking-form {
    display: flex;

```

```

    align-items: center;
    justify-content: center;
    align-self: center;
    height: 100%;
    width: 60%;
    margin: auto;
    flex-direction: column;
}

.dashboard_box {
    width: 1050px;
    height: 650px;
    top: 85%;
}

.display_box {
    top: 60%;
    width: 1050px;
    height: 450px;
}

.booking_box {
    top: 70%;
    width: 1050px;
    height: 650px;
}

.left h3 {
    text-align: center;
    margin-bottom: 40px;
}

.display h3 {
    text-align: center;
    margin-bottom: 10px;
}

.left input, .display {
    border: none;
    width: 80%;
    margin: 15px 0px;
    border-bottom: 1px solid #4f30677d;
    padding: 7px 9px;
    width: 100%;
    overflow: hidden;
    background: transparent;
    font-weight: 600;
    font-size: 14px;
}

.left p {
    border: none;
    width: 80%;
    margin: 15px 0px;
    padding: 7px 9px;
    width: 100%;
    overflow: hidden;
}

```

```

background: transparent;
font-weight: 600;
font-size: 14px;
margin-bottom: 0;
padding-bottom: 0;
color: #757576;
}

.left {
background: linear-gradient(-45deg, #dcd7e0, #fff);
}

.submit {
border: none;
padding: 15px 70px;
border-radius: 8px;
display: block;
margin: auto;
margin-top: 120px;
background: #CC6047;
color: #fff;
font-weight: bold;
-webkit-box-shadow: 0px 9px 15px -11px rgba(88, 54, 114, 1);
-moz-box-shadow: 0px 9px 15px -11px rgba(88, 54, 114, 1);
box-shadow: 0px 9px 15px -11px rgba(88, 54, 114, 1);
}

.right {
background: linear-gradient(212.38deg, rgba(186, 83, 112, 0.7) 0%,
rgba(244, 226, 216, 0.71) 100%), url('../images/index-bg.jpg');
/* background-image: linear-gradient(to right, #9796f0, #fbc7d4),
url('../images/index-bg.jpg'); */
color: #fff;
position: relative;
}

.right .right-text {
height: 100%;
position: relative;
transform: translate(0%, 45%);
}

.right-text h2 {
display: block;
width: 100%;
text-align: center;
font-size: 50px;
font-weight: 500;
}

.right-text h5 {
display: block;
width: 100%;
text-align: center;
font-size: 19px;
font-weight: 400;
}

```

```

.right .right-inductor {
  position: absolute;
  width: 70px;
  height: 7px;
  background: #fff0;
  left: 50%;
  bottom: 70px;
  transform: translate(-50%, 0%);
}

.top_link img {
  width: 28px;
  padding-right: 7px;
  margin-top: -3px;
}

.table {
  display: table; /* Allow the centering to work */
  margin: 0 auto;
}

ul#horizontal-list {
  min-width: 696px;
  list-style: none;
  padding-top: 20px;
  display: flex;
  justify-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
}
ul#horizontal-list li {
  display: inline;
  padding: 5px 10px;
  margin: 5px;
  border: 1px solid #CC6047;
  align-items: center;
  color: #CC6047;
}
ul#horizontal-list li:hover {
  border: 1px solid #CC6047;
  align-items: center;
  background-color: #CC6047;
  color: #fff;
}

.popup {
  margin: 70px auto;
  padding: 20px;
  background: #fff;
  border-radius: 15px;
  width: 60%;
  position: relative;
  transition: all 5s ease-in-out;
}

.popup h2 {

```

```

        margin-top: 0;
        color: #333;
        font-family: Tahoma, Arial, sans-serif;
    }
    .popup .close {
        position: absolute;
        top: 20px;
        right: 30px;
        transition: all 200ms;
        font-size: 30px;
        font-weight: bold;
        text-decoration: none;
        color: #333;
    }
    .popup .close:hover {
        color: red;
    }
    .popup .content {
        max-height: 30%;
        overflow: scroll;
        text-decoration: none;
    }
}

.overlay {
    position: fixed;
    top: 0;
    bottom: 0;
    left: 0;
    right: 0;
    background: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.7);
    transition: opacity 500ms;
    visibility: hidden;
    opacity: 0;
}

.overlay:target {
    visibility: visible;
    opacity: 1;
}

/*-----
   GENERAL
   -----*/

* {
    -webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
    -moz-box-sizing: border-box;
    box-sizing: border-box;
}

*::before,
*::after {
    -webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
    -moz-box-sizing: border-box;
    box-sizing: border-box;
}

```

```

a {
  color: var(--link-color);
  font-weight: normal;
  text-decoration: none;
  transition: all 0.3s ease;
}

a:hover,
a:active,
a:focus {
  color: var(--primary-color);
  outline: none;
  text-decoration: none;
}

/* BG OVERLAY */

.bg-overlay {
  background: var(--dark-color);
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  left: 0;
  width: 100%;
  height: 100%;
  opacity: 0.85;
}

.top-text.header-text {
  padding-top: 5rem;
}

.backlist-button {
  float: right;
  margin: 2rem;
}

form.add {
  margin-top: 3rem;
  margin-bottom: 3rem;
}

form#add input{
  width: 100%;
  height: 46px;
  border-radius: 7px;
  background-color: transparent;
  border: 1px solid #8d99af;
  outline: none;
  font-size: 15px;
  font-weight: 300;
  color: #8d99af;
  padding: 0px 15px;
  margin-bottom: 30px;
  margin-top: 10px;
}

```

```

}

form#add textarea{
  width: 100%;
  border-radius: 7px;
  background-color: transparent;
  border: 1px solid #8d99af;
  outline: none;
  font-size: 15px;
  font-weight: 300;
  color: #8d99af;
  padding: 0px 15px;
  margin-bottom: 30px;
  margin-top: 10px;
}

.news-form {
  padding: 0 5rem;
}

.news-form > .container{
  padding: 3rem;
}

a.btn.btn-lg {
  float: right;
  border-color: var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--primary-color);
  background-color: var(--white-color);
}

a.btn.btn-lg:hover {
  border-color: var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--white-color);
  background-color: var(--primary-color);
}

button.btn.btn-secondary.btn-lg {
  background-color: var(--primary-color);
  border-color: var(--primary-color);
}

button.btn.btn-secondary.btn-lg:hover {
  color: var(--primary-color);
  background-color: var(--white-color);
  border-color: var(--primary-color);
}

.options_button {
  margin-left: 1rem;
}

.view-style {
  display: grid;
  padding: 0.5rem;
  margin-bottom: 1.5rem;
  row-gap: 2rem;
}

```

```

        column-gap: 3rem;
        justify-content: space-evenly;
        grid-template-columns: 1fr 1fr 1fr;
    }

.view-style > .class-thumb.col{
    background-color: #f4d29938;
    border: 0.15rem solid #cc60475e;
    border-radius: 0.25rem;
}
p.publish{
    font-size: 14px;
}
/*-----
    MODAL
    -----*/

.modal-content {
    padding: 2rem 3rem;
}

.modal-header,
.modal-body,
.modal-footer {
    border: 0;
    padding: 0;
}

.membership-form a {
    color: var(--primary-color);
}

/*-----
    Book Now
    -----*/

.booknow {
    background-image: linear-gradient(to right, #9796f0, #fbc7d4);
    padding: 5rem 0;
}

/*-----
    FEATURE
    -----*/

.feature {
    background: #CC6047;
    padding: 5rem 0;
}

/*-----
    MENU
    -----*/

```

```

.navbar {
  background: #CC6047;
  padding: 1rem;
}

.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .nav-link {
  padding-right: 1.5rem;
  padding-left: 1.5rem;
}

.navbar-brand {
  color: var(--white-color);
  font-size: var(--h3-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
  line-height: normal;
  padding-top: 0;
}

.nav-item .nav-link {
  display: block;
  color: var(--white-color);
  font-size: var(--menu-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-normal);
  text-transform: uppercase;
  padding: 2px 6px;
}

.nav-item .nav-link.active,
.nav-item .nav-link:hover {
  color: var(--white-color);
  text-decoration: underline;
  text-decoration-color: transparent;
  text-decoration-offset: 0.2rem;
}

.navbar .social-icon li a {
  color: var(--white-color);
}

.navbar-toggler {
  border: 0;
  padding: 0;
  cursor: pointer;
  margin: 0 10px 0 0;
  width: 30px;
  height: 35px;
  outline: none;
}

.navbar-toggler:focus {
  outline: none;
}

.navbar-toggler[aria-expanded="true"] .navbar-toggler-icon {
  background: transparent;
}

.navbar-toggler[aria-expanded="true"] .navbar-toggler-icon::before,

```

```

.navbar-toggler[aria-expanded="true"] .navbar-toggler-icon::after {
  transition: top 300ms 50ms ease, -webkit-transform 300ms 350ms ease;
  transition: top 300ms 50ms ease, transform 300ms 350ms ease;
  transition: top 300ms 50ms ease, transform 300ms 350ms ease, -webkit-
transform 300ms 350ms ease;
  top: 0;
}

.navbar-toggler[aria-expanded="true"] .navbar-toggler-icon::before {
  transform: rotate(45deg);
}

.navbar-toggler[aria-expanded="true"] .navbar-toggler-icon::after {
  transform: rotate(-45deg);
}

.navbar-toggler .navbar-toggler-icon {
  background: var(--primary-color);
  transition: background 10ms 300ms ease;
  display: block;
  width: 30px;
  height: 2px;
  position: relative;
}

.navbar-toggler .navbar-toggler-icon::before,
.navbar-toggler .navbar-toggler-icon::after {
  transition: top 300ms 350ms ease, -webkit-transform 300ms 50ms ease;
  transition: top 300ms 350ms ease, transform 300ms 50ms ease;
  transition: top 300ms 350ms ease, transform 300ms 50ms ease, -webkit-
transform 300ms 50ms ease;
  position: absolute;
  right: 0;
  left: 0;
  background: var(--primary-color);
  width: 30px;
  height: 2px;
  content: '';
}

.navbar-toggler .navbar-toggler-icon::before {
  top: -8px;
}

.navbar-toggler .navbar-toggler-icon::after {
  top: 8px;
}

/*-----
HERO
-----*/

.hero {
  background-image: url('../images/index-bg.jpg');
  background-size: cover;
  background-position: top;
}

```

```

background-repeat: no-repeat;
vertical-align: middle;
min-height: 100vh;
position: relative;
}

.hero p {
  color: var(--white-color);
}

/*-----
  CLASS
-----*/

.class-info {
  background: var(--white-color);
  box-shadow: 6px 0 38px rgba(20, 20, 20, 0.10);
  border-radius: 0 0 2px 2px;
  padding: 1rem 2rem;
  position: relative;
}

.class-info img {
  border-radius: 2px 2px 0 0;
}

.class-info strong {
  color: var(--gray-color);
}

.class-price {
  background: var(--primary-color);
  border-radius: var(--border-radius-large);
  color: var(--white-color);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
  display: block;
  position: absolute;
  top: 2rem;
  right: 2rem;
  width: 3.5rem;
  height: 3.5rem;
  line-height: 1.5rem;
  text-align: center;
}

/*-----
  SCHEDULE
-----*/

.schedule {
  background: var(--about-bg-color);
}

.schedule-table {
  display: table;
  border: 0;

```

```

    text-align: center;
}

.schedule-table strong,
.schedule-table span {
    display: block;
    text-align: center;
}

.schedule-table strong {
    color: var(--white-color);
}

.schedule-table span {
    color: var(--gray-color);
}

.schedule-table span,
.schedule-table small {
    font-size: var(--menu-font-size);
    text-transform: uppercase;
}

.schedule-table small {
    position: relative;
    top: 10px;
}

.table .thead-light th,
.schedule-table tr td:first-child {
    background: var(--primary-color);
    border: 1px solid #212122;
    color: var(--white-color);
}

.schedule-table .thead-light th {
    border-bottom: 0;
    text-transform: uppercase;
}

.table-bordered td,
.table-bordered th {
    border: 1px solid #212122;
}

.table-bordered td {
    padding-bottom: 22px;
}

.table td,
.table th {
    padding: 1rem;
}

/*-----
ABOUT & TEAM

```

```

-----*/
.about {
  background: var(--about-bg-color);
}

.about-working-hours {
  border-left: 2px solid var(--white-color);
  padding-left: 3.5rem;
}

.about-working-hours strong {
  color: var(--white-color);
  opacity: 0.85;
}

.team-thumb {
  position: relative;
}

.team-info {
  background: var(--white-color);
  border-radius: 0 0 2px 2px;
  box-shadow: 6px 0 38px rgba(20, 20, 20, 0.10);
  padding: 20px;
  position: relative;
}

.team-info span {
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-light);
  opacity: 0.85;
}

.team-info .social-icon {
  position: absolute;
  top: 10px;
  right: 20px;
}

.team-info .social-icon li {
  display: block;
}

/*-----
   CONTACT
-----*/

.webform input,
button#submit-button {
  height: calc(2.25rem + 20px);
}

.form-control {
  border-radius: var(--border-radius-small);
  margin: 1.3rem 0;
}

```

```

.form-control:focus {
  box-shadow: none;
  border-color: var(--dark-color);
}

button#submit-button {
  background: var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--white-color);
  cursor: pointer;
  transition: all 0.3s ease;
}

button#submit-button:hover {
  background: transparent;
  border: 1px solid var(--primary-color);
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

.contact h2+p {
  max-width: 90%;
}

.google-map {
  border-top: 1px solid #efebef;
  margin-top: 2.5rem;
  padding-top: 2.5rem;
}

.google-map iframe {
  width: 100%;
}

/*-----
   FOOTER
   -----*/

.site-footer {
  border-top: 1px solid #efebef;
  padding: 1rem 0;
  background: #CC6047;
  bottom: 0;
  width: 100%;
}

.site-footer a {
  color: var(--white-color);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-light);
}

.site-footer p {
  font-size: var(--base-font-size);
  color: var(--white-color);
}

.contact .fa,

```

```

.site-footer .fa {
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

/*-----
   SOCIAL ICON
   -----*/

.social-icon {
  position: relative;
  padding: 0;
  margin: 5px 0 0 0;
}

.social-icon li {
  display: inline-block;
  list-style: none;
}

.social-icon li a {
  text-decoration: none;
  display: inline-block;
  color: var(--p-color);
  font-size: var(--p-font-size);
  font-weight: var(--font-weight-bold);
  margin: 5px 10px;
  text-align: center;
}

.social-icon li a:hover {
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

/*-----
   ACCORDION STYLES
   -----*/

.accordion-section h1 {
  padding-top: 7rem;
}

.accordion-section .panel-default > .panel-heading {
  border: 0;
  background: #f4f4f4;
  padding: 0;
}

.accordion-section .panel-default .panel-title a {
  display: block;
  font-style: italic;
  font-size: 1.5rem;
}

.accordion-section .panel-default .panel-title a:after {
  font-family: 'FontAwesome';
  font-style: normal;
  font-size: 3rem;
  content: "\f106";
  color: var(--primary-color);
}

```

```

float: right;
margin-top: -12px;
}
.accordion-section .panel-default .panel-title a.collapsed:after {
  content: "\f107";
}
.accordion-section .panel-default .panel-body {
  font-size: 1.2rem;
}

button.submit:hover {
  color: #cc6047;
  background-color: white;
  /* border: 2px solid #cc6047;*/
}

/*-----
RESPONSIVE STYLES
-----*/

@media screen and (max-width: 992px) {
  .section {
    padding: 5rem 0;
  }
  .nav-item .nav-link {
    padding: 6px;
  }
  .navbar .social-icon {
    margin-top: 22px;
  }
  .navbar-collapse,
  .site-footer {
    text-align: center;
  }
  .schedule-table {
    display: block;
  }
  .modal-content {
    padding: 2rem;
  }
}

@media screen and (max-width: 767px) {
  h1 {
    font-size: 38px;
  }
  .about-working-hours {
    border-left: 0;
    padding: 22px 0 0 0;
  }
  .contact h2 span {
    display: block;
  }
}

@media screen and (max-width: 700px){
  .popup{

```

```
width: 70%;
}
}
```

2. Js

Aos.js

```
!function(e,t){"object"===typeof exports&&"object"===typeof
module?module.exports=t():"function"===typeof
define&&define.amd?define([],t):"object"===typeof
exports?exports.AOS=t():e.AOS=t()}(this,function(){return
function(e){function t(o){if(n[o])return n[o].exports;var
i=n[o]={exports:{},id:o,loaded:!1};return
e[o].call(i.exports,i,i.exports,t),i.loaded=!0,i.exports}var n={};return
t.m=e,t.c=n,t.p="dist/",t()}([function(e,t,n){"use strict";function
o(e){return e&&e.__esModule?e:{default:e}}var
i=Object.assign||function(e){for(var t=1;t<arguments.length;t++){var
n=arguments[t];for(var o in
n)Object.prototype.hasOwnProperty.call(n,o)&&(e[o]=n[o])}return
e},r=n(1),a=(o(r),n(6)),u=o(a),c=n(7),f=o(c),s=n(8),d=o(s),l=n(9),p=o(1),m=n(
10),b=o(m),v=n(11),y=o(v),g=n(14),h=o(g),w=[],k=!1,x=document.all&&!window.at
ob,j={offset:120,delay:0,easing:"ease",duration:400,disable:!1,once:!1,startE
vent:"DOMContentLoaded",throttleDelay:99,debounceDelay:50,disableMutationObse
rver:!1},O=function(){var e=arguments.length>0&&void
0!==arguments[0]&&arguments[0];if(e&&(k=!0),k)return
w=(0,y.default)(w,j),(0,b.default)(w,j.once),w,_=function(){w=(0,h.default)(
),O()},S=function(){w.forEach(function(e,t){e.node.removeAttribute("data-
aos"),e.node.removeAttribute("data-aos-easing"),e.node.removeAttribute("data-
aos-duration"),e.node.removeAttribute("data-aos-
delay")})},z=function(e){return
e===!0||"mobile"===e&&p.default.mobile()||"phone"===e&&p.default.phone()||"ta
blet"===e&&p.default.tablet()||"function"===typeof
e&&e()===!0},A=function(e){return
j=i(j,e),w=(0,h.default)(),z(j.disable)||x?S():(document.querySelector("body"
).setAttribute("data-aos-
easing",j.easing),document.querySelector("body").setAttribute("data-aos-
duration",j.duration),document.querySelector("body").setAttribute("data-aos-
delay",j.delay),"DOMContentLoaded"===j.startEvent&&["complete","interactive"
].indexOf(document.readyState)>-
1?O(!0):"load"===j.startEvent?window.addEventListener(j.startEvent,function()
{O(!0)}):document.addEventListener(j.startEvent,function(){O(!0)}),window.add
EventListener("resize",(0,f.default)(O,j.debounceDelay,!0)),window.addEventLi
stener("orientationchange",(0,f.default)(O,j.debounceDelay,!0)),window.addEve
ntListener("scroll",(0,u.default)(function(){(0,b.default)(w,j.once)},j.throt
tleDelay)),j.disableMutationObserver||(0,d.default)("[data-
aos]",_),w);e.exports={init:A,refresh:O,refreshHard:_}},function(e,t){},,,,,,
function(e,t){"use strict";function n(e,t,n){function o(t){var
n=b,o=v;return b=v=void 0,k=t,g=e.apply(o,n)}function r(e){return
k=e,h=setTimeout(s,t),_?o(e):g}function a(e){var n=e-w,o=e-k,i=t-n;return
S?j(i,y-o):i}function c(e){var n=e-w,o=e-k;return void
0===w||n>=t||n<0||S&&o>=y}function s(){var e=O();return
c(e)?d(e):void(h=setTimeout(s,a(e)))}function d(e){return h=void
0,z&&b?o(e):(b=v=void 0,g)}function l(){void
0!==h&&clearTimeout(h),k=0,b=w=v=h=void 0}function p(){return void
0===h?g:d(O())}function m(){var
```

```

e=0(),n=c(e);if(b=arguments,v=this,w=e,n){if(void 0===h)return
r(w);if(S)return h=setTimeout(s,t),o(w)}return void
0===h&&(h=setTimeout(s,t),g}var
b,v,y,g,h,w,k=0,_=!1,S=!1,z=!0;if("function"!==typeof e)throw new
TypeError(f);return t=u(t)||0,i(n)&&(_=!1,n.leading,S="maxWait"in
n,y=S?x(u(n.maxWait)||0,t):y,z="trailing"in
n?!n.trailing:z),m.cancel=l,m.flush=p,m}function o(e,t,o){var
r=!0,a=!0;if("function"!==typeof e)throw new TypeError(f);return
i(o)&&(r="leading"in o?!o.leading:r,a="trailing"in
o?!o.trailing:a),n(e,t,{leading:r,maxWait:t,trailing:a})}function i(e){var
t="undefined"===typeof
e?"undefined":c(e);return!e&&("object"===t||"function"===t)}function
r(e){return!e&&"object"===("undefined"===typeof e?"undefined":c(e))}function
a(e){return"symbol"===("undefined"===typeof
e?"undefined":c(e))||r(e)&&k.call(e)==d}function u(e){if("number"===typeof
e)return e;if(a(e))return s;if(i(e)){var t="function"===typeof
e.valueOf?e.valueOf():e;e=i(t)?t+"":t;if("string"!==typeof e)return
0===e?e:+e;e=e.replace(1,"");var n=m.test(e);return
n||b.test(e)?v(e.slice(2),n?2:8):p.test(e)?s:+e}var c="function"===typeof
Symbol&&"symbol"===typeof Symbol.iterator?function(e){return typeof
e}:function(e){return e&&"function"===typeof
Symbol&&e.constructor===Symbol&&!e===Symbol.prototype?"symbol":typeof
e},f="Expected a function",s=NaN,d="[object Symbol]",l=/^\s+|\s+$/g,p=/^[-
+]?0x[0-9a-f]+$/i,m=/^0b[01]+$/i,b=/^0o[0-
7]+$/i,v=parseInt,y="object"===("undefined"===typeof
t?"undefined":c(t))&&t&&t.Object===Object&&t,g="object"===("undefined"===typeof
self?"undefined":c(self))&&self&&self.Object===Object&&self,h=y||g||Function(
"return
this")(),w=Object.prototype,k=w.toString,x=Math.max,j=Math.min,O=function(){r
return h.Date.now()};e.exports=o}).call(t,function(){return
this}()),function(e,t){(function(t){"use strict";function n(e,t,n){function
i(t){var n=b,o=v;return b=v=void 0,O=t,g=e.apply(o,n)}function r(e){return
O=e,h=setTimeout(s,t),_?i(e):g}function u(e){var n=e-w,o=e-O,i=t-n;return
S?x(i,y-o):i}function f(e){var n=e-w,o=e-O;return void
0===w||n>=t||n<0||S&&o>=y}function s(){var e=j();return
f(e)?d(e):void(h=setTimeout(s,u(e)))}function d(e){return h=void
0,z&&b?i(e):(b=v=void 0,g)}function l(){void
0!==(h&&clearTimeout(h),O=0,b=w=v=h=void 0)}function p(){return void
0===h?g:d(j())}function m(){var
e=j(),n=f(e);if(b=arguments,v=this,w=e,n){if(void 0===h)return
r(w);if(S)return h=setTimeout(s,t),i(w)}return void
0===h&&(h=setTimeout(s,t),g}var
b,v,y,g,h,w,O=0,_=!1,S=!1,z=!0;if("function"!==typeof e)throw new
TypeError(c);return t=a(t)||0,o(n)&&(_=!1,n.leading,S="maxWait"in
n,y=S?k(a(n.maxWait)||0,t):y,z="trailing"in
n?!n.trailing:z),m.cancel=l,m.flush=p,m}function o(e){var
t="undefined"===typeof
e?"undefined":u(e);return!e&&("object"===t||"function"===t)}function
i(e){return!e&&"object"===("undefined"===typeof e?"undefined":u(e))}function
r(e){return"symbol"===("undefined"===typeof
e?"undefined":u(e))||i(e)&&w.call(e)==s}function a(e){if("number"===typeof
e)return e;if(r(e))return f;if(o(e)){var t="function"===typeof
e.valueOf?e.valueOf():e;e=o(t)?t+"":t;if("string"!==typeof e)return
0===e?e:+e;e=e.replace(d,"");var n=p.test(e);return
n||m.test(e)?b(e.slice(2),n?2:8):l.test(e)?f:+e}var u="function"===typeof
Symbol&&"symbol"===typeof Symbol.iterator?function(e){return typeof
e}:function(e){return e&&"function"===typeof

```

```

Symbol&&e.constructor===Symbol&&!Symbol.prototype?"symbol":typeof
e},c="Expected a function",f=NaN,s="[object Symbol]",d=/^\s+|\s+$/g,l=/^[-
+]0x[0-9a-f]+$/i,p=/^0b[01]+$/i,m=/^0o[0-
7]+$/i,b=parseInt,v="object"=="(undefined"==typeof
t?"undefined":u(t))&&t&&t.Object===Object&&t,y="object"=="(undefined"==typeof
self?"undefined":u(self))&&self&&self.Object===Object&&self,g=v||y|Function(
"return
this")(),h=Object.prototype,w=h.toString,k=Math.max,x=Math.min,j=function(){r
eturn g.Date.now()};e.exports=n}).call(t,function(){return
this}()),function(e,t){"use strict";function n(e,t){var n=new
r(o);a=t,n.observe(i.documentElement,{childList:!0,subtree:!0,removedNodes:!0
})}function o(e){e&&e.forEach(function(e){var
t=Array.prototype.slice.call(e.addedNodes),n=Array.prototype.slice.call(e.rem
ovedNodes),o=t.concat(n).filter(function(e){return
e.hasAttribute&&e.hasAttribute("data-
aos")}).length;o&&a({})}Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var
i=window.document,r=window.MutationObserver||window.WebKitMutationObserver||w
indow.MozMutationObserver,a=function(){};t.default=n},function(e,t){"use
strict";function n(e,t){if(!(e instanceof t))throw new TypeError("Cannot call
a class as a function")}function o(){return
navigator.userAgent||navigator.vendor||window.opera||""}Object.defineProperty
(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var i=function(){function e(e,t){for(var
n=0;n<t.length;n++){var
o=t[n];o.enumerable=o.enumerable||!1,o.configurable=!0,"value"in
o&&(o.writable=!0),Object.defineProperty(e,o.key,o)}return
function(t,n,o){return
n&&e(t.prototype,n),o&&e(t,o),t}}(),r="/(android|bb\d+|meego).+mobile|avantgo|
bada\/|blackberry|blazer|compal|elaine|fennec|hiptop|iemoible|ip(hone|od)|iri
s|kindle|lge|maemo|midp|mmp|mobile.+firefox|netfront|opera_m(ob|in)i|palm(
os)?|phone|p(ixi|re)|\/|plucker|pocket|psp|series(4|6)0|symbian|treo|up\.(brow
ser|link)|vodafone|wap|windows
ce|xda|xiino|i,a=/1207|6310|6590|3gso|4thp|50[1-6]i|770s|802s|a
wa|abac|ac(er|oo|s\-
)|ai(ko|rn)|al(av|ca|co)|amoi|an(ex|ny|yw)|aptu|ar(ch|go)|as(te|us)|attw|au(d
i|\-m|r|s )|avan|be(ck|ll|nq)|bi(lb|rd)|bl(ac|az)|br(e|v)w|bumb|bw\
(n|u)|c55\/|capi|ccwa|cdm\|-|cell|chtm|cldc|cmd\
|co(mp|nd)|craw|da(it|ll|ng)|dbte|dc\-s|devi|dica|dmob|do(c|p)o|ds(12|\-
d)|el(49|ai)|em(12|ul)|er(ic|k0)|esl8|ez([4-7]0|os|wa|ze)|fetc|fly(\-|_)|g1
u|g560|gene|gf\5|g\-mo|go(\.w|od)|gr(ad|un)|haie|hcit|hd\-(m|p|t)|hei\
|hi(pt|ta)|hp( i|ip)|hs\-c|ht(c\-\|_|a|g|p|s|t)|tp|hu(aw|tc)|i\
(20|go|ma)|i230|iac( |)\
|\/) |ibro|idea|ig01|ikom|im1k|inno|ipaq|iris|ja(t|v)a|jbro|jemu|jigs|kddi|kej
i|kgt( |\/)|klon|kpt |kwc\-|kyo(c|k)|le(no|xi)|lg( g|\/(k|l|u)|50|54|\-[a-
w])|libw|lynx|m1\-w|m3ga|m50\/|ma(te|ui|xo)|mc(01|21|ca)|m\
cr|me(rc|ri)|mi(o8|oa|ts)|mmef|mo(01|02|bi|de|do|t(\-| |o|v)|zz)|mt(50|p1|v
)|mwbp|mywa|n10[0-2]|n20[2-3]|n30(0|2)|n50(0|2|5)|n7(0(0|1)|10)|ne((c|m)\
|on|tf|wf|wg|wt)|nok(6|i)|nzph|o2im|op(ti|wv)|oran|owg1|p800|pan(a|d|t)|pdxg|
pg(13|\-(1-8)|c)|phil|pire|pl(ay|uc)|pn\2|po(ck|rt|se)|prox|psio|pt\
g|qa\-a|qc(07|12|21|32|60|\-[2-7])i\
)|qtek|r380|r600|raks|rim9|ro(ve|zo)|s55\/|sa(ge|ma|mm|ms|ny|va)|sc(01|h\
|oo|p\)|sdk\/|se(c\-\|0|1)|47|mc|nd|ri)|sgh\-\|shar|sie(\-|m)|sk\
0|sl(45|id)|sm(al|ar|b3|it|t5)|so(ft|ny)|sp(01|h\-\|v\-\|v
)|sy(01|mb)|t2(18|50)|t6(00|10|18)|ta(gt|lk)|tcl\-\|tdg\-\|tel(i|m)|tim\-\|t\
mo|to(pl|sh)|ts(70|m\-\|m3|m5)|tx\
9|up(\.b|g1|si)|utst|v400|v750|veri|vi(rg|te)|vk(40|5[0-3])\
v)|vm40|voda|vulc|vx(52|53|60|61|70|80|81|83|85|98)|w3c(\-| )|webc|whit|wi(g
|nc|nw)|wmlb|wonu|x700|yas\-\|your|zeto|zte\

```

```
/i,u=/ (android|bb\d+|meego) .+mobile|avantgo|bada\|blackberry|blazer|compal|elaine|fennec|hiptop|iemobile|ip(hone|od)|iris|kindle|lge|maemo|midp|mmp|mobile.+firefox|netfront|opera_m(ob|in)i|palm( os)?|phone|p(ixi|re)\|plucker|pocket|psp|series(4|6)0|symbian|treo|up\.(browser|link)|vodafone|wap|windows ce|xda|xiino|android|ipad|playbook|silk/i,c=/1207|6310|6590|3gso|4thp|50[1-6]i|770s|802s|a_walabac|ac(er|oo|s\- )|ai(ko|rn)|al(av|ca|co)|amoi|an(ex|ny|yw)|aptu|ar(ch|go)|as(te|us)|attw|au(d|i|-m|r|s )|avan|be(ck|ll|nq)|bi(lb|rd)|bl(ac|az)|br(e|v)w|bumb|bw\-(n|u)|c55\|capi|ccwa|cdm\|-|cell|chtm|cldc|cmd\|-|co(mp|nd)|craw|da(it|ll|ng)|dbte|dc\-s|devi|dica|dmob|do(c|p)o|ds(12|\-d)|el(49|ai)|em(12|ul)|er(ic|k0)|esl8|ez([4-7]0|os|wa|ze)|fetc|fly(\-|_)|g1 u|g560|gene|gf\-5|g\|-mo|go(\.w|od)|gr(ad|un)|haie|hcrit|hd\-(m|p|t)|hei\-\|hi(pt|ta)|hp( i|ip)|hs\-c|ht(c\-\|_|a|g|p|s|t)|tp)|hu(aw|tc)|i\-(20|go|ma)|i230|iac( | \-|\/)|ibro|idea|ig01|ikom|im1k|inno|ipaq|iris|ja(t|v)a|jbro|jemu|jigs|kddi|keji|kgt( |\/)|klon|kpt |kwc\|-|kyo(c|k)|le(no|xi)|lg( g|\/|(k|l|u)|50|54|\-[a-w])|libw|lynx|m1\-w|m3ga|m50\|ma(te|ui|xo)|mc(01|21|ca)|m\-\cr|me(rc|ri)|mi(o8|oa|ts)|mmef|mo(01|02|bi|de|do|t(\-| |o|v)|zz)|mt(50|p1|v )|mwbp|mywa|n10[0-2]|n20[2-3]|n30(0|2)|n50(0|2|5)|n7(0(0|1)|10)|ne((c|m)\-|on|tf|wf|wg|wt)|nok(6|i)|nzph|o2im|op(ti|wv)|oran|owg1|p800|pan(a|d|t)|pdxg|pg(13|\-([1-8]|c))|phil|pire|pl(ay|uc)|pn\-\2|po(ck|rt|se)|prox|psio|pt\-\g|qa\-\a|qc(07|12|21|32|60|\-\[2-7]|i\-\ )|qtek|r380|r600|raks|rim9|ro(ve|zo)|s55\|sa(ge|ma|mm|ms|ny|va)|sc(01|h\-\|oo|p\-\)|sdk\|se(c\-\|0|1)|47|mc(nd|ri)|sgh\-\|shar|sie(\-|m)|sk\-\0|sl(45|id)|sm(al|ar|b3|it|t5)|so(ft|ny)|sp(01|h\-\|v\-\|v )|sy(01|mb)|t2(18|50)|t6(00|10|18)|ta(gt|lk)|tcl\-\|tdg\-\|tel(i|m)|tim\-\|t\-\mo|to(pl|sh)|ts(70|m\-\|m3|m5)|tx\-\9|up(\.b|g|l|si)|utst|v400|v750|veri|vi(rg|te)|vk(40|5[0-3])\-\v|vm40|voda|vulc|vx(52|53|60|61|70|80|81|83|85|98)|w3c(\-| )|webc|whit|wi(g|nc|nw)|wmlb|wonu|x700|yas\-\|your|zeto|zte\-\ /i,f=function(){function e(){n(this,e)}return i(e,[{key:"phone",value:function(){var e=o();return(!r.test(e)&&!a.test(e.substr(0,4)))}},{key:"mobile",value:func tion(){var e=o();return(!u.test(e)&&!c.test(e.substr(0,4)))}},{key:"tablet",value:func tion(){return this.mobile()&&!this.phone()}}]),e());t.default=new f},function(e,t){"use strict";Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var n=function(e,t,n){var o=e.node.getAttribute("data-aos-once");t>e.position?e.node.classList.add("aos-animate"):"undefined"!==typeof o&&("false"===o||!n&&"true"!==o)&&e.node.classList.remove("aos-animate");o=function(e,t){var o=window.pageYOffset,i=window.innerHeight;e.forEach(function(e,r){n(e,i+o,t)});t.default=o},function(e,t,n){"use strict";function o(e){return e&&e.__esModule?e:{default:e}}Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var i=n(12),r=o(i),a=function(e,t){return e.forEach(function(e,n){e.node.classList.add("aos-init"),e.position=(0,r.default)(e.node,t.offset)}),e};t.default=a},function(e,t,n){"use strict";function o(e){return e&&e.__esModule?e:{default:e}}Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var i=n(13),r=o(i),a=function(e,t){var n=0,o=0,i=window.innerHeight,a={offset:e.getAttribute("data-aos-offset"),anchor:e.getAttribute("data-aos-anchor"),anchorPlacement:e.getAttribute("data-aos-anchor-placement")};switch(a.offset&&!isNaN(a.offset)&&(o=parseInt(a.offset)),a.anchor&&document.querySelectorAll(a.anchor)&&(e=document.querySelectorAll(a.anch or)[0]),n=(0,r.default)(e).top,a.anchorPlacement){case"top-
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bottom":break;case"center-bottom":n+=e.offsetHeight/2;break;case"bottom-  
bottom":n+=e.offsetHeight;break;case"top-center":n+=i/2;break;case"bottom-  
center":n+=i/2+e.offsetHeight;break;case"center-  
center":n+=i/2+e.offsetHeight/2;break;case"top-top":n+=i;break;case"bottom-  
top":n+=e.offsetHeight+i;break;case"center-top":n+=e.offsetHeight/2+i}return  
a.anchorPlacement||a.offset||isNaN(t)||o=t,n+o};t.default=a},function(e,t){  
"use strict";Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var  
n=function(e){for(var  
t=0,n=0;e&&!isNaN(e.offsetLeft)&&!isNaN(e.offsetTop);)t+=e.offsetLeft-  
("BODY"!=e.tagName?e.scrollLeft:0),n+=e.offsetTop-  
("BODY"!=e.tagName?e.scrollTop:0),e=e.offsetParent;return{top:n,left:t}};t.de  
fault=n},function(e,t){"use  
strict";Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0});var  
n=function(e){return e=e|document.querySelectorAll("[data-  
aos]"),Array.prototype.map.call(e,function(e){return{node:e}})};t.default=n]  
});
```

Bootstrap.mini.js

```
/*!
 * Bootstrap v4.2.1 (https://getbootstrap.com/)
 * Copyright 2011-2018 The Bootstrap Authors
 * Licensed under MIT
 * (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */
!function(t,e){"object"==typeof exports&&"undefined"!=typeof module?e(exports,require("popper.js"),require("jquery")):"function"==typeof define&&define.amd?define(["exports","popper.js","jquery"],e):e(t.bootstrap={},t.Popper,t.jQuery)}(this,function(t,u,g){"use strict";function i(t,e){for(var n=0;n<e.length;n++){var i=e[n];i.enumerable=i.enumerable||!1,i.configurable=!0,"value"in i&&(i.writable=!0),Object.defineProperty(t,i.key,i)}}function s(t,e,n){return e&&i(t.prototype,e),n&&i(t,n),t}function l(o){for(var t=1;t<arguments.length;t++){var r=null!=arguments[t]?arguments[t]:{};e=Object.keys(r);"function"==typeof Object.getOwnPropertySymbols&&(e=e.concat(Object.getOwnPropertySymbols(r).filter(function(t){return Object.getOwnPropertyDescriptor(r,t).enumerable}))),e.forEach(function(t){var e,n,i;e=o,i=r[n=t],n in e?Object.defineProperty(e,n,{value:i,enumerable:!0,configurable:!0,writable:!0}):e[n]=i})}return o}u=u&&u.hasOwnProperty("default"?u.default:u,g=g&&g.hasOwnProperty("default"?g.default:g;var e="transitionend";function n(t){var e=this,n=!1;return g(this).one(_.TRANSITION_END,function(){n=!0}),setTimeout(function(){n||_.triggerTransitionEnd(e)},t),this}var _={TRANSITION_END:"bsTransitionEnd",getUID:function(t){for(;t+~~(1e6*Math.random()),document.getElementById(t););return t},getSelectorFromElement:function(t){var e=t.getAttribute("data-target");if(!e||"#"===e){var n=t.getAttribute("href");e=n&&"#"!==n?n.trim():""}return e&&document.querySelector(e)?e:null},getTransitionDurationFromElement:function(t){if(!t)return 0;var e=g(t).css("transition-duration"),n=g(t).css("transition-delay"),i=parseFloat(e),o=parseFloat(n);return i||o?(e=e.split(",")[0],n=n.split(",")[0],1e3*(parseFloat(e)+parseFloat(n))):0},reflow:function(t){return t.offsetHeight},triggerTransitionEnd:function(t){g(t).trigger(e)},supportsTransitionEnd:function(){return Boolean(e)},isElement:function(t){return t[0]||t.nodeType},typeCheckConfig:function(t,e,n){for(var i in n)if(Object.prototype.hasOwnProperty.call(n,i)){var o=n[i],r=e[i],s=r&&_.isElement(r)?"element":(a=r,{}.toString.call(a).match(/\s([a-z]+)/i)[1].toLowerCase());if(!new RegExp(o).test(s))throw new Error(t.toUpperCase()+': Option "'+i+'" provided type "'+s+'" but expected type "'+o+'".')}}var a),findShadowRoot:function(t){if(!document.documentElement.attachShadow)return null;if("function"!=typeof t.getRootNode)return t instanceof ShadowRoot?t:t.parentNode?_.findShadowRoot(t.parentNode):null;var e=t.getRootNode();return e instanceof ShadowRoot?e:null};g.fn.emulateTransitionEnd=n,g.event.special[_.TRANSITION
```

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END]={bindType:e,delegateType:e,handle:function(t){if(g(t.target).is(this))return t.handleObj.handler.apply(this,arguments)};var
o="alert",r="bs.alert",a="."+r,c=g.fn[o],h={CLOSE:"close"+a,CLOSED:"closed"+a
,CLICK_DATA_API:"click"+a+".data-
api"},f="alert",d="fade",m="show",p=function(){function
i(t){this._element=t}var t=i.prototype;return t.close=function(t){var
e=this._element;t&&(e=this._getRootElement(t)),this._triggerCloseEvent(e).isD
efaultPrevented()||this._removeElement(e)},t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(
this._element,r),this._element=null},t._getRootElement=function(t){var
e=_getSelectorFromElement(t),n=!1;return
e&&(n=document.querySelector(e)),n||(n=g(t).closest("."+f)[0]),n},t._triggerC
loseEvent=function(t){var e=g.Event(h.CLOSE);return
g(t).trigger(e,e),t._removeElement=function(e){var
n=this;if(g(e).removeClass(m),g(e).hasClass(d)){var
t=_getTransitionDurationFromElement(e);g(e).one(_.TRANSITION_END,function(t)
{return n._destroyElement(e,t)}).emulateTransitionEnd(t)}else
this._destroyElement(e)},t._destroyElement=function(t){g(t).detach().trigger(
h.CLOSED).remove()},i._jQueryInterface=function(n){return
this.each(function(){var t=g(this),e=t.data(r);e||(e=new
i(this),t.data(r,e)),"close"===n&&e[n](this)}),i._handleDismiss=function(e){
return
function(t){t&&t.preventDefault(),e.close(this)},s(i,null,[{key:"VERSION",ge
t:function(){return"4.2.1"}}]),i)});g(document).on(h.CLICK_DATA_API,'[data-
dismiss="alert"]',p._handleDismiss(new
p)),g.fn[o]=p._jQueryInterface,g.fn[o].Constructor=p,g.fn[o].noConflict=funct
ion(){return g.fn[o]=c,p._jQueryInterface};var
v="button",E="bs.button",y="."+E,C="."+E,
api",T=g.fn[v],S="active",b="btn",I="focus",D='[data-
toggle^="button"]',w='[data-
toggle="buttons"]',A='input:not([type="hidden"])',N=".active",O=".btn",k={CLI
CK_DATA_API:"click"+y+C,FOCUS_BLUR_DATA_API:"focus"+y+C+"
blur"+y+C},P=function(){function n(t){this._element=t}var
t=n.prototype;return t.toggle=function(){var
t=!0,e=!0,n=g(this._element).closest(w)[0];if(n){var
i=this._element.querySelector(A);if(i){if("radio"===i.type)if(i.checked&&this
._element.classList.contains(S))t=!1;else{var
o=n.querySelector(N);o&&g(o).removeClass(S)}if(t){if(i.hasAttribute("disabled")
||n.hasAttribute("disabled")||i.classList.contains("disabled")||n.classList
.contains("disabled"))return;i.checked=!this._element.classList.contains(S),g
(i).trigger("change")}i.focus(),e=!1}}e&&this._element.setAttribute("aria-
pressed",!this._element.classList.contains(S)),t&&g(this._element).toggleClas
s(S)},t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(this._element,E),this._element=null},
n._jQueryInterface=function(e){return this.each(function(){var
t=g(this).data(E);t||(t=new
n(this),g(this).data(E,t)),"toggle"===e&&t[e]()}),s(n,null,[{key:"VERSION",g
et:function(){return"4.2.1"}}]),n)});g(document).on(k.CLICK_DATA_API,D,functi
on(t){t.preventDefault();var
e=t.target;g(e).hasClass(b)||e=g(e).closest(O),P._jQueryInterface.call(g(e)
,"toggle")).on(k.FOCUS_BLUR_DATA_API,D,function(t){var
e=g(t.target).closest(O)[0];g(e).toggleClass(I,/^(focus(in)?$/).test(t.type)
)},g.fn[v]=P._jQueryInterface,g.fn[v].Constructor=P,g.fn[v].noConflict=functi
on(){return g.fn[v]=T,P._jQueryInterface};var
L="carousel",j="bs.carousel",H="."+j,R="."+j,
api",U=g.fn[L],W={interval:5e3,keyboard:!0,slide:!1,pause:"hover",wrap:!0,tou
ch:!0},x={interval:"(number|boolean)",keyboard:"boolean",slide:"(boolean|stri
ng)",pause:"(string|boolean)",wrap:"boolean",touch:"boolean"},F="next",q="pre
v",M="left",K="right",Q={SLIDE:"slide"+H,SLID:"slid"+H,KEYDOWN:"keydown"+H,MO

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USEENTER:"mouseenter"+H,MOUSELEAVE:"mouseleave"+H,TOUCHSTART:"touchstart"+H,T
OUCHMOVE:"touchmove"+H,TOUCHEND:"touchend"+H,POINTERDOWN:"pointerdown"+H,POIN
TERUP:"pointerup"+H,DRAG_START:"dragstart"+H,LOAD_DATA_API:"load"+H+R,CLICK_D
ATA_API:"click"+H+R},B="carousel",V="active",Y="slide",X="carousel-item-
right",z="carousel-item-left",G="carousel-item-next",J="carousel-item-
prev",Z="pointer-event",$=".active",tt=".active.carousel-item",et=".carousel-
item",nt=".carousel-item img",it=".carousel-item-next, .carousel-item-
prev",ot=".carousel-indicators",rt="[data-slide], [data-slide-to]",st="[data-
ride="carousel"]',at={TOUCH:"touch",PEN:"pen"},lt=function() {function
r(t,e){this._items=null,this._interval=null,this._activeElement=null,this._is
Paused=!1,this._isSliding=!1,this.touchTimeout=null,this.touchStartX=0,this.t
ouchDeltaX=0,this._config=this._getConfig(e),this._element=t,this._indicators
Element=this._element.querySelector(ot),this._touchSupported="ontouchstart"in
document.documentElement||0<navigator.maxTouchPoints,this._pointerEvent=Boole
an(window.PointerEvent||window.MSPointerEvent),this._addEventListenerListeners()}var
t=r.prototype;return
t.next=function(){this._isSliding||this._slide(F)},t.nextWhenVisible=function
(){!document.hidden&&g(this._element).is(":visible")&&"hidden"!==g(this._elem
ent).css("visibility")&&this.next()},t.prev=function(){this._isSliding||this.
_slide(q)},t.pause=function(t){t||(this._isPaused=!0),this._element.querySele
ctor(it)&&(_ .triggerTransitionEnd(this._element),this.cycle(!0)),clearInterva
l(this._interval),this._interval=null},t.cycle=function(t){t||(this._isPaused
=!1),this._interval&&(clearInterval(this._interval),this._interval=null),this
._config.interval&&!this._isPaused&&(this._interval=setInterval((document.vis
ibilityState?this.nextWhenVisible:this.next).bind(this),this._config.interval
)),t.to=function(t){var
e=this;this._activeElement=this._element.querySelector(tt);var
n=this._getItemIndex(this._activeElement);if(!(t>this._items.length-
1||t<0))if(this._isSliding)g(this._element).one(Q.SLID,function(){return
e.to(t)});else{if(n===t)return this.pause(),void this.cycle();var
i=n<t?F:q;this._slide(i,this._items[t])},t.dispose=function(){g(this._elemen
t).off(H),g.removeData(this._element,j),this._items=null,this._config=null,th
is._element=null,this._interval=null,this._isPaused=null,this._isSliding=null
,this._activeElement=null,this._indicatorsElement=null},t._getConfig=function
(t){return
t=l({},W,t),_.typeCheckConfig(L,t,x),t},t._handleSwipe=function(){var
t=Math.abs(this.touchDeltaX);if(!(t<=40)){var
e=t/this.touchDeltaX;0<e&&this.prev(),e<0&&this.next()}},t._addEventListenerListeners
=function(){var
e=this;this._config.keyboard&&g(this._element).on(Q.KEYDOWN,function(t){retur
n
e._keydown(t)}),"hover"===this._config.pause&&g(this._element).on(Q.MOUSEENTE
R,function(t){return e.pause(t)}).on(Q.MOUSELEAVE,function(t){return
e.cycle(t)}),this._addTouchEventListeners(),t._addTouchEventListeners=functi
on(){var n=this;if(this._touchSupported){var
e=function(t){n._pointerEvent&&at[t.originalEvent.pointerType.toUpperCase()]?
n.touchStartX=t.originalEvent.clientX:n._pointerEvent||(n.touchStartX=t.origi
nalEvent.touches[0].clientX)},i=function(t){n._pointerEvent&&at[t.originalEve
nt.pointerType.toUpperCase()]&&(n.touchDeltaX=t.originalEvent.clientX-
n.touchStartX),n._handleSwipe(),"hover"===n._config.pause&&(n.pause(),n.touch
Timeout&&clearTimeout(n.touchTimeout),n.touchTimeout=setTimeout(function(t){r
eturn
n.cycle(t)},500+n._config.interval))};g(this._element.querySelectorAll(nt)).o
n(Q.DRAG_START,function(t){return
t.preventDefault()}),this._pointerEvent?(g(this._element).on(Q.POINTERDOWN,fu
nction(t){return e(t)}),g(this._element).on(Q.POINTERUP,function(t){return
i(t)}),this._element.classList.add(Z)):g(this._element).on(Q.TOUCHSTART,func

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tion(t){return e(t)},g(this._element).on(Q.TOUCHMOVE,function(t){var
e;(e=t).originalEvent.touches&&1<e.originalEvent.touches.length?n.touchDeltaX
=0:n.touchDeltaX=e.originalEvent.touches[0].clientX-
n.touchStartX}),g(this._element).on(Q.TOUCHEND,function(t){return
i(t)}))}},t._keydown=function(t){if(!/input|textarea/i.test(t.target.tagName)
)switch(t.which){case 37:t.preventDefault(),this.prev();break;case
39:t.preventDefault(),this.next()}},t._getItemIndex=function(t){return
this._items=t&&t.parentNode?.slice.call(t.parentNode.querySelectorAll(et)):
[],this._items.indexOf(t)},t._getItemByDirection=function(t,e){var
n=t===F,i=t===q,o=this._getItemIndex(e),r=this._items.length-
1;if((i&&0===o|n&&o===r)&&!this._config.wrap)return e;var s=(o+(t===q?-
1:1))%this._items.length;return-1===s?this._items[this._items.length-
1]:this._items[s]},t._triggerSlideEvent=function(t,e){var
n=this._getItemIndex(t),i=this._getItemIndex(this._element.querySelector(tt)
),o=g.Event(Q.SLIDE,{relatedTarget:t,direction:e,from:i,to:n});return
g(this._element).trigger(o,o),t._setActiveIndicatorElement=function(t){if(th
is._indicatorsElement){var
e=[] slice.call(this._indicatorsElement.querySelectorAll($));g(e).removeClass
(V);var
n=this._indicatorsElement.children[this._getItemIndex(t)];n&&g(n).addClass(V)
}},t._slide=function(t,e){var
n,i,o,r=this,s=this._element.querySelector(tt),a=this._getItemIndex(s),l=e||s
&&this._getItemByDirection(t,s),c=this._getItemIndex(l),h=Boolean(this._inter
val);if(o=t===F?(n=z,i=G,M):(n=X,i=J,K),l&&g(l).hasClass(V))this._isSliding=!
1;else
if(!this._triggerSlideEvent(l,o).isDefaultPrevented()&&s&&l){this._isSliding=
!0,h&&this.pause(),this._setActiveIndicatorElement(l);var
u=g.Event(Q.SLID,{relatedTarget:l,direction:o,from:a,to:c});if(g(this._elemen
t).hasClass(Y)){g(l).addClass(i),_.reflow(l),g(s).addClass(n),g(l).addClass(n)
);var f=parseInt(l.getAttribute("data-
interval"),10);this._config.interval=f?(this._config.defaultInterval=this._co
nfig.defaultInterval||this._config.interval,f):this._config.defaultInterval||
this._config.interval;var
d=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(s);g(s).one(_.TRANSITION_END,function(){
g(l).removeClass(n+" "+i).addClass(V),g(s).removeClass(V+" "+i+"
"+n),r._isSliding=!1,setTimeout(function(){return
g(r._element).trigger(u)},0)}.emulateTransitionEnd(d)}else
g(s).removeClass(V),g(l).addClass(V),this._isSliding=!1,g(this._element).trig
ger(u);h&&this.cycle()}},r._jQueryInterface=function(i){return
this.each(function(){var
t=g(this).data(j),e=l({},W,g(this).data());"object"===typeof
i&&(e=l({},e,i));var n="string"===typeof i?i:e.slide;if(t||t=new
r(this,e),g(this).data(j,t),"number"===typeof i)t.to(i);else
if("string"===typeof n){if("undefined"===typeof t[n])throw new TypeError('No
method named "'+n+'");t[n]() }else
e.interval&&(t.pause(),t.cycle())}},r._dataApiClickHandler=function(t){var
e=_.getSelectorFromElement(this);if(e){var
n=g(e)[0];if(n&&g(n).hasClass(B)){var
i=l({},g(n).data(),g(this).data()),o=this.getAttribute("data-slide-
to");o&&(i.interval=!1),r._jQueryInterface.call(g(n),i),o&&g(n).data(j).to(o)
,t.preventDefault()}}},s(r,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}
},{key:"Default",get:function(){return
W}}]),r)();g(document).on(Q.CLICK_DATA_API,rt,lt._dataApiClickHandler),g(wind
ow).on(Q.LOAD_DATA_API,function(){for(var
t=[] slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(st)),e=0,n=t.length;e<n;e++){var
i=g(t[e]);lt._jQueryInterface.call(i,i.data())}},g.fn[L]=lt._jQueryInterface
,g.fn[L].Constructor=lt,g.fn[L].noConflict=function(){return

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g.fn[L]=U,lt._jQueryInterface};var
ct="collapse",ht="bs.collapse",ut="."+ht,ft=g.fn[ct],dt={toggle:!0,parent:""}
,gt={toggle:"boolean",parent:"(string|element)",_t={SHOW:"show"+ut,SHOWN:"sh
own"+ut,HIDE:"hide"+ut,HIDDEN:"hidden"+ut,CLICK_DATA_API:"click"+ut+".data-
api"},mt="show",pt="collapse",vt="collapsing",Et="collapsed",yt="width",Ct="h
eight",Tt=".show, .collapsing",St='[data-
toggle="collapse"]',bt=function(){function
a(e,t){this._isTransitioning=!1,this._element=e,this._config=this._getConfig(
t),this._triggerArray=[]}.slice.call(document.querySelectorAll('[data-
toggle="collapse"][href="#'+e.id+'"]',[data-toggle="collapse"][data-
target="#'+e.id+'"]'));for(var
n=[]}.slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(St)),i=0,o=n.length;i<o;i++){var
r=n[i],s=_getSelectorFromElement(r),a=[]}.slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(s)).filter(function(t){return
t===e});null!==s&&0<a.length&&(this._selector=s,this._triggerArray.push(r))}t
his._parent=this._config.parent?this._getParent():null,this._config.parent||t
his._addAriaAndCollapsedClass(this._element,this._triggerArray),this._config.
toggle&&this.toggle()}var t=a.prototype;return
t.toggle=function(){g(this._element).hasClass(mt)?this.hide():this.show()},t.
show=function(){var
t,e,n=this;if(!this._isTransitioning&&!g(this._element).hasClass(mt)&&(this._
parent&&0===t=[]}.slice.call(this._parent.querySelectorAll(Tt)).filter(funciti
on(t){return"string"===typeof n._config.parent?t.getAttribute("data-
parent")===n._config.parent:t.classList.contains(pt)})).length&&(t=null),!(t&
&(e=g(t).not(this._selector).data(ht))&&e._isTransitioning)){var
i=g.Event(_t.SHOW);if(g(this._element).trigger(i),!i.isDefaultPrevented()){t&
&(a._jQueryInterface.call(g(t).not(this._selector),"hide"),e||g(t).data(ht,nu
ll));var
o=this._getDimension();g(this._element).removeClass(pt).addClass(vt),this._el
ement.style[o]=0,this._triggerArray.length&&g(this._triggerArray).removeClass
(Et).attr("aria-expanded",!0),this.setTransitioning(!0);var
r="scroll"+(o[0].toUpperCase()+o.slice(1)),s=_getTransitionDurationFromEleme
nt(this._element);g(this._element).one(_TRANSITION_END,function(){g(n._eleme
nt).removeClass(vt).addClass(pt).addClass(mt),n._element.style[o]="",n.setTra
nsitioning(!1),g(n._element).trigger(_t.SHOWN)}).emulateTransitionEnd(s),this
._element.style[o]=this._element[r]+"px"}}},t.hide=function(){var
t=this;if(!this._isTransitioning&&g(this._element).hasClass(mt)){var
e=g.Event(_t.HIDE);if(g(this._element).trigger(e),!e.isDefaultPrevented()){va
r
n=this._getDimension();this._element.style[n]=this._element.getBoundingClientRect()[n]+"px",_.reflow(this._element),g(this._element).addClass(vt).removeCl
ass(pt).removeClass(mt);var i=this._triggerArray.length;if(0<i)for(var
o=0;o<i;o++){var
r=this._triggerArray[o],s=_getSelectorFromElement(r);if(null!==s)g([]}.slice.
call(document.querySelectorAll(s)).hasClass(mt)||g(r).addClass(Et).attr("ari
a-expanded",!1)}this.setTransitioning(!0);this._element.style[n]="";var
a=_getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._element);g(this._element).one(_TR
ANSITION_END,function(){t.setTransitioning(!1),g(t._element).removeClass(vt).
addClass(pt).trigger(_t.HIDDEN)}).emulateTransitionEnd(a)}},t.setTransitioni
ng=function(t){this._isTransitioning=t},t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(thi
s._element,ht),this._config=null,this._parent=null,this._element=null,this._t
riggerArray=null,this._isTransitioning=null},t._getConfig=function(t){return(
t=l({},dt,t)).toggle=Boolean(t.toggle),_.typeCheckConfig(ct,t,gt),t},t._getDi
mension=function(){return
g(this._element).hasClass(yt)?yt:Ct},t._getParent=function(){var
t,n=this;_.isElement(this._config.parent)?(t=this._config.parent,"undefined"!
=typeof

```

```

this._config.parent.jquery&&(t=this._config.parent[0]):t=document.querySelec
tor(this._config.parent);var e='[data-toggle="collapse"][data-
parent="'+this._config.parent+'"]',i=[] .slice.call(t.querySelectorAll(e));ret
urn
g(i).each(function(t,e){n._addAriaAndCollapsedClass(a._getTargetFromElement(e
),[e])),t,t._addAriaAndCollapsedClass=function(t,e){var
n=g(t).hasClass(mt);e.length&&g(e).toggleClass(Et,!n).attr("aria-
expanded",n)},a._getTargetFromElement=function(t){var
e=_getSelectorFromElement(t);return
e?document.querySelector(e):null},a._jQueryInterface=function(i){return
this.each(function(){var
t=g(this),e=t.data(ht),n=l({},dt,t.data(),"object"==typeof
i&&i?i:{});if(!e&&n.toggle&&/show|hide/.test(i)&&(n.toggle=!1),e||(e=new
a(this,n),t.data(ht,e)),"string"==typeof i){if("undefined"==typeof e[i])throw
new TypeError('No method named
'+i+'');e[i]()}}),s(a,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}},
{key:"Default",get:function(){return
dt}}]),a}());g(document).on(_t.CLICK_DATA_API,St,function(t){"A"===t.currentTa
rget.tagName&&t.preventDefault();var
n=g(this),e=_getSelectorFromElement(this),i=[] .slice.call(document.querySele
ctorAll(e));g(i).each(function(){var
t=g(this),e=t.data(ht)?"toggle":n.data();bt._jQueryInterface.call(t,e)})),g.
fn[ct]=bt._jQueryInterface,g.fn[ct].Constructor=bt,g.fn[ct].noConflict=functi
on(){return g.fn[ct]=ft,bt._jQueryInterface};var
It="dropdown",Dt="bs.dropdown",wt="."+Dt,At=".data-api",Nt=g.fn[It],Ot=new
RegExp("38|40|27"),kt={HIDE:"hide"+wt,HIDDEN:"hidden"+wt,SHOW:"show"+wt,SHOWN
:"shown"+wt,CLICK:"click"+wt,CLICK_DATA_API:"click"+wt+At,KEYDOWN_DATA_API:"k
eydown"+wt+At,KEYUP_DATA_API:"keyup"+wt+At},Pt="disabled",Lt="show",jt="dropu
p",Ht="dropright",Rt="dropleft",Ut="dropdown-menu-right",Wt="position-
static",xt='[data-toggle="dropdown"]',Ft=".dropdown-form",qt=".dropdown-
menu",Mt=".navbar-nav",Kt=".dropdown-menu .dropdown-
item:not(.disabled):not(:disabled)",Qt="top-start",Bt="top-end",Vt="bottom-
start",Yt="bottom-end",Xt="right-start",zt="left-
start",Gt={offset:0,flip:!0,boundary:"scrollParent",reference:"toggle",displa
y:"dynamic"},Jt={offset:"(number|string|function)",flip:"boolean",boundary:"(
string|element)",reference:"(string|element)",display:"string"},Zt=function()
{function
c(t,e){this._element=t,this._popper=null,this._config=this._getConfig(e),this
._menu=this._getMenuElement(),this._inNavbar=this._detectNavbar(),this._addEv
entListeners()}var t=c.prototype;return
t.toggle=function(){if(!this._element.disabled&&!g(this._element).hasClass(Pt
)){var
t=c._getParentFromElement(this._element),e=g(this._menu).hasClass(Lt);if(c._c
learMenus(),!e){var
n={relatedTarget:this._element},i=g.Event(kt.SHOW,n);if(g(t).trigger(i),!i.is
DefaultPrevented()){if(!this._inNavbar){if("undefined"==typeof u)throw new
TypeError("Bootstrap's dropdowns require Popper.js
(https://popper.js.org/)");var
o=this._element;"parent"===this._config.reference?o=t._isElement(this._confi
g.reference)&&(o=this._config.reference,"undefined"!==typeof
this._config.reference.jquery&&(o=this._config.reference[0])), "scrollParent"!
===this._config.boundary&&g(t).addClass(Wt),this._popper=new
u(o,this._menu,this._getPopperConfig())}"ontouchstart"in
document.documentElement&&0===g(t).closest(Mt).length&&g(document.body).child
ren().on("mouseover",null,g.noop),this._element.focus(),this._element.setAttr
ibute("aria-
expanded",!0),g(this._menu).toggleClass(Lt),g(t).toggleClass(Lt).trigger(g.Ev

```

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ent(kt.SHOWN,n))}}},t.show=function(){if(!(this._element.disabled||g(this._element).hasClass(Pt)||g(this._menu).hasClass(Lt))){var
t={relatedTarget:this._element},e=g.Event(kt.SHOW,t),n=c._getParentFromElement(this._element);g(n).trigger(e),e.isDefaultPrevented()||(g(this._menu).toggleClass(Lt),g(n).toggleClass(Lt).trigger(g.Event(kt.SHOWN,t)))}},t.hide=function(){if(!this._element.disabled&&!g(this._element).hasClass(Pt)&&g(this._menu).hasClass(Lt)){var
t={relatedTarget:this._element},e=g.Event(kt.HIDE,t),n=c._getParentFromElement(this._element);g(n).trigger(e),e.isDefaultPrevented()||(g(this._menu).toggleClass(Lt),g(n).toggleClass(Lt).trigger(g.Event(kt.HIDDEN,t)))}},t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(this._element,Dt),g(this._element).off(wt),this._element=null,(this._menu=null)!=this._popper&&(this._popper.destroy(),this._popper=null)},t.update=function(){this._inNavbar=this._detectNavbar(),null!=this._popper&&this._popper.scheduleUpdate()},t._addEventListeners=function(){var
e=this;g(this._element).on(kt.CLICK,function(t){t.preventDefault(),t.stopPropagation(),e.toggle()})},t._getConfig=function(t){return
t=l({},this.constructor.Default,g(this._element).data(),t),_.typeCheckConfig(It,t,this.constructor.DefaultType),t},t._getMenuElement=function(){if(!this._menu){var
t=c._getParentFromElement(this._element);t&&(this._menu=t.querySelector(qt))}return this._menu},t._getPlacement=function(){var
t=g(this._element.parentNode),e=Vt;return
t.hasClass(jt)?(e=Qt,g(this._menu).hasClass(Ut)&&(e=Bt)):t.hasClass(Ht)?e=Xt:t.hasClass(Rt)?e=zt:g(this._menu).hasClass(Ut)&&(e=Yt),e},t._detectNavbar=function(){return
0<g(this._element).closest(".navbar").length},t._getPopperConfig=function(){var
e=this,t={};"function"===typeof this._config.offset?t.fn=function(t){return
t.offsets=l({},t.offsets,e._config.offset(t.offsets)||{}),t}:t.offset=this._config.offset;var
n={placement:this._getPlacement(),modifiers:{offset:t,flip:{enabled:this._config.flip},preventOverflow:{boundariesElement:this._config.boundary}}};return
"static"===this._config.display&&(n.modifiers.applyStyle={enabled:!1}),n},c._jQueryInterface=function(e){return this.each(function(){var
t=g(this).data(Dt);if(t||(t=new c(this,"object"===typeof
e?e:null),g(this).data(Dt,t)),"string"===typeof e){if("undefined"===typeof
t[e])throw new TypeError("No method named
"+e+"");t[e]()}}},c._clearMenus=function(t){if(!t||3!==t.which&&("keyup"!==t.type||9===t.which))for(var
e=[] .slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(xt)),n=0,i=e.length;n<i;n++){var
o=c._getParentFromElement(e[n]),r=g(e[n]).data(Dt),s={relatedTarget:e[n]};if(t&&"click"===t.type&&(s.clickEvent=t),r){var
a=r._menu;if(g(o).hasClass(Lt)&&!(t&&("click"===t.type&&/input|textarea|input.test(t.target.tagName)||"keyup"===t.type&&9===t.which)&&g.contains(o,t.target))){var
l=g.Event(kt.HIDE,s);g(o).trigger(l),l.isDefaultPrevented()||("ontouchstart"i
n
document.documentElement&&g(document.body).children().off("mouseover",null,g.noop),e[n].setAttribute("aria-
expanded","false"),g(a).removeClass(Lt),g(o).removeClass(Lt).trigger(g.Event(kt.HIDDEN,s)))}}},c._getParentFromElement=function(t){var
e,n=_.getSelectorFromElement(t);return
n&&(e=document.querySelector(n)),e||t.parentNode},c._dataApiKeydownHandler=function(t){if((/input|textarea/i.test(t.target.tagName)?!(32===t.which||27===t.which&&(40===t.which&&38===t.which||g(t.target).closest(qt).length)):Ot.test(t.which))&&(t.preventDefault(),t.stopPropagation(),!this.disabled&&!g(this).hasClass(Pt))){var
e=c._getParentFromElement(this),n=g(e).hasClass(Lt);if(n&&(n||27===t.which&&

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32!==(t.which)) {var
i=[] .slice.call(e.querySelectorAll(Kt));if(0!==i.length) {var
o=i.indexOf(t.target);38===t.which&&0<o&&o--,40===t.which&&o<i.length-
1&&o++,o<0&&(o=0),i[o].focus()}}else{if(27===t.which) {var
r=e.querySelector(xt);g(r).trigger("focus")}g(this).trigger("click")}}},s(c,n
ull, [{key:"VERSION",get:function() {return"4.2.1"}}, {key:"Default",get:functio
n() {return Gt}}, {key:"DefaultType",get:function() {return
Jt}}]),c)();g(document).on(kt.KEYDOWN_DATA_API,xt,Zt._dataApiKeydownHandler).
on(kt.KEYDOWN_DATA_API,qt,Zt._dataApiKeydownHandler).on(kt.CLICK_DATA_API+"
"+kt.KEYUP_DATA_API,Zt._clearMenus).on(kt.CLICK_DATA_API,xt,function(t){t.pre
ventDefault(),t.stopPropagation(),Zt._jQueryInterface.call(g(this),"toggle")}
).on(kt.CLICK_DATA_API,Ft,function(t){t.stopPropagation()}),g.fn[It]=Zt._jQue
ryInterface,g.fn[It].Constructor=Zt,g.fn[It].noConflict=function() {return
g.fn[It]=Nt,Zt._jQueryInterface};var
$t="modal",te="bs.modal",ee="."+te,ne=g.fn[$t],ie={backdrop:!0,keyboard:!0,fo
cus:!0,show:!0},oe={backdrop:"(boolean|string)",keyboard:"boolean",focus:"boo
lean",show:"boolean"},re={HIDE:"hide"+ee,HIDDEN:"hidden"+ee,SHOW:"show"+ee,SH
OWN:"shown"+ee,FOCUSIN:"focusin"+ee,RESIZE:"resize"+ee,CLICK_DISMISS:"click.d
ismiss"+ee,KEYDOWN_DISMISS:"keydown.dismiss"+ee,MOUSEUP_DISMISS:"mouseup.dism
iss"+ee,MOUSEDOWN_DISMISS:"mousedown.dismiss"+ee,CLICK_DATA_API:"click"+ee+"
.data-api"},se="modal-scrollbar-measure",ae="modal-backdrop",le="modal-
open",ce="fade",he="show",ue=".modal-dialog",fe='[data-
toggle="modal"]',de='[data-dismiss="modal"]',ge=".fixed-top, .fixed-bottom,
.is-fixed, .sticky-top",_e=".sticky-top",me=function() {function
o(t,e){this._config=this._getConfig(e),this._element=t,this._dialog=t.querySe
lector(ue),this._backdrop=null,this._isShown=!1,this._isBodyOverflowing=!1,th
is._ignoreBackdropClick=!1,this._isTransitioning=!1,this._scrollbarWidth=0}va
r t=o.prototype;return t.toggle=function(t){return
this._isShown?this.hide():this.show(t)},t.show=function(t){var
e=this;if(!this._isShown&&!this._isTransitioning){g(this._element).hasClass(c
e)&&(this._isTransitioning=!0);var
n=g.Event(re.SHOW,{relatedTarget:t});g(this._element).trigger(n),this._isSho
wn||n.isDefaultPrevented()||(this._isShown=!0,this._checkScrollbar(),this._set
Scrollbar(),this._adjustDialog(),this._setEscapeEvent(),this._setResizeEvent(
),g(this._element).on(re.CLICK_DISMISS,de,function(t){return
e.hide(t)}),g(this._dialog).on(re.MOUSEDOWN_DISMISS,function() {g(e._element)
.one(re.MOUSEUP_DISMISS,function(t){g(t.target).is(e._element)&&(e._ignoreBack
dropClick=!0)}))},this._showBackdrop(function() {return
e._showElement(t)}))},t.hide=function(t){var
e=this;if(t&&t.preventDefault(),this._isShown&&!this._isTransitioning){var
n=g.Event(re.HIDE);if(g(this._element).trigger(n),this._isShown&&!n.isDefault
Prevented()){this._isShown=!1;var
i=g(this._element).hasClass(ce);if(i&&(this._isTransitioning=!0),this._setEsc
apeEvent(),this._setResizeEvent(),g(document).off(re.FOCUSIN),g(this._element
).removeClass(he),g(this._element).off(re.CLICK_DISMISS),g(this._dialog).off(
re.MOUSEDOWN_DISMISS),i){var
o=_ .getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._element);g(this._element).one(_ .TR
ANSITION_END,function(t){return
e._hideModal(t)}).emulateTransitionEnd(o)}else
this._hideModal()}}},t.dispose=function() {[window,this._element,this._dialog]
.forEach(function(t){return
g(t).off(ee)}),g(document).off(re.FOCUSIN),g.removeData(this._element,te),thi
s._config=null,this._element=null,this._dialog=null,this._backdrop=null,this
._isShown=null,this._isBodyOverflowing=null,this._ignoreBackdropClick=null,thi
s._isTransitioning=null,this._scrollbarWidth=null},t.handleUpdate=function() {
this._adjustDialog()},t._getConfig=function(t){return
t=l({},ie,t),_ .typeCheckConfig($t,t,oe),t},t._showElement=function(t){var

```

```

e=this,n=g(this._element).hasClass(ce);this._element.parentNode&&this._elemen
t.parentNode.nodeType===Node.ELEMENT_NODE||document.body.appendChild(this._el
ement),this._element.style.display="block",this._element.removeAttribute("ari
a-hidden"),this._element.setAttribute("aria-
modal",!0),this._element.scrollTop=0,n&&_.reflow(this._element),g(this._eleme
nt).addClass(he),this._config.focus&&this._enforceFocus();var
i=g.Event(re.SHOWN,{relatedTarget:t}),o=function(){e._config.focus&&e._elemen
t.focus(),e._isTransitioning=!1,g(e._element).trigger(i)};if(n){var
r=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._dialog);g(this._dialog).one(_TRAN
SITION_END,o).emulateTransitionEnd(r)}else
o(),t._enforceFocus=function(){var
e=this;g(document).off(re.FOCUSIN).on(re.FOCUSIN,function(t){document!==t.tar
get&&e._element!==t.target&&0===g(e._element).has(t.target).length&&e._elemen
t.focus()}),t._setEscapeEvent=function(){var
e=this;this._isShown&&this._config.keyboard?g(this._element).on(re.KEYDOWN_DI
SMISS,function(t){27===t.which&&(t.preventDefault(),e.hide())}):this._isShown
||g(this._element).off(re.KEYDOWN_DISMISS)},t._setResizeEvent=function(){var
e=this;this._isShown?g(window).on(re.RESIZE,function(t){return
e.handleUpdate(t)}):g(window).off(re.RESIZE)},t._hideModal=function(){var
t=this;this._element.style.display="none",this._element.setAttribute("aria-
hidden",!0),this._element.removeAttribute("aria-
modal"),this._isTransitioning=!1,this._showBackdrop(function(){g(document.bod
y).removeClass(le),t._resetAdjustments(),t._resetScrollbar(),g(t._element).tr
igger(re.HIDDEN)}),t._removeBackdrop=function(){this._backdrop&&(g(this._bac
kdrop).remove(),this._backdrop=null)},t._showBackdrop=function(t){var
e=this,n=g(this._element).hasClass(ce)?ce:"";if(this._isShown&&this._config.b
ackdrop){if(this._backdrop=document.createElement("div"),this._backdrop.class
Name=ae,n&&this._backdrop.classList.add(n),g(this._backdrop).appendTo(documen
t.body),g(this._element).on(re.CLICK_DISMISS,function(t){e._ignoreBackdropCli
ck?e._ignoreBackdropClick=!1:t.target===t.currentTarget&&("static"===e._confi
g.backdrop?e._element.focus():e.hide())}),n&&_.reflow(this._backdrop),g(this.
_backdrop).addClass(he),!t)return;if(!n)return void t();var
i=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._backdrop);g(this._backdrop).one(_
TRANSITION_END,t).emulateTransitionEnd(i)}else
if(!this._isShown&&this._backdrop){g(this._backdrop).removeClass(he);var
o=function(){e._removeBackdrop(),t&&t()};if(g(this._element).hasClass(ce)){va
r
r=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._backdrop);g(this._backdrop).one(_
TRANSITION_END,o).emulateTransitionEnd(r)}else o()}else
t&&t(),t._adjustDialog=function(){var
t=this._element.scrollHeight>document.documentElement.clientHeight;!this._isB
odyOverflowing&&t&&(this._element.style.paddingLeft=this._scrollbarWidth+"px"
),this._isBodyOverflowing&&!t&&(this._element.style.paddingRight=this._scroll
barWidth+"px")},t._resetAdjustments=function(){this._element.style.paddingLef
t="",this._element.style.paddingRight=""},t._checkScrollbar=function(){var
t=document.body.getBoundingClientRect();this._isBodyOverflowing=t.left+t.righ
t<window.innerWidth,this._scrollbarWidth=this._getScrollbarWidth(),t._setScr
ollbar=function(){var o=this;if(this._isBodyOverflowing){var
t=[] .slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(ge)),e=[] .slice.call(document.query
SelectorAll(_e));g(t).each(function(t,e){var
n=e.style.paddingRight,i=g(e).css("padding-right");g(e).data("padding-
right",n).css("padding-
right",parseFloat(i)+o._scrollbarWidth+"px")}),g(e).each(function(t,e){var
n=e.style.marginRight,i=g(e).css("margin-right");g(e).data("margin-
right",n).css("margin-right",parseFloat(i)-o._scrollbarWidth+"px")});var
n=document.body.style.paddingRight,i=g(document.body).css("padding-
right");g(document.body).data("padding-right",n).css("padding-

```

```

right",parseFloat(i)+this._scrollbarWidth+"px"}g(document.body).addClass(1e
},t._resetScrollbar=function(){var
t=[];t.slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(ge));g(t).each(function(t,e){var
n=g(e).data("padding-right");g(e).removeData("padding-
right"),e.style.paddingRight=n||""});var
e=[];e.slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(""+_e));g(e).each(function(t,e){var
n=g(e).data("margin-right");"undefined"!==typeof n&&g(e).css("margin-
right",n).removeData("margin-right")});var n=g(document.body).data("padding-
right");g(document.body).removeData("padding-
right"),document.body.style.paddingRight=n||"",t._getScrollbarWidth=function
(){var
t=document.createElement("div");t.className=se,document.body.appendChild(t);v
ar e=t.getBoundingClientRect().width-t.clientWidth;return
document.body.removeChild(t),e},o._jQueryInterface=function(n,i){return
this.each(function(){var
t=g(this).data(te),e=l({},ie,g(this).data(),"object"===typeof
n&&n?n:{});if(t||(t=new o(this,e),g(this).data(te,t)),"string"===typeof
n){if("undefined"===typeof t[n])throw new TypeError('No method named
'+n+'');t[n](i)}else
e.show&&t.show(i)}}),s(o,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}},
{key:"Default",get:function(){return
ie}}]),o}());g(document).on(re.CLICK_DATA_API,fe,function(t){var
e,n=this,i=_;getSelectorFromElement(this);i&&(e=document.querySelector(i));va
r
o=g(e).data(te)?"toggle":l({},g(e).data(),g(this).data());"A"!==this.tagName&
&"AREA"!==this.tagName||t.preventDefault();var
r=g(e).one(re.SHOW,function(t){t.isDefaultPrevented()||r.one(re.HIDDEN,functi
on){g(n).is(":visible")&&n.focus()});me._jQueryInterface.call(g(e),o,this)
}),g.fn[$t]=me._jQueryInterface,g.fn[$t].Constructor=me,g.fn[$t].noConflict=f
unction(){return g.fn[$t]=ne,me._jQueryInterface};var
pe="tooltip",ve="bs.tooltip",Ee="."+ve,ye=g.fn[pe],Ce="bs-tooltip",Te=new
RegExp("(^|\\s)"+Ce+"\\s+","g"),Se={animation:"boolean",template:"string",tit
le:"(string|element|function)",trigger:"string",delay:"(number|object)",html:
"boolean",selector:"(string|boolean)",placement:"(string|function)",offset:"(
number|string)",container:"(string|element|boolean)",fallbackPlacement:"(stri
ng|array)",boundary:"(string|element)"},be={AUTO:"auto",TOP:"top",RIGHT:"righ
t",BOTTOM:"bottom",LEFT:"left"},Ie={animation:!0,template:'<div
class="tooltip" role="tooltip"><div class="arrow"></div><div class="tooltip-
inner"></div></div>',trigger:"hover
focus",title:"",delay:0,html:!1,selector:!1,placement:"top",offset:0,containe
r:!1,fallbackPlacement:"flip",boundary:"scrollParent"},De="show",we="out",Ae=
{HIDE:"hide"+Ee,HIDDEN:"hidden"+Ee,SHOW:"show"+Ee,SHOWN:"shown"+Ee,INSERTED:"
inserted"+Ee,CLICK:"click"+Ee,FOCUSIN:"focusin"+Ee,FOCUSOUT:"focusout"+Ee,MOU
SEENTER:"mouseenter"+Ee,MOUSELEAVE:"mouseleave"+Ee},Ne="fade",Oe="show",ke="
.tooltip-
inner",Pe=".arrow",Le="hover",je="focus",He="click",Re="manual",Ue=function()
{function i(t,e){if("undefined"===typeof u)throw new TypeError("Bootstrap's
tooltips require Popper.js
(https://popper.js.org/)");this._isEnabled=!0,this._timeout=0,this._hoverStat
e="",this._activeTrigger={},this._popper=null,this.element=t,this.config=this
._getConfig(e),this.tip=null,this._setListeners()}var t=i.prototype;return
t.enable=function(){this._isEnabled=!0},t.disable=function(){this._isEnabled=
!1},t.toggleEnabled=function(){this._isEnabled=!this._isEnabled},t.toggle=fun
ction(t){if(this._isEnabled)if(t){var
e=this.constructor.DATA_KEY,n=g(t.currentTarget).data(e);n||(n=new
this.constructor(t.currentTarget,this._getDelegateConfig()),g(t.currentTarget
).data(e,n)),n._activeTrigger.click=!n._activeTrigger.click,n._isWithActiveTr

```

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igger()?n._enter(null,n):n._leave(null,n)}else{if(g(this.getTipElement()).hasClass(Oe))return void
this._leave(null,this);this._enter(null,this)},t.dispose=function(){clearTimeout(this._timeout),g.removeData(this.element,this.constructor.DATA_KEY),g(this.element).off(this.constructor.EVENT_KEY),g(this.element).closest(".modal").off("hide.bs.modal"),this.tip&&g(this.tip).remove(),this._isEnabled=null,this._timeout=null,this._hoverState=null,(this._activeTrigger=null)!==this._popper&&this._popper.destroy(),this._popper=null,this.element=null,this.config=null,this.tip=null},t.show=function(){var e=this;if("none"===g(this.element).css("display"))throw new Error("Please use show on visible elements");var t=g.Event(this.constructor.Event.SHOW);if(this.isWithContent()&&this._isEnabled){g(this.element).trigger(t);var n=_findShadowRoot(this.element),i=g.contains(null!==n?n:this.element.ownerDocument.documentElement,this.element);if(t.isDefaultPrevented()||!i)return;var o=this.getTipElement(),r=_getUID(this.constructor.NAME);o.setAttribute("id",r),this.element.setAttribute("aria-describedby",r),this.setContent(),this.config.animation&&g(o).addClass(Ne);var s="function"===typeof this.config.placement?this.config.placement.call(this,o,this.element):this.config.placement,a=this._getAttachment(s);this.addClassAttachmentClass(a);var l=this._getContainer();g(o).data(this.constructor.DATA_KEY,this),g.contains(this.element.ownerDocument.documentElement,this.tip)||g(o).appendTo(l),g(this.element).trigger(this.constructor.Event.INSERTED),this._popper=new u(this.element,o,{placement:a,modifiers:{offset:{offset:this.config.offset},flip:{behavior:this.config.fallbackPlacement},arrow:{element:Pe},preventOverflow:{boundariesElement:this.config.boundary}},onCreate:function(t){t.originalPlacement!==t.placement&&e._handlePopperPlacementChange(t)},onUpdate:function(t){return e._handlePopperPlacementChange(t)}}),g(o).addClass(Oe),"ontouchstart"in document.documentElement&&g(document.body).children().on("mouseover",null,g.noop);var c=function(){e.config.animation&&e._fixTransition();var t=e._hoverState;e._hoverState=null,g(e.element).trigger(e.constructor.Event.SHOWN),t===we&&e._leave(null,e)};if(g(this.tip).hasClass(Ne)){var h=_getTransitionDurationFromElement(this.tip);g(this.tip).one(_.TRANSITION_END,c).emulateTransitionEnd(h)}else c()},t.hide=function(t){var e=this,n=this.getTipElement(),i=g.Event(this.constructor.Event.HIDE),o=function(){e._hoverState!==De&&n.parentNode&&n.parentNode.removeChild(n),e._cleanTipClass(),e.element.removeAttribute("aria-describedby"),g(e.element).trigger(e.constructor.Event.HIDDEN),null!==e._popper&&e._popper.destroy(),t&&t()};if(g(this.element).trigger(i),!i.isDefaultPrevented()){if(g(n).removeClass(Oe),"ontouchstart"in document.documentElement&&g(document.body).children().off("mouseover",null,g.noop),this._activeTrigger[He]=!1,this._activeTrigger[je]=!1,this._activeTrigger[Le]=!1,g(this.tip).hasClass(Ne)){var r=_getTransitionDurationFromElement(n);g(n).one(_.TRANSITION_END,o).emulateTransitionEnd(r)}else o();this._hoverState=""},t.update=function(){null!==this._popper&&this._popper.scheduleUpdate(),t.isWithContent=function(){return Boolean(this.getTitle())},t.addClassAttachmentClass=function(t){g(this.getTipElement()).addClass(Ce+"-"+t)},t.getTipElement=function(){return this.tip=this.tip||g(this.config.template)[0],this.tip},t.setContent=function(){var t=this.getTipElement();this.setElementContent(g(t.querySelectorAll(ke)),this.getTitle()),g(t).removeClass(Ne+" "+Oe),t.setElementContent=function(t,e){var n=this.config.html;"object"===typeof

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e&&(e.nodeType||e.jquery)?n?g(e).parent().is(t)||t.empty().append(e):t.text(
(e).text()):t[n?"html":"text"](e)},t.getTitle=function(){var
t=this.element.getAttribute("data-original-title");return
t||(t="function"===typeof
this.config.title?this.config.title.call(this.element):this.config.title),t},
t._getContainer=function(){return!1===this.config.container?document.body:_i
sElement(this.config.container)?g(this.config.container):g(document).find(thi
s.config.container)},t._getAttachment=function(t){return
be[t.toUpperCase()]},t._setListeners=function(){var
i=this;this.config.trigger.split("
").forEach(function(t){if("click"===t)g(i.element).on(i.constructor.Event.CLI
CK,i.config.selector,function(t){return i.toggle(t)});else if(t!==Re){var
e=t===Le?i.constructor.Event.MOUSEENTER:i.constructor.Event.FOCUSIN,n=t===Le?
i.constructor.Event.MOUSELEAVE:i.constructor.Event.FOCUSOUT;g(i.element).on(e
,i.config.selector,function(t){return
i._enter(t)}).on(n,i.config.selector,function(t){return
i._leave(t)}))},g(this.element).closest(".modal").on("hide.bs.modal",functio
n(){i.element&&i.hide()}),this.config.selector?this.config=l({},this.config,{
trigger:"manual",selector:""}):this._fixTitle(),t._fixTitle=function(){var
t=typeof this.element.getAttribute("data-original-
title");(this.element.getAttribute("title")||"string"!==t)&&(this.element.set
Attribute("data-original-
title",this.element.getAttribute("title")||""),this.element.setAttribute("tit
le","")),t._enter=function(t,e){var
n=this.constructor.DATA_KEY;(e=e||g(t.currentTarget).data(n))||(e=new
this.constructor(t.currentTarget,this._getDelegateConfig()),g(t.currentTarget
).data(n,e),t&&(e._activeTrigger["focusin"===t.type?je:Le]=!0),g(e.getTipEle
ment()).hasClass(Oe)||e._hoverState===De?e._hoverState=De:(clearTimeout(e._ti
meout),e._hoverState=De,e.config.delay&&e.config.delay.show?e._timeout=setTim
eout(function(){e._hoverState===De&&e.show()},e.config.delay.show):e.show())}
,t._leave=function(t,e){var
n=this.constructor.DATA_KEY;(e=e||g(t.currentTarget).data(n))||(e=new
this.constructor(t.currentTarget,this._getDelegateConfig()),g(t.currentTarget
).data(n,e),t&&(e._activeTrigger["focusout"===t.type?je:Le]=!1),e._isWithAct
iveTrigger()||(clearTimeout(e._timeout),e._hoverState=we,e.config.delay&&e.co
nfig.delay.hide?e._timeout=setTimeout(function(){e._hoverState===we&&e.hide()
},e.config.delay.hide):e.hide()),t._isWithActiveTrigger=function(){for(var t
in
this._activeTrigger)if(this._activeTrigger[t])return!0;return!1},t._getConfig
=function(t){return"number"===typeof(t=l({},this.constructor.Default,g(this.el
ement).data(),"object"===typeof
t&&t?t:{})).delay&&(t.delay={show:t.delay,hide:t.delay}),"number"===typeof
t.title&&(t.title=t.title.toString()),"number"===typeof
t.content&&(t.content=t.content.toString()),_typeCheckConfig(pe,t,this.const
ructor.DefaultType),t},t._getDelegateConfig=function(){var
t={};if(this.config)for(var e in
this.config)this.constructor.Default[e]!==this.config[e]&&(t[e]=this.config[e
]);return t},t._cleanTipClass=function(){var
t=g(this.getTipElement()),e=t.attr("class").match(Te);null!==e&&e.length&&t.r
emoveClass(e.join("")),t._handlePopperPlacementChange=function(t){var
e=t.instance;this.tip=e.popper,this._cleanTipClass(),this.addAttachmentClass(
this._getAttachment(t.placement))},t._fixTransition=function(){var
t=this.getTipElement(),e=this.config.animation;null===t.getAttribute("x-
placement")&&(g(t).removeClass(Ne),this.config.animation=!1,this.hide(),this.
show(),this.config.animation=e)},i._jQueryInterface=function(n){return
this.each(function(){var t=g(this).data(ve),e="object"===typeof
n&&n;if((t||!/dispose|hide/.test(n))&&(t||(t=new

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i(this,e),g(this).data(ve,t),"string"===typeof n){if("undefined"===typeof
t[n])throw new TypeError('No method named
'+n+'');t[n]({})}},s(i,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}},
{key:"Default",get:function(){return Ie}},{key:"NAME",get:function(){return
pe}},{key:"DATA_KEY",get:function(){return
ve}},{key:"Event",get:function(){return
Ae}},{key:"EVENT_KEY",get:function(){return
Ee}},{key:"DefaultType",get:function(){return
Se}}]),i()};g.fn[pe]=Ue._jQueryInterface,g.fn[pe].Constructor=Ue,g.fn[pe].noC
onflict=function(){return g.fn[pe]=ye,Ue._jQueryInterface};var
We="popover",xe="bs.popover",Fe="."+xe,qe=g.fn[We],Me="bs-popover",Ke=new
RegExp("(^|\\s)"+Me+"\\s+","g"),Qe=l({},Ue.Default,{placement:"right",trigger
:"click",content:"",template:'<div class="popover" role="tooltip"><div
class="arrow"></div><h3 class="popover-header"></h3><div class="popover-
body"></div></div>'},Be=l({},Ue.DefaultType,{content:"(string|element|functi
on)"},Ve="fade",Ye="show",Xe=".popover-header",ze=".popover-
body",Ge={HIDE:"hide"+Fe,HIDDEN:"hidden"+Fe,SHOW:"show"+Fe,SHOWN:"shown"+Fe,I
NSERTED:"inserted"+Fe,CLICK:"click"+Fe,FOCUSIN:"focusin"+Fe,FOCUSOUT:"focusou
t"+Fe,MOUSEENTER:"mouseenter"+Fe,MOUSELEAVE:"mouseleave"+Fe},Je=function(t){v
ar e,n;function i(){return
t.apply(this,arguments)||this}n=t,(e=i).prototype=Object.create(n.prototype),
(e.prototype.constructor=e).__proto__=n;var o=i.prototype;return
o.isWithContent=function(){return
this.getTitle()||this._getContent()},o.addAttachmentClass=function(t){g(this.
getTipElement()).addClass(Me+"-"+t)},o.getTipElement=function(){return
this.tip=this.tip||g(this.config.template)[0],this.tip},o.setContent=function
(){var
t=g(this.getTipElement());this.setElementContent(t.find(Xe),this.getTitle());
var e=this._getContent();"function"===typeof
e&&(e=e.call(this.element)),this.setElementContent(t.find(ze),e),t.removeClas
s(Ve+" "+Ye)},o._getContent=function(){return
this.element.getAttribute("data-
content")||this.config.content},o._cleanTipClass=function(){var
t=g(this.getTipElement()),e=t.attr("class").match(Ke);null!=e&&0<e.length&&t
.removeClass(e.join(" ")),i._jQueryInterface=function(n){return
this.each(function(){var t=g(this).data(xe),e="object"===typeof
n?n:null;if((t||!/dispose|hide/.test(n))&&(t||(t=new
i(this,e),g(this).data(xe,t)),"string"===typeof n){if("undefined"===typeof
t[n])throw new TypeError('No method named
'+n+'');t[n]({})}},s(i,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}},
{key:"Default",get:function(){return Qe}},{key:"NAME",get:function(){return
We}},{key:"DATA_KEY",get:function(){return
xe}},{key:"Event",get:function(){return
Ge}},{key:"EVENT_KEY",get:function(){return
Fe}},{key:"DefaultType",get:function(){return
Be}}]),i)(Ue);g.fn[We]=Je._jQueryInterface,g.fn[We].Constructor=Je,g.fn[We].n
oConflict=function(){return g.fn[We]=qe,Je._jQueryInterface};var
Ze="scrollspy",$e="bs.scrollspy",tn="."+$e,en=g.fn[Ze],nn={offset:10,method:"
auto",target:""},on={offset:"number",method:"string",target:"(string|element)
"},rn={ACTIVATE:"activate"+tn,SCROLL:"scroll"+tn,LOAD_DATA_API:"load"+tn+".da
ta-api"},sn="dropdown-item",an="active",ln='[data-spy="scroll"]',cn=".nav,
.list-group",hn=".nav-link",un=".nav-item",fn=".list-group-
item",dn=".dropdown",gn=".dropdown-item",_n=".dropdown-
toggle",mn="offset",pn="position",vn=function(){function n(t,e){var
n=this;this._element=t,this._scrollElement="BODY"===t.tagName?window:t,this.
config=this._getConfig(e),this._selector=this._config.target+"
"+hn+", "+this._config.target+" "+fn+", "+this._config.target+"

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"+gn,this._offsets=[],this._targets=[],this._activeTarget=null,this._scrollHeight=0,g(this._scrollElement).on(rn.SCROLL,function(t){return n._process(t)}),this.refresh(),this._process()}var t=n.prototype;return t.refresh=function(){var e=this,t=this._scrollElement===this._scrollElement.window?mn:pn,o="auto"===this._config.method?t:this._config.method,r=o===pn?this._getScrollTop():0;this._offsets=[],this._targets=[],this._scrollHeight=this._getScrollHeight(),[].slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(this._selector)).map(function(t){var e,n=_.getSelectorFromElement(t);if(n&&(e=document.querySelector(n)),e){var i=e.getBoundingClientRect();if(i.width||i.height)return[g(e)[0]().top+r,n]}return null}).filter(function(t){return t}).sort(function(t,e){return t[0]-e[0]}).forEach(function(t){e._offsets.push(t[0]),e._targets.push(t[1])}),t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(this._element,$e),g(this._scrollElement).off(tn),this._element=null,this._scrollElement=null,this._config=null,this._selector=null,this._offsets=null,this._targets=null,this._activeTarget=null,this._scrollHeight=null},t._getConfig=function(t){if("string"!==typeof(t=l({},nn,"object")===typeof t&&t:t:{})).target){var e=g(t.target).attr("id");e||(e=_.getUID(Ze),g(t.target).attr("id",e)),t.target="#"+e}return _.typeCheckConfig(Ze,t,on),t},t._getScrollTop=function(){return this._scrollElement===window?this._scrollElement.pageYOffset:this._scrollElement.scrollTop},t._getScrollHeight=function(){return this._scrollElement.scrollHeight||Math.max(document.body.scrollHeight,document.documentElement.scrollHeight)},t._getOffsetHeight=function(){return this._scrollElement===window?window.innerHeight:this._scrollElement.getBoundingClientRect().height},t._process=function(){var t=this._getScrollTop()+this._config.offset,e=this._getScrollHeight(),n=this._config.offset+e-this._getOffsetHeight();if(this._scrollHeight!==e&&this.refresh(),n<=t){var i=this._targets[this._targets.length-1];this._activeTarget!==i&&this._activate(i)}else{if(this._activeTarget&&t<this._offsets[0]&&0<this._offsets[0])return this._activeTarget=null,void this._clear();for(var o=this._offsets.length;o-->){this._activeTarget!==this._targets[o]&&t>=this._offsets[o]&&("undefined"===typeof this._offsets[o+1]||t<this._offsets[o+1])&&this._activate(this._targets[o])}}},t._activate=function(e){this._activeTarget=e,this._clear();var t=this._selector.split(",").map(function(t){return t+'[data-target="'+e+'"]','+t+'[href="'+e+'"]')},n=g([].slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(t.join(","))));n.hasClass(sn)?(n.closest(dn).find(_n).addClass(an),n.addClass(an)):n.addClass(an),n.parents(cn).prev(hn+",""+fn).addClass(an),n.parents(cn).prev(un).children(hn).addClass(an)},g(this._scrollElement).trigger(rn.ACTIVATE,{relatedTarget:e}),t._clear=function(){[].slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(this._selector)).filter(function(t){return t.classList.contains(an)}).forEach(function(t){return t.classList.remove(an)}),n._jQueryInterface=function(e){return this.each(function(){var t=g(this).data($e);if(t||t=new n(this,"object"===typeof e&&e),g(this).data($e,t),"string"===typeof e){if("undefined"===typeof t[e])throw new TypeError('No method named '+e+'');t[e]()}},s(n,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}},{key:"Default",get:function(){return nn}}]),n)();g(window).on(rn.LOAD_DATA_API,function(){for(var t=[].slice.call(document.querySelectorAll(ln)),e=t.length;e-->){var n=g(t[e]);vn._jQueryInterface.call(n,n.data())}},g.fn[Ze]=vn._jQueryInterface,g.fn[Ze].Constructor=vn,g.fn[Ze].noConflict=function(){return g.fn[Ze]=en,vn._jQueryInterface};var En="bs.tab",yn="."+En,Cn=g.fn.tab,Tn={HIDE:"hide"+yn,HIDDEN:"hidden"+yn,SHOW:

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"show"+yn, SHOWN:"shown"+yn, CLICK_DATA_API:"click"+yn+".data-
api"}, Sn="dropdown-
menu", bn="active", In="disabled", Dn="fade", wn="show", An=".dropdown", Nn=".nav,
.list-group", On=".active", kn="> li > .active", Pn=' [data-toggle="tab"], [data-
toggle="pill"], [data-toggle="list"]', Ln=".dropdown-toggle", jn="> .dropdown-
menu .active", Hn=function(){function i(t){this._element=t}var
t=i.prototype;return t.show=function(){var
n=this;if(!(this._element.parentNode&&this._element.parentNode.nodeType===Nod
e.ELEMENT_NODE&&g(this._element).hasClass(bn)|g(this._element).hasClass(In)
){var
t,i,e=g(this._element).closest(Nn)[0],o=_._getSelectorFromElement(this._elemen
t);if(e){var
r="UL"===e.nodeName||"OL"===e.nodeName?kn:On;i=(i=g.makeArray(g(e).find(r)))[
i.length-1]}var
s=g.Event(Tn.HIDE,{relatedTarget:this._element}),a=g.Event(Tn.SHOW,{relatedTa
rget:i});if(i&&g(i).trigger(s),g(this._element).trigger(a),!a.isDefaultPreven
ted()&&!s.isDefaultPrevented()){o&&(t=document.querySelector(o)),this._activa
te(this._element,e);var l=function(){var
t=g.Event(Tn.HIDDEN,{relatedTarget:n._element}),e=g.Event(Tn.SHOWN,{relatedTa
rget:i});g(i).trigger(t),g(n._element).trigger(e);t?this._activate(t,t.paren
tNode,l):l()}}},t.dispose=function(){g.removeData(this._element,En),this._ele
ment=null},t._activate=function(t,e,n){var
i=this,o=(!e||"UL"!===e.nodeName&&"OL"!===e.nodeName?g(e).children(On):g(e).fin
d(kn))[0],r=n&&o&&g(o).hasClass(Dn),s=function(){return
i._transitionComplete(t,o,n)};if(o&&r){var
a=_._getTransitionDurationFromElement(o);g(o).removeClass(wn).one(_._TRANSITION
_END,s).emulateTransitionEnd(a)}else
s(),t._transitionComplete=function(t,e,n){if(e){g(e).removeClass(bn);var
i=g(e.parentNode).find(jn)[0];i&&g(i).removeClass(bn),"tab"===e.getAttribute(
"role")&&e.setAttribute("aria-
selected",!1)}if(g(t).addClass(bn),"tab"===t.getAttribute("role")&&t.setAttri
bute("aria-
selected",!0),_.reflow(t),g(t).addClass(wn),t.parentNode&&g(t.parentNode).has
Class(Sn)){var o=g(t).closest(An)[0];if(o){var
r=[].slice.call(o.querySelectorAll(Ln));g(r).addClass(bn)}t.setAttribute("ari
a-expanded",!0)}n&&n(),i._jQueryInterface=function(n){return
this.each(function(){var t=g(this),e=t.data(En);if(e||(e=new
i(this),t.data(En,e)),"string"===typeof n){if("undefined"===typeof e[n])throw
new TypeError('No method named
'+n+'');e[n]()}})},s(i,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1"}}]
),i());g(document).on(Tn.CLICK_DATA_API,Pn,function(t){t.preventDefault(),Hn.
_jQueryInterface.call(g(this),"show")}),g.fn.tab=Hn._jQueryInterface,g.fn.tab
.Constructor=Hn,g.fn.tab.noConflict=function(){return
g.fn.tab=Cn,Hn._jQueryInterface};var
Rn="toast",Un="bs.toast",Wn="."+Un,xn=g.fn[Rn],Fn={CLICK_DISMISS:"click.dismiss"+Wn,HIDE:"hide"+Wn,HIDDEN:"hidden"+Wn,SHOW:"show"+Wn,SHOWN:"shown"+Wn},qn=
"fade",Mn="hide",Kn="show",Qn="showing",Bn={animation:"boolean",autohide:"boo
lean",delay:"number"},Vn={animation:!0,autohide:!0,delay:500},Yn=' [data-
dismiss="toast"]',Xn=function(){function
i(t,e){this._element=t,this._config=this._getConfig(e),this._timeout=null,thi
s._setListeners()}var t=i.prototype;return t.show=function(){var
t=this;g(this._element).trigger(Fn.SHOW),this._config.animation&&this._elemen
t.classList.add(qn);var
e=function(){t._element.classList.remove(Qn),t._element.classList.add(Kn),g(t
._element).trigger(Fn.SHOWN),t._config.autohide&&t.hide()};if(this._element.c
lassList.remove(Mn),this._element.classList.add(Qn),this._config.animation){v
ar

```

```

n=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._element);g(this._element).one(._TR
ANSITION_END,e).emulateTransitionEnd(n)}else e()},t.hide=function(t){var
e=this;this._element.classList.contains(Kn)&&(g(this._element).trigger(Fn.HID
E),t?this._close():this._timeout=setTimeout(function(){e._close()},this._conf
ig.delay)},t.dispose=function(){clearTimeout(this._timeout),this._timeout=nu
ll,this._element.classList.contains(Kn)&&this._element.classList.remove(Kn),g
(this._element).off(Fn.CLICK_DISMISS),g.removeData(this._element,Un),this._el
ement=null,this._config=null},t._getConfig=function(t){return
t=l({},Vn,g(this._element).data(),"object"===typeof
t&&t:t:{}),_.typeCheckConfig(Rn,t,this.constructor.DefaultType),t},t._setList
eners=function(){var
t=this;g(this._element).on(Fn.CLICK_DISMISS,Yn,function(){return
t.hide(!0)}),t._close=function(){var
t=this,e=function(){t._element.classList.add(Mn),g(t._element).trigger(Fn.HID
DEN)};if(this._element.classList.remove(Kn),this._config.animation){var
n=_.getTransitionDurationFromElement(this._element);g(this._element).one(._TR
ANSITION_END,e).emulateTransitionEnd(n)}else
e()},i._jQueryInterface=function(n){return this.each(function(){var
t=g(this),e=t.data(Un);if(e||(e=new i(this,"object"===typeof
n&&n),t.data(Un,e)),"string"===typeof n){if("undefined"===typeof e[n])throw new
TypeError('No method named
'+n+'');e[n](this)}}),s(i,null,[{key:"VERSION",get:function(){return"4.2.1
"}},{key:"DefaultType",get:function(){return
Bn}}]),i}());g.fn[Rn]=Xn._jQueryInterface,g.fn[Rn].Constructor=Xn,g.fn[Rn].noC
onflict=function(){return
g.fn[Rn]=xn,Xn._jQueryInterface},function(){if("undefined"===typeof g)throw
new TypeError("Bootstrap's JavaScript requires jQuery. jQuery must be
included before Bootstrap's JavaScript.");var t=g.fn.jquery.split("
")[0].split(".");if(t[0]<2&&t[1]<9||1===t[0]&&9===t[1]&&t[2]<1||4<=t[0])throw
new Error("Bootstrap's JavaScript requires at least jQuery v1.9.1 but less
than
v4.0.0")}(),t.Util=_,t.Alert=p,t.Button=P,t.Carousel=lt,t.Collapse=bt,t.Dropd
own=Zt,t.Modal=me,t.Popover=Je,t.Scrollspy=vn,t.Tab=Hn,t.Toast=Xn,t.Tooltip=U
e,Object.defineProperty(t,"__esModule",{value:!0}));
//# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.min.js.map

```

Custom.js

```
$(function () {  
  
  // MENU  
  $('.navbar-collapse a').on('click',function(){  
    $(".navbar-collapse").collapse('hide');  
  });  
  
  // AOS ANIMATION  
  AOS.init({  
    disable: 'mobile',  
    duration: 800,  
    anchorPlacement: 'center-bottom'  
  });  
  
  // SMOOTHSCROLL NAVBAR  
  $(function() {  
    $('.navbar a, .hero-text a').on('click', function(event) {  
      var $anchor = $(this);  
      $('html, body').stop().animate({  
        scrollTop: $($anchor.attr('href')).offset().top - 49  
      }, 1000);  
      event.preventDefault();  
    });  
  });  
});
```

Jquery.mini.js

```
/*! jQuery v3.3.1 | (c) JS Foundation and other contributors |
jquery.org/license */
!function(e,t){"use strict";"object"==typeof module&&"object"==typeof
module.exports?module.exports=e.document?t(e,!0):function(e){if(!e.document)
throw new Error("jQuery requires a window with a document");return
t(e)}:t(e)}("undefined"!==typeof window?window:this,function(e,t){"use
strict";var
n=[],r=e.document,i=Object.getPrototypeOf,o=n.slice,a=n.concat,s=n.push,u=n.i
ndexOf,l={},c=l.toString,f=l.hasOwnProperty,p=f.toString,d=p.call(Object),h={
},g=function e(t){return"function"==typeof t&&"number"!==typeof
t.nodeType},y=function e(t){return
null!=t&&t===t.window},v={type:!0,src:!0,noModule:!0};function m(e,t,n){var
i,o=(t=t||r).createElement("script");if(o.text=e,n)for(i in
v)n[i]&&(o[i]=n[i]);t.head.appendChild(o).parentNode.removeChild(o)}function
x(e){return null==e+"":"object"==typeof e||"function"==typeof
e?l[c.call(e)]||"object":typeof e}var b="3.3.1",w=function(e,t){return new
w.fn.init(e,t)},T=/^\s\uFEFF\uA0+|[\s\uFEFF\uA0]+$/g;w.fn=w.prototype={jque
ry:"3.3.1",constructor:w,length:0,toArray:function(){return
o.call(this)},get:function(e){return
null==e?o.call(this):e<0?this[e+this.length]:this[e]},pushStack:function(e){
var t=w.merge(this.constructor(),e);return
t.prevObject=this,t},each:function(e){return
w.each(this,e)},map:function(e){return
this.pushStack(w.map(this,function(t,n){return
e.call(t,n,t)}))},slice:function(){return
this.pushStack(o.apply(this,arguments))},first:function(){return
this.eq(0)},last:function(){return this.eq(-1)},eq:function(e){var
t=this.length,n=e+(e<0?t:0);return
this.pushStack(n>=0&&n<t?[this[n]]:[])},end:function(){return
this.prevObject||this.constructor()},push:s,sort:n.sort,splice:n.splice},w.ex
tend=w.fn.extend=function(){var
e,t,n,r,i,o,a=arguments[0]||{},s=1,u=arguments.length,l=!1;for("boolean"==typ
eof a&&(l=a,a=arguments[s]||{}),s++),"object"==typeof
a||g(a)||(a={}),s===u&&(a=this,s--);s<u;s++)if(null!=(e=arguments[s]))for(t
in
e)n=a[t],a!==(r=e[t])&&(l&&r&&(w.isPlainObject(r)||i=Array.isArray(r)))?(i?
i=!1,o=n&&Array.isArray(n)?n:[]:o=n&&w.isPlainObject(n)?n:{},a[t]=w.extend(l
,o,r)):void 0!==r&&(a[t]=r)};return
a},w.extend({expando:"jQuery"+"3.3.1"+Math.random()).replace(/D/g,""),isRea
dy:!0,error:function(e){throw new
Error(e)},noop:function(){},isPlainObject:function(e){var
t,n;return!(e||"[object
Object]"!==c.call(e))&&(!t=i(e)||"function"==typeof(n=f.call(t,"constructor
")&&t.constructor)&&p.call(n)===d)},isEmptyObject:function(e){var t;for(t in
e)return!1;return!0},globalEval:function(e){m(e)},each:function(e,t){var
n,r=0;if(C(e)){for(n=e.length;r<n;r++)if(!1===t.call(e[r],r,e[r]))break}else
for(r in e)if(!1===t.call(e[r],r,e[r]))break;return
e},trim:function(e){return
null==e?"":(e+"").replace(T,"")},makeArray:function(e,t){var n=t||[];return
null!=e&&(C(Object(e))?w.merge(n,"string"==typeof
e?[e]:e):s.call(n,e)),n},isArray:function(e,t,n){return null==t?-
1:u.call(t,e,n)},merge:function(e,t){for(var
n=+t.length,r=0,i=e.length;r<n;r++)e[i++]=t[r];return
n=+t.length,r=0,i=e.length;r<n;r++)e[i++]=t[r];return
```

```

e.length=i,e},grep:function(e,t,n){for(var
r,i=[],o=0,a=e.length,s=!n;o<a;o++)(r=!t(e[o],o))!==s&&i.push(e[o]);return
i},map:function(e,t,n){var
r,i,o=0,s=[];if(C(e))for(r=e.length;o<r;o++)null!=(i=t(e[o],o,n))&&s.push(i);
else for(o in e)null!=(i=t(e[o],o,n))&&s.push(i);return
a.apply([],s)},guid:1,support:h}),"function"===typeof
Symbol&&(w.fn[Symbol.iterator]=n[Symbol.iterator]),w.each("Boolean Number
String Function Array Date RegExp Object Error Symbol".split("
"),function(e,t){l["[object "+t+"]"]=t.toLowerCase();});function C(e){var
t=!!e&&"length"in
e&&e.length,n=x(e);return!g(e)&&!y(e)&&("array"===n||0===t||"number"===typeof
t&&t>0&&t-1 in e)}var E=function(e){var
t,n,r,i,o,a,s,u,l,c,f,p,d,h,g,y,v,m,x,b="sizzle"+1*new
Date,w=e.document,T=0,C=0,E=ae(),k=ae(),S=ae(),D=function(e,t){return
e===t&&(f=!0),0},N={}.hasOwnProperty,A=[],j=A.pop,q=A.push,L=A.push,H=A.slice
,O=function(e,t){for(var n=0,r=e.length;n<r;n++)if(e[n]===t)return n;return-
1},P="checked|selected|async|autofocus|autoplay|controls|defer|disabled|hidde
n|ismap|loop|multiple|open|readonly|required|scoped",M="[\\x20\\t\\r\\n\\f]",
R="(?:\\\\\\\\.|[\\\\w-]|[^\\0-
\\\\xa0])+",I="\\["+M+"*("+R+")(?:"+M+"*([*^$|!~]?=)"+M+"*(?:'([^\\"
])*)'|\"([^\\""])*\"|\"([^\"]*)\"|"+M+"*\\)",W=":("+R+")(?:\\\\((('(:
:\\\\\\\\.|[^\\\\\\'])*'|\"([^\\""])*\"|\"([^\"]*)\"|"+I+
)*)|\\.*)\\)",$,new RegExp(M+"+", "g"),B=new
RegExp("^"+M+"+|((?:^|^[\\\\\\\\])?(?:\\\\\\\\.)*"+M+"+$", "g"),F=new
RegExp("^"+M+"*", "+M+"*"),_=new RegExp("^"+M+"*([>+~]|"+M+"")"+M+"*"),z=new
RegExp("="+M+"*([^\\""])*?"+M+"*\\)", "g"),X=new RegExp(W),U=new
RegExp("^"+R+"$"),V={ID:new RegExp("^#("+R+")"),CLASS:new
RegExp("^\\.("+R+")"),TAG:new RegExp("^("+R+"|[*])"),ATTR:new
RegExp("^"+I),PSEUDO:new RegExp("^"+W),CHILD:new
RegExp("^:(only|first|last|nth|nth-last)-(child|of-
type)(?:\\("+M+"*(even|odd|(([+-]|)(\\d*)n|)"+M+"*(?:([+-
]|)"+M+"*(\\d+)|)"+M+"*\\)|)"+M+"*\\)", "i"),bool:new
RegExp("^(?:"+P+")$", "i"),needsContext:new
RegExp("^"+M+"*([>+~]|:(even|odd|eq|gt|lt|nth|first|last)(?:\\("+M+"*(?:(-
\\d)?\\d*)"+M+"*\\)|)(?=[^-
]|$)", "i")},G=/^(?:input|select|textarea|button)$/i,Y=/^h\d$/i,Q=/^[^+]{s*
\\[native \\w/,J=/^(?:#[\\w-]+|\\w+|\\.([\\w-]+))$/i,K=/[+~]/,Z=new
RegExp("\\\\([\\da-f]{1,6})"+M+"?|"+M+"|\\.)", "ig"),ee=function(e,t,n){var
r="0x"+t-65536;return
r!==r||n?t:r<0?String.fromCharCode(r+65536):String.fromCharCode(r>>10|55296,1
023&r|56320)},te=/([\0-\x1f\x7f]|^-\?d|^-$|[\0-\x1f\x7f-\uFFFF\w-
]/g,ne=function(e,t){return t?"\0"===e?"\ufffd":e.slice(0,-
1)+"\\"+e.charCodeAt(e.length-1).toString(16)+"
":\\""+e},re=function(){p()},ie=me(function(e){return!0===e.disabled&&("form"
in e||"label"in
e)},{dir:"parentNode",next:"legend"});try{L.apply(A=H.call(w.childNodes),w.ch
ildNodes),A[w.childNodes.length].nodeType}catch(e){L={apply:A.length?function
(e,t){q.apply(e,H.call(t)):function(e,t){var
n=e.length,r=0;while(e[n++]=t[r++]);e.length=n-1}}function oe(e,t,r,i){var
o,s,l,c,f,h,v,m=t&&t.ownerDocument,T=t?t.nodeType:9;if(r=r||[],"string"!==type
of e||!e||1!==T&&9!==T&&11!==T)return
r;if(!i&&(t?t.ownerDocument||t:w)!==d&&p(t),t=t||d,g){if(11!==T&&(f=J.exec(
e)))if(o=f[1]){if(9===T){if(!l=t.getElementById(o))return
r;if(l.id===o)return r.push(l),r}else
if(m&&(l=m.getElementById(o))&&x(t,l)&&l.id===o)return
r.push(l),r}else{if(f[2])return
L.apply(r,t.getElementsByTagName(e)),r;if((o=f[3])&&n.getElementsByClassName&

```

```

&t.getElementsByClassName) return
L.apply(r,t.getElementsByClassName(o)),r}if(n.qsa&&!S[e+"
"]&&(!y||!y.test(e))){if(1!==T)m=t,v=e;else
if("object"!==t.nodeName.toLowerCase()){c=t.getAttribute("id")}?c=c.replace(
te,ne):t.setAttribute("id",c=b),s=(h=a(e)).length;while(s-->)h[s]="#"+c+"
"+ve(h[s]);v=h.join(",");m=K.test(e)&&ge(t.parentNode)||t}if(v)try{return
L.apply(r,m.querySelectorAll(v)),r}catch(e){}finally{c===b&&t.removeAttribute
("id")}}return u(e.replace(B,"$1"),t,r,i)}function ae(){var e=[];function
t(n,i){return e.push(n+" ")>r.cacheLength&&delete t[e.shift()],t[n+"
"]=i}return t}function se(e){return e[b]=!0,e}function ue(e){var
t=d.createElement("fieldset");try{return !e(t)}catch(e){return!1}finally{t.pa
rentNode&&t.parentNode.removeChild(t),t=null}}function le(e,t){var
n=e.split("|"),i=n.length;while(i-->)r.attrHandle[n[i]]=t}function ce(e,t){var
n=t&&e,r=n&&1===e.nodeType&&1===t.nodeType&&e.sourceIndex-
t.sourceIndex;if(r)return r;if(n)while(n=n.nextSibling)if(n===t)return-
1;return e?1:-1}function fe(e){return
function(t){return"input"===t.nodeName.toLowerCase()&&t.type===e}}function
pe(e){return function(t){var
n=t.nodeName.toLowerCase();return("input"===n||"button"===n)&&t.type===e}}fun
ction de(e){return function(t){return"form"i
n t?t.parentNode&&!1===t.disabled?"label"in t?"label"in
t.parentNode?t.parentNode.disabled===e:t.disabled===e:t.isDisabled===e||t.isD
isabled!==e&&ie(t)===e:t.disabled===e:"label"in t&&t.disabled===e}}function
he(e){return se(function(t){return t+=t,se(function(n,r){var
i,o=e([],n.length,t),a=o.length;while(a-->)n[i=o[a]]&&(n[i]=!(r[i]=n[i]))})})}function ge(e){return
e&&"undefined"!==typeof
e.getElementsByTagName&&e)n=oe.support={},o=oe.isXML=function(e){var
t=e&&(e.ownerDocument||e).documentElement;return!t&&"HTML"!==t.nodeName},p=o
e.setDocument=function(e){var t,i,a=e?e.ownerDocument||e:w;return
a!==d&&9===a.nodeType&&a.documentElement?(d=a,h=d.documentElement,g=!o(d),w!=
=d&&(i=d.defaultView)&&i.top!==i&&(i.addEventListener?i.addEventListener("unl
oad",re,!1):i.attachEvent&&i.attachEvent("onunload",re)),n.attributes=ue(func
tion(e){return
e.className="i",!e.getAttribute("className")}),n.getElementsByTagName=ue(func
tion(e){return
e.appendChild(d.createComment("")),!e.getElementsByTagName("*").length}),n.ge
tElementsByClassName=Q.test(d.getElementsByClassName),n.getById=ue(function(e
){return
h.appendChild(e).id=b,!d.getElementsByName||!d.getElementsByName(b).length}),
n.getById?(r.filter.ID=function(e){var t=e.replace(Z,ee);return
function(e){return
e.getAttribute("id")===t}),r.find.ID=function(e,t){if("undefined"!==typeof
t.getElementById&&g){var n=t.getElementById(e);return
n?[n]:[]}):(r.filter.ID=function(e){var t=e.replace(Z,ee);return
function(e){var n="undefined"!==typeof
e.getAttributeNode&&e.getAttributeNode("id");return
n&&n.value===t}),r.find.ID=function(e,t){if("undefined"!==typeof
t.getElementById&&g){var
n,r,i,o=t.getElementById(e);if(o){if((n=o.getAttributeNode("id"))&&n.value===
e)return[o];i=t.getElementsByName(e),r=0;while(o=i[r++])if((n=o.getAttributeN
ode("id"))&&n.value===e)return[o]}return[]})},r.find.TAG=n.getElementsByTagNa
me?function(e,t){return"undefined"!==typeof
t.getElementsByTagName?t.getElementsByTagName(e):n.qsa?t.querySelectorAll(e):
void 0}:function(e,t){var
n,r=[],i=0,o=t.getElementsByTagName(e);if("*"===e){while(n=o[i++])1===n.nodeT
ype&&r.push(n);return r}return

```

```

o),r.find.CLASS=n.getElementsByClassName&&function(e,t){if("undefined"!=typeof
f t.getElementsByClassName&&g) return
t.getElementsByClassName(e)},v=[],y=[],(n.qsa=Q.test(d.querySelectorAll))&&(u
e(function(e){h.appendChild(e).innerHTML="<a id='"+b+"'></a><select
id='"+b+"-\r\\' msallowcapture=''><option
selected=''></option></select>",e.querySelectorAll("[msallowcapture^='']").le
ngth&&y.push("[*^$]="+M+"*(?:'|\"\\")"),e.querySelectorAll("[selected]").leng
th|y.push("\\["+M+"*(?:value|"+P+"")"),e.querySelectorAll("[id~="+b+"-
]").length|y.push("~="),e.querySelectorAll(":checked").length|y.push(":chech
ked"),e.querySelectorAll("#"+b+"*").length|y.push("#.#+[+~]")}),ue(function
(e){e.innerHTML="<a href='\" disabled='disabled'></a><select
disabled='disabled'><option/></select>";var
t=d.createElement("input");t.setAttribute("type","hidden"),e.appendChild(t).s
etAttribute("name","D"),e.querySelectorAll("[name=d]").length&&y.push("name"+
M+"*[*^$|!~]?="),2!==e.querySelectorAll(":enabled").length&&y.push(":enabled"
,":disabled"),h.appendChild(e).disabled=!0,2!==e.querySelectorAll(":disabled"
).length&&y.push(":enabled",":disabled"),e.querySelectorAll("*,:x"),y.push(",
.*:"))), (n.matchesSelector=Q.test(m=h.matches||h.webkitMatchesSelector||h.mo
zMatchesSelector||h.oMatchesSelector||h.msMatchesSelector))&&ue(function(e){n
.disconnectedMatch=m.call(e,"*"),m.call(e,"[s!='']:x"),v.push("!=",W)},y=y.l
ength&&new RegExp(y.join("|")),v=v.length&&new
RegExp(v.join("|")),t=Q.test(h.compareDocumentPosition),x=t||Q.test(h.contain
s)?function(e,t){var
n=9===e.nodeType?e.documentElement:e,r=t&&t.parentNode;return
e===r||!(r||!r||!r.nodeType||!(n.contains?n.contains(r):e.compareDocumentPosi
tion&&16&e.compareDocumentPosition(r))):function(e,t){if(t)while(t=t.parentN
ode)if(t===e)return!0;return!1},D=t?function(e,t){if(e===t)return f=!0,0;var
r=!e.compareDocumentPosition-!t.compareDocumentPosition;return
r||!(1&(r=(e.ownerDocument||e)===t.ownerDocument||t)?e.compareDocumentPositio
n(t):1)||n.sortDetached&&t.compareDocumentPosition(e)===r?e===d||e.ownerDocu
ment===w&&x(w,e)?-1:t===d||t.ownerDocument===w&&x(w,t)?1:c?O(c,e)-
O(c,t):0:4&r?-1:1}):function(e,t){if(e===t)return f=!0,0;var
n,r=0,i=e.parentNode,o=t.parentNode,a=[e],s=[t];if(!i||!o)return e===d?-
1:t===d?1:i?-1:o?1:c?O(c,e)-O(c,t):0;if(i===o)return
ce(e,t);n=e;while(n=n.parentNode)a.unshift(n);n=t;while(n=n.parentNode)s.unsh
ift(n);while(a[r]===s[r])r++;return r?ce(a[r],s[r]):a[r]===w?-
1:s[r]===w?1:0},d):d},oe.matches=function(e,t){return
oe(e,null,null,t)},oe.matchesSelector=function(e,t){if((e.ownerDocument||e)!
=d&&p(e),t=t.replace(z,"'$1'"),n.matchesSelector&&g&&!S[t+"
"]&&(!v||!v.test(t))&&(!y||!y.test(t)))try{var
r=m.call(e,t);if(r||n.disconnectedMatch||e.document&&11!==e.document.nodeType
)return r}catch(e){}return
oe(t,d,null,[e]).length>0},oe.contains=function(e,t){return(e.ownerDocument||
e)!==d&&p(e),x(e,t)},oe.attr=function(e,t){(e.ownerDocument||e)!==d&&p(e);var
i=r.attrHandle[t.toLowerCase()],o=i&&N.call(r.attrHandle,t.toLowerCase())?i(e
,t,!g):void 0;return void
0!==o?o:n.attributes||!g?e.getAttribute(t):(o=e.getAttributeNode(t))&&o.speci
fied?o.value:null},oe.escape=function(e){return(e+"").replace(te,ne)},oe.erro
r=function(e){throw new Error("Syntax error, unrecognized expression:
"+e)},oe.uniqueSort=function(e){var
t,r=[],i=0,o=0;if(f=!n.detectDuplicates,c=!n.sortStable&&e.slice(0),e.sort(D
),f){while(t=e[o++])t===e[o]&&(i=r.push(o));while(i--)e.splice(r[i],1)}return
c=null,e},i=oe.getText=function(e){var
t,n="",r=0,o=e.nodeType;if(o){if(1===o||9===o||11===o){if("string"===typeof
e.textContent)return
e.textContent;for(e=e.firstChild;e;e=e.nextSibling)n+=i(e)}else
if(3===o||4===o)return e.nodeValue}else while(t=e[r++])n+=i(t);return

```

```

n}, (r=oe.selectors={cacheLength:50,createPseudo:se,match:V,attrHandle:{},find
: {},relative:{ ">":{dir:"parentNode",first:!0},"
":{dir:"parentNode"},"+":{dir:"previousSibling",first:!0},"~":{dir:"previousS
ibling"}},preFilter:{ATTR:function(e){return
e[1]=e[1].replace(Z,ee),e[3]=(e[3]||e[4]||e[5]||"").replace(Z,ee),"~"===e[2]
&&(e[3]=" "+e[3]+" "),e.slice(0,4)},CHILD:function(e){return
e[1]=e[1].toLowerCase(),"nth"===e[1].slice(0,3)?(e[3]||oe.error(e[0]),e[4]+=
e[4]?e[5]+(e[6]||1):2*(("even"===e[3]||"odd"===e[3])),e[5]+(e[7]+e[8]||"odd"
===e[3])):e[3]&&oe.error(e[0]),e},PSEUDO:function(e){var
t,n=!e[6]&&e[2];return
V.CHILD.test(e[0])?null:(e[3]?e[2]=e[4]||e[5]||"":n&&X.test(n)&&(t=a(n,!0))&&
(t=n.indexOf(")",n.length-t)-
n.length)&&(e[0]=e[0].slice(0,t),e[2]=n.slice(0,t),e.slice(0,3))},filter:{T
AG:function(e){var
t=e.replace(Z,ee).toLowerCase();return"*"===e?function(){return!0}:function(e
){return e.nodeName&&e.nodeName.toLowerCase()===t}},CLASS:function(e){var
t=E[e+" "];return t||(t=new
RegExp("(^|"+M+")"+e+"( "+M+"|$)"))&&E(e,function(e){return
t.test("string"===typeof e.className&&e.className||"undefined"!==typeof
e.getAttribute&&e.getAttribute("class")||"")}),ATTR:function(e,t,n){return
function(r){var i=oe.attr(r,e);return
null===i?"!="===t?!t||i+"="===t?i===n:"!="===t?i!==n:"^="===t?n&&0===i.in
dexOf(n):"*"===t?n&&i.indexOf(n)>-1:"$="===t?n&&i.slice(-
n.length)===n:"~"===t?(" "+i.replace($,"")+").indexOf(n)>-
1:"|"===t&&(i===n||i.slice(0,n.length+1)===n+"-
")}},CHILD:function(e,t,n,r,i){var
o="nth"!==e.slice(0,3),a="last"!==e.slice(-4),s="of-type"===t;return
1===r&&0===i?function(e){return!e.parentNode}:function(t,n,u){var
l,c,f,p,d,h,g=o!===a?"nextSibling":"previousSibling",y=t.parentNode,v=s&&t.nod
eName.toLowerCase(),m=!u&&!s,x=!1;if(y){if(o){while(g){p=t;while(p=p[g])if(s?
p.nodeName.toLowerCase()===v:1===p.nodeType)return!1;h=g="only"===e&&!h&&"nex
tSibling"}return!0}if(h=[a?y.firstChild:y.lastChild],a&&m){x=(d=(l=(c=(f=(p=y
)[b]||p[b]={})))[p.uniqueID]||f[p.uniqueID]={})[e]||[])[0]===T&&l[1])&&l[2]
,p=d&&y.childNodes[d];while(p=++d&&p&&p[g]||x=d=0||h.pop())if(1===p.nodeType
e&&+x&&p===t){c[e]=[T,d,x];break}}else
if(m&&(x=d=(l=(c=(f=(p=t)[b]||p[b]={})))[p.uniqueID]||f[p.uniqueID]={})[e]||
[])[0]===T&&l[1],!1===x)while(p=++d&&p&&p[g]||x=d=0||h.pop())if((s?p.node
Name.toLowerCase()===v:1===p.nodeType)&&+x&&(m&&(c=(f=p[b]||p[b]={})))[p.un
iqueID]||f[p.uniqueID]={})[e]=[T,x],p===t)break;return(x-
=i)===r||x%r===0&&x/r>=0}},PSEUDO:function(e,t){var
n,i=r.pseudos[e]||r.setFilters[e.toLowerCase()]||oe.error("unsupported
pseudo: "+e);return
i[b]?i(t):i.length>1?(n=[e,e,"",t],r.setFilters.hasOwnProperty(e.toLowerCase(
))?se(function(e,n){var r,o=i(e,t),a=o.length;while(a--
)e[r=0(e,o[a])]=!(n[r]=o[a])}:function(e){return
i(e,0,n)}:i)},pseudos:{not:se(function(e){var
t=[],n=[],r=s(e.replace(B,"$1"));return r[b]?se(function(e,t,n,i){var
o,a=r(e,null,i,[]),s=e.length;while(s--
)(o=a[s])&&(e[s]=!(t[s]=o))}:function(e,i,o){return
t[0]=e,r(t,null,o,n),t[0]=null,!n.pop()}),has:se(function(e){return
function(t){return oe(e,t).length>0}),contains:se(function(e){return
e=e.replace(Z,ee),function(t){return(t.textContent||t.innerText||i(t)).indexO
f(e)>-1}},lang:se(function(e){return U.test(e||"")||oe.error("unsupported
lang: "+e),e=e.replace(Z,ee).toLowerCase(),function(t){var
n;do{if(n=g?t.lang:t.getAttribute("xml:lang")||t.getAttribute("lang"))return
n=n.toLowerCase()===e||0===n.indexOf(e+"-
")}while((t=t.parentNode)&&1===t.nodeType);return!1}}),target:function(t){var

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n=e.location&&e.location.hash;return
n&&n.slice(1)==t.id},root:function(e){return e==h},focus:function(e){return
e==d.activeElement&&(!d.hasFocus||d.hasFocus())&&!(e.type|e.href|~e.tabIn
dex)},enabled:de(!1),disabled:de(!0),checked:function(e){var
t=e.nodeName.toLowerCase();return"input"===t&&!!e.checked||"option"===t&&!!e.
selected},selected:function(e){return
e.parentNode&&e.parentNode.selectedIndex,!0===e.selected},empty:function(e){f
or(e=e.firstChild;e=e.nextSibling)if(e.nodeType<6)return!1;return!0},parent
:function(e){return!r.pseudos.empty(e)},header:function(e){return
Y.test(e.nodeName)},input:function(e){return
G.test(e.nodeName)},button:function(e){var
t=e.nodeName.toLowerCase();return"input"===t&&"button"===e.type||"button"===t
},text:function(e){var
t;return"input"===e.nodeName.toLowerCase()&&"text"===e.type&&(null==(t=e.getA
ttribute("type"))||"text"===t.toLowerCase())},first:he(function(){return[0]})
,last:he(function(e,t){return[t-
1]}),eq:he(function(e,t,n){return[n<0?n+t:n]}),even:he(function(e,t){for(var
n=0;n<t;n+=2)e.push(n);return e}),odd:he(function(e,t){for(var
n=1;n<t;n+=2)e.push(n);return e}),lt:he(function(e,t,n){for(var r=n<0?n+t;n;-
-r>=0;)e.push(r);return e}),gt:he(function(e,t,n){for(var
r=n<0?n+t;n;++r<t;)e.push(r);return e}}).pseudos.nth=r.pseudos.eq;for(t
in{radio:!0,checkbox:!0,file:!0,password:!0,image:!0})r.pseudos[t]=fe(t);for(
t in{submit:!0,reset:!0})r.pseudos[t]=pe(t);function
ye(){ye.prototype=r.filters=r.pseudos,r.setFilters=new
ye,a=oe.tokenize=function(e,t){var n,i,o,a,s,u,l,c=k[e+" "];if(c)return
t?0:c.slice(0);s=e,u=[],l=r.preFilter;while(s){n&&!(i=F.exec(s))||i&&(s=s.sl
ice(i[0].length)||s),u.push(o=[]),n=!1,(i=_.exec(s))&&(n=i.shift()),o.push({v
alue:n,type:i[0].replace(B," ")}),s=s.slice(n.length)};for(a in
r.filter)!(i=V[a].exec(s))||l[a]&&!(i=l[a](i))||n=i.shift(),o.push({value:n,
type:a,matches:i}),s=s.slice(n.length);if(!n)break}return
t?s.length:s?oe.error(e):k(e,u).slice(0)};function ve(e){for(var
t=0,n=e.length,r="";t<n;t++)r+=e[t].value;return r}function me(e,t,n){var
r=t.dir,i=t.next,o=i||r,a=n&&"parentNode"===o,s=C++;return
t.first?function(t,n,i){while(t=t[r])if(1===t.nodeType||a)return
e(t,n,i);return!1}:function(t,n,u){var
l,c,f,p=[T,s];if(u){while(t=t[r])if((1===t.nodeType||a)&&e(t,n,u))return!0}el
se
while(t=t[r])if(1===t.nodeType||a)if(f=t[b]||t[b]={},c=f[t.uniqueID]||f[t.
uniqueID]={},i&&i===t.nodeName.toLowerCase())t=t[r]||t;else{if((l=c[o])&&l[0
]===T&&l[1]===s)return
p[2]=l[2];if(c[o]=p,p[2]=e(t,n,u))return!0}return!1}}function xe(e){return
e.length>1?function(t,n,r){var i=e.length;while(i--
)if(!e[i](t,n,r))return!1;return!0}:e[0]}function be(e,t,n){for(var
r=0,i=t.length;r<i;r++)oe(e,t[r],n);return n}function we(e,t,n,r,i){for(var
o,a=[],s=0,u=e.length,l=null!=t;s<u;s++)(o=e[s])&&(n&&!n(o,r,i)||a.push(o),l
&&t.push(s));return a}function Te(e,t,n,r,i,o){return
r&&!r[b]&&(r=Te(r)),i&&!i[b]&&(i=Te(i,o)),se(function(o,a,s,u){var
l,c,f,p=[],d=[],h=a.length,g=o||be(t||"*",s.nodeType?[s]:s,[],),y=!e||!o&&t?g:
we(g,p,e,s,u),v=n?i||o?e:h||r?[]:a:y;if(n&&n(y,v,s,u),r){l=we(v,d),r(l,[],s
,u),c=l.length;while(c--
)(f=l[c])&&(v[d[c]]!=v[d[c]]?f)}if(o){if(i||e){if(i){l=[],c=v.length;while(
c--)(f=v[c])&&l.push(y[c]=f);i(null,v,[],l,u)}c=v.length;while(c--
)(f=v[c])&&(l=i?0(o,f):p[c])>-1&&(o[l]!=a[l]=f)}}else
v=we(v===a?v.splice(h,v.length):v),i?i(null,a,v,u):L.apply(a,v)}function
Ce(e){for(var t,n,i,o=e.length,a=r.relative[e[0].type],s=a||r.relative["
"],u=a?1:0,c=me(function(e){return e===t},s,!0),f=me(function(e){return
0(t,e)>-1},s,!0),p=[function(e,n,r){var

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i=!a&&(r||n!==(l)||((t=n).nodeType?c(e,n,r):f(e,n,r));return
t=null,i};u<o;u++)if(n=r.relative[e[u].type])p=[me(xe(p),n)];else{if((n=r.fi
lter[e[u].type].apply(null,e[u].matches))[b]){for(i=++u;i<o;i++)if(r.relative
[e[i].type])break;return Te(u>1&&xe(p),u>1&&ve(e.slice(0,u-1).concat({value:"
"==e[u-
2].type?"*":""})).replace(B,"$1"),n,u<i&&Ce(e.slice(u,i)),i<o&&Ce(e=e.slice(i
)),i<o&&ve(e))p.push(n)}return xe(p)}function Ee(e,t){var
n=t.length>0,i=e.length>0,o=function(o,a,s,u,c){var
f,h,y,v=0,m="0",x=o&&[],b=[],w=1,C=o||i&&r.find.TAG("*",c),E=T+=null==w?1:Mat
h.random()|.1,k=C.length;for(c&&(l=a==d||a|c);m!=k&&null!=(f=C[m]);m++){i
f(i&&f){h=0,a||f.ownerDocument==d||p(f),s=!g);while(y=e[h++])if(y(f,a|d,s)
){u.push(f);break}c&&(T=E)}n&&(f=!y&&f)&&v--
,o&&x.push(f)}if(v+=m,n&&m!==(v){h=0;while(y=t[h++])y(x,b,a,s);if(o){if(v>0)w
hile(m--
)x[m]||b[m]||b[m]=j.call(u);b=we(b)}L.apply(u,b),c&&!o&&b.length>0&&v+t.len
gth>1&&oe.uniqueSort(u)}return c&&(T=E,l=w),x};return n?se(o):o}return
s=oe.compile=function(e,t){var n,r=[],i=[],o=S[e+"
"];if(!o){t||t=a(e),n=t.length;while(n--
)(o=Ce(t[n]))[b]?r.push(o):i.push(o);(o=S(e,Ee(i,r))).selector=e}return
o},u=oe.select=function(e,t,n,i){var o,u,l,c,f,p="function"===typeof
e&&e,d=!i&&a(e=p.selector|e);if(n=n||[],1==d.length){if((u=d[0]=d[0].slice(
0)).length>2&&"ID"==(l=u[0]).type&&9==t.nodeType&&g&&r.relative[u[1].type])
{if(!(t=(r.find.ID(l.matches[0].replace(Z,ee),t)||[])[0]))return
n;p&&(t=t.parentNode),e=e.slice(u.shift().value.length)}o=V.needsContext.test
(e)?0:u.length;while(o--
){if(l=u[o],r.relative[c=l.type])break;if((f=r.find[c])&&(i=f(l.matches[0].re
place(Z,ee),K.test(u[0].type)&&ge(t.parentNode)|t))){if(u.splice(o,1),!(e=i.
length&&ve(u))return
L.apply(n,i),n;break}}return(p||s(e,d))(i,t,!g,n,!t||K.test(e)&&ge(t.parentN
ode)|t),n),n.sortStable=b.split("").sort(D).join("")==b,n.detectDuplicates=
!!f,p(),n.sortDetached=ue(function(e){return
l&e.compareDocumentPosition(d.createElement("fieldset"))},ue(function(e){ret
urn e.innerHTML="<a
href='#'></a>","#"==e.firstChild.getAttribute("href"))||le("type|href|height
|width",function(e,t,n){if(!n)return
e.getAttribute(t,"type"===t.toLowerCase()?1:2)}),n.attributes&&ue(function(e)
{return
e.innerHTML="<input/>",e.firstChild.setAttribute("value",""),"===e.firstChil
d.getAttribute("value")})||le("value",function(e,t,n){if(!n&&"input"===e.node
Name.toLowerCase())return e.defaultValue}),ue(function(e){return
null==e.getAttribute("disabled")})||le(P,function(e,t,n){var
r;if(!n)return!0==e[t]?t.toLowerCase():(r=e.getAttributeNode(t))&&r.specifie
d?r.value:null}},oe)(e);w.find=E,w.expr=E.selectors,w.expr[":"]=w.expr.pseudo
s,w.uniqueSort=w.unique=E.uniqueSort,w.text=E.getText,w.isXMLDoc=E.isXML,w.co
ntains=E.contains,w.escapeSelector=E.escape;var k=function(e,t,n){var
r=[],i=void
0!==(n;while((e=e[t])&&9!==(e.nodeType))if(1==e.nodeType){if(i&&w(e).is(n))brea
k;r.push(e)}return r},S=function(e,t){for(var
n=[];e=e.nextSibling)1==e.nodeType&&e!==t&&n.push(e);return
n},D=w.expr.match.needsContext;function N(e,t){return
e.nodeName&&e.nodeName.toLowerCase()===t.toLowerCase()}var A=/^(<([a-
z][^\s\/>:\x20\t\r\n\f]*)[\x20\t\r\n\f]*\/?>(?:<\/\1>|)$/i;function
j(e,t,n){return
g(t)?w.grep(e,function(e,r){return!!t.call(e,r,e)!==(n)}):t.nodeType?w.grep(e,f
unction(e){return e==t!==(n)}):"string"!==typeof t?w.grep(e,function(e){return
u.call(t,e)>-1!==(n)}):w.filter(t,e,n)}w.filter=function(e,t,n){var
r=t[0];return

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n&&(e!=":not("+e+")"),1===t.length&&1===r.nodeType?w.find.matchesSelector(r,e)
?[r]:[]:w.find.matches(e,w.grep(t,function(e){return
1===e.nodeType})),w.fn.extend({find:function(e){var
t,n,r=this.length,i=this;if("string"!==typeof e)return
this.pushStack(w(e).filter(function(){for(t=0;t<r;t++)if(w.contains(i[t],this)
)return!0}));for(n=this.pushStack([],t=0;t<r;t++)w.find(e,i[t],n);return
r>1?w.uniqueSort(n):n},filter:function(e){return
this.pushStack(j(this,e||[],!1)),not:function(e){return
this.pushStack(j(this,e||[],!0)),is:function(e){return!j(this,"string"===typ
eof e&&D.test(e)?w(e):e||[],!1).length}});var
q,L=/^(?:\s*(<[\w\W]+>)[^>]*|#([\w-]+))$/;(w.fn.init=function(e,t,n){var
i,o;if(!e)return this;if(n=n||q,"string"===typeof
e){if(!i=i("<"===e[0]&&">"===e[e.length-
1]&&e.length>=3?[null,e,null]:L.exec(e))||!i[1]&&t)return!t||t.jquery?(t||n).
find(e):this.constructor(t).find(e);if(i[1]){if(t=t instanceof
w?t[0]:t,w.merge(this,w.parseHTML(i[1],t&&t.nodeType?t.ownerDocument||t:r,!0)
),A.test(i[1])&&w.isPlainObject(t))for(i in
t)g(this[i]?this[i](t[i]):this.attr(i,t[i]));return
this}return(o=r.getElementById(i[2]))&&(this[0]=o,this.length=1),this}return
e.nodeType?(this[0]=e,this.length=1,this):g(e)?void
0!:=n.ready?n.ready(e):e(w):w.makeArray(e,this)}.prototype=w.fn,q=w(r);var
H=/^(?:parents|prev(?:Until|All))/,O={children:!0,contents:!0,next:!0,prev:!0
};w.fn.extend({has:function(e){var t=w(e,this),n=t.length;return
this.filter(function(){for(var
e=0;e<n;e++)if(w.contains(this,t[e]))return!0})),closest:function(e,t){var
n,r=0,i=this.length,o=[],a="string"!==typeof
e&&w(e);if(!D.test(e))for(;r<i;r++)for(n=this[r];n&&n!==t;n=n.parentNode)if(n
.nodeType<11&&(a?a.index(n)>-
1:1===n.nodeType&&w.find.matchesSelector(n,e)){o.push(n);break}return
this.pushStack(o.length>1?w.uniqueSort(o):o)},index:function(e){return
e?"string"===typeof
e?u.call(w(e),this[0]):u.call(this,e.jquery?e[0]:e):this[0]&&this[0].parentNo
de?this.first().prevAll().length:-1},add:function(e,t){return
this.pushStack(w.uniqueSort(w.merge(this.get(),w(e,t))))},addBack:function(e)
{return
this.add(null===e?this.prevObject:this.prevObject.filter(e))});function
P(e,t){while((e=e[t])&&1!==e.nodeType);return
e}w.each({parent:function(e){var t=e.parentNode;return
t&&1!==t.nodeType?t:null},parents:function(e){return
k(e,"parentNode")},parentsUntil:function(e,t,n){return
k(e,"parentNode",n)},next:function(e){return
P(e,"nextSibling")},prev:function(e){return
P(e,"previousSibling")},nextAll:function(e){return
k(e,"nextSibling")},prevAll:function(e){return
k(e,"previousSibling")},nextUntil:function(e,t,n){return
k(e,"nextSibling",n)},prevUntil:function(e,t,n){return
k(e,"previousSibling",n)},siblings:function(e){return
S((e.parentNode||{}).firstChild,e)},children:function(e){return
S(e.firstChild)},contents:function(e){return
N(e,"iframe")?e.contentDocument:(N(e,"template")&&(e=e.content||e),w.merge([],
e.childNodes))},function(e,t){w.fn[e]=function(n,r){var
i=w.map(this,t,n);return"Until"!==e.slice(-5)&&(r=n),r&&"string"===typeof
r&&(i=w.filter(r,i)),this.length>1&&(O[e]||w.uniqueSort(i),H.test(e)&&i.rever
se()),this.pushStack(i)};var M=/^\x20\t\r\n\f+/g;function R(e){var
t={};return
w.each(e.match(M)||[],function(e,n){t[n]=!0}),t}w.Callbacks=function(e){e="st
ring"===typeof e?R(e):w.extend({},e);var t,n,r,i,o=[],a=[],s=-

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1, u=function () {for (i=i || e.once, r=t=!0; a.length; s=-
1) {n=a.shift (); while (++s<o.length) !1===o[s].apply (n[0], n[1]) && e.stopOnFalse&&
(s=o.length, n=!1) } e.memory || (n=!1), t=!1, i&& (o=n?[]: "") }, l={add: function () {ret
urn o&& (n&&!t&& (s=o.length-1, a.push (n)), function
t (n) {w.each (n, function (n, r) {g (r) ? e.unique&&l.has (r) || o.push (r): r&&r.length&&"
string"!==x (r) &&t (r) })} (arguments), n&&!t&&u ()), this}, remove: function () {return
w.each (arguments, function (e, t) {var n; while ((n=w.inArray (t, o, n))>-
1) o.splice (n, 1), n<=s&&s--}, this}, has: function (e) {return e?w.inArray (e, o)>-
1:o.length>0}, empty: function () {return
o&&(o=[]), this}, disable: function () {return
i=a=[], o=n="", this}, disabled: function () {return !o}, lock: function () {return
i=a=[], n || t || (o=n=""), this}, locked: function () {return !!i}, fireWith: function (e,
n) {return
i || (n=[e, (n=n || []).slice ? n.slice () : n], a.push (n), t || u ()), this}, fire: function ()
{return l.fireWith (this, arguments), this}, fired: function () {return !!r}}; return
l}; function I (e) {return e} function W (e) {throw e} function $ (e, t, n, r) {var
i; try {e&&g (i=e.promise) ? i.call (e).done (t).fail (n): e&&g (i=e.then) ? i.call (e, t, n
): t.apply (void 0, [e].slice (r))} catch (e) {n.apply (void
0, [e])}} w.extend ({Deferred: function (t) {var
n=[["notify", "progress", w.Callbacks ("memory"), w.Callbacks ("memory"), 2], ["reso
lve", "done", w.Callbacks ("once memory"), w.Callbacks ("once
memory"), 0, "resolved"], ["reject", "fail", w.Callbacks ("once
memory"), w.Callbacks ("once
memory"), 1, "rejected"]], r="pending", i={state: function () {return
r}, always: function () {return
o.done (arguments).fail (arguments), this}, "catch": function (e) {return
i.then (null, e)}, pipe: function () {var e=arguments; return
w.Deferred (function (t) {w.each (n, function (n, r) {var
i=g (e[r[4]]) &&e[r[4]] (function () {var
e=i&&i.apply (this, arguments); e&&g (e.promise) ? e.promise ().progress (t.notify).d
one (t.resolve).fail (t.reject): t[r[0]+"With"] (this, i?[e]: arguments) }}), e=null
}).promise (}), then: function (t, r, i) {var o=0; function a (t, n, r, i) {return
function () {var s=this, u=arguments, l=function () {var
e, l; if (! (t<o)) {if ((e=r.apply (s, u))===n.promise ()) throw new
TypeError ("Thenable self-resolution"); l=e&& ("object"===typeof
e || "function"===typeof
e) &&e.then, g (l) ? i?l.call (e, a (o, n, I, i), a (o, n, W, i)): (o++, l.call (e, a (o, n, I, i), a
(o, n, W, i), a (o, n, I, n.notifyWith))) : (r!==I&&(s=void
0, u=[e]), (i || n.resolveWith) (s, u))}}, c=i?l: function () {try {l ()} catch (e) {w.Defer
red.exceptionHook&&w.Deferred.exceptionHook (e, c.stackTrace), t+1>=o&&(r!==W&&(
s=void
0, u=[e]), n.rejectWith (s, u))}}; t?c (): (w.Deferred.getStackHook&&(c.stackTrace=w
.Deferred.getStackHook ()), e.setTimeout (c))}} return
w.Deferred (function (e) {n[0][3].add (a (0, e, g (i) ? i: I, e.notifyWith)), n[1][3].add (
a (0, e, g (t) ? t: I), n[2][3].add (a (0, e, g (r) ? r: W))}).promise (}), promise: function (e
) {return null!=e?w.extend (e, i): i}, o: {}}, return w.each (n, function (e, t) {var
a=t[2], s=t[5]; i[t[1]]=a.add, s&&a.add (function () {r=s}, n[3-e][2].disable, n[3-
e][3].disable, n[0][2]).lock, n[0][3].lock, a.add (t[3].fire), o[t[0]]=function () {
return o[t[0]+"With"] (this===o?void
0: this, arguments), this}, o[t[0]+"With"]=a.fireWith}), i.promise (o), t&&t.call (o,
o, o), when: function (e) {var
t=arguments.length, n=t, r=Array (n), i=o.call (arguments), a=w.Deferred (), s=functi
on (e) {return
function (n) {r[e]=this, i[e]=arguments.length>1?o.call (arguments): n, --
t || a.resolveWith (r, i)}}; if (t<=1&& ($ (e, a.done (s (n)).resolve, a.reject, !t), "pend
ing"===a.state () || g (i[n] &&i[n].then))) return a.then (); while (n--
) $ (i[n], s (n), a.reject); return a.promise ()}}); var

```

```

B=/^(Eval|Internal|Range|Reference|Syntax|Type|URI)Error$/;w.Deferred.exception
onHook=function(t,n){e.console&&e.console.warn&&t&&B.test(t.name)&&e.console.
warn("jQuery.Deferred exception:
"+t.message,t.stack,n)},w.readyException=function(t){e.setTimeout(function(){
throw t});var F=w.Deferred();w.fn.ready=function(e){return
F.then(e)["catch"](function(e){w.readyException(e)}),this},w.extend({isReady:
!1,readyWait:1,ready:function(e){(!0===e?--
w.readyWait:w.isReady)||w.isReady=!0,!0!==e&&--
w.readyWait>0||F.resolveWith(r,[w])}}),w.ready.then=F.then;function
_(r){r.removeEventListener("DOMContentLoaded",_),e.removeEventListener("load",
_),w.ready()}"complete"===r.readyState||"loading"!==r.readyState&&!r.document
Element.doScroll?e.setTimeout(w.ready):(r.addEventListener("DOMContentLoaded"
,_) ,e.addEventListener("load",_));var z=function(e,t,n,r,i,o,a){var
s=0,u=e.length,l=null==n;if("object"===x(n)){i=!0;for(s in
n)z(e,t,s,n[s],!0,o,a)}else if(void
0!==r&&(i=!0,g(r)||a=!0),l&&a?(t.call(e,r),t=null):(l=t,t=function(e,t,n){r
return
l.call(w(e),n)}),t)for(;s<u;s++)t(e[s],n,a?r:r.call(e[s],s,t(e[s],n)));retu
rn i?e:l?t.call(e):u?t(e[0],n):o},X=/^-ms-/ ,U=-([a-z])/g;function
V(e,t){return t.toUpperCase()}function G(e){return e.replace(X,"ms-
").replace(U,V)}var Y=function(e){return
1===e.nodeType||9===e.nodeType||!+e.nodeType};function
Q(){this.expando=w.expando+Q.uid++}Q.uid=1,Q.prototype={cache:function(e){var
t=e[this.expando];return
t||t={},Y(e)&&(e.nodeType?e[this.expando]=t:Object.defineProperty(e,this.exp
ando,{value:t,configurable:!0})),t},set:function(e,t,n){var
r,i=this.cache(e);if("string"===typeof t)i[G(t)]=n;else for(r in
t)i[G(r)]=t[r];return i},get:function(e,t){return void
0===t?this.cache(e):e[this.expando]&&e[this.expando][G(t)],access:function(e
,t,n){return void 0===t||t&&"string"===typeof t&&void
0===n?this.get(e,t):(this.set(e,t,n),void
0!==n?n:t),remove:function(e,t){var n,r=e[this.expando];if(void
0!==r){if(void 0!==t){n=(t=Array.isArray(t)?t.map(G):(t=G(t))in
r?[t]:t.match(M)||[]).length;while(n--)delete r[t[n]]}(void
0===t||w.isEmptyObject(r))&&(e.nodeType?e[this.expando]=void 0:delete
e[this.expando])}},hasData:function(e){var t=e[this.expando];return void
0!==t&&!w.isEmptyObject(t)}},var J=new Q,K=new
Q,Z=/^(?:(\{[\w\W]*\})|([\w\W]*))$/ ,ee=/[A-Z]/g;function
te(e){return"true"===e||"false"!==e&&("null"===e?null:e===+e+""?+e:Z.test(e)?
JSON.parse(e):e)}function ne(e,t,n){var r;if(void
0===n&&1===e.nodeType)if(r="data-"+t.replace(ee,"-
$&").toLowerCase(),"string"===typeof(n=e.getAttribute(r))){try{n=te(n)}catch(e
){}K.set(e,t,n)}else n=void 0;return n}w.extend({hasData:function(e){return
K.hasData(e)||J.hasData(e)},data:function(e,t,n){return
K.access(e,t,n)},removeData:function(e,t){K.remove(e,t)},_data:function(e,t,n
){return
J.access(e,t,n)},_removeData:function(e,t){J.remove(e,t)}},w.fn.extend({data
:function(e,t){var n,r,i,o=this[0],a=o&&o.attributes;if(void
0===e){if(this.length&&(i=K.get(o),1===o.nodeType&&!J.get(o,"hasDataAttrs"))
){n=a.length;while(n--)a[n]&&0===(r=a[n].name).indexOf("data-
")&&(r=G(r.slice(5)),ne(o,r,i[r]));J.set(o,"hasDataAttrs",!0)}return
i}return"object"===typeof
e?this.each(function(){K.set(this,e)}):z(this,function(t){var n;if(o&&void
0===t){if(void 0!==(n=K.get(o,e))return n;if(void 0!==(n=ne(o,e)))return
n}else
this.each(function(){K.set(this,e,t)}),null,t,arguments.length>1,null,!0)},r
emoveData:function(e){return

```

```

this.each(function() {K.remove(this,e)})),w.extend({queue:function(e,t,n){var
r;r;if(e)return
t=(t||"fx")+"queue",r=J.get(e,t),n&&(!r||Array.isArray(n)?r=J.access(e,t,w.ma
keArray(n)):r.push(n),r||[]},dequeue:function(e,t){t=t||"fx";var
n=w.queue(e,t),r=n.length,i=n.shift(),o=w._queueHooks(e,t),a=function(){w.deq
ueue(e,t)};"inprogress"===i&&(i=n.shift(),r--
),i&&("fx"===t&&n.unshift("inprogress"),delete
o.stop,i.call(e,a,o),!r&&o&&o.empty.fire()),_queueHooks:function(e,t){var
n=t+"queueHooks";return J.get(e,n)||J.access(e,n,{empty:w.Callbacks("once
memory").add(function(){J.remove(e,[t+"queue",n])})})},w.fn.extend({queue:f
unction(e,t){var n=2;return"string"!==typeof e&&(t=e,e="fx",n--
),arguments.length<n?w.queue(this[0],e):void
0===t?this:this.each(function(){var
n=w.queue(this,e,t);w._queueHooks(this,e),"fx"===e&&"inprogress"!==n[0]&&w.de
queueue(this,e)}},dequeue:function(e){return
this.each(function(){w.dequeue(this,e)}},clearQueue:function(e){return
this.queue(e||"fx",[]),promise:function(e,t){var
n,r=1,i=w.Deferred(),o=this,a=this.length,s=function(){--
r||i.resolveWith(o,[o])};"string"!==typeof e&&(t=e,e=void
0),e=e||"fx";while(a--
)(n=J.get(o[a],e+"queueHooks"))&&n.empty&&(r++,n.empty.add(s));return
s(),i.promise(t)});var re=/[+-]?(\d*\.\d+)?([eE][+-
]?[a-z%]*)$/i,ie=new RegExp("^([+-])=|("+re+")([a-
z%]*)$","i"),oe=["Top","Right","Bottom","Left"],ae=function(e,t){return"none"
===(e=t||e).style.display||""===e.style.display&&w.contains(e.ownerDocument,e
)&&"none"===w.css(e,"display")},se=function(e,t,n,r){var i,o,a={};for(o in
t)a[o]=e.style[o],e.style[o]=t[o];i=n.apply(e,r||[]);for(o in
t)e.style[o]=a[o];return i};function ue(e,t,n,r){var
i,o,a=20,s=r?function(){return r.cur()}:function(){return
w.css(e,t,"")},u=s(),l=n&&n[3]||(w.cssNumber[t]?"":"px"),c=(w.cssNumber[t]||"
px"!==l&&+u)&&ie.exec(w.css(e,t));if(c&&c[3]!==1){u/=2,l=1||c[3],c=+u||1;whil
e(a-->w.style(e,t,c+1),(1-o)*(1-
(o=s()/u||.5))<=0&&(a=0),c/=o;c*=2,w.style(e,t,c+1),n=n||[])}return
n&&(c=c||+u||0,i=n[1]?c+(n[1]+1)*n[2]:+n[2],r&&(r.unit=1,r.start=c,r.end=i)
),i}var le={};function ce(e){var
t,n=e.ownerDocument,r=e.nodeName,i=le[r];return
i||(t=n.body.appendChild(n.createElement(r)),i=w.css(t,"display"),t.parentNod
e.removeChild(t),"none"===i&&(i="block"),le[r]=i,i)}function fe(e,t){for(var
n,r,i=[],o=0,a=e.length;o<a;o++)(r=e[o]).style&&(n=r.style.display,t?("none"=
===n&&(i[o]=J.get(r,"display")||null,i[o]||(r.style.display="")),""===r.style.
display&&ae(r)&&(i[o]=ce(r)):"none"!==n&&(i[o]="none",J.set(r,"display",n)
);for(o=0;o<a;o++)null!==i[o]&&(e[o].style.display=i[o]);return
e}w.fn.extend({show:function(){return fe(this,!0)},hide:function(){return
fe(this)},toggle:function(e){return"boolean"===typeof
e?e?this.show():this.hide():this.each(function(){ae(this)?w(this).show():w(th
is).hide()})});var pe=/^(?:checkbox|radio)$/i,de=/<([a-
z][^\s/\0>\x20\t\r\n\f]+)/i,he=/^$|^module$/i/(?:java|ecma)script/i,ge={option
:[1,"<select
multiple='multiple'>","</select>"],thead:[1,"<table>","</table>"],col:[2,"<ta
ble><colgroup>","</colgroup></table>"],tr:[2,"<table><tbody>","</tbody></tabl
e>"],td:[3,"<table><tbody><tr>","</tr></tbody></table>"],_default:[0,"",""];
ge.optgroup=ge.option,ge.tbody=ge.tfoot=ge.colgroup=ge.caption=ge.thead,ge.th
=ge.td;function ye(e,t){var n;return n="undefined"!==typeof
e.getElementsByTagName?e.getElementsByTagName(t||"*"):"undefined"!==typeof
e.querySelector?e.querySelector(t||"*"):[],void
0===t||t&&N(e,t)?w.merge([e],n):n}function ve(e,t){for(var
n=0,r=e.length;n<r;n++)J.set(e[n],"globalEval",!t||J.get(t[n],"globalEval"))}

```

```

var me=/<|&#?\w+;/;function xe(e,t,n,r,i){for(var
o,a,s,u,l,c,f=t.createDocumentFragment(),p=[],d=0,h=e.length;d<h;d++)if((o=e[
d])||0===o)if("object"===x(o))w.merge(p,o.nodeType?[o]:o);else
if(me.test(o)){a=a||f.appendChild(t.createElement("div")),s=(de.exec(o)||["",
""])[1].toLowerCase(),u=ge[s]||ge._default,a.innerHTML=u[1]+w.htmlPrefilter(o
)+u[2],c=u[0];while(c--
)a=a.lastChild;w.merge(p,a.childNodes),(a=f.firstChild).textContent=""}else
p.push(t.createTextNode(o));f.textContent="",d=0;while(o=p[d++])if(r&&w.inArr
ay(o,r)>-1)i&&i.push(o);else
if(l=w.contains(o.ownerDocument,o),a=ye(f.appendChild(o),"script"),l&&ve(a,n
){c=0;while(o=a[c++])he.test(o.type||"")&&n.push(o)}return f)!function(){var
e=r.createDocumentFragment().appendChild(r.createElement("div")),t=r.createEl
ement("input");t.setAttribute("type","radio"),t.setAttribute("checked","check
ed"),t.setAttribute("name","t"),e.appendChild(t),h.checkClone=e.cloneNode(!0)
.cloneNode(!0).lastChild.checked,e.innerHTML="<textarea>x</textarea>",h.noClo
neChecked=!!e.cloneNode(!0).lastChild.defaultValue}();var
be=r.documentElement,we=/^key/,Te=/^(?:mouse|pointer|contextmenu|drag|drop)|c
lick/,Ce=/^(\[.\]*)?(?:\.(.+)|)/;function Ee(){return!0}function
ke(){return!1}function Se(){try{return r.activeElement}catch(e){}}function
De(e,t,n,r,i,o){var a,s;if("object"===typeof t){"string"!==typeof
n&&(r=r||n,n=void 0);for(s in t)De(e,s,n,r,t[s],o);return
e}if(null===r&&null===i?(i=n,r=n=void 0):null===i&&("string"===typeof
n?(i=r,r=void 0):(i=r,r=n,n=void 0)),!1===i)i=ke;else if(!i)return e;return
l===o&&(a=i,(i=function(e){return
w().off(e),a.apply(this,arguments)}).guid=a.guid||(a.guid=w.guid++)),e.each(f
unction(){w.event.add(this,t,i,r,n)}))w.event={global:{},add:function(e,t,n,r
,i){var
o,a,s,u,l,c,f,p,d,h,g,y=J.get(e);if(y){n.handler&&(n=(o=n).handler,i=o.select
or),i&&w.find.matchesSelector(be,i),n.guid||(n.guid=w.guid++),(u=y.events)||
(u=y.events={}),a=y.handle||a=y.handle=function(t){return"undefined"!==typeo
f w&&w.event.triggered!==t.type?w.event.dispatch.apply(e,arguments):void
0}},l=(t=(t||"").match(M)||[""]).length;while(l--
)d=g=(s=Ce.exec(t[l])||[])[1],h=(s[2]||"").split(".").sort(),d&&(f=w.event.sp
eial[d]||{}),d=(i?f.delegateType:f.bindType)||d,f=w.event.special[d]||{}),c=w
.extend({type:d,origType:g,data:r,handler:n,guid:n.guid,selector:i,needsContex
t:i&&w.expr.match.needsContext.test(i),namespace:h.join("."),o,(p=u[d])||((
p=u[d]=[]).delegateCount=0,f.setup&&!1!==f.setup.call(e,r,h,a)||e.addEventLis
tener&&e.addEventListener(d,a),f.add&&(f.add.call(e,c),c.handler.guid||(c.ha
ndler.guid=n.guid)),i?p.splice(p.delegateCount++,0,c):p.push(c),w.event.globa
l[d]=!0)}},remove:function(e,t,n,r,i){var
o,a,s,u,l,c,f,p,d,h,g,y=J.hasData(e)&&J.get(e);if(y&&(u=y.events)){l=(t=(t||"
").match(M)||[""]).length;while(l--
)if(s=Ce.exec(t[l])||[],d=g=s[1],h=(s[2]||"").split(".").sort(),d){f=w.event
.special[d]||{}),p=u[d=(r?f.delegateType:f.bindType)||d]||[],s=s[2]&&new
RegExp("(^|\\.)"+h.join("\\.(?:.*\\.|)"+("\\.|$)"),a=o.p.length;while(o--
)c=p[o],!i&&g!==c.origType|n&&n.guid!==c.guid|s&&!s.test(c.namespace)|r&&r
!==c.selector&&("*"!==r||!c.selector)||p.splice(o,1),c.selector&&p.delegate
Count--
,f.remove&&f.remove.call(e,c);a&&p.length&&(f.teardown&&!1!==f.teardown.cal
l(e,h,y.handle)||w.removeEvent(e,d,y.handle),delete u[d])}else for(d in
u)w.event.remove(e,d+t[l],n,r,!0);w.isEmptyObject(u)&&J.remove(e,"handle
events")},dispatch:function(e){var t=w.event.fix(e),n,r,i,o,a,s,u=new
Array(arguments.length),l=(J.get(this,"events")||{})[t.type]||[],c=w.event.sp
eial[t.type]||{};for(u[0]=t,n=1;n<arguments.length;n++)u[n]=arguments[n];if(
t.delegateTarget=this,!c.preDispatch||!1!==c.preDispatch.call(this,t)){s=w.ev
ent.handlers.call(this,t,l),n=0;while((o=s[n++])&&!t.isPropagationStopped()){
t.currentTarget=o.elem,r=0;while((a=o.handlers[r++])&&!t.isImmediatePropagati

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```

onStopped() ) t.rnamespace&&!t.rnamespace.test(a.namespace) || (t.handleObj=a,t.data=a.data,void
0!== (i=(w.event.special[a.origType] || {}).handle || a.handler).apply(o.elem,u)
&&!1=== (t.result=i) &&(t.preventDefault(),t.stopPropagation())) } return
c.postDispatch&&c.postDispatch.call(this,t),t.result}},handlers:function(e,t)
{var
n,r,i,o,a,s=[],u=t.delegateCount,l=e.target;if(u&&l.nodeType&&!("click"===e.type&&e.button>=1)) for(;l!==this;l=l.parentNode || this) if(1===l.nodeType&&("click"!==e.type || !0!==l.disabled)) {for(o=[],a={},n=0;n<u;n++) void
0===a[i=(r=t[n]).selector+" "] &&(a[i]=r.needsContext?w(i,this).index(l)>-
1:w.find(i,this,null,[l]).length),a[i]&&o.push(r);o.length&&s.push({elem:l,handlers:o}) } return
l=this,u<t.length&&s.push({elem:l,handlers:t.slice(u)},s),addProp:function(e,t){Object.defineProperty(w.Event.prototype,e,{enumerable:!0,configurable:!0,
get:g(t)?function(){if(this.originalEvent) return
t(this.originalEvent)}:function(){if(this.originalEvent) return
this.originalEvent[e]},set:function(t){Object.defineProperty(this,e,{enumerable:!0,configurable:!0,writable:!0,value:t})}},fix:function(e){return
e[w.expando]?e:new
w.Event(e)},special:{load:{noBubble:!0},focus:{trigger:function(){if(this!==S
e()) &&this.focus) return
this.focus(),!1},delegateType:"focusin"},blur:{trigger:function(){if(this===S
e()) &&this.blur) return
this.blur(),!1},delegateType:"focusout"},click:{trigger:function(){if("checkbox"===this.type&&this.click&&N(this,"input")) return
this.click(),!1},_default:function(e){return
N(e.target,"a")}},beforeunload:{postDispatch:function(e){void
0!==e.result&&e.originalEvent&&(e.originalEvent.returnValue=e.result)}}},w.r
emoveEvent=function(e,t,n){e.removeEventListener&&e.removeEventListener(t,n)
},w.Event=function(e,t){if(!(this instanceof w.Event)) return new
w.Event(e,t);e&&e.type?(this.originalEvent=e,this.type=e.type,this.isDefaultP
revented=e.defaultPrevented || void
0===e.defaultPrevented&&!1===e.returnValue?Ee:ke,this.target=e.target&&3===e.
target.nodeType?e.target.parentNode:e.target,this.currentTarget=e.currentTarget,
this.relatedTarget=e.relatedTarget):this.type=e,t&&w.extend(this,t),this.t
imeStamp=e&&e.timeStamp || Date.now(),this[w.expando]=!0},w.Event.prototype={co
nstructor:w.Event,isDefaultPrevented:ke,isPropagationStopped:ke,isImmediatePr
opagationStopped:ke,isSimulated:!1,preventDefault:function(){var
e=this.originalEvent;this.isDefaultPrevented=Ee,e&&!this.isSimulated&&e.preve
ntDefault(),stopPropagation:function(){var
e=this.originalEvent;this.isPropagationStopped=Ee,e&&!this.isSimulated&&e.sto
pPropagation(),stopImmediatePropagation:function(){var
e=this.originalEvent;this.isImmediatePropagationStopped=Ee,e&&!this.isSimulat
ed&&e.stopImmediatePropagation(),this.stopPropagation()}},w.each({altKey:!0,b
ubbles:!0,cancelable:!0,changedTouches:!0,ctrlKey:!0,detail:!0,eventPhase:!0,
metaKey:!0,pageX:!0,pageY:!0,shiftKey:!0,view:!0,"char":!0,charCode:!0,key:!0
,keyCode:!0,button:!0,buttons:!0,clientX:!0,clientY:!0,offsetX:!0,offsetY:!0,
pointerId:!0,pointerType:!0,screenX:!0,screenY:!0,targetTouches:!0,toElement:
!0,touches:!0,which:function(e){var t=e.button;return
null===e.which&&we.test(e.type)?null!=e.charCode?e.charCode:e.keyCode:!e.which
&&void
0!==t&&Te.test(e.type)?1&t?1:2&t?3:4&t?2:0:e.which}},w.event.addProp),w.each(
{mouseenter:"mouseover",mouseleave:"mouseout",pointerenter:"pointerover",poin
terleave:"pointerout"},function(e,t){w.event.special[e]={delegateType:t,bindT
ype:t,handle:function(e){var n,r=this,i=e.relatedTarget,o=e.handleObj;return
i&&(i===r || w.contains(r,i) || (e.type=o.origType,n=o.handler.apply(this, argue
nts),e.type=t),n)}}},w.fn.extend({on:function(e,t,n,r){return

```

```

De(this,e,t,n,r)},one:function(e,t,n,r){return
De(this,e,t,n,r,l)},off:function(e,t,n){var
r,i;if(e&&e.preventDefault&&e.handleObj)return
r=e.handleObj,w(e.delegateTarget).off(r.namespace?r.origType+"."+r.namespace:
r.origType,r.selector,r.handler),this;if("object"===typeof e){for(i in
e)this.off(i,t,e[i]);return this}return!1!==t&&"function"!==typeof
t|| (n=t,t=void
0),!1===n&&(n=ke),this.each(function(){w.event.remove(this,e,n,t)}});var
Ne=/<(?!area|br|col|embed|hr|img|input|link|meta|param)([a-
z][^\s/>\x20\t\r\n\f]*)[>]*\s\/>/gi,Ae=/<script|<style|<link/i,je=/checked\s
*(?:[^\s]|=\s*.checked.)/i,qe=/^\s*<!(?:\s*[CDATA\[| |--)|(?:\s*\s)|--
)\s*$/g;function Le(e,t){return
N(e,"table")&&N(!1!==t.nodeType?t:t.firstChild,"tr"?w(e).children("tbody")[0
]||e:e)}function He(e){return
e.type=(null!==e.getAttribute("type"))+"/"+e.type,e}function
Oe(e){return"true/"===(e.type||"").slice(0,5)?e.type=e.type.slice(5):e.remove
Attribute("type"),e}function Pe(e,t){var
n,r,i,o,a,s,u,l;if(1===t.nodeType){if(J.hasData(e)&&(o=J.access(e),a=J.set(t,
o),l=o.events)){delete a.handle,a.events={};for(i in
l)for(n=0,r=l[i].length;n<r;n++)w.event.add(t,i,l[i][n])}K.hasData(e)&&(s=K.a
ccess(e),u=w.extend({},s),K.set(t,u))}function Me(e,t){var
n=t.nodeName.toLowerCase();"input"===n&&pe.test(e.type)?t.checked=e.checked:"
input"!==n&&"textarea"!==n|| (t.defaultValue=e.defaultValue)}function
Re(e,t,n,r){t=a.apply([],t);var i,o,s,u,l,c,f=0,p=e.length,d=p-
1,y=t[0],v=g(y);if(v||p>1&&"string"===typeof
y&&!h.checkClone&&je.test(y))return e.each(function(i){var
o=e.eq(i);v&&(t[0]=y.call(this,i,o.html()));Re(o,t,n,r)});if(p&&(i=xe(t,e[0].
ownerDocument,!1,e,r),o=i.firstChild,1===i.childNodes.length&&(i=o,o||r)){fo
r(u=s=w.map(ye(i,"script"),He)).length;f<p;f++)l=i,f!==d&&(l=w.clone(l,!0,!0
),u&&w.merge(s,ye(l,"script"))),n.call(e[f],l,f);if(u)for(c=s[s.length-
1].ownerDocument,w.map(s,Oe),f=0;f<u;f++)l=s[f],he.test(l.type||"")&&!J.acces
s(l,"globalEval")&&w.contains(c,l)&&(l.src&&"module"!==l.type||"").toLowerCa
se()?w._evalUrl&&w._evalUrl(l.src):m(l.textContent.replace(qe,""),c,l)}retur
n e}function Ie(e,t,n){for(var
r,i=t?w.filter(t,e):e,o=0,null!=(r=i[0]);o++)n||!1!==r.nodeType||w.cleanData(y
e(r)),r.parentNode&&(n&&w.contains(r.ownerDocument,r)&&ve(ye(r,"script"))),r.p
arentNode.removeChild(r);return e}w.extend({htmlPrefilter:function(e){return
e.replace(Ne,"<$1></$2>"),clone:function(e,t,n){var
r,i,o,a,s=e.cloneNode(!0),u=w.contains(e.ownerDocument,e);if(! (h.noCloneCheck
ed||!1!==e.nodeType&&!1!==e.nodeType||w.isXMLDoc(e)))for(a=ye(s),r=0,i=(o=ye(e
)).length;r<i;r++)Me(o[r],a[r]);if(t)if(n)for(o=o||ye(e),a=a||ye(s),r=0,i=o.l
ength;r<i;r++)Pe(o[r],a[r]);else
Pe(e,s);return(a=ye(s,"script")).length>0&&ve(a,!u&&ye(e,"script")),s},cleanD
ata:function(e){for(var t,n,r,i=w.event.special,o=0;void
0!== (n=e[o]);o++)if(Y(n)){if(t=n[J.expando]){if(t.events)for(r in
t.events)i[r]?w.event.remove(n,r):w.removeEvent(n,r,t.handle);n[J.expando]=vo
id 0}n[K.expando]&&(n[K.expando]=void
0)}}},w.fn.extend({detach:function(e){return
Ie(this,e,!0)},remove:function(e){return Ie(this,e)},text:function(e){return
z(this,function(e){return void
0===e?w.text(this):this.empty().each(function(){!1!==this.nodeType&&!1!==this.
nodeType&&!9!==this.nodeType|| (this.textContent=e)})},null,e,arguments.length)
},append:function(){return
Re(this,arguments,function(e){!1!==this.nodeType&&!1!==this.nodeType&&!9!==this.
nodeType||Le(this,e).appendChild(e)}),prepend:function(){return
Re(this,arguments,function(e){if(1===this.nodeType||!1===this.nodeType||!9===t
his.nodeType){var

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t=Le(this,e);t.insertBefore(e,t.firstChild)})),before:function(){return
Re(this,arguments,function(e){this.parentNode&&this.parentNode.insertBefore(e
,this)})),after:function(){return
Re(this,arguments,function(e){this.parentNode&&this.parentNode.insertBefore(e
,this.nextSibling)})),empty:function(){for(var
e,t=0;null!=(e=this[t]);t++)1===e.nodeType&&(w.cleanData(ye(e,!1)),e.textCont
ent="");return this},clone:function(e,t){return
e=null!=e&&e,t=null==t?e:t,this.map(function(){return
w.clone(this,e,t)}),html:function(e){return z(this,function(e){var
t=this[0]||{},n=0,r=this.length;if(void 0===e&&1===t.nodeType)return
t.innerHTML;if("string"===typeof
e&&!Ae.test(e)&&!ge[(de.exec(e)||["",""])[1].toLowerCase()]}{e=w.htmlPrefilte
r(e);try{for(;n<r;n++)1===(t=this[n]||{}).nodeType&&(w.cleanData(ye(t,!1)),t.
innerHTML=e);t=0}catch(e){}t&&this.empty().append(e)},null,e,arguments.lengt
h)},replaceWith:function(){var e=[];return Re(this,arguments,function(t){var
n=this.parentNode;w.inArray(this,e)<0&&(w.cleanData(ye(this)),n&&n.replaceChi
ld(t,this)},e)},w.each({appendTo:"append",prependTo:"prepend",insertBefore
:"before",insertAfter:"after",replaceAll:"replaceWith"},function(e,t){w.fn[e]
=function(e){for(var n,r=[],i=w(e),o=i.length-
1,a=0;a<=o;a++)n=a===o?this:this.clone(!0),w(i[a])[t](n),s.apply(r,n.get());r
eturn this.pushStack(r)}});var We=new RegExp("^("+re+")(?!px)[a-
z%]+$", "i"),$e=function(t){var n=t.ownerDocument.defaultView;return
n&&n.opener||(n=e),n.getComputedStyle(t)},Be=new
RegExp(oe.join("|"),"i");!function(){function
t(){if(c){l.style.cssText="position:absolute;left:-11111px;width:60px;margin-
top:1px;padding:0;border:0",c.style.cssText="position:relative;display:block;
box-sizing:border-
box;overflow:scroll;margin:auto;border:1px;padding:1px;width:60%;top:1%",be.a
ppendChild(l).appendChild(c);var
t=e.getComputedStyle(c);i="1%"!==t.top,u=12===n(t.marginLeft),c.style.right="
60%",s=36===n(t.right),o=36===n(t.width),c.style.position="absolute",a=36===c
.offsetWidth||"absolute",be.removeChild(l),c=null}}function n(e){return
Math.round(parseFloat(e))}var
i,o,a,s,u,l=r.createElement("div"),c=r.createElement("div");c.style&&(c.style
.backgroundColor="content-
box",c.cloneNode(!0).style.backgroundColor="",h.clearCloneStyle="content-
box"===c.style.backgroundColor,w.extend(h,{boxSizingReliable:function(){return
t(),o},pixelBoxStyles:function(){return
t(),s},pixelPosition:function(){return
t(),i},reliableMarginLeft:function(){return
t(),u},scrollboxSize:function(){return t(),a}}));function Fe(e,t,n){var
r,i,o,a,s=e.style;return(n=n||$e(e))&&("!"==(a=n.getPropertyValue(t)||n[t])||
w.contains(e.ownerDocument,e)||(a=w.style(e,t),!h.pixelBoxStyles())&&We.test(
a)&&Be.test(t)&&(r=s.width,i=s.minWidth,o=s.maxWidth,s.minWidth=s.maxWidth=s.
width=a,a=n.width,s.width=r,s.minWidth=i,s.maxWidth=o)),void
0!==(a?a+"":a)}function
_e(e,t){return{get:function(){if(!e())return(this.get=t).apply(this,arguments
);delete this.get}}var ze=/^(none|table|?!-c[ea]).+/,Xe=/^--
/,Ue={position:"absolute",visibility:"hidden",display:"block"},Ve={letterSpac
ing:"0",fontWeight:"400"},Ge=["Webkit","Moz","ms"],Ye=r.createElement("div").
style;function Qe(e){if(e in Ye)return e;var
t=e[0].toUpperCase()+e.slice(1),n=Ge.length;while(n--)if((e=Ge[n]+t)in
Ye)return e}function Je(e){var t=w.cssProps[e];return
t||(t=w.cssProps[e]=Qe(e)||e),t}function Ke(e,t,n){var r=ie.exec(t);return
r?Math.max(0,r[2]-(n||0))+r[3]||"px":t}function Ze(e,t,n,r,i,o){var
a="width"===t?1:0,s=0,u=0;if(n===(r?"border":"content"))return
0;for(;a<4;a+=2)"margin"===n&&(u+=w.css(e,n+oe[a],!0,i)),r?("content"===n&&(u

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-w.css(e, "padding"+oe[a], !0, i), "margin"!==n&&(u-
-w.css(e, "border"+oe[a]+"Width", !0, i)): (u+=w.css(e, "padding"+oe[a], !0, i), "pa
dding"!==n?u+=w.css(e, "border"+oe[a]+"Width", !0, i):s+=w.css(e, "border"+oe[a]+
"Width", !0, i));return!r&&o>=0&&(u+=Math.max(0, Math.ceil(e["offset"+t[0].toUpp
erCase()+t.slice(1)]-o-u-s-.5)), u)function et(e, t, n){var
r=$e(e), i=Fe(e, t, r), o="border-
box"===w.css(e, "boxSizing", !1, r), a=o;if(We.test(i)){if(!n)return
i; i="auto"}return
a=a&&(h.boxSizingReliable()||i===e.style[t]), ("auto"===i||!parseFloat(i)&&"in
line"===w.css(e, "display", !1, r))&&(i=e["offset"+t[0].toUpperCase()+t.slice(1)
], a=!0), (i=parseFloat(i)||0)+Ze(e, t, n|| (o?"border": "content"), a, r, i)+"px"}w.e
xtend({cssHooks:{opacity:{get:function(e, t){if(t){var
n=Fe(e, "opacity");return""===n?"1":n}}, cssNumber:{animationIterationCount:!
0, columnCount:!0, fillOpacity:!0, flexGrow:!0, flexShrink:!0, fontWeight:!0, lineH
eight:!0, opacity:!0, order:!0, orphans:!0, widows:!0, zIndex:!0, zoom:!0}, cssProps
: {}, style:function(e, t, n, r){if(e&&3!==e.nodeType&&8!==e.nodeType&&e.style){va
r
i, o, a, s=G(t), u=Xe.test(t), l=e.style;if(u||(t=Je(s)), a=w.cssHooks[t]||w.cssHoo
ks[s], void 0===n)return a&&"get"in a&&void
0!==(i=a.get(e, !1, r))?i:l[t]; "string"==(o=typeof
n)&&(i=ie.exec(n))&&i[1]&&(n=ue(e, t, i), o="number"), null!=n&&n===n&&("number"=
==o&&(n+=i&&i[3]|| (w.cssNumber[s]?"":"px")), h.clearCloneStyle||""!==n||0!==(t.
indexOf("background")|| (l[t]="inherit"), a&&"set"in a&&void
0=== (n=a.set(e, n, r))|| (u?l.setProperty(t, n):l[t]=n))}}, css:function(e, t, n, r){
var i, o, a, s=G(t);return
Xe.test(t)|| (t=Je(s)), (a=w.cssHooks[t]||w.cssHooks[s])&&"get"in
a&&(i=a.get(e, !0, n), void 0===i&&(i=Fe(e, t, r)), "normal"===i&&t in
Ve&&(i=Ve[t]), ""===n|n?(o=parseFloat(i), !0===n||isFinite(o)?o||0:i:i)), w.e
ach(["height", "width"], function(e, t){w.cssHooks[t]={get:function(e, n, r){if(n)
return!ze.test(w.css(e, "display"))||e.getClientRects().length&&e.getBoundingC
lientRect().width?et(e, t, r):se(e, ue, function(){return
et(e, t, r)}}), set:function(e, n, r){var i, o=$e(e), a="border-
box"===w.css(e, "boxSizing", !1, o), s=r&&Ze(e, t, r, a, o);return
a&&h.scrollboxSize()===o.position&&(s-
=Math.ceil(e["offset"+t[0].toUpperCase()+t.slice(1)]-parseFloat(o[t])-
Ze(e, t, "border", !1, o)-
.5)), s&&(i=ie.exec(n))&&"px"!=(i[3]||"px")&&(e.style[t]=n, n=w.css(e, t)), Ke(e
, n, s)}}), w.cssHooks.marginLeft=_e(h.reliableMarginLeft, function(e, t){if(t)re
turn(parseFloat(Fe(e, "marginLeft"))||e.getClientRect().left-
se(e, {marginLeft:0}, function(){return
e.getClientRect().left}))+"px"}), w.each({margin:"", padding:"", border:
"Width"}, function(e, t){w.cssHooks[e+t]={expand:function(n){for(var
r=0, i={}, o="string"==typeof n?n.split("
"): [n]; r<4; r++)i[e+oe[r]+t]=o[r]||o[r-2]||o[0];return
i}}, "margin"!==e&&(w.cssHooks[e+t].set=Ke)}), w.fn.extend({css:function(e, t){r
eturn z(this, function(e, t, n){var
r, i, o={}, a=0; if(Array.isArray(t)){for(r=$e(e), i=t.length; a<i; a++)o[t[a]]=w.cs
s(e, t[a], !1, r);return o}return void
0!==(n?w.style(e, t, n):w.css(e, t)), e, t, arguments.length>1)});function
tt(e, t, n, r, i){return new
tt.prototype.init(e, t, n, r, i)}w.Tween=tt, tt.prototype={constructor:tt, init:fun
ction(e, t, n, r, i, o){this.elem=e, this.prop=n, this.easing=i||w.easing._default, t
his.options=t, this.start=this.now=this.cur(), this.end=r, this.unit=o|| (w.cssNu
mber[n]?"":"px")}, cur:function(){var e=tt.propHooks[this.prop];return
e&&e.get?e.get(this):tt.propHooks._default.get(this)}, run:function(e){var
t, n=tt.propHooks[this.prop];return
this.options.duration?this.pos=t=w.easing[this.easing](e, this.options.duratio

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n*e,0,1,this.options.duration):this.pos=t=e,this.now=(this.end-
this.start)*t+this.start,this.options.step&&this.options.step.call(this.elem,
this.now,this),n&&n.set?n.set(this):tt.propHooks._default.set(this),this}},tt
.prototype.init.prototype=tt.prototype,tt.propHooks={_default:{get:function(e
){var t;return
1!==e.elem.nodeType||null!=e.elem[e.prop]&&null==e.elem.style[e.prop]?e.elem[
e.prop]:(t=w.css(e.elem,e.prop,""))&&"auto"!==t?t:0},set:function(e){w.fx.ste
p[e.prop]?w.fx.step[e.prop](e):1!==e.elem.nodeType||null==e.elem.style[w.cssP
rops[e.prop]]&&!w.cssHooks[e.prop]?e.elem[e.prop]=e.now:w.style(e.elem,e.prop
,e.now+e.unit)}}},tt.propHooks.scrollTop=tt.propHooks.scrollLeft={set:functio
n(e){e.elem.nodeType&&e.elem.parentNode&&(e.elem[e.prop]=e.now)},w.easing={l
inear:function(e){return e},swing:function(e){return.5-
Math.cos(e*Math.PI)/2},_default:"swing"},w.fx=tt.prototype.init,w.fx.step={};
var nt,rt,it=/^(?:toggle|show|hide)$/ot=/queueHooks$/;function
at(){rt&&(1===r.hidden&&e.requestAnimationFrame?e.requestAnimationFrame(at):
e.setTimeout(at,w.fx.interval),w.fx.tick())}function st(){return
e.setTimeout(function(){nt=void 0},nt=Date.now())}function ut(e,t){var
n,r=0,i={height:e};for(t=t?1:0;r<4;r+=2-
t)i["margin"+(n=oe[r])]=i["padding"+n]=e;return
t&&(i.opacity=i.width=e),i}function lt(e,t,n){for(var
r,i=(pt.tweeners[t]||[]).concat(pt.tweeners["*"]),o=0,a=i.length;o<a;o++)if(r
=i[o].call(n,t,e))return r}function ct(e,t,n){var r,i,o,a,s,u,l,c,f="width"in
t||"height"in
t,p=this,d={},h=e.style,g=e.nodeType&&ae(e),y=J.get(e,"fxshow");n.queue||((nul
l==(a=w._queueHooks(e,"fx")).unqueued&&(a.unqueued=0,s=a.empty.fire,a.empty.f
ire=function(){a.unqueued||s()}),a.unqueued++,p.always(function(){p.always(fu
nction(){a.unqueued--,w.queue(e,"fx").length||a.empty.fire()}))));for(r in
t)if(i=t[r],it.test(i)){if(delete
t[r],o=0||"toggle"===i,i===(g?"hide":"show")){if("show"!==i||!y||void
0===y[r])continue;g=!0}d[r]=y&&y[r]||w.style(e,r)}if((u=!w.isEmptyObject(t))|
!w.isEmptyObject(d)){f&&1===e.nodeType&&(n.overflow=[h.overflow,h.overflowX,
h.overflowY],null==(l=y&&y.display)&&(l=J.get(e,"display")),("none"===c=w.css
(e,"display"))&&(l?c=l:(fe([e],!0),l=e.style.display||l,c=w.css(e,"display"),
fe([e]))),("inline"===c||"inline-
block"===c&&null!=l)&&"none"===w.css(e,"float")&&(u||p.done(function(){h.dis
play=l}),null==l&&(c=h.display,l="none"===c?"":c)),h.display="inline-
block"),n.overflow&&(h.overflow="hidden",p.always(function(){h.overflow=n.ov
erflow[0],h.overflowX=n.overflow[1],h.overflowY=n.overflow[2]})),u=!1;for(r
in d)u||(y?"hidden"in
y&&(g=y.hidden):y=J.access(e,"fxshow",{display:l}),o&&(y.hidden=!g),g&&fe([e
,!0],p.done(function(){g||fe([e]),J.remove(e,"fxshow");for(r in
d)w.style(e,r,d[r])})),u=lt(g?y[r]:0,r,p),r in
y||y[r]=u.start,g&&(u.end=u.start,u.start=0))}}function ft(e,t){var
n,r,i,o,a;for(n in
e)if(r=G(n),i=t[r],o=e[n],Array.isArray(o)&&(i=o[1],o=e[n]=o[0]),n!==r&&(e[r
]=o,delete e[n]),(a=w.cssHooks[r])&&"expand"in a){o=a.expand(o),delete
e[r];for(n in o)n in e||e[n]=o[n],t[n]=i}else t[r]=i}function pt(e,t,n){var
r,i,o=0,a=pt.prefilters.length,s=w.Deferred().always(function(){delete
u.elem}),u=function(){if(i)return!1;for(var
t=nt||st(),n=Math.max(0,l.startTime+l.duration-t),r=1-
(n/l.duration||0),o=0,a=l.tweens.length;o<a;o++)l.tweens[o].run(r);return
s.notifyWith(e,[l,r,n]),r<1&&a?n:(a||s.notifyWith(e,[l,1,0]),s.resolveWith(e,
[l]),!1)},l=s.promise({elem:e,props:w.extend({},t),opts:w.extend(!0,{specialE
asing:{},easing:w.easing._default},n),originalProperties:t,originalOptions:n,
startTime:nt||st(),duration:n.duration,tweens:[],createTween:function(t,n){va
r r=w.Tween(e,l.opts,t,n,l.opts.specialEasing[t]||l.opts.easing);return
l.tweens.push(r),r},stop:function(t){var

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n=0,r=t?l.tweens.length:0;if(i) return
this;for(i=!0;n<r;n++)l.tweens[n].run(1);return
t?(s.notifyWith(e,[l,1,0]),s.resolveWith(e,[l,t])):s.rejectWith(e,[l,t]),this
})),c=l.props;for(ft(c,l.opts.specialEasing);o<a;o++)if(r=pt.prefilters[o].ca
ll(l,e,c,l.opts))return
g(r.stop)&&(w._queueHooks(l.elem,l.opts.queue).stop=r.stop.bind(r)),r;return
w.map(c,lt,l),g(l.opts.start)&&l.opts.start.call(e,l),l.progress(l.opts.progr
ess).done(l.opts.done,l.opts.complete).fail(l.opts.fail).always(l.opts.always
),w.fx.timer(w.extend(u,{elem:e,anim:l,queue:l.opts.queue})),l)w.Animation=w.
extend(pt,{tweener:{"*":[function(e,t){var n=this.createTween(e,t);return
ue(n.elem,e,ie.exec(t),n),n]}},tweener:function(e,t){g(e)?(t=e,e=["*"]):e=e.m
atch(M);for(var
n,r=0,i=e.length;r<i;r++)n=e[r],pt.tweeners[n]=pt.tweeners[n]||[],pt.tweeners
[n].unshift(t)},prefilters:[ct],prefilter:function(e,t){t?pt.prefilters.unshi
ft(e):pt.prefilters.push(e)}}),w.speed=function(e,t,n){var
r=e&&"object"===typeof
e?w.extend({},e):{complete:n||!n&&t||g(e)&&e,duration:e,easing:n&&t||t&&!g(t)
&&t};return w.fx.off?r.duration=0:"number"!==typeof r.duration&&(r.duration in
w.fx.speeds?r.duration=w.fx.speeds[r.duration]:r.duration=w.fx.speeds._defaul
t),null!=r.queue&&!0!=r.queue||(r.queue="fx"),r.old=r.complete,r.complete=fun
ction(){g(r.old)&&r.old.call(this),r.queue&&w.dequeue(this,r.queue)},r},w.fn
.extend({fadeTo:function(e,t,n,r){return
this.filter(ae).css("opacity",0).show().end().animate({opacity:t},e,n,r)},ani
mate:function(e,t,n,r){var
i=w.isEmptyObject(e),o=w.speed(t,n,r),a=function(){var
t=pt(this,w.extend({},e),o);(i||J.get(this,"finish"))&&t.stop(!0)};return
a.finish=a,i||!1==o.queue?this.each(a):this.queue(o.queue,a),stop:function(
e,t,n){var r=function(e){var t=e.stop;delete
e.stop,t(n)};return"string"!==typeof e&&(n=t,t=e,e=void
0),t&&!1!=e&&this.queue(e||"fx",[]),this.each(function(){var
t=!0,i=null!=e&&e+"queueHooks",o=w.timers,a=J.get(this);if(i)a[i]&&a[i].stop&
&r(a[i]);else for(i in
a)a[i]&&a[i].stop&&ot.test(i)&&r(a[i]);for(i=o.length;i--
);o[i].elem!==this||null!=e&&o[i].queue!==e||o[i].anim.stop(n),t=!1,o.splice
(i,1);!t&&n||w.dequeue(this,e)}),finish:function(e){return!1!=e&&(e=e||"fx
"),this.each(function(){var
t,n=J.get(this),r=n[e+"queue"],i=n[e+"queueHooks"],o=w.timers,a=r?r.length:0;
for(n.finish=!0,w.queue(this,e,[]),i&&i.stop&&i.stop.call(this,!0),t=o.length
;t--
);o[t].elem===this&&o[t].queue===e&&(o[t].anim.stop(!0),o.splice(t,1));for(t=
0;t<a;t++)r[t]&&r[t].finish&&r[t].finish.call(this);delete
n.finish}})),w.each(["toggle","show","hide"],function(e,t){var
n=w.fn[t];w.fn[t]=function(e,r,i){return null==e||"boolean"===typeof
e?n.apply(this,arguments):this.animate(ut(t,!0),e,r,i)}}),w.each({slideDown:u
t("show"),slideUp:ut("hide"),slideToggle:ut("toggle"),fadeIn:{opacity:"show"}
,fadeOut:{opacity:"hide"},fadeToggle:{opacity:"toggle"}},function(e,t){w.fn[e
]=function(e,n,r){return
this.animate(t,e,n,r)},w.timers=[],w.fx.tick=function(){var
e,t=0,n=w.timers;for(nt=Date.now();t<n.length;t++)(e=n[t])()||n[t]!==e||n.spl
ice(t--,1);n.length||w.fx.stop(),nt=void
0},w.fx.timer=function(e){w.timers.push(e),w.fx.start()},w.fx.interval=13,w.f
x.start=function(){rt||rt=!0,at()}},w.fx.stop=function(){rt=null},w.fx.speed
s={slow:600,fast:200,_default:400},w.fn.delay=function(t,n){return
t=w.fx?w.fx.speeds[t]||t:t,n=n||"fx",this.queue(n,function(n,r){var
i=e.setTimeout(n,t);r.stop=function(){e.clearTimeout(i)}})},function(){var
e=r.createElement("input"),t=r.createElement("select").appendChild(r.createEl
ement("option"));e.type="checkbox",h.checkOn=""!=e.value,h.optSelected=t.sel

```

```

ected, (e=r.createElement("input")).value="t",e.type="radio",h.radioValue="t"==e.value}());var
dt,ht=w.expr.attrHandle;w.fn.extend({attr:function(e,t){return
z(this,w.attr,e,t,arguments.length>1)},removeAttr:function(e){return
this.each(function(){w.removeAttr(this,e)}})},w.extend({attr:function(e,t,n)
{var r,i,o=e.nodeType;if(3!==o&&8!==o&&2!==o)return"undefined"===typeof
e.getAttribute?w.prop(e,t,n):(1===o&&w.isXMLDoc(e)||i=w.attrHooks[t.toLowerCase()])||w.expr.match.bool.test(t)?dt:void 0),void 0!==n?null===n?void
w.removeAttr(e,t):i&&"set"in i&&void
0!==(r=i.set(e,n,t))?r:(e.setAttribute(t,n+""),n):i&&"get"in
i&&null!==(r=i.get(e,t))?r:null==(r=w.find.attr(e,t))?void
0:r)},attrHooks:{type:{set:function(e,t){if(!h.radioValue&&"radio"===t&&N(e,"
input")){var n=e.value;return
e.setAttribute("type",t),n&&(e.value=n),t}}},removeAttr:function(e,t){var
n,r=0,i=t&&t.match(M);if(i&&1===e.nodeType)while(n=i[r++])e.removeAttribute(n
)}}),dt={set:function(e,t,n){return!1===t?w.removeAttr(e,n):e.setAttribute(n,
n)},w.each(w.expr.match.bool.source.match(/\w+/g),function(e,t){var
n=ht[t]||w.find.attr;ht[t]=function(e,t,r){var i,o,a=t.toLowerCase();return
r||o=ht[a],ht[a]=i,i=null!==(n(e,t,r)?a:null,ht[a]=o),i}});var
gt=/^(?:input|select|textarea|button)$/i,yt=/^(?:a|area)$/i;w.fn.extend({prop
:function(e,t){return
z(this,w.prop,e,t,arguments.length>1)},removeProp:function(e){return
this.each(function){delete
this[w.propFix[e]||e]}})},w.extend({prop:function(e,t,n){var
r,i,o=e.nodeType;if(3!==o&&8!==o&&2!==o)return
1===o&&w.isXMLDoc(e)||t=w.propFix[t]||t,i=w.propHooks[t],void
0!==(n=i&&"set"in i&&void 0!==(r=i.set(e,n,t))?r:e[t]=n:i&&"get"in
i&&null!==(r=i.get(e,t))?r:e[t]),propHooks:{tabIndex:{get:function(e){var
t=w.find.attr(e,"tabindex");return
t?parseInt(t,10):gt.test(e.nodeName)||yt.test(e.nodeName)&&e.href?0:-
1}}},propFix:{"for":"htmlFor","class":"className"}},h.optSelected||w.propHo
oks.selected={get:function(e){var t=e.parentNode;return
t&&t.parentNode&&t.parentNode.selectedIndex,null},set:function(e){var
t=e.parentNode;t&&(t.selectedIndex,t.parentNode&&t.parentNode.selectedIndex)
}},w.each(["tabIndex","readOnly","maxLength","cellSpacing","cellPadding","row
Span","colSpan","useMap","frameBorder","contentEditable"],function(){w.propFi
x[this.toLowerCase()]=this});function vt(e){return(e.match(M)||[]).join("
")}function mt(e){return e.getAttribute&&e.getAttribute("class")||""}function
xt(e){return Array.isArray(e)?e:"string"===typeof
e?e.match(M)||[]:[]}w.fn.extend({addClass:function(e){var
t,n,r,i,o,a,s,u=0;if(g(e))return
this.each(function(t){w(this).addClass(e.call(this,t,mt(this)))});if((t=xt(e)
).length)while(n=this[u++])if(i=mt(n),r=1===n.nodeType&&" "+vt(i)+"
"){a=0;while(o=t[a++])r.indexOf(" "+o+" ")<0&&(r+=o+"
");i!==(s=vt(r))&&n.setAttribute("class",s)}return
this},removeClass:function(e){var t,n,r,i,o,a,s,u=0;if(g(e))return
this.each(function(t){w(this).removeClass(e.call(this,t,mt(this)))});if(!argu
ments.length)return
this.attr("class","");if((t=xt(e)).length)while(n=this[u++])if(i=mt(n),r=1===
n.nodeType&&" "+vt(i)+" ")a=0;while(o=t[a++])while(r.indexOf(" "+o+" ")>-
1)r=r.replace(" "+o+" ","");i!==(s=vt(r))&&n.setAttribute("class",s)}return
this},toggleClass:function(e,t){var n=typeof
e,r="string"===n|Array.isArray(e);return"boolean"===typeof
t&&r?t?this.addClass(e):this.removeClass(e):g(e)?this.each(function(n){w(this)
.toggleClass(e.call(this,n,mt(this),t),t)}):this.each(function(){var
t,i,o,a;if(r){i=0,o=w(this),a=xt(e);while(t=a[i++])o.hasClass(t)?o.removeClas
s(t):o.addClass(t)}else void

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0!==(e&&"boolean"!=n||((t=mt(this))&&J.set(this,"__className",t),this.setAt
tribute&&this.setAttribute("class",t||!1==e?"":J.get(this,"__className")||
"")))),hasClass:function(e){var t,n,r=0;t=" "+e+"
";while(n=this[r++])if(1==n.nodeType&&(" "+vt(mt(n))+").indexOf(t)>-
1)return!0;return!1});var bt=/\r/g;w.fn.extend({val:function(e){var
t,n,r,i=this[0];{if(arguments.length)return r=g(e),this.each(function(n){var
i;1==this.nodeType&&(null==(i=r?e.call(this,n,w(this).val()):e)?i="":"number
"==typeof i?i+="":Array.isArray(i)&&(i=w.map(i,function(e){return
null==e?"":e+""})),(t=w.valHooks[this.type]|w.valHooks[this.nodeName.toLower
Case()])&&"set"in t&&void
0!==(t.set(this,i,"value")|(this.value=i)});if(i)return(t=w.valHooks[i.type]
|w.valHooks[i.nodeName.toLowerCase()])&&"get"in t&&void
0!==(n=t.get(i,"value"))?n:"string"==typeof(n=i.value)?n.replace(bt,""):null=
=n?"":n}}),w.extend({valHooks:{option:{get:function(e){var
t=w.find.attr(e,"value");return
null!=t?t:vt(w.text(e))}},select:{get:function(e){var
t,n,r,i=e.options,o=e.selectedIndex,a="select-
one"===e.type,s=a?null:[],u=a?o+1:i.length;for(r=o<0?u:a?o:0;r<u;r++)if((n=i
[r]).selected||r==o)&&!n.disabled&&(!n.parentNode.disabled||!N(n.parentNode,
"optgroup")){if(t=w(n).val(),a)return t;s.push(t)}return
s},set:function(e,t){var n,r,i=e.options,o=w.makeArray(t),a=i.length;while(a-
-)((r=i[a]).selected=w.inArray(w.valHooks.option.get(r),o)>-1)&&(n=!0);return
n||e.selectedIndex=-
1),o}}}),w.each(["radio","checkbox"],function(){w.valHooks[this]={set:functi
on(e,t){if(Array.isArray(t))return e.checked=w.inArray(w(e).val(),t)>-
1}},h.checkOn||w.valHooks[this].get=function(e){return
null==e.getAttribute("value")?"on":e.value}}),h.focusin="onfocusin"in e;var
wt=/^(?:focusin|focusout|blur)$/,Tt=function(e){e.stopPropagation()};w.ex
tend(w.event,{trigger:function(t,n,i,o){var
a,s,u,l,c,p,d,h,v=[i|r],m=f.call(t,"type")?t.type:t,x=f.call(t,"namespace")?
t.namespace.split("."):[];if(s=h=u=i|i|r,3!==i.nodeType&&8!==i.nodeType&&!wt
.test(m+w.event.triggered)&&(m.indexOf(".")>-
1&&(m=(x=m.split(".")).shift(),x.sort()),c=m.indexOf(":")<0&&"on"+m,t=t[w.exp
ando]?t:new w.Event(m,"object"==typeof
t&&t),t.isTrigger=o?2:3,t.namespace=x.join("."),t.rnamespace=t.namespace?new
RegExp("(^|\\\\"+x.join("\\.(?:.*\\.|)")+"(\\.|$)"):null,t.result=void
0,t.target||(t.target=i),n=null==n?[t]:w.makeArray(n,[t]),d=w.event.special[
m]||{,o||!d.trigger||!1==d.trigger.apply(i,n))){if(!o&&!d.noBubble&&!y(i)){f
or(l=d.delegateType||m,wt.test(l+m)||s=s.parentNode);s=s.parentNode)v.push
(s),u=s;u==(i.ownerDocument||r)&&v.push(u.defaultView||u.parentWindow||e)}a=
0;while((s=v[a++])&&!t.isPropagationStopped())h=s,t.type=a>1?l:d.bindType||m,
(p=(J.get(s,"events")||{])[t.type]&&J.get(s,"handle"))&&p.apply(s,n),(p=c&&s[
c])&&p.apply&&Y(s)&&(t.result=p.apply(s,n),!1==t.result&&t.preventDefault())
;return
t.type=m,o||t.isDefaultPrevented()||d._default&&!1==d._default.apply(v.pop()
,n)||!Y(i)||c&&g(i[m])&&!y(i)&&(u=i[c])&&(i[c]=null),w.event.triggered=m,t.i
sPropagationStopped()&&h.addEventListener(m,Tt),i[m](),t.isPropagationStopped
())&&h.removeEventListener(m,Tt),w.event.triggered=void
0,u&&(i[c]=u),t.result}},simulate:function(e,t,n){var r=w.extend(new
w.Event,n,{type:e,isSimulated:!0});w.event.trigger(r,null,t)}),w.fn.extend({
trigger:function(e,t){return
this.each(function(){w.event.trigger(e,t,this)}),triggerHandler:function(e,t
){var n=this[0];if(n)return
w.event.trigger(e,t,n,!0)}},h.focusin||w.each({focus:"focusin",blur:"focusou
t"},function(e,t){var
n=function(e){w.event.simulate(t,e.target,w.event.fix(e)};w.event.special[t]
={setup:function(){var

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r=this.ownerDocument||this,i=J.access(r,t);i||r.addEventListener(e,n,!0),J.ac
cess(r,t,(i||0)+1)},teardown:function(){var
r=this.ownerDocument||this,i=J.access(r,t)-
1;i?J.access(r,t,i):(r.removeEventListener(e,n,!0),J.remove(r,t))}});var
Ct=e.location,Et=Date.now(),kt=/\?/;w.parseXML=function(t){var
n;if(!t||"string"!==typeof t)return null;try{n=(new
e.DOMParser).parseFromString(t,"text/xml")}catch(e){n=void 0}return
n&&!n.getElementsByTagName("parsererror").length||w.error("Invalid XML:
"+t),n};var
St=/[\(\)\$\]/,Dt=/\r?\n/g,Nt=/^(?:submit|button|image|reset|file)$/i,At=/^(?:inp
ut|select|textarea|keygen)/i;function jt(e,t,n,r){var
i;if(Array.isArray(t))w.each(t,function(t,i){n||St.test(e)?r(e,i):jt(e+"["+("
object"===typeof i&&null!=i?t:"")+"]",i,n,r)});else
if(n||"object"!==x(t))r(e,t);else for(i in
t)jt(e+"["+i+"]",t[i],n,r)}w.param=function(e,t){var
n,r=[],i=function(e,t){var
n=g(t)?t():t;r[r.length]=encodeURIComponent(e)+"="+encodeURIComponent(null==n
?"":n)};if(Array.isArray(e)||e.jquery&&!w.isPlainObject(e))w.each(e,function(
){i(this.name,this.value)});else for(n in e)jt(n,e[n],t,i);return
r.join("&")},w.fn.extend({serialize:function(){return
w.param(this.serializeArray())},serializeArray:function(){return
this.map(function(){var e=w.prop(this,"elements");return
e?w.makeArray(e):this}).filter(function(){var e=this.type;return
this.name&&!w(this).is(":disabled")&&At.test(this.nodeName)&&!Nt.test(e)&&(th
is.checked||!pe.test(e))}).map(function(e,t){var n=w(this).val();return
null==n?null:Array.isArray(n)?w.map(n,function(e){return{name:t.name,value:e.
replace(Dt,"\\r\\n")})}:{name:t.name,value:n.replace(Dt,"\\r\\n")}).get()});var
qt=%20/g,Lt=#.*$/Ht=/([\?&])_=[^&]*/Ot=/^(.?)?:[
\t]*([\r\n]*)$/gm,Pt=/^(?:about|app|app-storage|.+
extension|file|res|widget):$/Mt=/^(?:GET|HEAD)$/Rt=/^\/\//It={},Wt={},$t="
*/".concat("*"),Bt=r.createElement("a");Bt.href=Ct.href;function Ft(e){return
function(t,n){"string"!==typeof t&&(n=t,t="*");var
r,i=0,o=t.toLowerCase().match(M)||[];if(g(n))while(r=o[i++])"+"===r[0]?(r=r.s
lice(1)||"*",(e[r]=e[r]||[]).unshift(n)):(e[r]=e[r]||[]).push(n)}function
_t(e,t,n,r){var i={},o=e===Wt;function a(s){var u;return
i[s]!==0,w.each(e[s]||[],function(e,s){var l=s(t,n,r);return"string"!==typeof
l||o||i[l]?o?!(u=1):void 0:(t.dataTypes.unshift(l),a(l),!1)},u)}return
a(t.dataTypes[0])||!i["*"]&&a("*")}function zt(e,t){var
n,r,i=w.ajaxSettings.flatOptions||{};for(n in t)void
0!==t[n]&&((i[n]?e:r||(r={})))[n]=t[n];return r&&w.extend(!0,e,r),e}function
Xt(e,t,n){var
r,i,o,a,s=e.contents,u=e.dataTypes;while("*"===u[0])u.shift(),void
0===r&&(r=e.mimeType||t.getResponseHeader("Content-Type"));if(r)for(i in
s)if(s[i]&&s[i].test(r)){u.unshift(i);break}if(u[0]in n)o=u[0];else{for(i in
n){if(!u[0]||e.converters[i+" "+u[0]]){o=i;break}a||(a=i)}o=o||a}if(o)return
o!:=u[0]&&u.unshift(o),n[o]}function Ut(e,t,n,r){var
i,o,a,s,u,l={},c=e.dataTypes.slice();if(c[1])for(a in
e.converters)l[a.toLowerCase()]=e.converters[a];o=c.shift();while(o)if(e.resp
onseFields[o]&&(n[e.responseFields[o]]=t),!u&&r&&e.dataFilter&&(t=e.dataFilde
r(t,e.dataType)),u=o,o=c.shift())if("*"===o)o=u;else
if("*"!==u&&u!:=o){if(!(a=l[u+" "+o])||l["* "+o])for(i in l)if((s=i.split("
"))[1]===o&&(a=l[u+" "+s[0]]||l["*
"+s[0]]))){!0===a?a=l[i]:!0!==l[i]&&(o=s[0],c.unshift(s[1]));break}if(!0===a)
if(a&&e["throws"])t=a(t);else
try{t=a(t)}catch(e){return{state:"parsererror",error:a?e:"No conversion from
"+u+" to
"+o}}return{state:"success",data:t}}w.extend({active:0,lastModified:{},etag:

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{ }, ajaxSettings: { url: Ct.href, type: "GET", isLocal: Pt.test(Ct.protocol), global: !
0, processData: !0, async: !0, contentType: "application/x-www-form-urlencoded;
charset=UTF-
8", accepts: { "*": $t, text: "text/plain", html: "text/html", xml: "application/xml,
text/xml", json: "application/json,
text/javascript" }, contents: { xml: /\bxml\b/, html: /\bhtml/, json: /\bjson\b/ }, resp
onseFields: { xml: "responseXML", text: "responseText", json: "responseJSON" }, conver
ters: { "* text": String, "text html": !0, "text json": JSON.parse, "text
xml": w.parseXML }, flatOptions: { url: !0, context: !0 }, ajaxSetup: function (e, t) { ret
urn
t?zt (zt (e, w.ajaxSettings), t) : zt (w.ajaxSettings, e) }, ajaxPrefilter: Ft (It), ajaxTr
ansport: Ft (Wt), ajax: function (t, n) { "object" == typeof t && (n = t, t = void
0), n = n || {}; var
i, o, a, s, u, l, c, f, p, d, h = w.ajaxSetup ({}, n), g = h.context || h, y = h.context && (g.nodeType | | g.jquery) ? w (g) : w.event, v = w.Deferred (), m = w.Callbacks ("once
memory"), x = h.statusCode || {}, b = {}, T = {}, C = "canceled", E = { readyState: 0, getRespons
eHeader: function (e) { var
t; if (c) { if (!s) { s = {}; while (t = Ot.exec (a)) s [t [1].toLowerCase ()] = t [2] } t = s [e.toLow
erCase ()] } return null == t ? null : t }, getAllResponseHeaders: function () { return
c ? a : null }, setRequestHeader: function (e, t) { return
null == c && (e = T [e.toLowerCase ()] = T [e.toLowerCase ()] || e, b [e] = t), this }, overrideMi
meType: function (e) { return
null == c && (h.mimeType = e), this }, statusCode: function (e) { var
t; if (e) if (c) E.always (e [E.status]); else for (t in e) x [t] = [x [t], e [t]]; return
this }, abort: function (e) { var t = e || C; return
i && i.abort (t), k (0, t), this }; if (v.promise (E), h.url = (t || h.url || Ct.href) + "" ).re
place (Rt, Ct.protocol + "/" /), h.type = n.method | | n.type | | h.method | | h.type, h.dataTy
pes = (h.dataType | | "*" ).toLowerCase ().match (M) | | [""], null == h.crossDomain { l = r.c
reateElement ("a"); try { l.href = h.url, l.href = l.href, h.crossDomain = Bt.protocol + "/"
/" + Bt.host != !1.protocol + "/" / + !1.host } catch (e) { h.crossDomain = !0 } } if (h.data && h.pr
ocessData && "string" != typeof
h.data && (h.data = w.param (h.data, h.traditional)), _t (It, h, n, E), c) return
E; (f = w.event && h.global) && 0 == w.active++ && w.event.trigger ("ajaxStart"), h.type = h
.type.toUpperCase (), h.hasContent = !Mt.test (h.type), o = h.url.replace (Lt, ""), h.ha
sContent ? h.data && h.processData && 0 == (h.contentType | | "").indexOf ("application/
x-www-form-
urlencoded") && (h.data = h.data.replace (qt, "+")) : (d = h.url.slice (o.length), h.data
&& (h.processData | | "string" == typeof
h.data) && (o += (kt.test (o) ? "&": "?") + h.data, delete
h.data), !1 == h.cache && (o = o.replace (Ht, "$1"), d = (kt.test (o) ? "&": "?") + "_=" + Et + ++
d), h.url = o + d), h.ifModified && (w.lastModified [o] && E.setRequestHeader ("If-
Modified-Since", w.lastModified [o]), w.etag [o] && E.setRequestHeader ("If-None-
Match", w.etag [o])), (h.data && h.hasContent && !1 == h.contentType | | n.contentType) &
& E.setRequestHeader ("Content-
Type", h.contentType), E.setRequestHeader ("Accept", h.dataTypes [0] && h.accepts [h.
dataTypes [0]] ? h.accepts [h.dataTypes [0]] + ("*" != h.dataTypes [0] ? ", "+ $t + ";
q=0.01": "") : h.accepts ["*"]); for (p in
h.headers) E.setRequestHeader (p, h.headers [p]); if (h.beforeSend && (!1 == h.beforeS
end.call (g, E, h) | | c)) return
E.abort (); if (C = "abort", m.add (h.complete), E.done (h.success), E.fail (h.error), i =
_t (Wt, h, n, E)) { if (E.readyState = 1, f && y.trigger ("ajaxSend", [E, h]), c) return
E; h.async && h.timeout > 0 && (u = e.setTimeout (function () { E.abort ("timeout") }, h.time
out)); try { c = !1, i.send (b, k) } catch (e) { if (c) throw e; k (-1, e) } } else k (-1, "No
Transport"); function k (t, n, r, s) { var
l, p, d, b, T, C = n; c | | (c = !0, u && e.clearTimeout (u), i = void
0, a = s | | "", E.readyState = t > 0 ? 4 : 0, l = t >= 200 && t < 300 | | 304 == t, r && (b = Xt (h, E, r)), b = Ut
(h, b, E, l), l ? (h.ifModified && (T = E.getResponseHeader ("Last-

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Modified")) && (w.lastModified[o]=T), (T=E.getResponseHeader("etag")) && (w.etag[o]=T)), 204===t || "HEAD"===h.type?C="nocontent":304===t?C="notmodified":(C=b.state,p=b.data,l=(d=b.error)): (d=C,!t&&C || (C="error",t<0&&(t=0))), E.status=t,E.statusText=(n || C)+"", l?v.resolveWith(g,[p,C,E]):v.rejectWith(g,[E,C,d]), E.statusCode(x),x=void
0,f&&y.trigger(l?"ajaxSuccess":"ajaxError",[E,h,l?p:d]),m.fireWith(g,[E,C]),f&&(y.trigger("ajaxComplete",[E,h]),--
w.active|w.event.trigger("ajaxStop"))}return
E},getJSON:function(e,t,n){return
w.get(e,t,n,"json"),getScript:function(e,t){return w.get(e,void
0,t,"script")},w.each(["get","post"],function(e,t){w[t]=function(e,n,r,i){r
eturn g(n)&&(i=i||r,r=n,n=void
0),w.ajax(w.extend({url:e,type:t,dataType:i,data:n,success:r},w.isPlainObject
(e)&&e))}),w._evalUrl=function(e){return
w.ajax({url:e,type:"GET",dataType:"script",cache:!0,async:!1,global:!1,"throw
s":!0}),w.fn.extend({wrapAll:function(e){var t;return
this[0]&&(g(e)&&(e=e.call(this[0])),t=w(e,this[0].ownerDocument).eq(0).clone(
!0),this[0].parentNode&&t.insertBefore(this[0]),t.map(function(){var
e=this;while(e.firstElementChild)e=e.firstElementChild;return
e}).append(this)),this},wrapInner:function(e){return
g(e)?this.each(function(t){w(this).wrapInner(e.call(this,t))}):this.each(func
tion(){var
t=w(this),n=t.contents();n.length?n.wrapAll(e):t.append(e)}),wrap:function(e
){var t=g(e);return
this.each(function(n){w(this).wrapAll(t?e.call(this,n):e)}),unwrap:function(
e){return
this.parent(e).not("body").each(function(){w(this).replaceWith(this.childNodes
)},this)},w.expr.pseudos.hidden=function(e){return!w.expr.pseudos.visible(
e)},w.expr.pseudos.visible=function(e){return!!(e.offsetWidth|e.offsetHeight
|e.getClientRects().length)},w.ajaxSettings.xhr=function(){try{return new
e.XMLHttpRequest}catch(e){}};var
Vt={0:200,1223:204},Gt=w.ajaxSettings.xhr();h.cors=!!Gt&&"withCredentials"in
Gt,h.ajax=Gt=!!Gt,w.ajaxTransport(function(t){var
n,r;if(h.cors||Gt&&!t.crossDomain)return{send:function(i,o){var
a,s=t.xhr();if(s.open(t.type,t.url,t.async,t.username,t.password),t.xhrFields
)for(a in
t.xhrFields)s[a]=t.xhrFields[a];t.mimeType&&s.overrideMimeType&&s.overrideMim
eType(t.mimeType),t.crossDomain||i["X-Requested-With"]||(i["X-Requested-
With"]="XMLHttpRequest");for(a in
i)s.setRequestHeader(a,i[a]);n=function(e){return
function(){n&&(n=r=s.onload=s.onerror=s.onabort=s.ontimeout=s.onreadystatechange
nge=null,"abort"===e?s.abort():"error"===e?"number"!==typeof
s.status?o(0,"error"):o(s.status,s.statusText):o(Vt[s.status]||s.status,s.sta
tusText,"text"!==(s.responseType||"text")||"string"!==typeof
s.responseText?{binary:s.response}:{text:s.responseText},s.getAllResponseHead
ers())}},s.onload=n(),r=s.onerror=s.ontimeout=n("error"),void
0!==s.onabort?s.onabort=r:s.onreadystatechange=function(){4===s.readyState&&e
.setTimeout(function(){n&&r()})},n=n("abort");try{s.send(t.hasContent&&t.data
||null)}catch(e){if(n)throw
e},abort:function(){n&&n()}}},w.ajaxPrefilter(function(e){e.crossDomain&&(e
.contents.script=!1)},w.ajaxSetup({accepts:{script:"text/javascript,
application/javascript, application/ecmascript, application/x-
ecmascript"},contents:{script:/\b(?:java|ecma)script\b/},converters:{"text
script":function(e){return
w.globalEval(e),e}}},w.ajaxPrefilter("script",function(e){void
0===e.cache&&(e.cache=!1),e.crossDomain&&(e.type="GET")}),w.ajaxTransport("sc
ript",function(e){if(e.crossDomain){var

```

```

t,n;return{send:function(i,o){t=w("<script>").prop({charset:e.scriptCharset,s
rc:e.url}).on("load
error",n=function(e){t.remove(),n=null,e&&o("error"===e.type?404:200,e.type)}
),r.head.appendChild(t[0]),abort:function(){n&&n()}}});var
Yt=[],Qt=/(=)\?(?=&|$)|\?\?/?;w.ajaxSetup({jsonp:"callback",jsonpCallback:func
tion(){var e=Yt.pop()||w.expand+"_"+Et++;return
this[e]=!0,e}},w.ajaxPrefilter("json jsonp",function(t,n,r){var
i,o,a,s=!1!==t.jsonp&&(Qt.test(t.url)?"url":"string"===typeof
t.data&&0===(t.contentType||"").indexOf("application/x-www-form-
urlencoded"))&&Qt.test(t.data)&&"data");if(s||"jsonp"===t.dataTypes[0])return
i=t.jsonpCallback=g(t.jsonpCallback)?t.jsonpCallback:t.jsonpCallback,s?t[s]
=t[s].replace(Qt,"$1"+i):!1!==t.jsonp&&(t.url+=(kt.test(t.url)?"&":"?")+t.jso
np+"="+i),t.converters["script json"]=function(){return a||w.error(i+" was
not
called"),a[0]},t.dataTypes[0]="json",o=e[i],e[i]=function(){a=arguments},r.al
ways(function(){void
0===o?w(e).removeProp(i):e[i]=o,t[i]&&(t.jsonpCallback=n.jsonpCallback,Yt.pus
h(i),a&&g(o)&&o(a[0]),a=o=void
0),"script"}),h.createHTMLDocument=function(){var
e=r.implementation.createHTMLDocument("").body;return
e.innerHTML="<form></form><form></form>",2===e.childNodes.length(),w.parseHT
ML=function(e,t,n){if("string"!==typeof e)return[];"boolean"===typeof
t&&(n=t,t=!1);var i,o,a;return
t||h.createHTMLDocument?(i=(t=r.implementation.createHTMLDocument(""))).crea
teElement("base").href=r.location.href,t.head.appendChild(i):t=r,o=A.exec(
e),a=!n&&[],o?[t.createElement(o[1]):(o=xe([e],t,a),a&&a.length&&w(a).remove
(),w.merge([],o.childNodes))],w.fn.load=function(e,t,n){var
r,i,o,a=this,s=e.indexOf(" ");return s>-
1&&(r=vt(e.slice(s)),e=e.slice(0,s)),g(t)?(n=t,t=void 0):t&&"object"===typeof
t&&(i="POST"),a.length>0&&w.ajax({url:e,type:i||"GET",dataType:"html",data:t}
).done(function(e){o=arguments,a.html(r?w("<div>").append(w.parseHTML(e)).fin
d(r):e)).always(n&&function(e,t){a.each(function(){n.apply(this,o||[e.respon
seText,t,e]))},this),w.each(["ajaxStart","ajaxStop","ajaxComplete","ajaxErr
or","ajaxSuccess","ajaxSend"],function(e,t){w.fn[t]=function(e){return
this.on(t,e)}}),w.expr.pseudos.animated=function(e){return
w.grep(w.timers,function(t){return
e===t.elem}).length},w.offset={setOffset:function(e,t,n){var
r,i,o,a,s,u,l,c=w.css(e,"position"),f=w(e),p={};"static"===c&&(e.style.positi
on="relative"),s=f.offset(),o=w.css(e,"top"),u=w.css(e,"left"),(l=("absolute"
===c||"fixed"===c)&&(o+u).indexOf("auto"))>-
1?(a=(r=f.position()).top,i=r.left):(a=parseFloat(o)||0,i=parseFloat(u)||0),
g(t)&&(t=t.call(e,n,w.extend({},s)),null!==t.top&&(p.top=t.top-
s.top+a),null!==t.left&&(p.left=t.left-s.left+i),"using"in
t?t.using.call(e,p):f.css(p)}),w.fn.extend({offset:function(e){if(arguments.l
ength)return void
0===e?t:this.each(function(t){w.offset.setOffset(this,e,t)});var
t,n,r=this[0];if(r)return
r.getClientRects().length?(t=r.getBoundingClientRect(),n=r.ownerDocument.defa
ultView,{top:t.top+n.pageYOffset,left:t.left+n.pageXOffset}):{top:0,left:0},
position:function(){if(this[0]){var
e,t,n,r=this[0],i={top:0,left:0};if("fixed"===w.css(r,"position"))t=r.getBoun
dingClientRect();else{t=this.offset(),n=r.ownerDocument,e=r.offsetParent||n.d
ocumentElement;while(e&&(e===n.body||e===n.documentElement)&&"static"===w.css
(e,"position"))e=e.parentNode;e&&e!==r&&1===e.nodeType&&(i=w(e).offset()).to
p+=w.css(e,"borderTopWidth",!0),i.left+=w.css(e,"borderLeftWidth",!0)}return
{top:t.top-i.top-w.css(r,"marginTop",!0),left:t.left-i.left-
w.css(r,"marginLeft",!0)}}},offsetParent:function(){return

```

```

this.map(function() {var
e=this.offsetParent;while(e&&"static"===w.css(e,"position"))e=e.offsetParent;
return
e||be}})},w.each({scrollLeft:"pageXOffset",scrollTop:"pageYOffset"},function
(e,t){var n="pageYOffset"===t;w.fn[e]=function(r){return
z(this,function(e,r,i){var
o;if(y(e)?o=e:9===e.nodeType&&(o=e.defaultView),void 0===i)return
o?o[t]:e[r];o?o.scrollTo(n?o.pageXOffset:i,n?o.pageYOffset):e[r]=i},e,r,arg
uments.length)}}),w.each(["top","left"],function(e,t){w.cssHooks[t]=_e(h.pixe
lPosition,function(e,n){if(n)return
n=Fe(e,t),We.test(n)?w(e).position()[t]+"px":n})),w.each({Height:"height",Wi
dth:"width"},function(e,t){w.each({padding:"inner"+e,content:t,"":"outer"+e},
function(n,r){w.fn[r]=function(i,o){var
a=arguments.length&&(n||"boolean"!==typeof
i),s=n||(!0===i||!0===o?"margin":"border");return z(this,function(t,n,i){var
o;return
y(t)?0===r.indexOf("outer")?t["inner"+e]:t.document.documentElement["client"+
e]:9===t.nodeType?(o=t.documentElement,Math.max(t.body["scroll"+e],o["scroll"
+e],t.body["offset"+e],o["offset"+e],o["client"+e])):void
0===i?w.css(t,n,s):w.style(t,n,i,s)},t,a?i:void 0,a)}})},w.each("blur focus
focusin focusout resize scroll click dblclick mousedown mouseup mousemove
mouseover mouseout mouseenter mouseleave change select submit keydown
keypress keyup contextmenu".split("
"),function(e,t){w.fn[t]=function(e,n){return
arguments.length>0?this.on(t,null,e,n):this.trigger(t)}}),w.fn.extend({hover:
function(e,t){return
this.mouseenter(e).mouseleave(t||e)}},w.fn.extend({bind:function(e,t,n){retu
rn this.on(e,null,t,n)},unbind:function(e,t){return
this.off(e,null,t)},delegate:function(e,t,n,r){return
this.on(t,e,n,r)},undelegate:function(e,t,n){return
1===arguments.length?this.off(e,"**"):this.off(t,e||"**",n)}},w.proxy=functi
on(e,t){var n,r,i;if("string"===typeof t&&(n=e[t],t=e,e=n),g(e))return
r=o.call(arguments,2),i=function(){return
e.apply(t||this,r.concat(o.call(arguments)))},i.guid=e.guid=e.guid||w.guid++,
i},w.holdReady=function(e){e?w.readyWait++:w.ready(!0)},w.isArray=Array.isArr
ay,w.parseJSON=JSON.parse,w.nodeName=N,w.isFunction=g,w.isWindow=y,w.camelCas
e=G,w.type=x,w.now=Date.now,w.isNumeric=function(e){var
t=w.type(e);return("number"===t||"string"===t)&&!isNaN(e-
parseFloat(e))},"function"===typeof
define&&define.amd&&define("jquery",[],function(){return w});var
Jt=e.jQuery,Kt=e.$;return w.noConflict=function(t){return
e.$===w&&(e.$=Kt),t&&e.jQuery===w&&(e.jQuery=Jt),w},t||e.jQuery=e.$=w),w);

```

Smoothscroll.js

```
/**
 * SmoothScroll
 * This helper script created by DWUser.com. Copyright 2013 DWUser.com.
 * Dual-licensed under the GPL and MIT licenses.
 * All individual scripts remain property of their copyrighters.
 * Date: 10-Sep-2013
 * Version: 1.0.1
 */
if (!window['jQuery']) alert('The jQuery library must be included before the
smoothscroll.js file. The plugin will not work properly.');
```

```
/**
 * jQuery.ScrollTo - Easy element scrolling using jQuery.
 * Copyright (c) 2007-2013 Ariel Flesler - aflesler(at)gmail(dot)com |
http://flesler.blogspot.com
 * Dual licensed under MIT and GPL.
 * @author Ariel Flesler
 * @version 1.4.3.1
 */
;(function($){var
h=$.scrollTo=function(a,b,c){$(window).scrollTo(a,b,c)};h.defaults={axis:'xy'
,duration:parseFloat($.fn.jquery)>=1.3?0:1,limit:true};h.window=function(a){r
eturn $(window)._scrollable()};$.fn._scrollable=function(){return
this.map(function(){var
a=this,isWin=!a.nodeName||$.inArray(a.nodeName.toLowerCase(),['iframe','#docu
ment','html','body'])!=-1;if(!isWin)return a;var
b=(a.contentWindow||a).document||a.ownerDocument||a;return/webkit/i.test(navi
gator.userAgent)||b.compatMode=='BackCompat'?b.body:b.documentElement});$.fn
.scrollTo=function(e,f,g){if(typeof f=='object'){g=f;f=0}if(typeof
g=='function')g={onAfter:g};if(e=='max')e=9e9;g=$.extend({},h.defaults,g);f=f
||g.duration;g.queue=g.queue&&g.axis.length>1;if(g.queue)f/=2;g.offset=both(g
.offset);g.over=both(g.over);return
this._scrollable().each(function(){if(e==null)return;var
d=this,$elem=$(d),targ=e,toff,attr={},win=$elem.is('html,body');switch(typeof
targ){case'number':case'string':if(/^([+-
])?\d+(\.\d+)?(px|%)?$/i.test(targ)){targ=both(targ);break}targ=$(targ,this);
if(!targ.length)return;case'object':if(targ.is||targ.style)toff=(targ=$(targ)
).offset()$.each(g.axis.split(''),function(i,a){var
b=a=='x'?'Left':'Top',pos=b.toLowerCase(),key='scroll'+b,old=d[key],max=h.max
(d,a);if(toff){attr[key]=toff[pos]+(win?0:old-
$elem.offset()[pos]);if(g.margin){attr[key]-
=parseInt(targ.css('margin'+b))||0;attr[key]-
=parseInt(targ.css('border'+b+'Width'))||0}attr[key]+=g.offset[pos]||0;if(g.o
ver[pos])attr[key]+=targ[a=='x'?'width':'height']()*g.over[pos]}else{var
c=targ[pos];attr[key]=c.slice&&c.slice(-
1)=='%'?parseFloat(c)/100*max:c;if(g.limit&&/^\d+$/i.test(attr[key]))attr[key]
=attr[key]<=0?0:Math.min(attr[key],max);if(!i&&g.queue){if(old!=attr[key])ani
mate(g.onAfterFirst);delete attr[key]}});animate(g.onAfter);function
animate(a){$elem.animate(attr,f,g.easing,a&&function(){a.call(this,e,g)}}).
end()};h.max=function(a,b){var
c=b=='x'?'Width':'Height',scroll='scroll'+c;if(!$elem.is('html,body'))return
a[scroll]-$elem[c.toLowerCase()]();var
d='client'+c,html=a.ownerDocument.documentElement,body=a.ownerDocument.body;r
```

```

return Math.max(html[scroll],body[scroll])-Math.min(html[d],body[d]);function
both(a){return typeof a=='object'?a:{top:a,left:a}})(jQuery);

/**
 * jQuery.LocalScroll
 * Copyright (c) 2007-2010 Ariel Flesler - aflesler(at)gmail(dot)com |
http://flesler.blogspot.com
 * Dual licensed under MIT and GPL.
 * Date: 05/31/2010
 * @author Ariel Flesler
 * @version 1.2.8b
 */
;(function(b){function g(a,e,d){var
h=e.hash.slice(1),f=document.getElementById(h)||document.getElementsByName(h)
[0];if(f){a&&a.preventDefault();var
c=b(d.target);if(!(d.lock&&c.is(":animated")||d.onBefore&&!1===d.onBefore(a,f
,c))){d.stop&&c._scrollable().stop(!0);if(d.hash){var
a=f.id==h?"id":"name",g=b("<a>
</a>").attr(a,h).css({position:"absolute",top:b(window).scrollTop(),left:b(wi
ndow).scrollLeft()});f[a]="";b("body").prepend(g);location=e.hash;g.remove();
f[a]=h)c.scrollTo(f,d).trigger("notify.serialScroll",
[f])}}var
i=location.href.replace(/#.*\/,""),c=b.localScroll=function(a){b("body").local
Scroll(a);c.defaults={duration:1E3,axis:"y",event:"click",stop:!0,target:win
dow,reset:!0};c.hash=function(a){if(location.hash){a=b.extend({},c.defaults,a
);a.hash=!1;if(a.reset){var e=a.duration;delete
a.duration;b(a.target).scrollTo(0,a);a.duration=e}g(0,location,a)}};b.fn.loca
lScroll=function(a){function
e(){return!!this.href&&!!this.hash&&this.href.replace(this.hash,"")==i&&(!a.f
ilter||b(this).is(a.filter))}
a=b.extend({},c.defaults,a);return a.lazy?this.bind(a.event,function(d){var
c=b([d.target,d.target.parentNode]).filter(e)[0];c&&g(d,c,a)}):this.find("a,a
rea").filter(e).bind(a.event,function(b,this,a){}).end().end()})(jQuery)
;

// Initialize all .smoothScroll links
jQuery(function($){$.localScroll({filter:".smoothScroll"});});

```